

1st INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SCIENCE AND EDUCATION SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

**VENUE: FRANCIS IDIBIYE HALL, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, AKURE, ONDO
STATE, NIGERIA**

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

Knowledge for Global Development

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**SCIENCE AND EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE
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PREFACE

On behalf of the board members, local organizing committee and my humble self, I welcome you all to the first ever conference organized by Science and Education Development Institute, Akure, Nigeria. The “THEME: SCIENCE AND EDUCATION POTENTIALS: MAKING THE TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS MEET THE CHALLENGES” was carefully selected to meet the challenges faced by institutions especially in developing countries. We have anticipated that this forum would bring together best brains to contribute to knowledge.

This book of abstract has been produced to provide incite of what to expect at the conference. At the end of the conference a book of proceedings would be printed. This is meant to document the conference.

We hope you will enjoy your stay here - Akure, the capital city of Ondo State (Sunshine State). Please feel free to visit some interesting places during this short stay.

Welcome to our Sunshine State

Abulude, F.O
President/CEO

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SEDInst 2013

Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria 8th – 9th October, 2013

The aim of this first international conference with **THEME: SCIENCE AND EDUCATION POTENTIALS: MAKING THE TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS MEET THE CHALLENGES** is to create a forum for exchange and discussion between scientists, engineers, educationists, students and other stakeholders throughout Africa and beyond.

Subject Areas: Accounting, Agriculture, Art and Humanities, Biological Sciences, Business Management, Education, Engineering, Environmental, Law, Management Sciences, Medical Sciences, Pharmaceutical Sciences, Physical Science, Sciences and Social Sciences.

The topics will be grouped under the following general areas:

1. **i.** Sustainable Science Research
2. **ii.** Sustainable Education Development Research
3. **iii.** Sustainable Medical Development Research
4. **iv.** Sustainable Tropical Agriculture Development Research
5. **v.** Advances in Social Sciences
6. **vi.** Technological Innovations
7. **vii.** Advances in Environmental Research

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GUEST SPEAKERS

1. Prof. V.A. Aletor – Vice Chancellor, Elizade University, IlaraMokin, Ondo State, Nigeria
2. Prof. T.T. Adebolu – Department of Microbiology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

GUEST OF HONOUR

Prof. Adebisi Daramola – Vice Chancellor: Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

The venue of the conference Akure, is a city in the southwestern region of Nigeria, and is the largest city and capital of Ondo State. The city has a population of approximately 387,087. The people are of the Yoruba ethnic group. Oral tradition states that Akure was founded by Omoremi Omoluabi, a grandson of the Emperor Oduduwa. Akure's King is known as the Deji of Akure and is supported by six (6) high chiefs or Iwarefa in his or her domain. Within the modern Akure kingdom are two other autonomous communities with their separate obas and traditions.

The town is blessed with radio and television stations, government and private hospitals, three tertiary institutions, secondary, nursery and primary schools, central bank and commercial banks. Akure is also blessed with many cuisines, stadium well equipped with sporting facilities. Indigenes are free to imbibe any religion of their choice.

SEDInst will continue to foster cross fertilisation between disciplines and multidisciplinary between colleagues. It is anticipated that SEDInst will hold 4-yearly meetings in any country of board and stakeholders' choice. There will be varied and exciting programme of oral and poster presentations with more than 300 registered participants throughout Africa and beyond.

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PROGRAMME

DAY ONE: TUESDAY OCTOBER 8, 2013

OPENING CEREMONY

1st SESSION

8.30 – 9.30am	Registration of Participants
9.30 – 10.00am	Arrival of Guests
10.00 – 10.05am	Opening Prayer
10.05 – 10.10am	National Anthem/Pledge
10.10 – 10.20am	Introduction of Guests/Special Invitees
10.20 – 10.30am	President/CEO's Address
10.30 – 10.40am	Chairman Advisory Board's Address
10.40 – 10.50am	Special Guest of Honour's Welcome Address Conference Declared Open - Prof Biyi Daramola (Vice Chancellor – Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.
10.50 – 11. 20am	1 st Paper - Prof. V.A. Aletor – Vice Chancellor, Elizade University, Ilara Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria.
11. 20 – 11.50am	2 nd Paper - Prof. T.T. Adebolu – Department of Microbiology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.
11.50 – 12.20pm	Goodwill Messages

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12.20 – 12.30pm	Conference Declared Open - Special Guest of Honour - Prof Biyi Daramola (Vice Chancellor – Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria).
12.30 – 12.40pm	Vote of Thanks – Dr E.I. Moyinjesu (LOC Chairman)
12.40 – 1.30pm	Lunch

2nd SESSION

1.30 – 5.00pm	Technical Sessions (Presentation of Papers at Different Groups)
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DAY TWO: WEDNESDAY OCTOBER 9, 2013

TECHNICAL SESSION

9.00 – 12.00noon	Technical Sessions (Presentation of Papers at Different Groups)
12.00 – 12.50pm	Interactive Session/Collection of Certificate of Attendance
12.50 – 1.30pm	Lunch/ Closing

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Oluwayomi, Seun
Adeleke, Ayomide

CATERING SERVICE

Sweet Savor, Catering Service, Akure, Nigeria

APPRECIATION

The Science and Education Development Institute (SEDIInst) heartily extend her sincere thanks and appreciation to you all for being part of this conference.

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SUSTAINABLE SCIENCE RESEARCH

APPLICATION OF HELIGMAN AND POLLARD MODEL AND SMOOTH SPLINE POISON REGRESSION TO MODELING FEMALE MORTALITY IN NIGERIA

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KEYWORDS: Mortality, Modeling, Heligman and Pollard, Smooth spline poison Regression, AIC, BIC.

ABSTRACT

Child Mortality modeling has dominated the centre stage of Statistical Modeling. Little effort has been geared towards developing a mortality model that captured Nigeria general mortality rate. This research paper, focus on the Female Mortality Modeling using Heligman and Pollard Mortality model with Spline Smooth Poison Regression Model. We considered the robustness of the two models as they both fit into the Nigeria Female mortality data for 2002 to 2006. The Heligman and Pollard model fit the data very well but there is no Basic rule of estimating the parametes. Spline Smooth Poison Regression Model with the smoothing parameter to be 0.00316, with AIC to be 268.88 and BIC as 274.21 having effective dimension as 5.992.

INTRODUCTION

Indicators obtained from mortality rates provide a good picture of overall population health. These indicators include infant and child mortality, adult mortality and overall life expectancy at birth. According to the world development indicators database, adult mortality rate" is the probability of a fifteen year old dying before reaching age sixty, if subjected to current age-specific mortality rates between those ages.

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For several decades, global public-health efforts have focused on the development and application of disease control programs to improve child survival in developing countries. Consequently, methods for calculating child mortality levels and trends from surveys are well-developed and generally yield accurate estimates. By contrast, little emphasis has been placed on adult mortality especially in a developing country like Nigeria. Although attempts have been made to measure adult mortality, these attempts have often produced implausibly low estimates of adult mortality. As a result, many are remarkably ignorant about current level and patterns of adult mortality in the country, and how they are changing with time.

In September 2000, all the 191 United Nations member states pledged that by the year 2015, all the MDGs consisting of a frame of 8 goals, 18 targets and 48 indicators to track progress towards meeting the goals would be met. Goal 5 focuses on issues relating to maternal mortality and maternal health. The target is to reduce by three-quarters, between 1990 and 2015, the maternal mortality ratio. Goal 6 is aimed at targets in epidemiology of HIV/AIDS, malaria and other major diseases leading to adult mortality and their social consequences. It is expected that these diseases must have halted and their spread reversed by 2020. This is year 2013 the question is; will Nigeria be able to meet up with these goals?

The Government needs accurate information on deaths in the population to help them plan health care policies and monitor the effectiveness of public-health programs designed in order to achieve the MDG targets. Without details on adult mortality, it is hard to identify effective strategies for curbing adult mortality in the country.

Modeling is one of the MDGs indicators. According to Bamiduro (2007), a good model is measurable, tractable, efficient and identifiable. It must allow for the application of all the three functions of statistics namely description, inference and prescription providing insight where necessary into the development and

implication of the events being measured. These reasons underline the choice of developing a statistical model that fit Nigeria data.

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Data: The source of the data for this research work is from Nigeria Federal bureau of Statistics data jointly obtained by the Bureau and Central Bank of Nigeria on mortality by age and gender from 2002 to 2006. For the purpose of this research work, we have used the provided data.

Mortality Model

The development of a law of mortality, in which an analytic expression is used to represent all or part of the age pattern of mortality (in term of, say $\mu(x)$ or $q(x)$), has been of interest since the development of the first life table, which is compiled by renowned English astronomer Edmund Helley (1693). Probably, the first mathematical mortality model is the one proposed by Abraham De Moivre's in 1725, who suggested that the probability of survival from birth until age x could be expressed as linear function of age. In terms of the hazard rate, the model can be written as:

$$\mu(x) = \frac{1}{\omega - x}, 0 \leq x \leq \omega$$

(1)

where ω is the highest attainable age.

However, the most successful and influential mortality law belongs to Benjamin Gompertz. In 1825, Gompertz found that an exponential increase in age can approximately capture the behavior of human mortality rates for large portions of the life table. He therefore proposed, in terms of the hazard rate, that:

$$\mu(x) = A \exp(\theta x), x > 0$$

(2)

The Gompertz law has played a central role in the development of theoretical hypotheses about the pattern of mortality. The close fit of the Gompertz function to empirical data seems to suggest that a law of mortality may exist to explain the age patterns of death for human populations. This has stimulated a lot of researches to modify or generalize the Gompertz formula.

For example, in 1860, William Makeham noticed that the Gompertz equation failed to capture the behavior of mortality at higher ages and added a constant term, B , in order to correct for this deficiency. The

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constant can be thought of representing the risk of death by causes that are independent of age. Hence Makeham's model can be expressed as

$$\mu(x) = B + A \exp(\theta x) \quad (3)$$

Another good extension from Gompertz's model is Perks's model (1932),

$$\mu(x) = \frac{B + A \exp(\theta x)}{1 + C \exp(\theta x)}$$

(4)

which allows the curve to more closely approximate the slower rate of increase in mortality at older ages.

Also in 1963, Beard developed a model to reflect the effect of heterogeneity in the mortality risks to alter the shape of the mortality rate increasing:

$$\mu(x) = \frac{A \exp(\theta x)}{1 + C \exp(\theta x)} \quad (5)$$

In 1980, Heligman and Pollard extended Gompertz's law to an eight parameter formula that can better fit the whole mortality curve, models. A well known graduation technique is the use of a mathematical formula,

$$\frac{qx}{1 - qx} = A(x + B)^C + D \exp\left(-E \left(\log\left(\frac{x}{F}\right)\right)^2\right) + GH^x$$

(6)

The model:

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Heligman and pollard (1980) proposed the above model, which describes the entire life time. They applied the model to fit the Australian life table. The three components of the formula represent early childhood mortality, accident mortality and senescent mortality respectively. The third component GH^x is interpreted as a discrete version of the Gompertz law where q_x is the probability that a person at age $x+1$, $p_x = 1 - q_x$ and A to H are parameters. When applying the model, the parameters are determined by minimizing the square sum of

$$S^2 = \sum_{x=0}^x \left(\frac{qx}{\mu x} - 1 \right)^2$$

(7)

Where, qx represents the fitted mortality and μx represents the observed mortality.

We analyze our data instead of age $x+1$ as used by Heligman and pollard in their original work by using age $x+5$. The model is used for the analysis as shown below.

PENALIZED LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION

Penalized likelihood estimation is a likelihood based estimation method which traces its origin back to Whittaker (1923) (discrete case) and Kimeldorf and Wahba(1970a,70b,71)and Good and Gaskins (1971). The central idea is to estimate a function of interest on

$$L(\eta | data) + \frac{\lambda}{2} J(\eta)$$

(8)

Where $L(\eta|data)$ is the negative log-likelihood and $J(\eta)$ is a quadratic roughness penalty with a low dimensional null-space $NJ = \{ f \in H : J(f) = 0 \}$. The minimizer above can be seen to be the restricted maximum likelihood estimator in a model space $M\rho = \{ f: J(f) = \rho \}$ for some $\rho > 0$. Moreover, λ above can be seen to be the Lagrange Multiplier.

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An example of the above formulation is the cubic smoothing spline, see Klugman, Panjerand Willmott (2004). It arises from the regression problem

$$Y_i = \eta(x_i) + e_i, i = 1, \dots, n \quad (9)$$

Where e_i are independent random variables with $e_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$. Let us assume that $x_i \in [0, 1]$, $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then with the quadratic roughness penalty taken to be $\int_0^1 \hat{\eta}^2(x) dx$ where $\hat{\eta}$ is the second derivative of η Now (9) in this problem is equivalent to

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{y_i - \eta(x_i)}{\delta_i} \right)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_0^1 \hat{\eta}^2(x) dx \quad (10)$$

and from elementary properties of spline we see that the minimizer has to be a cubic spline which is called the cubic smoothing spline. The above setup naturally leads to functional spaces which are Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces (RKHS) as the optimization problem then becomes tractable. This is so as the log likelihood, being a smooth function of the evaluation functionals, and be a continuous functional requires that the function space (a Hilbert space) to be a RKHS. Moreover, it is then natural to take the smoothness

penalty J to be one induced by a semi-inner product on the RKHS. This general setup is useful in extending the method to multivariate function estimation and allows one to consider interesting classes of smooth functions, see Gu (2002). Of particular interest is the equivalence of the penalized likelihood method to a Bayes model with a Gaussian prior on $H \ominus NJ$ (with the covariance related to the reproducing kernel) and a diffuse prior on NJ . This Bayes model makes available Bayesian posterior confidence intervals. And these become approximate Bayesian confidence intervals in the case of non-Gaussian response as it involves quadratic approximation of the likelihood (Laplace's method).

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Smoothing parameter selection is an important practical issue in penalized likelihood estimation. There are different score based methods, the scores being asymptotically close to

$$\frac{1}{n} = \sum_{i=0}^n n \lambda((x_i) - \eta(x_i))^2 \quad (11)$$

The idea being that the smoothing parameter is chosen to minimize the above. For details see Gu (2002). Interestingly, using the generalized cross validation based score for choosing the smoothing parameter results in the point wise Bayesian confidence intervals having good across-the-function coverage, see Gu (2002) and references there in for more details.

Let D_x , for $x = 0, 1, \dots$, be the number of deaths observed at age (according to any of the common used definition) x . Also let E_x , for $x = 0, 1, \dots$, be the total amount of time the persons were under observation at age x . We assume that D_x is a Poisson distributed random variable with parameter $E_x \lambda(x)$, i.e.

$$\Pr(D_x = k) = \frac{1}{k!} \lambda(x) E(x)^k \exp(-E_x \lambda(x)) \sum_{x=0}^x \left(\frac{qx}{\mu x} - 1 \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

Such a Poisson distribution has been assumed by many, for e.g. see Forfar, McCutcheon and Wilkie (1988). Assuming the constant force of mortality within integral ages results in the same likelihood as the above Poisson likelihood, see Hoem (1984). This fact has been used in the Bayesian analysis of Broffitt (1988). Also for an argument that the Poisson distribution assumption results from using the above constant force assumption, see Scott (1982, 1984). In this connection also interesting are the articles Sverdup (1965) and Borgan (1984). In the following we will assume the constant force within integral ages.

Given the above model we suppose that $\eta(\cdot) = \log \lambda(\cdot)$ lies in the space of all twice continuously differentiable functions and by using the roughness penalty

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$$\int \ddot{\eta}(x)^2 dx \quad (13)$$

where $\ddot{\eta}$ is the second derivative of η

we force the estimate to be a cubic spline. Estimates for q_x are derived using the formula

$$q_x = 1 - \exp[-\lambda(x)] \quad (14)$$

which result from the constant force assumption.

The choice of selecting smoothing parameter

The user of P -splines has a number of choices to make: (a) the number of knots, the degree of the P -spline and the order of the penalty, and (b) the smoothing parameter. The parameters in (a) we call the P -spline parameters and denote them by ndx , $bdeg$ and $pard$ respectively. We will see that when forecasting with P -splines the forecast values depend critically on the order of the penalty. The choice of the other P -spline parameters, ndx and $bdeg$, can be less critical since different choices often lead to similar fitted smooth functions. Eilers and Marx (1996), Ruppert (2002) and Currie and Durban (2002) discuss the choice of the

P -spline parameters; the following simple rule-of-thumb is often sufficient: We will use the Bayesian Information Criterion, BIC and Aike information criterion to choose the smoothing parameter

$$AIC(R, \lambda) = n \log(RSS(R, \lambda)) + 2df(R, \lambda) \quad (15)$$

where

$$RSS(R, \lambda) = \{y - \mu_{\lambda}(x)\}^T R^{-1} \{y - \mu_{\lambda}(x)\}$$

and

$$df(R, \lambda) = \text{tr}(S_R, \lambda), \text{ with } \text{tr}(\cdot) \text{ as trace of the matrix.}$$

$$BIC = 2Dev + \log n \text{Tr}$$

Where

Dev is the deviance in a generalized Linear Model (GLM)

and $\text{Tr} = \text{tr}(H)$ is the effective dimension of the fitted model and n is the number of observation.

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AIC and BIC have been used for this work, but there is evidence that BIC performed better than AIC which is believed to be under-smooth the data. See for example, Hurvich et al. (1998) or Lee (2003). BIC penalizes model complexity heavily than AIC.

Application and Discussion of the Result

We analyze the data using both solver technique in excel and gss from R package as shown below.

Figure1:

The parameter for Heligman and Pollard Model for 2002-2006 are shown below

Figure2: Helingman and pollard eight parameter

Year/parameter	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
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A	0.06	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.08
B	0.02	0.04	0.24	0.08	0.05
C	0.08	0.08	0.34	0.03	0.98
D	0.05	0.01	0.07	0.06	0.8
E	12	24	23	28	32
F	0.05	0.88	0.01	0.7	0.88
G	0.8	0.02	0.09	0.90	0.6
H	006	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.06
Error	12.4112	13.77264	16.7719	11.013	7.2834

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Figure 2: Helingman and Pollard eight parameter

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Figure 3:Log Mortality for Female in Nigeria

DISCUSSION

From the analysis, we discovered that Heligman and Pollard mortality curve of series three which is 2004 mortality curve of figure 1 slope down gently and portrait the picture that the mortality for each age group is high throughout that period. The other years curve slope down sharply as one move from childhood age to youthful age and rise sharply as the ages are above seventy. The parameters and the errors for the Heligman

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and Pollard Model were given in figure 2 and the graph showing the eight parameters for those years under study is in figure

3. The problem with this model is that starting with different values may lead to having different parameters. As good as the model fits the data very well; there is no basic solution to arrive at the best parameters.

Based on the deficiency of the earlier model we analyze our data using the proposed model smoothing spline poisson regression. From the analysis the following results were obtained and displayed in figure 3 and four respectively.

Effective dimension = 17.83 and the (Selected) smoothing parameter = 0.00316
The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) = 274.21, and Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) = 268.88
(Estimated) dispersion parameter (ψ^2) = 21.4 and the convergence tolerance of the model is 4.5382-08.
The AIC and BIC allowed for the selection of the best smoothing parameter.

The model shows a smooth rise in the log-mortality as Age increases except some situations we have a sharp rise and fall as portrayed by the curve of figure 3

Further research area using this model is the computation of life table and forecast for future mortality.

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FUNGI: A REVIEW ON MUSHROOMS

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KEYWORDS: Mushrooms, Nigeria, New employment, Medicinal value

ABSTRACT

This paper reviews a fungus – mushrooms. In this paper, identification, cultivation, uses, side effects, nutritional and medicinal values, storage, marketing and other uses of mushrooms were discussed. From the review too it was observed that its usefulness surpasses the side effects. These side effects could be

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eliminated if proper ‘processing’ could be employed. Due to advances in both basic knowledge and practical technology relevant to mushroom farming, mushroom products and mushroom bioremediation, developing countries should harness the potentials of mushrooms as this would boost the revenue income and healthy living. It is hoped that this paper would add to existing information on this fungus.

INTRODUCTION

The organisms of the fungal lineage include mushrooms, rusts, smuts, puffballs, truffles, morels, and yeasts, as well as many less well known organisms (Blackwell *et al*, 2011). More than 700, 00 species of fungi have been described however, some estimates of total numbers suggests that 1.5 million species may exist (James *et al*, 2006).

Edible mushroom (Figs 1 & 2) have for a long time been recognized not only as a delicacy, but also for their use as food in man’s diets. Mushrooms have been found to be rich sources of protein, lipids, amino acids, glycogen, vitamins and mineral elements (Okhuoya *et al.*, 2010). According to Rambeli (1983), the mineral salt content of mushrooms is superior to that of meat and fish and nearly twice that of the most common vegetables.

Nigeria is a country of many tribes, the Hausa in the North, Yoruba in the West, Urhobo in the Mid – West and the Ibo in the East, to mention a few. Each tribe has recognized mushrooms for many years, and the people have made use of a number of them economically in their daily life.

The Yorubas have recognized mushrooms for many years as in fungi have always played an important role in their everyday life. They have descriptive Yoruba names for their species of mushrooms as well as mythical stories and beliefs, which explain the origin of some of them. These myths and beliefs sometimes play a role in determining which of the mushrooms are edible and which of them may be used for medical purposes by the Yoruba native doctors.

The nutritional and medicinal values of mushrooms have long been recognized. In recent times, however, mushrooms have assumed greater importance in the diets of both rural urban dwellers. For example, they

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are being marketed along major highways and urban centers where the trade now booms. It is conceivable that the increased demand for mushrooms is contingent upon the phenomenal rise in the unit costs of the conventional sources of meat (e.g beef, pork, chicken, etc).

Edible mushrooms have been placed into five categories according to the derivation of their names, viz., those named according to the taste, morphology, growth habit, texture, and habitat (Oso, 1975). Examples in each category are: taste (*Volvariella volvacea*, *Volvariella esculenta* Yor. Ogiri agbe) *Termitomyces clypeatus* (Yor. Takete): Morphology (*Termitomyces manniformis*) (Yor. Rooro) *Termitomyces robustus* (Yor.Ewe) *Schizophyllum commune* Fr (Yor. Ese-adie) *Agrocyber broadway* (Murr) (Yor. Gunnugu); growth habit (*Termitomyces globulus*, *Pleurotus tuber-reguim*) (Yor. Olu); texture (*Pleurotus squarrouslus*) (Yor. Erirokiro), *Psathyrella atroumbonata* (Yor.Wowo); habitat (*Francolimus bicalcaratus*)

(Yor.Isoaparo). In addition to the above, the natives have observed the growth of many fungi on different kinds of dead wood and have named each fungus after the wood on which it grows.

Besides the edible mushrooms, the natives also recognize some poisonous or none edible fungi a few of which are listed here. *Coprinus africanus* (Yor. Ajeimutin), *Phallus aurantiacus*, *Phallus industiatus*, *Phallus rubicundus* and *Mutinus bambustinus* (Yor.Akufodewa), *Celtis zenkeri* (Yor.Asa-ita), *Coprinus ephemerus* (Yor.Olu-gbongaga).

There has been a recent upsurge of interest in mushrooms not only as a health vegetable (food) which is rich in protein but also as a source of biologically active compounds of medicinal value. Uses include complementary medicine/dietary supplements for anticancer, antiviral, immunopotentiating, hypocholesterolemic, and hepatoprotective agents. This new class of compounds, termed *mushroom nutraceuticals* are extractable from either the mushroom mycelium or fruiting body and represent an important component of the expanding mushroom biotechnology industry. It has been shown that constant intake of either mushrooms or mushroom nutraceuticals (dietary supplements) can make people fitter and healthier. In addition, mushroom cultivation can also help to convert agricultural and forest wastes into

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useful matter and reduce pollution in the environment. Therefore, mushroom cultivation can make three important contributions: production of health food, manufacture of nutraceuticals, and reduction of environmental pollution.

Mushrooms are among the largest fungi, which have attracted the attention of naturalists before microscopes, or even simple lenses had thought of. Mushrooms date back to antiquity and are even associated with some past. For example, the Romans attributed the appearance of mushrooms and truffles to lightning hurled by Jupiter to the earth. Even, the Indians of Mexico and Guatemala believe that the appearance of certain mushrooms such as the “fly agaric” *Amanita muscaria* is correlated with a relationship between thunder, lightning and the earth.

CEREMONIAL USES OF MUSHROOMS

For centuries, some mushrooms have been used in religious ceremonies of many ancient people and primitive tribes.

Mushrooms are believed by the Romans to have properties that could produce super human strength, help in finding lost objects and lead the soul to the realm of the gods (Grube *et al.*, 2001). Here in Nigeria, the people of Ohia, in Abia State during one of their festivals consume the fungi (Lebo, 2004).

CULTIVATION OF MUSHROOMS

As a group, mushrooms occur in different parts of the world, ranging from arctic to the tropics. While some species occur only in restricted areas, others exist in areas that are widely separated geographically. However, most species seem to show a preference for a certain type of habitat. Some are, for instance, found primarily in upland wooded areas; others exist in swamps and still others prefer open areas such as gardens, lawns or pasture e.g *Pleurotus tuber-regium*. Many species particularly the mycorrhizal forms are associated with certain types of vegetations. Within a certain habitat, mushrooms may also show a preference for a particular substratum. Basidiocarps of some are typically produced on the soil and are generally referred to as terrestrial forms. Others are found on dead leaves (follicolous) or litter e.g *Cortinarius melliolens* and *Tricholoma lobayensis*, on wood (lignicolous) e.g *Lentinus edodes* or on dung

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(corpophilous) e.g *Coprinus lagopus*. A few grow on nasidiocarps of other mushrooms and are termed fungicolus.

Mushrooms are mostly found on wastes such as sawdust, garbages and composting materials (Gbolagade *et al.*, 2006). Statemet (2001) noted that garden mushrooms were propagated from fermented horse dung and moist litter all the year round. Miles and Chang (2004) deduced from the evidence presented in various early publications, that mushroom cultivation started in France about 1630, since then, series of studies have been conducted to monitor different growth parameters in both natural and pure culture. Compositing

progress was measured by changes in temperature, hydrogen ion concentration (pH), and ability of compost top support growth of mushroom mycelia. Growth of mushroom was observed to take place over a wide range of pH, i.e pH 3.4 – pH 9.0 (Adebayo *et al.*, 2009). The investigation carried out on *Coprinus cineris* and *Volvariella volvacea* in relationship to pH showed that a drop in pH enhanced the growth of *C. cineris* while neutral pH favors *V. volvacea*.

A combination of condition such as temperature, pH, light, physical properties of subtraction and proportion of nutritional factors have effect on the growth of mycelia as well as production of fruiting bodies.

During mycelia growth on their substrate, mushroom produce a number of enzymes which breakdown complex organic compounds such as cellulose and lignin into soluble production, which are absorbed by the hyphae. Different types of mushrooms were qualitatively examined for their ability to hydrolyse starch. Kuforiji and Fasidi, (2008) proved that *Lentnus adodes* mycelia are known to grow on various agar media and liquid cultures. Composts supplemented with organic material containing vitamin B-complex were claimed to enhance greater yield of mushroom.

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The general pattern carbon source utilization of *Agaricus bisporus* is similar among the various reports despite considerable difference in strains, time and place of study. Generally glucose, fructose and xylose are reported as good carbon sources. All fungi require a nitrogen source.

Investigations on the effect of several environmental factors on mushroom both independently and in different conditions were carried out by Adenipekun and Fasidi, (2005); Kuforiji and Fasidi, (2007); Ukoima *et al.*, (2009a & b). They found out that a combination of condition such as temperatures, pH, physical properties of substratum of proportion of nutritional factors have effect on the growth of mycelia. Mycelia are produced as a result of spore germination. It is the fruit body that attracts the attention of mushroom hunters because it is fleshy and also more conspicuous.

Lots of researches have been carried out in Nigeria. Some of the works include cultivation on sawdust of different plants (Okhuoya (1998); Gyar and Ogbonna (2006); Kuforiji and Fasidi, (2008), agricultural and agro industrial wastes (Fasidi and Kadiri, (1993); Adenipekun and Fasidi (2005); Ayodele and Okhuoya (2007); Kuforiji and Fasidi, (2007); Onuoha *et al.* (2009); Ukoima *et al.* (2009), cotton waste and cassava peel (Adebayo *et al.* 2009) and culture media (Ukoima *et al.* 2009). Elsewhere, examples of the different formulas for spawn substrates are: Mother grain spawn: (i) Wheat/rye grain C 1.5% gypsum or slaked lime. (ii) Cotton seed hull 40%, sawdust 38%, wheat bran 20%, sugar 1%, and gypsum 1%. (iii) Sugar cane bagasse 40%, sawdust 38%, wheat bran 20%, sugar 1%, and gypsum 1%. Planting spawn: A number of materials, mostly agricultural and forest wastes, can be used to prepare mushroom planting spawn. Three of them are given here as examples: sawdust 78%, rice/wheat bran 16%, sugar 1.5%, corn flour 1.7%, ammonium sulphate 0.3%, calcium superphosphate 0.5%, and gypsum 2%; sawdust 64%, wheat bran 15%, spent coffee grounds 20%, and gypsum/lime 1%; and sawdust 78%, sucrose 1%, wheat bran 20%, and calcium carbonate 1%.(Chang, 2008).

Apart from cultivation from wastes, there is the mushroom industry. Mushroom industry can be considered to be composed of cultivated edible mushrooms, medicinal mushrooms, and wild mushrooms (Chang, 2006).

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According to the Training manual on Mushroom Cultivation Technology, (2008), there are advantages of mushrooms cultivation, these are highlighted below:

1. Wastes such as cereal straws are largely burnt by the farmers, which causes air pollution. However, these raw materials can actually be used for the cultivation of mushrooms. This kind of bioconversion exercise can greatly reduce environmental pollution.
2. It serves as means of generating employment, particularly for rural women and youths in order to raise their social status.
3. It provides the people with an additional vegetable of high quality, and enrich the diet with high quality proteins, minerals and vitamins which can be of direct benefit to the human health and fitness. The extractable bioactive compounds from medicinal mushrooms would enhance human's immune systems and improve their quality of life.
4. Mushroom cultivation is a cash crop. It improves economic standards of the people some warm mushrooms, e.g. *Volvariella volvacea* (Straw mushrooms) and *Pleurotussajor-caju* (Oyster mushrooms) are relatively fast growing organisms and can be harvested in 3 to 4 weeks after spawning. It is a short return agricultural business and can be of immediate benefit to the community.

IDENTIFICATION

Macroscopic structure of mushrooms must be understood before identification can be made. Most of them are Basidiomycetes and gilled. Their spores called basidiospores are produced on the gills and fall in a fine rain of powder from under the caps as a result. At the microscopic level the basidiospore are short off basisia and then falls between the gills in the dead air space. As a result, for most mushrooms, if the cap is cut off and placed gill – side – down overnight, a powdery impression reflecting the shape of the gills is formed. The color of the powdery print, called a spore print is used to help classify mudrooms and can help to identify them. Spores prints colors include white, brown, black, purple-brown, pink, yellow and cream, but almost never blue, green, or red.

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A good reference material, usually a book with color, pictures of the different mushrooms known, is a basic requirement. A key is usually provided to simplify identification in most reference texts (Carluccio, (2003); Fuhrer, (2005). In using the reference, it is essential that one knows some specific characteristics of the mushroom being identified. These characteristics are (1) size, color, and consistency of the cap and the stalk; (2) mode of attachment of the gills to the stalk; (3) spore color in mass; and (4) chemical tests or reactions.

There is no single reference work in which all mushrooms are illustrated or described. In most cases, mushroom species in publications are grouped by region or locality, for example, North American mushrooms, mushrooms of the Western Hemisphere, mushrooms of South Africa and those found in Nigeria. While certain mushrooms are easy to identify, many are not. In fact, there are a great number of look-alikes. To avoid any unpleasant experiences, especially when identifying mushrooms for the purpose of determining edibility, experts should always be consulted.

NUTRITIONAL VALUES OF MUSHROOMS

Edible mushrooms are important sources of food. They form very nourishing meals especially for invalids, for they are easily digestible. They are consumed not only for their innate flavour and taste, but also for their important nutritional value. On fresh weight basis mushrooms are superior in protein content (Aremu *et al.*, 2009) to all vegetables and fruits, but are inferior to meat and dairy products, which are the conventional protein sources. On dry-weight basis, however, mushrooms are similar with respect to dried-yeast and superior to dried peas and beans. The nutrient content varies from species and depends on their growth requirement. Mushrooms have a high percentage of water 93-95% as compared to lean beef (70%) and fresh vegetables (92%). They also contain valuable minerals such as iron, potassium, phosphorus, calcium and copper, 56% carbohydrate, 30% protein, 2% fat and also 10% ash on dry weight basis. They are also rich in vitamin B and vitamin D.

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Mushrooms provide a high protein and low caloric diet and can thus be recommended to heart patients. They also contain all the essential amino-acid required by an adult (Koyyalamudi *et al.*, 2009). Tryptophan and lysine are present in high concentrations as compared to cystein and methionine.

Mushrooms is reported to be an excellent source of riboflavin and nicotinic acid; a good source of pantothenic acid and ascorbic acid (Ukpebor *et al.*, 2007). The carbohydrate and fat contents of edible mushrooms are quite low. The absence of starch in mushrooms makes it an ideal food for diabetic patients and for persons who wants to shed excess fat.

Edible mushrooms known as the meat of the vegetable world (Haas and James, 2009) can be prepared into a variety of delicious dishes and as flavours for other dishes. Among the Nigerian mushroom dishes are mushrooms with vegetable, mushroom with vegetable and melon soup, mushroom in okro soup, and mushroom in stew. These soups are used to eat a variety of foods. Some people use mushrooms as a substitute for meat in their stews (Abulude, 2005).

There is evidence that consumption of plant foods such as fruits and vegetables, provide protection against various diseases, especially chronic degenerative diseases (Selvi *et al* (2007). This protection can be explained by the free –radical scavenging capacity of antioxidants in plant foods. Plant foods are a good source of polyphenols, which have been reported to be effective radical scavenger and inhibitors of liquid peroxidation (Makam and Konig, 2001). Kettawan *et al.*, (2011) and Selvi *et al* (2007) have demonstrated that mushrooms contain antioxidants.

Apart from their nutritive values, mushrooms also have potential medicinal benefits especially as antitumour. Abulude, (2005); Kuforiji and Fasidi, (2008) and Kettawan *et al.*, (2011) elaborated on the medicinal uses of *Pleurotus tuber-regium* in Nigeria. The stated that these mushrooms can be used in combination with other herbs as ingredients to care ailments such as chest pain, cold, dropsy, fever,

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headache, smallpox and stomach pains. The low carbohydrate content of mushrooms makes it an ideal food for diabetics and people who intend to control their body weight.

SIDE EFFECTS OF MUSHROOMS

Mushrooms can also cause disease, decay and destruction in their search for food, since they have no chlorophyll, they must obtain organic material in prepared form, for example, *Armillaria mellea* “Honey fungus” causes serious damage to ramiferous trees and may attack shrubs and even herbaceous plants such as potatoes, and strawberries (Lange and Hora, 1963).

Cultivation of mushrooms on commercial scale is new to many developing countries of which Nigeria is one. This fact is due to the scantiness of information on the growth requirement of many indigenous mushrooms. In Nigeria, there are lots of industrial and agricultural wastes that may serve as potential source of raw material for commercial cultivation of mushroom at minimum cost.

Ita *et al.* (2008) in their study on bioaccumulation potential of heavy metals in sporocarps from Niger Delta region of Nigeria, revealed that certain mushrooms accumulate heavy metals. The accumulating potentials are affected by the species, substrate composition, age of mycelium and intervals between fructifications. Studies on metals in mushrooms have shown a correlation between fungal metals concentration and point sources of metal pollution (Isildak *et al.*, 2004; Gyar and Ogbonna, 2006).

Human activities have been reported to impact negatively on arable lands contaminating them with pesticides, petroleum hydrocarbons, heavy metals and waste engine oil pollutants, and consequently causing arable land shortage and other environmental challenges (Okhuoya *et al.*, 2010; Oghenekaro *et al.*, 2008). These challenges may exert negative effect such as kidney damage, impairment of circulatory, reproductive and nervous system damage (Abulude *et al.*, 2004) on man and animals when consumed (Ita *et al.*, 2008).

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Apart from the side effects, Mushroom mycelia can produce a group of complex extracellular enzymes which can degrade and utilize the lignocellulosic wastes in order to reduce pollution. It has been revealed recently that mushroom mycelia can play a significant role in the restoration of damaged environments.

Saprotrophic, endophytic, mycorrhizal, and even parasitic fungi/mushrooms can be used in mycorestoration, which can be performed in four different ways: mycofiltration (using mycelia to filter water), mycoforestry (using mycelia to restore forests), mycoremediation (using mycelia to eliminate toxic waste), and mycopedicides (using mycelia to control insect pests). These methods represent the potential to create a clean ecosystem, where no damage will be left after fungal implementation (Training Manual on Mushrooms cultivation, 2008).

STORAGE OF MUSHROOMS

At the post-harvest stage, mushrooms need to be stored in fresh condition to maintain their qualities and flavor, some common preservation methods are enumerated below which increase the shelf life of harvested mushrooms. Storage in 0.02-0.03mm dense polythene bags with nitrogen at 0°C is equivalent to 5 weeks of shelf life; storage at 50°C will give the mushroom a shelf life of 4 weeks while storage at 15°C under the same condition will preserve the fungi for 2 weeks. It is noted that storage in controlled atmosphere of 9% oxygen and 25% carbon-dioxide; preservation by gamma-radiation will preserve mushroom for 10 days. Mushrooms can also be freeze-dried. Dehydration, grinding and storage in an air tight container could also be employed. The stored powder can be used for making mushroom soup, mushrooms can be treated and canned (Roy, 1984).

MARKETING

About 160,000 metric tons of mushrooms are produced annually in Japan, half of which is dried and exported. It represents a two billion dollars industry which employs about 200,000 people (Anderson and Marconiller, 2006). Worldwide, the business is worth millions of pounds annually, for the countries of Eastern Europe in particular, wild mushrooms are precious exports. Poland and France are two of the major exporters of mushrooms. In a statement from Allbusiness.com (2003), China is the world's largest edible

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mushroom producer. The country produces about half of all cultivated mushrooms, and around 2.7 kilograms of mushrooms are consumed per person per year by over a billion people.

Authoritative source from Spore (2006) revealed economically, mushrooms growers' association in Uganda sold 44 tons per year to Japan, 40 tons to the US and 2 tons to the Democratic Republic of Congo.

According to Olubanjo *et al*, 2006 in Nigeria, the commercial production and trade s still in its infancy. They attributed this to poor underdeveloped nature of demand for edible, local and cultivated exotic mushrooms. To increase the mushroom marketing, constant advertisement to create awareness, good storage and packaging should be ensured. Good storage and value addition by processing and canning can solve the problem of seasonality in availability (Olubanjo *et al*, 2006). Gradually, mushrooms are income generating.

MEDICINAL VALUE

Medicinal mushrooms are mushrooms, or mushroom extracts, that are used or studied as possible treatments for diseases. *Lentinula edodes* (shiitake), *Grifola frondosa* (maitake), and *Ganoderma lucidum* (reishi), have a history of medicinal use spanning millennia in parts of Asia. Medicinal mushroom research has indicated possible cardiovascular, anticancer, antiviral, antibacterial, antiparasitic, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and antidiabetic activities (Lentinan, 2009).

In Nigeria benefits of mushrooms such as the nutrition, medicinal and mythological uses have been reviewed (Akpaja *et al.*, 2005; Osemwegie *et al.*, 2006). Even Labarere and Menini (2000) acknowledged that the uses of mushroom genetic resources are not only of high interest in agronomy, agriculture, human food and animal feed but also for the discovery, production and development of molecules or components with high added value in industries such as chemical and pharmaceutical industries.

Some mushrooms materials, including polysaccharide, glycoprotein and proteoglycens, modulate immune system responses and inhibit tumor growth. Currently, several extracts have wide spread use in Japan,

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Korea, and China, as adjuncts to radiation treatments and chemotherapy (Smith *et al*, 2002; Borchers *et al*, 2008). Mushrooms that have psychoactive substances have been used as sacraments for healing (Mental and physical) (Hudler 2000). Certain mushrooms, especially polypores like Reishi were thought to be able to benefit a wide variety of health ailments (Sarfraz *et al*, 2009).

Ogbe *et al.*, (2008), in a research carried out, they found out there were improvements of egg-laying and disease resistant capacity of birds when they used *Ganoderma* species. Beta-glucan based dietary supplements of mushroom origin are effective for the treatment of Buruli ulcer caused by *Mycobacterium ulcerans* in Ghana while *Ganoderma lucidum* (Leyss.) Karst. Tested in separate study for the treatment of *Eimeria tenella* infected broiler chickens in Nigeria (Okhuoya *et al.*, 2010).

OTHER USES

According to Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia (2011), mushrooms have been used for dyeing wood and other natural fibers. The chromophores of mushroom dyes are organic compound and produce strong and vivid colors, and all colors of the spectrum can be achieved with mushrooms dyes. Dyes from them have been the source of many dyes before the synthetic ones (Mussak and Bechtold 2009).

In the US, and other developed countries, mushrooms have been used as fire starters. They have also been applied by Ecovative design LLC to produce biodegradable packaging. Presently, they play a role in the development of new biological remediation techniques and filtration technologies (Wikipedia, 2011)

Mushrooms are used as gun powder (Akpaya *et al.*, 2005)

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ANALYSIS OF BIOGAS GENERATED FROM MAIZE WASTE (COB) AND CARROT LEAVES

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KEYWORDS; Biogas, Maize waste (cob), Carrot leaves

ABSTRACT

Biogas is an alternative source of fuel which can be generated by decomposition of organic matter such as sheep dung, agricultural waste, maize waste and carrot leaves. This work comparatively analyzes the biogas generated from maize waste (COB) and carrot leaves. Biogas were generated using locally constructed digesters and they were characterized using standard method. The result of the analysis showed that maize cob gave 640cm³ of the gas during the first week of digestion while the carrot leaves gave 900cm³. After

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the first week, the volume of gas generated continued to decrease. The ash content of the sample was determined and maize cob has 5% while carrot leaves has 20. The concentration of the mineral element showed that the sodium content gave 90ppm and 60ppm for the undigested and digested maize cob respectively, while the concentration of sodium content in the carrot leaves were found to be 1600ppm and 400ppm for both undigested and digested respectively. The concentration of potassium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, and nitrogen in all the samples are in appreciable quantities. The analysis showed that (maize cob waste and carrot leaves), can be used to generate biogas and undigested waste can be used as fertilizer

INTRODUCTION

Energy is a fundamental pillar of modern society as well as being an essential building block for socio-economic development, Unido, (2007). The awareness of the imminent depletion of fossil fuels coupled with a global energy crisis has stimulated interest in the research for alternative energy source. (Garba et al, 1996). Biogas production is the decomposition of organic waste materials by means of bacterial action in the absence of oxygen. The biochemical changes that take place in the digester are caused by a mixed culture of bacteria. (Unido 2007)

The biogas produced can provide a clear fuel in the form of gas that has versatile uses. The remnant from the process usually called the spent slurry is compost manure. Beside the fuel and fertilizer, it can provide ameliorated hygienic and sanitary environment and ecological balance (Garba et al, 2003).

Biogas is flammable gas produced by anaerobic fermentation of organic waste materials. Biogas is composed of methane (55-70%), carbon dioxide (30-40%) and a trace of other gases such as nitrogen, hydrogen carbon monoxide, water and hydrogen sulphide (Asere et al, 1992).

Anaerobic decomposition occurs in three stages Hydrolysis, Acidification and Methanogenic in which the intermediate component are converted to methane

Hydrolysis

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Wastes of plants and animal material consist mainly of carbohydrates, lipids, proteins and inorganic materials. Large molecular complex substances are solubilized into simpler ones with the help of extra-cellular enzyme released by bacteria, this stage is also known as polymer breakdown stage, for example, the cellulose consisting of polymerized glucose is broken down to dimeric, and then the monomeric sugar molecules (glucose) by cellulolytic bacteria (Malami, 2004).

Acidification

The monomer such as glucose produced in stage one is fermented under anaerobic condition into various acids with the help of enzymes produced by the acid forming bacteria at this stage high molecules are broken down into smaller molecules of less carbon atoms (Acids) which are in a more reduced state than

glucose by acid forming bacteria, the main acids produced in this process are ethanoic acid, propanoic acid, butanoic acid and ethanol (Malami, 2004).

Methanisation

The acids produced in the 2nd stage are processed by methanogenic bacteria to produce methane. The methanogenic bacteria act on the organic acids producing (CH₄) and carbon (iv) oxide (CO₂) in two distinctive routes; one is by reducing CO₂ in the presence of hydrogen produced by other bacterial species as in equation (3) and the other by metabolizing the acetic acid substrate as in equation (4) (Malami, 2004). The biochemical processes above mentioned are expressed by the following equations:

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Over important reactions in the production of methane include hydrolysis of carbon (iv) oxide into carbonic acid which is further reduced to methane and water (CH_4 , H_2O), hydrolysis of propanoic acid, ethanol. The equation 5,6, & 8 summarize all.

Hydrolysis

These equation shows that fermentation of these substrates give the same products of methane and carbon dioxide. The organic matter used in the methane fermentation generally contains organic matter and ash. The organic matter is made up of carbohydrates, fats, proteins, tannins, etc.

In the conversion of carbohydrates equal volumes of carbon dioxide and methane are produced. However, not all the CO_2 produced is released, as it is soluble in water. Also CO_2 reacts with (OH) hydroxyl ions to form bio-carbonates.

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$\text{OH} + \text{CO}_2$

The concentration of bicarbonate is affected by pH, temperature and pressure, and other materials in the liquid phase. In consequences, the quantity of methane in this stage is increased by conditions that favoured bicarbonates production, primarily, deamination of biodegradable protein in the first and second stages produces hydroxyl ions, when the ammonia released, dissolved in water.

Ionization of weak base

Furthermore, more when animal and human faeces are used, bacteria excreted in the intestine are the main source of sulphur containing protein. In organic sulphur, particularly sulphates can also be bio-chemically converted to H_2S in the fermentation chamber.

Application of Biogas

Biogas can use in the household, community farm or industry for:

1. Heating, cooking and lighting using domestic biogas stoves and lamps.
2. Electricity generation using internal combustion engine, which can be supplied to isolated communities that are away from national grid or the generation power, can be connected to the national grid. It can also be used for irrigation, pumping water, threshing, flouring, feed processing to mention a few.
3. Agricultural production: it is used in crop drying, baking tea, hatching eggs, cultivation of rice seedling and mushrooms, preservation of fruits, grain storage, seed soaking bio-manure e.g. urea and gaseous fertilizers of carbon dioxide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

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The materials used for this research work are maize waste cob and carrot leaves which were all collected within Sokoto metropolis, Sokoto State Nigeria. All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Determination of Nitrogen Content

2g of each maize waste and carrot leaves was taken and placed in macro keelhaul flask and one tablet of mercury catalyst was added then 20mls of concentrated H₂SO₄. The sample was then taken for digestion in a fumes cupboard on a digestion block at 400°C for 3hrs; it was then allowed to cool for 24hrs. The sample was then made to a known value of 50mls with distilled water 10mls was then pipetted out of this 50mls into a micro keelhaul flask, 20mls of 40% NaOH was added into the flask and it was then made to 50mls with distilled water, then it was taken to the micro keelhaul distillation and digestion apparatus for distillation. On distillation ammonia gas is produced as the distillate which passes through the condenser and become cooled and drops into a conical flask containing 20mls of boric acid indicator which is dark red in colour until when it changes to green and both samples showed similar change in colour. The conical flask content was titrated against 0.01N H₂SO₄ at end point the colour change observed was from green to pink. % Nitrogen content of the sample can be calculated using.

$$\% \text{ N} = \frac{\text{TV} \times \text{M}(0.001) \times \text{V}(0.0014) \times 50 \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times \text{mls of aliquot}}$$

Determination of Phosphorus

5mls of 20% HCl was added to the ashed sample and the filtered, it was then made up to 50mls. 2mls of the filtrate was taken and 2mls of NH₄Cl to extract the phosphorus content in the sample was added followed

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by 2mls of NH_4MoO_4 which developed colour. The solution was made up to 50ml with distilled water and the absorbance at 660\AA with a Jenway 6100 spectrophotometer of both samples was taken separately

which has already been calibrated with standard solution of $\text{NH}_4\text{F} + \text{HCl}$ of 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10ppm the value gotten was used in plotting graph which gives the concentration of phosphorus.

$C \times df \times 25$ $df =$ dilution factor
 $C =$ Conc. Of sample on graph

Determination of Na & K

2mls was taken out of the filtrate from 2.4.8, it was then made up to 50mls with distilled water, it was then taken to flame photometer which has been already calibrated with prepared standard solution of KCl at 0, 2, 6, 8, 10 for determination of potassium and standard solution of NaCl for solution determination was used for the calibration. The results were used in plot in the graph of concentration against absorbance the solution's concentration was used in determination sodium and potassium.

$C \times d.f \times 25$
 $C =$ Concentration of sample on graph
 $Df =$ Dilution factor

Determination of Mg and Ca

- i. 1ml of filtrate from 2.4.8 was diluted with 19mls distilled water to 20mls, 5mls of buffer solution was added followed by 3 drops of KCN, HONH_4HCl , triethanolamine, $\text{K}_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, eriochrome black T indicator, which gave blue colour upon titration with 0.01M EDTA the colour change observed was yellowish pink and give total magnesium and calcium present the formula below can be use in calculating it.

$\text{TV} \times \text{M} (0.01) \times 100/$

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Weight of sample x Vol. of aliquot

- ii. 1ml of sample from 2.4.8 was measured and diluted with 19mls distilled water to 20mls 1ml of 10% NaOH was added followed by 3 drops each of triethanolamine, KCN, HONH_2HCL and a tip of murexide indicator which made the solution purple in colour upon titration with 0.01M EDTA blue colour was observed at end point. Percentage calcium was calculated with formula below:

$\frac{\text{TV} \times \text{M}(0.01) \times 100}{\text{Weight of Sample} \times \text{Vol. of Sample}}$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The results of the analysis carried out in chapter two are recorded in Tables below

Table1 Weekly gas production

NO. OF WEEKS	A	B
1	640 cm ³	900 cm ³
2	330 cm ³	550 cm ³
3	300 cm ³	150 cm ³
4		220 cm ³
5	15 cm ³	30 cm ³
6	5 cm ³	100 cm ³
7	30 cm ³	-
8	60 cm ³	-
	1380 cm ³	1950 cm ³

Key: A = Maize waste (cob), B = Carrot leaves.

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Table 2 Showing results of Ca, Mg, Na, K, N, P, C/N, and O.C.

NUTRIENTS	SAMPLE	UNDIGESTED	DIGESTED
Na in ppm	A	90	50
	B	1600	400
K in ppm	A	320	1400
	B	13000	225
%Ca	A	0.025	0.055
	B	0.065	0.175
%Mg	A	0.035	0.13
	B	0.095	0.192
P in ppm	A	40	290.6\
	B	1125	303.3
% N	A	0.179	0.106
	B	0.567	0.456
C/N	A	190.3	264.5
	B	59.7	54.6
% organic Carbon	A	34.07	27.77
	B	33.84	24.90

Sodium (Na)

The growth of many plants is stimulated by sodium especially in deficiency of potassium; it is a micro element need by plants, which shows essential element for a group of plans exhibiting so-called Hatch-slack path way of carbohydrate metabolism. The result for sodium determination on this work shows that undigested samples of maize waste and carrot leaves with the content of 90ppm and 1600ppm respectively, on the other hand the digested sample has 50ppm and 400ppm respectively showing that the digested sample has lower sodium ion concentration, this could have been due to solubility of sodium compound resulting in having part of the element in effluent water. The sample sludge's can provide required amount

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to soil because the requirement is small and is in most cases provided by the soil itself. This is in contrast with that of (Uba, 2000)

Potassium (K)

This plays a part in the synthesis of carbohydrates in plants and also assist in the synthesis of protoplasmic protein also increase vigour in plants (Samuel, 1970). The K content of undigested samples were determined to be 3200, 1300ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively, also the concentration in the digested samples were 1400, 225ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively all the sludge samples contain adequate amount of potassium, for soil requirement which is 30ppm.

Magnesium (Mg)

It is also a secondary nutrient required in a small quantity by plants and in most cases can be provided by the soil itself. It plays a vital role in photosynthesis being a constituent of chlorophyll. The magnesium content of the undigested samples is 0.035%, 0.095% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively also that of digested samples gave 0.13%, 0.192% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively. The digested samples show a better result. A kilogram of soil for production requires 0.0274g/kg or 27.4mg/kg of potassium

Calcium (Ca)

The calcium requirement in soil for plant production is low. And the results for undigested samples gave 0.025%, 0.065% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively and the digested samples gave 0.055%, 0.175% for maize plant waste and carrot leaves respectively all are expected to give a better yield when applied to the soil for plant growth having low calcium ion content.

Phosphorus (P)

This is a major plant nutrient which stimulates early root formation, growth, flowering and seed formation. Phosphorus requirement for soil for crop production is 0.0274g p/kg soil, (i.e. 27.4ppm), phosphorus

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content determined in this work exceed soil requirement the undigested sample gave 40ppm and 1125ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively and the digested sample gave 290.6ppm, 302.3ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively. This means that carrot leaves has higher content because of higher P content in the plant.

Nitrogen (N)

It is a macro nutrient required by plants for growth at all stages. Plant having dark green coloration shows the soil it grew on, nitrogen induce rapid growth, protein content in crops and better yield. The recommended amount of nitrogen per hectare of land is 120kg. The results for nitrogen determination of undigested samples gave 0.179%, 0.56% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively, and the digested sample gave 0.105%, 0.456%. the carrot leaves has more nitrogen content than the maize waste compared to (Uba, 2000) this can be attributed to moderate nitrogen content in the plant and proper degradation therein. The undigested samples have higher nitrogen content than the digested samples. Which is in support of (Uba, 2000) that it's invariably giving an indication that the anaerobic digestion of the plant material as not good enough due to large amount of nitrogen.

CONCLUSION

The importance of research on biogas cannot be over emphasized considering it is cheap and its availability to the rural populace it also aid the sanitary condition of the rural area. The research carried out showed that both samples produce enough quantity of biogas which can be used to cook, dry crop, irrigate, and pump water. from the analysis, the results obtained in the research work can be concluded as follows.

Beginning of 1st week both samples produced highest yield of biogas, all the samples commence production on the 1st week. the highest daily production of samples B occurred in the first day while sample A 3rd day with 600cm³ and 450cm³ respectively. Biogas can be generated from maize waste and carrot of leaves. The undigested samples are better bio fertilizers than the residue due to their mineral contents. By comparison the gas production by the samples is in this order maize waste > carrot leaves.

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ATTITUDES OF NIGERIANS TOWARDS MUSHROOMS

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KEYWORDS: Mushrooms, mushrooms industry, Likert's scale, positive attitudes, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate the attitudes of Nigerians towards the consumption of mushrooms. This study was undertaken at the Southwest area of the country. Two hundred respondents were administered with questionnaires. The technique of analysing was by Likert's scale. In the analysis of data, all responses of strongly agree and agree were grouped under agreement, while strongly disagree and

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disagree were grouped under disagreement. From the results, the respondents showed positive attitudes towards mushrooms. On this note, we recommended that government and private individuals should embark upon the establishment of mushrooms industries. If these are established and sustained, benefits would include employment generation and others.

INTRODUCTION

Edible mushroom (Fig 1) have for a long time been recognized not only as a delicacy, but also for their use as food in man's diets. Mushrooms have been found to be rich sources of protein, lipids, amino acids, glycogen, vitamins and mineral elements [1]. Mushrooms have many uses which range from medicinal, ceremonial, nutritional and biotechnological based functions [2,3]. During the oil boom in Nigeria, these edible mushrooms were abandoned for costly alternatives like meat, fish, snail, fish, etc. As the economic situation of the people is dwindling, many had to source for protein alternatives. The question now is what are the attitudes of Nigerians towards mushrooms intake? In the light of this, we have been prompted to address this issue by embanking on this survey. The aim of this paper is therefore to determine the attitudes shown to intake of mushrooms by Nigerians. Suggestions were made on the outcome.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methods used for the collection of information were adopted from Yeo [3] with slight modifications. Two hundred respondents were contacted within the Southwest of Nigeria. Stratified sampling was used to capture the various subgroups based on age, sex, and income.

Questionnaires

This was divided into section A (demographic information about the respondents – age, sex, religion, occupation, income, marital status etc). Section B (A Likert's instrument). Ten statements were posed to them and they were expected to provide answers either as strongly agree or agree or undecided or strongly disagree or disagree.

Statistical Analysis

The data gathered were analysed using SPSS Statistics 19 by WebSOFT.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One hundred percent response rate was recorded. This could be the interest now shown on the food. Table 1 shows the results. It was observed that statements 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 had 71, 76, 84, 91 and 87.5%agreements rates. These percentages are positive signals towards mushrooms. The values of 62.5 and 82% recorded for disagreement depicted that not all mushrooms are poisonous and majority believed that religion has nothing to do with mushrooms intake. Less than 20% of the respondents were not sure of what to decide. The 42.5% recorded on cultivation and marketing was expected, the reason been that majority of the respondents were civil servants meaning that there may not be enough time for them to cultivate.

In Nigeria, the mushrooms quantities produced or obtained by local farmers are less than intakes of the consumers. It is on this note we are suggesting that stakeholders, government, and researchers should intensify the efforts in cultivating mushrooms on a large scale. Civil servants should be encourage on how to culture so that at their leisure they too can engage on the on the production rather than going to the forest to pick.

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Table 1: Results of attitudes of consumers

No	Statements	Agree	%	undecided	%	Disagree	%
1.	I like the taste when cooked	142	71	15	7.5	43	21.5
2.	I like the text when cooked	152	76	20	10	28	14
3.	Attractive when cooked	168	84	22	11	10	5
4.	I like eating it with different Soups	182	91	10	5	8	4
5.	It is against my religion	15	7.5	21	10.5	164	82
6.	Mushrooms are medicinal	175	87.5	15	7.5	10	5
7.	It is poisonous	25	12.5	20	10	125	62.6
8.	I can cultivate and market	100	50	15	7.5	85	42.5
9.	I prefer it more than meat and fish	110	55	40	20	50	25
10.	Price of mushroom is higher That of meat and fish	10	5	20	10	170	85

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Agaricus arvensis

Chloropyllum sp.

Macrolepiota sp.

Pycnoporus cinnabarinus

Tremella fuciformis

Pleurotus porrigens

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Pleurotus squarrosulus

icholoma sp

Daldiniacon centrica

Russula sp.

Schizophyllum commune

Scutellinia sp

Thelephora sp

Geastrum saccatus

Microstoma sp.

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Unknown

Auricularia auricula.

Fig 1 : Some mushroom resources found in Nigeria (Source: Osemwegie [4])

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NUTRIENT AND ANTINUTRIENT CONTENT OF *Calotropis procera* FLOWERS

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KEYWORDS: Nutrient, antinutrient, *Calotropis procera* flowers, Edible wild plant

ABSTRACT

Nutrient and antinutritional content of *Calotropis procera* flowers was investigated using standard analytical methods. On dry weight basis, the results showed the following proximate compositions; ash content ($7.50 \pm 1.52\%$), Crude lipid ($4.5 \pm 0.06\%$), Crude protein ($6.0 \pm 0.40\%$) available carbohydrate ($88 \pm 0.49\%$), Crude fibre ($1.5 \pm 0.03\%$), moisture content (61.0 ± 2.10) and calorific value (416kcal/100g). The study shows mineral concentrations of (54.2mg/100g)Na, (106.3mg/100g)K, (3.52mg/100g)P, (38.2mg/100g)Ca, (15.6mg/100g)Mg, (1.32mg/100g)Mn, (16.7mg/100g)Fe, (4.2mg/100g)Cu, (9.6mg/100g)Zn, (0.19mg/100g)Cd, (0.33mg/100g)Co, (0.35mg/100g)Cr, (0.32mg/100g)Pb and (6.33mg/100g)Ni. The concentration of antinutritive factors was observed to be phytate (3.79mg), oxalate (0.54mg), hydrocyanic acid (0.14mg), saponin (0.03mg) and nitrate (0.02mg); were lower than the reference toxic standard levels. Therefore, the flowers of *Calotropis procera* could contribute significantly to the nutrient requirement of man and should be used as a source of nutrients to supplement other major sources.

INTRODUCTION

In most developing nations like Nigeria, numerous types of edible wild plants are exploited as sources of food hence provide an adequate level of nutrition to the inhabitants (Ali, 2010). Edible wild plants are primary sources of medicines, food, shelters and other items used by humans every day. Their roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits and seeds provide food for humans (Edem and Miranda, 2011). Currently, edible wild plants and their products have played a substantial role in tackling the ever – increasing gap between population growth and food supply (Rajeev *et al.*, 2010; Madhumita and Naik, 2010). However, to tackle the problem, more attention has been given on the exploitation and utilization of unusual edible wild plants especially edible flowers which can be a source of nutrient to general populace.

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Many flowers of wild plants are highly consumed in Africa, but Mexico and Central America are probably some of the few areas where flowers are also used as food (Kislinchenko and Velma, 2006; Sotelo, 1997). Hassan *et al.* (2011) reported that, flowers of *Parkia biglobosa* are used as food in North – Western Nigeria especially by rural dwellers when mixed with groundnut cake and other ingredients to make a delicious salad.

Calotropis procera flowers are dense, multiflowered, umbellate cyme arising from the nodes and appearing axillary or terminal; flowers hermaphroditic, pentamerous; pedicle 1 – 3 cm long; calyx 5 – lobed, shortly united at the base (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). Flowers are eaten by goats, occasionally by sheep in time of need and rarely by cattle and other livestock. Nutritional analysis of shade – dried leaves of *Calotropis procera* shows they contain 94% dry matter, 43% acid detergent fibre, 20% ash and 19% crude protein (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). *Calotropis procera* flowers are eaten fresh and used as food in North – Western Nigeria especially by rural dwellers when mixed with groundnut cake and other ingredients to make a delicious dish. It is therefore, the aim of the study is to determine the nutritional and antinutritional potential of the flowers of *Calotropis procera* to ascertain its contribution to the world of food.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and Treatment

The flowers of *Calotropis procera* were obtained from branches of *Calotropis procera* tree at Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria. Identification of the sample was carried out at Botany Unit, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The food samples were washed, oven dried, and finely ground or used fresh for moisture analysis.

Proximate Analysis

The samples was analysed in triplicate using standard AOAC (2006) methods. The determination of crude nitrogen was based on the Kjeldahl procedure and crude protein values were obtained by multiplying the nitrogen value by a factor of 6.25. Estimation of the available carbohydrate was done by the difference method and crude lipids were extracted using soxhlet apparatus. The crude fibre values were determined

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by treating sample with dilute solution of H₂SO₄ and NaOH, the energy calculated using the equation: [energy Kcal/100g= (%CHO x 4) + (%CP x 4) + (%CL x 9)] (Hassan *et al.*, 2008) and ash was obtained after incineration of sample in a Murfle furnace.

Mineral Analysis

The minerals were determined after the sample wet digestion with a mixture of nitric/perchloric/sulphuric acids in the ratio of 9:2:1 v/v respectively. Ca, Na, K, Mg, Fe, Cu, Zn, Ni, Cd, Cr, Mn, Co, and Pb were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer and phosphorus by colorimetric method (AOAC, 2006).

Antinutritional Analysis

The method of Ola and Oboh (2000) was adapted for the determination of phytate. Hydrocyanic acid was determined by the AOAC (2006) method. Oxalate and nitrate were determined by the methods of Krishna and Ranjhan (1980), and saponin content was determined by Obadoni and Ochuka (2001) method.

Data Analysis

The Data obtained were expressed as mean ± standard deviation.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1: Proximate Composition of *Calotropis procera* flowers (%)

Component	Composition
Moisture (wet weight)(%)	61.0 ± 2.10
Ash content (%)	7.50 ± 1.52
Crude protein (%)	6.0 ± 0.40
Crude lipid (%)	4.50 ± 0.50
Carbohydrate (%)	88 ± 3.60
Crude fibre (%)	1.52 ± 0.03
Energy value (kcal/100g)	416.4 ± 0.50

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All values except for moisture are the mean \pm standard deviation of triplicate determinations expressed in dry weight basis.

Table 2: Mineral Composition of *Calotropis procera* Flowers.

Element	Concentration (mg/100g) DW
K	106.3 \pm 0.90
Na	54.2 \pm 0.97
Ca	38.2 \pm 1.56
Mg	15.6 \pm 0.93
P	3.52 \pm 0.08
Fe	16.7 \pm 1.12
Cu	4.2 \pm 0.04
Zn	9.6 \pm 0.56
Cr	0.35 \pm 0.04
Mn	1.32 \pm 0.08
Pb	0.32 \pm 0.04
Co	0.33 \pm 0.10
Ni	6.33 \pm 0.42
Cd	0.19 \pm 0.08

All values mean \pm standard deviation of triplicate

determinations expressed in dry weight basis.
DW = Dry Weight

Table 3: Antinutritional Composition of *Calotropis procera* Flowers

Parameters	<i>C. procera</i> flowers (mg/100gDW)
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Oxalate	0.54 ± 0.12
Phytate	3.79 ± 0.19
Saponins	0.03 ± 0.02
HCN	0.14 ± 0.09
Nitrate	0.02 ± 0.01

Data are mean ± standard deviation of triplicate result

Table 4: Anti-nutrient to nutrient molar ratio of *Calotropis procera* flowers

Anti-nutrient to nutrient ration	Ratio
[Oxalate]/[Ca]	6.28 X 10 ⁻³
[Oxalate]/[Ca + Mg]	3.74 X 10 ⁻³
[Ca][Phytate]/[Zn]	3.74 X 10 ⁻²
[Phytate]/[Ca]	6.01 X 10 ⁻³
[Phytate]/[Fe]	1.92 X 10 ⁻²
[Phytate]/[Zn]	3.91 X 10 ⁻²

DISCUSSION

Proximate composition: The result of proximate analysis showed that the *C. procera* flowers had moisture content of 61.0 ± 2.10% which is low when compared to (73.6 - 93.2 ± 2.6%) reported for some edible flowers (Richard *et al.*, 1996; Sotelo *et al.*, 2007; Madhumita and Naik, 2010 and Hassan *et al.*, 2011). Hassan *et al.*, (2009) and Ruzainah *et al.* (2009) reported that high moisture content is associated with the rise of microbial activities during storage. The ash content of the flowers (7.50 ± 1.52%) compares favorably to 6.50 ± 1.00% in *Parkia biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011), but within the range of 5.8 – 8.6% reported for some edible flowers (Sotelo *et al.*, 2007).

The crude protein content of the flower obtained from the analysis was 6.0 ± 0.40% which is similar to that 6.77% reported for *Parkia biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011) and that of the commonly consumed edible flowers (Sotelo *et al.*, 2007). The value is also lower than 14.9% reported for *C. esculenta* flower

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(Richard *et al.*, 1996). This result shows that *C. procer* flowers contains appreciable amount of protein content. As expected, the crude lipid was low ($4.5 \pm 0.50\%$). The value observed is similar to that of *Aloe vera* (4.2%), *Euphorbia radians* (4.9%) as reported by Sotelo *et al.* (2007) and (4.66%) for *P. biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). This indicates that *C. procer* flower contains low level of crude lipid. The crude fibre content obtained is low when compared to *P. biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). This value is lower than (17.3%) *Erythrina Americana*, (13.8%) *Aloe vera*, (12.7%) *Agave salmiana* (Sotelo *et al.*, 2007) and *C. esculenta* (20.4%) (Richard *et al.*, 1996). Fibre plays a role to a reduction in the incidence of certain diseases like colon cancer, coronary heart diseases, diabetes, high blood pressure, obesity and other digestive disorders (Ekpo, 2007). The flowers of *C. procer* have high carbohydrate content (88%). This was in close range with 78.9% reported for *P. biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011) and 70.4% reported for *C. esculenta* flowers (Richard *et al.*, 1996). The caloric value (416.4kcal/100g) is higher than 388.9kcal/100g reported in *Colocasia esculenta* flowers (Richard *et al.*, 1996), 34kcal/100g in *broccoli* flower (Bushway *et al.*, 2006) and 111kcal/100g in *Madhuca indica* flowers (Madhumita and Naik, 2010). This result shows that *C. procer* flower is a good source of energy to human populace.

Mineral Composition

The concentrations of different mineral elements in the flowers of *C. procer* analyzed were reported in Table 2. The potassium content (106.3mg/100g) is low when compared to 325mg/100g in *broccoli* flower (Bushway *et al.*, 2006). The contents of calcium and magnesium were 38.2 and 15.6mg/100g respectively and were higher than values reported in *Colocasia esculenta* flowers 8.9 and 3.6mg/100g respectively (Richard *et al.*, 1996). Sodium content obtained (54.2mg/100g) is low when compared to 139.2mg/100g for *P. biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011) and 104mg/100g for *Colocasia esculenta* flowers (Richard *et al.*, 1996). However, manganese, zinc, cobalt and chromium contents were 1.32, 9.6, 0.33 and 0.35mg/100g respectively which were lower than respective values reported in *P. biglobosa* flowers (5.3, 17.8, 0.7 and 0.7mg/100g) (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). The *C. procer* flowers also contain a reasonable amount of phosphorus (3.52mg/100g), copper (4.2mg/100g), iron (16.7mg/100g), cadmium (0.19mg/100g), lead (0.32mg/100g) and nickel (6.33mg/100g). Earlier research on humans and livestock has shown that optimal intakes of

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elements such as Na, K, Mg, Ca, Mn, Cu, and Zn can reduce individual's risk factors for health problems such as cardiovascular diseases (Mielcarz *et al.*, 2005).

Antinutritional Composition

The levels of the antinutritional factors are reported in Table 3. The results show that phytate (3.79mg), oxalate (0.54mg), hydrocyanic acid (0.14mg), nitrate (0.02mg) and saponin (0.03mg) determined are all below the recommended toxic levels caused by the presence of antinutritional factors (Birgitta and Gullick, 2000). The phytate value is high compared to that of *Parkia biglobosa* flower (1.41mg/100g) reported by (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). The oxalate content is higher than (0.03mg/100g) reported for *Parkia biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). High concentration of phytate causes adverse effect on digestibility (FAO, 1990). The HCN value obtained was quite similar compared to (0.17mg/100g) reported for *Parkia biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). The nitrate content of this flower is also lower than (1.32mg/100g) reported for *Parkia biglobosa* flower (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). The saponin value obtained is 0.03 ± 0.06 mg/100g. Saponins are known to reduce the uptake of certain nutrients like glucose and cholesterol at the gut through intra – luminal physiochemical interaction (Price *et al.*, 1987). Esenwah and Ikenebomeh, (2008), and El – adway. (2002) reported that, high contents of some of the antinutrients can be reduced through soaking, boiling and fermentation process.

To predict the bioavailability of elements such as calcium, iron and zinc antinutrients ratios were calculated. From the results, it was observed that, the values reported in [Oxalate]/[Ca], [Oxalate]/[Ca + Mg], [Ca] [phytate]/[Zn], [phytate]/[Zn] and [phytate]/[Ca] ratios are lower than the values reported for *Parkia biglobosa* flower ratios (Hassan *et al.*, 2011). However, the ratios were below the critical level to impaired zinc and calcium bioavailability (Hassan *et al.*, 2008).

CONCLUSION

This study showed that *C. procer* flowers contain high percentage of carbohydrate, calorific value which makes it a good source of human energy. It also contains enough essential nutrients like protein, lipid and mineral elements. However, the result also indicates low level of antinutrients thus; the plant could be used

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as source of food since most of the antinutritional factors are also eliminated in the broth or inactivated during the boiling process to reduce the levels of antinutrients.

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PROXIMATE ANALYSIS AND PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF SOME COMMONLY USED FOOD SPICES IN SOUTH-EAST NIGERIA

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KEYWORDS: Proximate, Phytochemical, Ethno- medicinal, Spices, Nutrition.

ABSTRACT

Spices and herbs are potent sources of natural antioxidants. The proximate composition and phytochemical constituents of some commonly used food spices in South-East Nigeria were analyzed. The result showed that *Tetrapleura tetraptera* has the highest percentage per weight ash followed by *Xylopia aethopica*, *Monodora myristica*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Chrysobal anusicaco* and *Afromo mumdanielli* (9.42, 6.97, 6.49, 5.94, 5.89 and 3.35%) respectively. The percentage crude protein contents are 7.80, 13.89, 21.67, 11.65, 6.78 and 10.94 respectively. The percentage crude fibre contents are 18.56, 9.28, 7.38, 9.06, 11.24 and 13.00 respectively. The percentage carbohydrate contents are 54.66, 52.94, 41.02, 54.26, 61.36 and 53.48 respectively, while fat moisture contents are 4.45, 7.81, 13.24, 9.21, 4.79, 7.16 and 5.11, 9.59, 9.72, 9.88, 9.94, 11.63 respectively. The phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of Flavonoids, anthraquinones, saponin, phenol, tannin, alkaloids, cardiac glycosides and terpenoids in all the tested spices, with the exception of anthraquinone which was not detected in *Afromo mumdanielli*. This is an indication that spices add nutritional and ethno-medicinal values to the diet.

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INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are important elements of traditional medicine in virtually all cultures. The idea that certain plants had healing potential was known long before human beings discovered the existence of pathogens. The therapeutic efficacies of many indigenous plants for various diseases have been described by traditional herbal medicine practitioners. Biologically active compounds present in medicinal plants have been of great interest to scientists working in the field. Phytochemical studies have attracted the attention of plant scientists due to the development of new and sophisticated techniques. These techniques played a significant role in giving the solution to systematic problems on the one hand and in the search for additional resources of raw materials for pharmaceutical industry on the other hand. Plants synthesize a wide variety of chemical compounds, which can be sorted by their chemical class, biosynthetic origin and functional groups into primary and secondary metabolites (Mukherjee and Laloraya, 1977). Primary metabolites make up the physical integrity of the plant cell and are involved with the primary metabolic process of building and maintaining of living cells. Secondary metabolites do not seem to be vital to the immediate survival of the organism that produces them and are not an essential part of the process of building and maintaining living cells, but are responsible for their therapeutic potentialities (Sharanabasappa *et al*, 2007). Many of the indigenous medicinal plants are used as spices and food plants.

A spice is a dried seed, fruit, root, bark or vegetative substance primarily used for flavouring, colouring or preserving food. Sometimes, a spice is used to hide other flavours (Scully, 1995). The cravings for spices have been one of the great factors in human progress and have done much to change the course of history and geography and to promote international relations (Akindahunsi and Salawu, 2005). Spices are used to season insipid foods and to add zest to an otherwise monotonous diet. They stimulate the appetite and increase the flow of gastric juice. For this reason they are often referred to as food accessories or adjuncts. They also play a role in many other industries, and are used in perfumery, soaps, incense, as dyes in histology and in various arts (Onyesom and Okoh, 2006).

Studies on spices have been mostly on their exciting flavors and aromas, medicinal values and as flavoring agents. These spices are said to be therapeutically useful in the management of several ailments which

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include convulsion, leprosy, stomachache, inflammation, rheumatoid pains, cough, loss of appetite, gastrointestinal disorder (Okwu, 2004; Valko et al., 2007). The spices are used for preparing soups for mothers

from the first day of delivery to prevent postpartum contraction and aid lactation (Okwu, 1999; 2001). They are also used for spicing meat and other foods. Most of these spices have been associated with abundant bitter principle which is claimed to reduce blood sugar levels, and their liquor taken as a purge for colic, stomach pains, and worm infections. It is also believed that newborn babies grow rapidly when they are fed with food made of these spices (Roger, 2002). The spices grow commonly in high forest areas of the South Eastern region of Nigeria, as climbers, perennial creepers, or slim shrubs and trees and are available all year round (Sofowora, 1993). Proximate and nutrient analysis of medicinal plants, edible fruits and vegetables plays a crucial role in assessing their nutritional significance (Pandey *et al.*, 2006). As various medicinal plant species are also consumed as food along with their medicinal benefits, evaluating their nutritional significance can help to understand the worth of these plant species (Pandey *et al.*, 2006). There are also various claims about the usefulness of these spices, especially their use in fattening homes, and remarkable growth of new born babies whose mothers use these spices. In addition, the World Health Organization supports the use of traditional medicine provided they are proven to be efficacious and safe (WHO 1985). In some developing countries, a huge number of people still live in extreme poverty and some are suffering and dying for want of safe water and medicine, they have no alternative for primary health care. There is therefore the need to look inwards to search for medicinal plants with the aim of validating the ethno-medicinal use and subsequently the isolation and characterization of compounds which will be added to the potential list of drugs. This study therefore focuses on the phytochemical and proximate composition of these spices. The results of this study will aid in appreciating the acclaimed medicinal properties of these spices and their age long usage by the people of South East of Nigeria. The spices analyzed were *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Chrysobalanus Icaco*, *Fromomum danielli*, *Xylopi aethopica*, *Monodora myristica* and *Tetrapleura tetraptera*. These spices have been described variously by Smith *et al.*, 1996.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

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Processing of samples

The spices were bought as sold from Oyingbo market Lagos state of Nigeria, and identified taxonomically at the Department of Botany, Olabisi Onabanjo University Ago Iwoye, Ogun State. The samples were washed with distilled water and dried in the oven at 65°C. The dried samples were milled in an Arthur Thomas coated milling machine and screened through 1 mm sieve to obtain a fine powder of processed sample. These were kept in separate air tight containers for later use.

Proximate analysis

The proximate analysis (carbohydrate, fats, protein, moisture, fibre and ash) of spices sample was determined by using AOAC (1995) methods. Carbohydrate was determined by difference method (100 – (protein + fat + moisture + fibre + ash)). The nitrogen value, which is the precursor for protein of a substance, was determined by micro-Kjeldahl method (Guebel et al., 1991). The nitrogen value was converted to protein by multiplying with a factor of 6.25. The moisture and ash were determined using weight difference method while determination of crude lipid content of the spices sample was done using Soxhlet type of the direct solvent extraction method while crude fibre was determined using acid/base method. The solvent used was petroleum ether (boiling range 40 to 60°C). All the proximate values were reported in percentage (AOCS, 2000; Okwuand Morah, 2004).

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical screening procedures carried out were adapted from the previous work on plant analysis (Sofowora, 1993; Trease and Evans, 1996; Harbourne, 1998). This analysis determines the biologically active nonnutritive compounds that contribute to the flavor, colour and other characteristics of plant parts. They are flavonoid, anthraquinone, saponin, phenol, tannin, alkaloid, cardiac glycoside and terpenoid.

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Reagents and apparatus

All the reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade obtained from Sigma Chemical Co and Randox laboratories Ltd authorized distributors in Nigeria. Distilled water and acid washed glassware were used throughout the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: The proximate composition of the spices (%)

Sample	Ash	Protein	Crude fibre	Carbohydrate	Fat	Moisture
<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	9.42	7.80	18.56	54.66	4.45	5.11
<i>Xylopia aethopica</i>	6.97	13.89	9.28	52.94	7.81	9.59
<i>Monodora myristica</i>	6.49	21.69	7.38	41.02	13.24	9.72
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	5.94	11.65	9.06	54.26	9.21	9.88
<i>Chrysobalanus icaco</i>	5.89	6.78	11.24	61.36	4.79	9.94
<i>Aframomum danielli</i>	3.35	10.94	13.00	53.48	7.16	11.63

Table 1 shows the result of the proximate composition of the spices studied, and it was observed that *M. myristica* had the highest protein and fat content out of all the spices that were analyzed; 21.69% and 13.24% respectively. While *C. icaco* had the least 6.78% protein content and *T. tetraptera* had the least fat 4.45%. However, the fat content in *T. tetraptera* was very close to the content in *C. icaco* which was 4.79%. *X. aethopica* had the second highest protein content of 13.89% and this was followed by *S. aromaticum* with a protein content of 11.65%. *T. tetraptera* had the highest ash content of 9.42% and the highest crude fibre content of 18.56%. It also had the second highest carbohydrate content of 54.66% with

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C. icaco having the highest carbohydrate content of 61.36% and the second highest crude fibre content of 11.24%. *A. danielli* had the least ash content of 3.35%, while *M. myristica* had the least crude fibre content of 7.38%. *A. danielli* had the second highest crude fibre content and *M. myristica* had the least carbohydrate content 41.02%. *A. danielli* had the highest moisture content of 11.63% with *T. tetraptera* having the least at 5.11%. The moisture contents of the remaining spices were rather very close ranging from 9.59% in *X. aethopica* to 9.94% in *C. icaco*

These results supports previous studies carried out by Uhegbu *et al*, 2011, where of all spices studied, *M. myristica* had the highest fat content at $14.66 \pm 0.03\%$, which is close to the value of 13.24% obtained in our laboratory. Also, *T. tetraptera* had the highest ash content of $10.36 \pm 0.03\%$, which is also close to the value of 9.42% obtained in our laboratory for the same sample. Uhegbu *et al* obtained a protein content of $11.90 \pm 0.06\%$ for *X. aethopico* to make it the sample with the highest protein content while in our laboratory, it was the second highest protein containing sample at 13.89%.

The high carbohydrate content in all the spices indicates that they can be ranked as carbohydrate rich food sources. The moderate fat content indicates that these spices are not sources of lipid accumulation which can cause arteriosclerosis and aging (Anita *et al*, 2006). Carbohydrate, protein and fat are macro nutrients and as such are needed by the body in large amounts for growth, metabolism and for other body functions. Regular use of plant foods rich in protein makes a valuable addition to a diet (Wardlaw and Kessel, 2002). We need protein for growth (especially important for children, teens, and pregnant women), tissue repair, immune function, making essential hormones and enzymes, energy when carbohydrate is not available, preserving lean muscle mass amongst other things. Fats insulate and protect body organs. It is

also essential for normal growth and development, energy (fat is the most concentrated source of energy), absorbing and transporting certain vitamins (like vitamins A, D, E, K, and carotenoids), maintaining cell membranes, providing taste, consistency, and stability to foods. The minimal intake of carbohydrate is 50 to 100 g per day, 60% of total energy intake is a typical recommendation (Wardlaw and Kessel, 2002). High carbohydrate; low fat diet aids control of hypertension and prevent obesity. Fat and protein stimulate

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the release of the hormone –gastric inhibitory peptide (GIP) from the walls of the small intestine. GIP slows the release of stomach contents into the small intestine (Wardlaw and Kessel, 2002). Fiber refers to certain types of carbohydrates that our body cannot digest. These carbohydrates pass through the intestinal tract intact and help to move waste out of the body. Diets that are low in fiber have been shown to cause problems such as constipation and hemorrhoids and to increase the risk of certain types of cancers such as colon cancer. Diets high in fiber; however, have been shown to decrease risks of heart disease, obesity, and they help lower cholesterol. The high chemical content of these spices tend to lend support for the benefits the consumer may derive. Rich macronutrients of food are beneficial to the body (Okaka and Okaka, 2001).

Table 2: phytochemical content of the spices

	<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	<i>Xylopi aethiopica</i>	<i>Monodora myristica</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	<i>Chrysobalanus icaco</i>	<i>Afromomum danielli</i>
Flavonoids	+	++	+	++	++	++
Anthraquinone	++	++	+	+	+	-
Saponin	+	++	+	++	+	+
Phenol	+	+	+	+	++	++
Tannin	+	+	+	+	+	+
Alkaloid Hager's Test	++	+++	++	++	+++	+++
Dragendorff's Test	-	++	+	-	-	++
Cardiac glycoside	++	++	++	+	++	++
terpenoid	++	++	+	+	+	+

+++ : Very strong presence

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++: Strong presence

+: Mild presence

-: Absent

Table 2 shows the result of phytochemical composition of the seeds. They all contain the phytochemicals; Flavonoids, Anthraquinones, Saponins, Phenols, Tannins, Alkaloids, Cardiac glycosides and terpenoids at varying intensities with the exception of *A. danielli* which showed no indication of the presence of anthraquinones. The Dragendorff's test seemed to be a more precise test for the indication of the presence of alkaloids because, from the results, absence of alkaloids or presence with lesser intensity were indicated with the reagents in cases where Hager's reagent had indicated the presence of the metabolite with a greater intensity. This may be connected with the fact that in the confirmatory test for the presence of alkaloids, using Thin-Layer Chromatography (TLC) method, the chromatogram is eventually sprayed with Dragendorff's reagent to indicate the presence of alkaloids (Sofowora, 1993). Thus, the Dragendorff's test is a more precise test for the presence of alkaloids.

Flavonoid was indicated strongly in *X. aethopica*, *S. aromaticum*, *C. icaco* and *A. danielli* while it was mildly detected in *T. tetraptera* and *M. myristica*. Anthraquinone was strongly detected in *T. tetraptera* and

X. aethopica, it was mildly detected in *M. myristica*, *S. aromaticum*, *C. icaco* and not detected in *A. danielli*. *T. tetraptera* indicated mild presence of saponin, phenol and tannin, with the presence of alkaloid strong with Hager's test, while it was not detectable using Dragendorff's test. Cardiac glycoside and terpenoid were also strongly detected in *T. tetraptera* and *X. aethopica*. Hager's test for alkaloid indicated a very strong presence in *X. aethopica*, *C. icaco* and *A. danielli* and a strong presence of alkaloid in *M. myristica* and *S. aromaticum*. Dragendorff's test on the other hand indicated a strong presence of alkaloid in *X. aethopica* and *A. danielli*, a mild presence of alkaloid in *M. myristica* and no indication for the presence of alkaloid in *S. aromaticum* and *C. icaco*. Presence of cardiac glycoside was strongly indicated in *M. myristica*, *C. icaco* and *A. danielli* and mildly indicated *M. myristica*, *S. aromaticum*, *C. icaco* and *A. danielli*. saponin was strongly indicated in *X. aethopica* and *S. aromaticum*. It was mild in *T. tetraptera*, *M.*

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myristica, *C. icaco* and *A. danielli*. The presence of phenol on the other hand was mild in *T.tetraptera*, *X.aethopica*, *M. myristica*, *S. aromaticum* and strong in *C. icaco* and *A. danielli*. The presence of tannin was mild in all the tested spices.

The medicinal value of plants lies in some chemical substances that have a definite physiological action on the human body. Different phytochemicals have been found to possess a wide range of activities, which may help in protection against chronic diseases. Alkaloids protect against chronic diseases such as cancer, it also possesses antimicrobial properties, it is also used in the treatment of malaria, it is used occasionally for the prevention of nocturnal leg cramps caused by vascular spasms amongst others (Kasolo *et al.*, 2010). Saponins protect against hypercholesterolemia, and also have a broad spectrum of biological and pharmacological activities such as anti-inflammatory, anti-hepatotoxin, hypoglycemic, antimicrobial and anti-viral activities (Price *et al.*, 1987, Oakenful and Sidhu, 1989). Although some saponins have been shown to be highly toxic under experimental conditions, acute poisoning is relatively rare both in animals and man. Studies have illustrated the beneficial effects on blood cholesterol levels, cancer, bone health and stimulation of the immune system. Flavonoids are widely distributed in plants fulfilling many functions. They have been shown to have antifungal activity *in vitro* (Galeotti *et al.*, 2008). The potent antioxidant activity of flavonoids reveals their ability to scavenge hydroxyl radicals, superoxide anions and lipid peroxy radicals, this may be the most important function of flavonoids (Alan and Miller, 1996). In addition, flavonoids help to strengthen capillary walls. The compound at times is referred to as phytoestrogens. Phytoestrogens are associated with relief of menopausal symptoms, reduction of osteoporosis, improvement of blood cholesterol levels and lowering the risk of certain hormone-related cancer and coronary heart disease. They also induce mechanisms that may kill cancer cells and inhibit tumor invasion (Williams *et al.*, 2004). Tannins are effective in curbing hemorrhages as well as restrict bare swellings. While tannins are proved haemostatic, they are also beneficial when applied on mucosal coating in mouth. Hence, herbs possessing tannins are widely used as mouthwashes, eyewashes, snuff and even as vaginal douches and also treat rectal disorders (Elvin-lewis *et al.*, 1977). When applied internally, tannins affect the walls of the stomach and other digestive parts. They sour the mucus secretions and contract or squeeze the membranes in such a manner that secretions from the cells are restricted. Long-term and/or excessive use of herbs/vegetables containing high concentrations of tannins is not recommended (Reed, 1995). As such, the

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mild presence of tannin in all the spices is beneficial in its medicinal use. Anthraquinones have an irritant laxative effect on the large intestine, causing contractions of the intestinal walls and stimulating a bowel movement and make the stool more liquid thereby easing bowel movements. Cardiac glycoside contains digitoxin, digoxin and ditoxin. It has a strong and direct action on the heart, helping to support its strength and rate of contraction when it is failing. Phenols are strong antioxidants which prevent oxidative damage to biomolecules such as DNA, lipids and proteins which play a role in chronic diseases such as cancer and cardiovascular disease. Plant phenols may interfere with all stages of the cancer process, potentially resulting in a reduction of cancer risk (Hollman, 2001). Terpenoids have been found to be useful in the prevention and therapy of several diseases, including cancer, and also to have antimicrobial, antifungal, antiparasitic, antiviral, anti-allergic, antispasmodic, antihyperglycemic, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties (Rabi and Bishayee, 2009; Wagner and Elmadfa, 2003; Sultana and Ata, 2008). In addition, terpenoids can be used as protective substances in storing agriculture products as they are known to have insecticidal properties (Theis and Lerda, 2003).

CONCLUSION

The screening of the spices for their proximate composition and phytochemical constituents shows that apart from having nutritional importance, they also have the potential to act as sources of useful drugs and thereby improving the health status of the consumers as a result of the presence of various phytochemicals that are vital for good health. Thus, validating their medicinal usage by the people of South-East Nigeria.

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ANALYSIS OF SCIENCE STUDENTS' SSCE RESULT USING PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

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KEYWORDS: WAEC results, students' performance, subjects areas

ABSTRACT

This research work intends to detect the subjects that contribute to the inconsistency in the relationship among the subjects of studied by using the method of Principal Component Analysis that was used to investigate the variability among the subjects. The data used for the analysis is students' WAEC results for the year 2011, Federal Science College, Sokoto. Out of fourteen subjects areas which the students sat for, nine subjects were used for the study. Single sets were formed that consists Economics, Geography, English Language, Hausa-Language, Mathematics, Agricultural Science, Biology, Chemistry, and Physics. Nine Components were formed, while only six Components were considered showing the subjects that contribute significantly to the variation and inconsistency among the subjects. However, there should be concentration on the subjects that contribute a high variation to check the students' performance.

INTRODUCTION

Principal component analysis is one of the methods that can be used to analyse multivariate dataset. It can reduce the dimensionality of large data set which consists of a number of interrelated variables to smaller components (Hussain et. al. 2011).

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Several authors including Anderson (1958), Marada, et. al.(1979), Jolliffe (1986), Hair et. al. (1998), Anderson, et. al. (1998) established that in principal component Analysis, we seek to maximize the variance of a linear combination of the variables. Essentially, Principal component is a one-sample technique applied to data with no groupings among the observations and no partitioning of the variables into subset y and x. Principal components are concerned only with the core structure of a single sample of observations on p variables. None of the variables is designated as dependent, and no grouping of observations is assumed (Rencher, 2002). The first principal component is the linear combination with maximal variance; we are essentially searching for a dimension along which the observations are maximally separated or spread out. The second principal component is the linear combination with maximal variance in a direction orthogonal to the first principal component, and so on.

Principal components are used to reduce the number of dimensions. Another useful dimension reduction device is to evaluate the first two principal components for each observation vector and construct a scatter plot to check for multivariate normality, outliers, and so on. Everitt and Dunn (1991) and Antonio, et. al.(2010) pointed out that, in general, the first few principal components are sensitive to outliers that inflate variances or distort co variances, and the last few are sensitive to outliers that introduce artificial dimensions or mask singularities.

For example, we might want to rank students on the basis of their scores on achievement test in English, Mathematics, Reading, and so on. An average score would provide a single scale on which to compare the students, but with unequal weights we can spread the students out further on the scale and obtain a better ranking.

Data used for the Analysis

The data used for the study were collected from Federal Science College, Sokoto.

The data consist of scores of 100 students for 2011 WEST AFRICA EXAMINATION COUNCIL (WAEC) Exams. Out of Fourteen Subjects areas which the students sat for, nine subjects are used. The selection was based on the number of students that sat for the interested subjects of study. The nine subjects were put in a

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single Set. The Set consists of Economics, Geography, English Language, Hausa-Language, Mathematics, Agricultural Science, Biology, Chemistry, and Physics.

Principal Component Analysis

The steps involved in the analysis of principal component analysis include the following methods as below. Algebraically, principal components are particular linear combinations of the p random variables.

Geometrically, these linear combinations represent the selection of new coordinate system obtained by rotating the original system with their development and does not require a multivariate normal assumption. On the other hand, principal components derived for multivariate normal populations have useful interpretations in terms of the constant ellipsoids.

Step 1: get the data

Consider the linear combinations:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= a_1'X = a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + \dots + a_{1p}X_p \\ Y_2 &= a_2'X = a_{21}X_1 + a_{22}X_2 + \dots + a_{2p}X_p \\ &\cdot \\ &\cdot \\ &\cdot \\ Y_p &= a_p'X = a_{p1}X_1 + a_{p2}X_2 + \dots + a_{pp}X_p \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

Step 2: standardise the data

Sometimes it makes sense to compute principal component for raw data. This is appropriate when all the variables are in the same units. Standardizing the data is often preferable when the variables are in different

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units or when the variance of different columns is substantial. This can be done by subtracting the means of each column and dividing by its standard deviation namely:

$$Z = \frac{(X - \mu_i)}{\sqrt{\sigma_{ii}}}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (3.2)$$

In matrix notation, it is given by:

$$Z = (V^{1/2})^{-1}(X - \mu) \quad (3.3)$$

where $V^{1/2}$ is the diagonal standard deviation matrix. From this, we obtain mean of Z equal zero, $E(Z) = 0$.

Step 3: calculate the covariance matrix.

Further, the covariance matrix of Z is calculated using the formula below

$$COV(Z) = (V^{1/2})^{-1} \Sigma (V^{1/2})^{-1} = \rho \quad (3.4)$$

where ρ also known as correlation.

Step 4: calculate the eigenvectors and Eigen values of the covariance matrix

The principal components of Z may be obtained from eigenvectors of the correlation matrix ρ of X , refer to equation (1.3).

The i^{th} principal component of the standardised variables $Z' = [Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_p]$ with $Cov(Z) = \rho$ is given by

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$$Y_i = \rho_i' Z = \rho_i' (V^{1/2})^{-1} (X - \mu), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (3.5)$$

The eigenvectors of correlation matrix are also known as principal components coefficients or principal component loadings

Moreover,

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \text{Var}(Y_i) = \sum_i \text{Var}(Z_i) = q \quad (3.6)$$

and

$$\rho_{Y_i, Z_k} = e_{ik} \sqrt{\lambda_i}, \quad i, k = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (3.7)$$

In this case, $(\lambda_1, e_1), (\lambda_2, e_2), \dots, (\lambda_p, e_p)$ are the Eigen values-eigenvectors pairs with $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \lambda_p \geq 0$.

As seen from equation (1.5), the total (standard variables) population variance is simply q , the sum of the diagonal elements of the matrix ρ , then the proportion of the total variance explained by the K^{th} principal component of Z is :

$$\frac{\lambda_k}{q}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (3.8)$$

where the $\lambda_{k's}$ are the Eigen values of ρ .

In short, principal component analysis consists of finding linear transformations Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_p of the original variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p , that have the property of being uncorrelated.

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The Y variables are chosen in such a way that Y_1 has maximum variance, Y_2 has maximum variance to being uncorrelated with Y_1 , and so on.

Bartlett's Test

Bartlett's Test is used to test the homogeneity of variance in the components. Test hypothesis :

$$H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k$$

$$H_1 : \delta_i \neq \delta_j \text{ for atleast one pair } (i, j)$$

Test Statistic:

$$T = \frac{(N - k) \ln S_p^2 - \sum_{i=1}^k (N_i - 1) \ln S_i^2}{1 + (1 / (3(k - 1))) (\sum_{i=1}^k 1 / (N_i - 1)) - 1 / (N - k)} \quad (3.9)$$

In the above, S_i^2 is the variance of the i^{th} group, N is the total sample size, N_i is the sample size of the i^{th} group, k is the number of groups, and S_p^2 is the pooled variance. The pooled variance is weighted

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average of the group variance and is defined as: $S_p^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k (N_i - 1)S_i^2 / (N - k)$.

(3.10) Significance Level: $\alpha = 0.05$

Critical Region: The variances are judged to be unequal if, $T > \chi_{(\alpha, k-1)}^2$

Where $\chi_{(\alpha, k-1)}^2$ is the upper critical value of the chi-square distribution with k-1 degree of freedom and a significance level of α .

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Bartlett's test

Test hypothesis:

$$H_0: \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_K$$

$$H_1: \delta_i \neq \delta_j \text{ For at least one pair } (i, j)$$

Reject H_0 if $p\text{-value} < \alpha = 0.05$

From the Bartlett's Test, Approximation chi-square equals 113.04 with degree of freedom of 36, probability level of 0.000, at $\alpha = 0.05$, we therefore reject H_0 and conclude that the variances across the variables are not equal.

In this regard, this calls for the use of Principal Component Analysis; to see the variables i.e. the subjects that posse's high variability contribution to the set of components considered.

Therefore, table 1 shows the Eigen values in column two, which are the proportions of total variance in all the variables, which are accounted for by the components. From the output component, one gives the

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highest variance explained followed by component two which gives the second highest variance explained and so on. The second component is formed from the variance remaining after those associated with the first component has been extracted, thus this account for the second largest amount of variance. It is worthwhile to note that the principal component coefficient that gives the variance explained for each component gives the value of less than 30% of the variance explained. Therefore, more than one component is needed to describe the variability of the data. In other to obtain a meaningful interpretation of the principal component analysis, we need to reduce to fewer than nine (9) components. In this study, we use the common decision in which we retain only the component with about 80% of variance explained. Therefore, from column 3 i.e. extraction Eigen Values for the retained components, we observed that six components are retained together with their percentage of variance explained by each component. The cumulative variance give as well, shows that the first six components account for about 82.37% of the total variance in the data. Rencher (2002)

A component's Eigen value may be computed as the sum of its squared component loadings for the entire variable.

A component's Eigen value divided by the number of variables (which equals the sum of variances because the variance of a standardized variance equals to 1.0) gives the percentage of variance in all the variables, which it explains. The ratio of Eigen values is the ratio of explanatory importance of the component with respect to the variable. And, so if a component has a low Eigen value less than the standardized variance i.e. 1, then it is contributing little to the explanatory importance of variance in the variable and may be ignored as redundant with more important components.

Table 1: Total Variance Explained by each Component

Components	Initial Eigen Values	Extraction Eigen Values for the retained components
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S/NO	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.4726	27.47	27.47	2.4726	27.47	27.47
2	1.3276	14.75	42.22	1.3276	14.75	42.22
3	1.0777	11.97	54.20	1.0777	11.97	54.20
4	0.8765	9.74	63.94	0.8765	9.74	63.94
5	0.8360	9.29	73.23	0.8360	9.29	73.23
6	0.8231	9.15	82.37	0.8231	9.15	82.37
7	0.6276	6.97	89.35			
8	0.5257	5.84	95.19			
9	0.4330	4.81	100.00			

Table 2 shows the communalities which measures the percent of variance in a given row explained by all the components. That is, the communality is the squared multiple correlation for the variable using the components as predictors. Communality for a variable is the sum of squared components loadings for that variable (row) and is the percent of variance due to the variable explained by all the components. For full orthogonal Principal Component Analysis, the communality will be 1.0 and all of the variance in the variables will be explained by all the components. Which their number equals that of the variables and is written under initial. The extracted communalities, is the percent of variance in a given variable explained by the components are the extracted, which are normally fewer in number than the original variables which led the coefficient to be less than 1.0.

Table 2: Communalities Extracted By each Variable

Variables	Initial	Extraction
Economics	1.0000	0.9769
Geography	1.0000	0.7832
English Language	1.0000	0.8567
Hausa Language	1.0000	0.7856

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Mathematics	1.0000	0.8570
Agric. Science	1.0000	0.8222
Biology	1.0000	0.8650
Chemistry	1.0000	0.6963
Physics	1.0000	0.7706

Table 3: Component Loading

Variables	Comp. 1	Comp. 2	Comp. 3	Comp. 4	Comp. 5	Comp. 6
Economics	-0.3435	-0.0590	0.6317	0.4752	0.1008	-0.4694
Geography	-0.6309	-0.1332	0.0061	-0.1475	-0.5694	-0.1466
Eng. Language	-0.4650	0.0448	0.4910	-0.6077	0.1571	-0.0590
Hau. Language	-0.4235	0.6985	-0.0289	0.3117	-0.0172	0.1415
Mathematics	-0.5520	-0.9970	-0.2723	-0.0619	0.6793	-0.0549
Agric. Science	-0.4050	0.6056	-0.3188	-0.2570	-0.0845	-0.3417
Biology	-0.5623	0.0694	0.3291	0.0222	-0.0251	0.6592
Chemistry	-0.6901	-0.1269	-0.3273	0.3036	-0.0354	0.0508
Physics	-0.5470	-0.6472	-0.2130	-0.0065	-0.0791	-0.0289

Table 3 is going to be used for interpretation. Interpretation for component loadings in principal components are similar to interpretation of coefficients for factor analysis and coefficients in multiple regressions as well as canonical loadings in Canonical correlation Analysis. We want to have some criterion, which helps us determine which of these are large and which of these are considered to be negligible.

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1. In Component 1, the percentage amount of variability explained, contributed by the coefficient of each variable. Economics has the highest coefficient with (-0.3435) followed by Agricultural Science (-0.4050) and Hausa Language (-0.4650), and to a lesser extent Chemistry (-0.6901).
2. Component 2, Hausa Language with (0.6985) has the highest contribution to the variability, followed by Agricultural Science (0.6056) and Biology (0.0694) and English Language (0.0448).
3. Component 3 is primarily related to Economics (0.6317), English Language (0.4910), and Biology (0.3291). As Economics increases, the other two subjects increase as well.
4. Component 4 is primarily related to Economics (0.6793), Hausa Language (0.3117) and Chemistry (0.3036). As Economics increases, the two other subjects increase as well, almost all the other subjects decrease.
5. Component 5 is primarily related to Mathematics (0.6592), and English Language (0.1517).
6. Component 6 is primarily related to Biology (0.6592) only. As From the Table 1.2 of communalities, it can be seen that all the causes are well represented, we can think of the value as multiple R^2 values for regression model predicting the variable of interest. The communality for a given variable can be interpreted as the proportion of variance in that variable explained by the 6 factors. In other word, if multiple regressions is performed on Biology against the 6 factors, therefore $R^2 = 0.865$ which is about 86.5% of the variable due to variation in Biology is explained by factors model. The results suggest that principal component analysis does the best job of explaining level of variation in Biology.

CONCLUSION

Principal component analysis was applied and showed six groups of closely inter-related subjects based on the fact that six components were used. It is also shown in Table 3 that values that close zero correlating a variable and a component can be dropped which indicates variable reduction. The strongest inter-related subjects are found in the beginning column of table 3 and decrease through the last column. The 27% of the variability captured by the inter-related variables is due to the contribution of all the subjects but Economics, Agricultural Science and Hausa Language contribute significantly. However, there should be more concentration on the subjects that contribute to the inconsistency in the students' performance.

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SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH

ACCESSIBILITY TO MOBILE TELECOMMUNICATION SERVICES AND ADOPTION OF E-LEARNING IN TERTIARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA: A PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The primary aim of this survey was to examine the effect of accessibility to mobile telecommunication service on the adoption of e-learning in tertiary educational institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria. One hundred students of the University of Lagos and Lagos State University were randomly selected and administered questionnaire at pilot stage. Two hypotheses were postulated to guide the study. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and parametric statistical tool for correlational analysis. The results revealed that there is significant relationship between accessibility to mobile telecom service and adoption of e-learning on one hand; and quality of mobile service delivery and adoption of e-learning on the other hand (at .05 level of significance). It was recommended that telecom service providers should make improved value-added data services accessible and affordable to their subscribers so as to enhance the adoption of e-learning in line with the best global practices.

KEYWORDS: e-learning, mobile telecommunication service, telecom service providers, tertiary educational institutional institutions and value-added data services.

INTRODUCTION

In realization of the changes in the global economy, wider accessibility to the mobile telecommunication services among the learning subscribers in various tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria has indeed signaled another beginning of the Telecom Revolution in the country. This revolution paved way for the

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adoption of learning methods and processes that are in consonance with the world best practices. According to Ndukwe (2008), the full gamut of telecommunication services in the hitherto traditional telecommunications sector in Nigeria were government led, resulting in poor infrastructure base. The contemporary liberalized telecommunications sector on the other hand, is private sector led. Ndukwe further remarks that there were approximately 400,000 fixed lines and 25,000 analogue wireless lines in a country with a population of over 120 million before the liberalization of the telecommunications sector by the Federal Government of Nigeria in 1999. However, the subsequent auction of the mobile licenses in year 2001 has enhanced tremendous growth in the telecommunications sector in Nigeria.

Meanwhile, an attempt was made to introduce analogue mobile telecom service by the then incumbent operator, Nigerian Telecommunications Limited (NITEL), but the spread was very limited and the sector was incapable of responding well to the yearnings of the numerous prospective subscribers to have affordable and high quality telecom service in the country (Juwah, 2011). Accessibilities to mobile telecom services were literally decreed out of the shopping list of ordinary folks! Today, a mobile telecom device can be found in every palm in all sectors of the Nigerian society. The economy has recorded remarkable growth as a result of this; information and communication are now widespread (NCC, 2011a).

According to NCC (2011b), Nigeria's teledensity stands at 66.76 lines per 100 inhabitants as at September 30, 2011. The teledensity ratio has significantly increased when compared with teledensity figures of 0.4 lines per 100 inhabitants recorded at the beginning of the year 2000. Similarly, an active subscribers base of 93,461, 436 has been recorded as at September 30, 2011, while all federating units in Nigeria are now covered by both voice and data services through the GSM and CDMA technologies (NCC, 2011b). According to Juwah (2011), the Nigerian telecommunications sector is the fastest growing telecoms market on the African continent. The wireless revolution, the internet phenomenon, the broadband capabilities and massive deployment of national and intercontinental optic fibre highways have accelerated global access to information resources, and changed people's perception on learning methods and processes.

Recent reforms by the National Universities Communication (NUC), among which is the requirement for the Nigerian universities to make full provision for e-learning, has brought to light the efficacy of e-

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learning in enhancing correspondence, open and distance learning processes. This requirement has certainly placed enormous burdens and responsibilities on various degree awarding tertiary educational institutions that offer one academic programme or the other via correspondence, open and distance learning processes (Ibiyemi, 2006). Nevertheless, this requirement was seen as a direct consequence of globalization via trade liberalization and advancement in information and communication technologies (ICTs). The development highlighted above generated interest for this study. Thus the primary objectives of this study are to examine the relationship between accessibility to mobile telecom service and adoption of e-learning on one hand; and to evaluate the relationship between quality of mobile service delivery and adoption of e-learning on the other hand. The study tested the null hypotheses that “accessibility to mobile telecom service has no significant effect on adoption of e-learning”, while the quality of mobile service delivery has no significant effect on adoption of e-learning”. The remainder of this article is organised as follows: section 2 reviews related literature, section 3 discusses data and methodology, section 4 presents the empirical results, while the section 5 concludes.

Review of Related Literature

The literature suggests that studies on the subject matter of telecommunication service and e-learning are relatively scarce but not new; bearing in mind that telecommunication is one of the most important services in an economy (Frempong, 2002). The role of the telecommunication service in an economy cannot be underemphasised because it is the means through which all daily business transactions and activities are undertaken. According to Boohene and Agyapong (2011), telecommunication service aids decision making, organizing, influencing, activating, instructing, providing feedback, promoting interpersonal and corporate relationships as well as exchange of information. In a nutshell, all social, economic, political, educational, cultural, trade and commercial activities are undertaken using telecommunications. Similarly, there is no gainsaying that the nature of a country’s telecommunication service affects its pace of commercial and domestic activities (Nigerian Telecomnews weekly, 2011).

Global System for Mobile communication (GSM), as an international mode for digital communication by cell phone, and Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA), as a telecommunication mode in which there is an agreement between two or more service providers to use their own sets of numbers for the services

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provided on another's platform, are the two main technologies that drive the contemporary telecommunication services (Onigbinde, 2013). Indeed, it becomes imperative to state that both GSM and CDMA represent the modern telecommunication technologies that extend people's reach on all fronts. Furthermore, telecom service providers that operate on GSM/CDMA technologies use high-capacity fibre-optic cable to enhance telecom process and provide excess bandwidth to all cities connected to the cable. According to Onigbinde (2013), this initiative has gone a long way toward improving teleconferencing, distance learning, disaster recovery and telemedicine among several other benefits.

This study, however, adopts transformative learning theory as theoretical framework. The development of this theory coincided with the process of constructing and appropriating new and revised interpretations of the meaning of an experience in the world. Learning is commonly referred to as a process that brings together cognitive, emotional, and environmental influences and experiences for acquiring, enhancing, or making changes in one's knowledge, skills, values, and world perspectives (Ormrod, 1995; Illeris, 2004). It is also described as the way in which information is absorbed, processed, and retained. Learning theories are elaborate hypotheses that demonstrate how exactly this procedure occurs.

According to Illeris (2001), transformative learning is the cognitive process of effecting change in a frame of reference of an individual. These frames of reference define individual view of the world, and every individual has tendency to reject or jettison any idea that does not ascribe or conform to his/her values, associations and concepts among others. Illeris (2004) further stresses that individual frame of reference is composed of two dimensions: habits of mind and points of view. Habits of mind, such as ethnocentrism, are more fixed and influence individual points of view and the resulting thoughts or feelings associated with them, whereas points of view may change over time as a result of influences such as reflection, appropriation, and feedback.

Transformative learners utilize discourse as a means of critical examination and reflection devoted to assessing reasons presented in support of competing interpretations, by critically examining evidences, arguments, and alternative points of view (Mezirow, 1997). However, when circumstances permit, transformative learners move toward a frame of reference that is more inclusive, discriminating, self-

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reflective, and integrative of experience (Illeris, 2001; 2004). Transformative learning leads to autonomous and responsible thinking which is essential for moral decision making and for creative initiative in situations of rapid change.

Moreover, a number of empirical studies have shown that ICTs aid learning and teaching. Initially, the computer-aided learning and teaching initiative was built on a computerized tutorial system to enhance teaching of calculus to students of Heriot-Watt University. Computer-aided learning and teaching courseware is a result of strong teamwork and dedicated teaching. According to Collins (1994) the results from the evaluation of learning and teaching impact showed that there is enthusiastic response to it by each new group of students. Therefore, lessons learnt over the decade have been built into the courseware, wherever possible, in order to help students learn more effectively and more efficiently. Furthermore, the comparison of the examination results of a pilot group with those of another group taking the same final examination in categories of similar school qualification was done over a period of three academic sessions. On average, students in the computerized tutorial system performed 15% better in the common examination. It is also estimated that the introduction of computer-aided learning and teaching has reduced students' failure rate by 5% per annum (Collins, 1994).

Data from students were collected through questionnaires, interviews, structured recall and informal contacts. The advantages of the computer-aided learning and teaching courseware were assessed through feedback from the students and observations of the researchers on the quality of learning that computer-aided teaching provided; and through enhanced examination performances of two pilot groups. Other studies that corroborated Collins'(1994) findings include Appleby (1994), Tabor (1994), Keele (1996), Archer (1998), and Wenglinsky (1998) that computer-aided learning and teaching via finite elements, mechanics module in Mathwise, standard packages, school's climate, and classroom computer use respectively. However, using ICTs could motivate learners and could further enhance or reinforce learning processes. It could also challenge learners, and nevertheless, help them apply their skills to solving problems in different curriculum areas.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

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This section presents the sequence of methods and procedures adopted in carrying out this study. Descriptive survey design as suggested by Asika (2004) was used as the study guide in determining the relative effect of accessibility to mobile telecommunication services on the adoption of e-learning in tertiary educational institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria. The population of the study at pilot stage is made up of the entire students that are currently undergoing their academic programmes in tertiary educational institutions within Lagos State, Nigeria, but a proportional representation of the population was adopted as sample which comprised the students of the University of Lagos and Lagos State University. A convenience sampling technique was adopted in drawing the working population which consists of students of the University of Lagos and Lagos State University. This is due to the fact that the duo of the University of Lagos and Lagos State University possess all features that are inherent in other tertiary educational institutions in Lagos State and therefore, would constitute a true representation of the dynamisms inherent in total population.

A sample size which consisted of one hundred students of selected tertiary educational institutions was adopted via process of randomization. The sample was drawn from various faculties and academic levels of the selected tertiary educational institutions, ranging from postgraduate to undergraduate academic programmes. A structured questionnaire was used as research instrument for the study. Likert's type interval rating scale which allows respondents to grade their opinions on scale 1 to 5 was adopted to elicit appropriate responses; where 5= strongly agree, 4= agree, 3= neither agree nor disagree, 2= disagree, and 1= strongly disagree. Copies of the research instrument that consists of forty two construct items each in closed-ended format were randomly distributed.

The reliability of the research instrument was determined using test – re-test reliability. In the use of test – re-test reliability technique, the research instrument could be used to take two separate measurements on the same population at different but similar occasions (Anastasi and Urbina, 2008). Responses from the two tests were subjected to Cronbach's Alpha reliability. The co-efficient of reliability measurement is 0.81 which guaranteed internal consistency of the measuring instrument (Nunnally, 1993). Expert opinion validation method was used in the study to ensure that the research instrument measures what it purports to measure. To ensure validity of the research instrument, copies of the questionnaire were given administered

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and given to the senior academics specializing in Educational Technology, Marketing, and Organizational Behaviour; as well as senior administrative staff in the tertiary educational institutions in Lagos for content validity. The data collected were analyzed with the aids of descriptive statistics and parametric statistical tool for correlational analysis via the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 16).

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

Findings based on the survey revealed that accessibility to mobile telecommunication services can positively enhance the adoption of e-learning in tertiary educational institutions.

Table 4.1 Test of Hypothesis I

Correlations

			Access to Mobile Telecom Service	Acceptability of E-Learning
Spearman's rho	Access to Mobile Telecom Service	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.591**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	100	100
Acceptability of E-Learning		Correlation Coefficient	.591**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Analysis and Interpretation of Result I

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Using Spearman Rank correlation, the findings show that there is a strong relationship between access to mobile telecom service and acceptability/adoption of e-learning by the students in tertiary educational institutions at .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that accessibility to mobile telecom service has no significant effect on adoption of e-learning in tertiary educational institutions is therefore rejected.

Table 4.2 Test of Hypothesis II

Correlations

		Quality of M-Learning Delivery	Acceptability of E-Learning
Spearman's rho	Quality of M-Learning Delivery	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.598**
		N	.000
Acceptability of E-Learning	Acceptability of E-Learning	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Analysis and Interpretation of Result II

Using Spearman Rank correlation, the findings show that there is a strong relationship between quality of mobile service delivery and acceptability/adoption of e-learning by the students in tertiary educational institutions at .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that the quality of mobile service delivery has no significant effect on adoption of e-learning in tertiary educational institutions is therefore rejected.

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CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Accessibility to mobile telecommunication services are essentially imperative for every adult, especially the telecommunication service subscribers and prospective subscribers that engage in learning and teaching in tertiary educational institutions in both developed and developing countries. There is no gainsaying the fact that telecommunication service has become an embodiment and sustenance of human existence, most especially in this contemporary regime of globalization via trade liberalization and advancement in information and communication technologies. However, in view of the fact that the study reveals strong relationship/ association between the accessibility to mobile telecommunication services and adoption of e-learning in some tertiary educational institutions does not make the application of this technological innovation a *sine qua non* for all tertiary educational institutions in the country.

It is therefore recommended to all educational institutions to adopt e-learning initiative into only the fields/ areas of studies that can bring about distinct outcomes in terms of student performance, teaching efficacy, school's climate, and learning effectiveness. In addition, the telecommunication service providers should strive towards a mark of excellence in providing improved value-added data services to their numerous subscribers. Furthermore, the service providers should also make these services more assessable and affordable to their respective subscribers so as to enhance the adoption of e-learning in line with the best global practices.

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SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION: A PANACEA FOR TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS' CHALLENGES

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KEYWORDS: examination malpractices, cultism, skill acquisition, community learning service

ABSTRACT

The paper looked at various challenges confronting tertiary institutions in Nigeria, such as insecurity, cultism, examination malpractices, corruption, poor funding among others. The paper highlighted importance of science and technical education in overcoming these challenges. Emphasis was laid on skill acquisition programme; entrepreneurship education and Community Learning Service (CLS) for both science and technical students in tertiary institutions. The paper was concluded by suggesting some recommendations for tackling tertiary institutions challenges in Nigeria such as funding of Science and Technical Education programs in Nigerian tertiary institutions; the funding should not be left for government alone, but stake holders and private/corporate organizations should join hands in funding Nigerian tertiary institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Tertiary institutions in Nigeria are still in their growing stage compare with the developed world because of various challenges that are peculiar to these citadels of learning. These challenges might not be peculiar to Nigeria alone however; the challenges often decimate the academic strength of the institutions.

Graduates of Nigerian tertiary institutions are being looked down upon outside the country not because of anything but due to these challenges. Polytechnics graduates in Nigeria can hardly performed when they

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get to the field because of lack of proper training. Graduates of colleges of Education who are trained to be professional teachers cannot teach effectively when they graduated from schools. The facilities in our campus are not conducive for teaching and learning where both staff and students are experiencing epileptic power outage to read, carry out assignments, research studies, and interact with their counterparts outside the classroom across the globe. All these are some of the situations in Nigerian tertiary institutions, putting Nigerian graduates into a box which make Nigeria a laughing stock among the nations.

Students of tertiary institution spend more time outside classroom because of industrial action emanating either from the government or from the students themselves and it could come from workers. All these are ill wind that does not blow the nation any good.

Conferences, workshops, seminars are being held even public debate on how to solve tertiary institutions problems but little has been achieved so far. Solution to these problems is not in heaven but in the institution itself; that is why this review is very important.

Before looking at the solution to the problems it would be very appropriate to consider some of these challenges that tend to weaken the academic strength of the institutions. Therefore the review is divided into the following sub-heading:

- Tertiary institution challenges
- Meeting the challenges of tertiary institution through science education
- Meeting the challenges of tertiary institution through technical education

Tertiary institution challenges

Many are the challenges of Nigerian tertiary institutions but this paper will highlight few of these challenges. These challenges are insecurity, cultism, corruption, examination malpractices and poor funding.

Insecurity

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Insecurity is the greatest challenge of Nigerian tertiary institutions; security is very important and germane to academic excellence (Aina, 2012). Gone are the days when Nigerian campuses were saved and secured; today lives and properties in campuses are not saved because of the types of students and workers we have in the institutions. Many students are already spoiled from home and parents thinking was that institutions will re- mould the life of such students but instead they turn out to be terrorists in the institutions.

There is declining in academic performance of students in the institutions thereby turning those who could not cope into a problem in the institution. Many students had been in the institution for many years without graduating; they remain there to cause security problem for the serious students and the entire learning community.

Effect of insecurity is great and incalculable. Consider the gruesome murder of three professors in a university in the northern part of Nigeria few years ago and lots of infrastructure that were destroyed by some people.

Cultism

Cultism is very rampant in all Nigerian institution of higher learning nowadays as observed by Ajuwon and Oyeniyi (2010) that cultists have made Nigerian higher institutions become a place of worry to everybody. Cultists are making campuses insecure for everybody including staffers of the institutions. The most painful thing about this cultism is that staff including heads of the institutions is involved in cultism; this makes their activities difficult to curb.

Cultism has devastated academic programmes of tertiary institutions in Nigeria in many ways; lecturers can no longer do their work objectively because of fear of cultist; serious students are no longer committed to their studies due to cult activities; institutions are closed down and academic activities paralysed for long period as a result of violence caused by cultists.

Examination malpractice

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Examination malpractices are rampant in the country institutions of learning as argued by Bello (2006) that, even in teachers training institutions this is being practiced. Students don't want to read and they want to pass by all means resulting into all forms of examination malpractices. Shameless staffers of institutions also participate in this ugly act because of wealth. It has become very difficult to conduct any free and fair examination in the institutions because of examination malpractices.

Effects of examination malpractices are obvious as graduates of many institutions cannot live up to expectation in their various professions after graduation because they do not merit the certificate they are holding. Many of Nigerian institutions are not respected outside the country even within Africa; they make mockery of Nigerian certificates only because those who really worked for the certificate are few.

Corruption

There is corruption everywhere in the nation as opined by EL-Rufai in Aina (2012) that corruption and terrorism has taking over the nation. According to Olagunju (2012), corruption is everywhere in Nigeria, tertiary institutions inclusive. Admission into tertiary institution is on whom you know not on merit again; award of contract in the institution is no longer for the best contractor but to the rogues. Aina (2013) observed that purchases of science equipment to schools are no longer done transparently because it is either the chief executive of the institution or any of his or her relation who did the supply.

Nigeria, which has a population of 168,883,776, is ranked 135 out of 176 most corrupt countries in the world which is slowing the pace of development (World Bank, 2013 & Transparency International, 2013 in Ogundele & Shehu, 2013). Presently, in an effort to assess the basic human development achievements in the world, Nigeria ranked 153 among 193 countries in the world. The implication is that Nigeria's poverty index will get worsen the more because presently, her multidimensional poverty index is 0.31% while 68.0% of her population is living below \$1.25 PPP per day ((United Nations Development Project, 2013 in Ogundele & Shehu, 2013). In this view, science and technical education has a greater role to play in overcoming these challenges in order to have a secured nation whose technological advancement cannot be compromised.

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Nevertheless, Nigeria's human development index which stands at 0.31% could be improved upon through some technical education programs such as in Automobile technology, Building technology, Electrical/Electronic technology, and Metalwork technology. This will reduce the country's high rate of unemployment that is still contributing to high rate of poverty among Nigerians (Ogundele & Shehu, 2013).

Mfon (2007) lamented that recruitment to job is tied down to criteria such as political favouritism, geographical area or quota system. Many of the teacher training institutions, polytechnics and universities are devoid of best academic staff because the best probably do not have godfather who could help.

Some lecturers are corrupt; they have left their primary duty of lecturing and researching to business of selling books and handouts to students at any price of their choices; they are promiscuous and committing immorality with female students with the view to give them marks. Corruption has ruin our tertiary institutions except something is done urgently the system may collapse soon.

Judging by the most corrupt institutions in Nigeria from an indices of 5% as high while 1% as low corruption index, recording the political parties and the police as most corrupt institutions in Nigeria with 4.7% respectively, the Education institution 's level of corruption is 3.4%. (Transparency International, 2013).

Poor funding

Funds are not made available for research and teaching in our tertiary institutions as opined by Oziegbe and Sharimakin (2010) that Nigerian public institutions and university are not well funded by the government and supported by Adedibu (2007) that tertiary institutions are poorly funded. Budgetary allocation to education in Nigeria is generally very low when compare with other Africa countries; a national news paper, Vanguard of November, 26th 2012 reported that, Nigeria spends less than nine per cent of its annual budget on education.

The table below show annual budget of some Africa countries as compare with Nigeria.

s/n	country	Budget (%)
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1	Botswana	19.0
2	Burkina Fasco	16.8
3	Cote d'Ivoire	30.0
4	Ghana	31.0
5	Kenya	23.0
6	Lesotho	19.0
7	Morocco	17.7
8	Nigeria	8 .0
9	South Africa	25.8
10	Swaziland	24.6
11	Tunisia	17.0
12	Uganda	27.0

Source: Vanguard, November 26, 2012

Nigeria government is not sincere to education; Obiajulu (2012) said government lack sincerity and that is why the quality of education is poor. Faborode (2013) was worried that country like Ghana committed 31 per cent of its budget to education as against Nigeria's eight per cent.

Lecturers' allowances and salary are not given priority forgetting that, role of teachers cannot be compared with that of politician. Oloyede (2007) posited that, in any stable political system, teachers and their education system are well catered for; teachers are not well catered for in Nigeria because of lack of fund.

Meeting the challenges of tertiary institution through science education

Science education is the study of biology, chemistry or physics in conjunction with the principle and method of education (Aina, 2013). The field of science education is aimed at sharing both science content

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and processes with individual that might not be traditionally in science community. Science education could be applied to meet tertiary institution through skill acquisition and entrepreneurship education.

Igbo and Ikpa (2013) stressed the necessity of using skill acquisition programme in science education to curb tertiary education challenges. Youths in tertiary institutions should not only be focusing on academic programme without regard for a particular skill while in the school. Youths should be equipped with scientific skills that will keep their minds and souls away from any evil inclination. For instance, students of physics education could be trained on electronics and ceramic making; since all these are part of what they have learnt in physics. Chemistry students could be trained on soap and dye making while biology students could specialize in fishery.

Equipping them with these skills will keep them engaged and away from cultism and other vices. An understanding of science and the processes of science contributes in no small way to these skills (National Academy Press, 1996).

To further assist the students on skill acquisition, teachers must be professionally upright; science education teachers at all level must be balance both theoretically and practically. They should be provided with opportunities to develop theoretical, practical understanding and ability, not just technical proficiencies (National Academy Press, 1996).

Adediran and Olugbuyi (2010) believed that the purpose of entrepreneurship education is to prepare youth to be responsible therefore asserted that:

Entrepreneurship education seeks to prepare people, especially youths to be responsible, enterprising individuals who become entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers and who contribute to economic development and sustainable communities (p.2)

Ojeifa (2013) said entrepreneurship education provides young graduates with training and support to enable them established career in small and medium businesses.

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A functional science education will prepare its products for a profitable future through quality training. Most of the training that goes on in tertiary institutions today focuses on learning to obtain certificate for paid jobs without thinking of what can be done when there is no paid job.

Youth in school should be trained to look beyond paid jobs; most of these youths tend to cause trouble because they felt staying in school is better since there is no job in the country.

A physics education student who has been taught on how to be self employed through ceramic making will never engage in any activities that can prolong his/her studies duration in school.

Institutions can use science education to establish money generating ventures in schools; for instance through chemistry education a school can establish chalk industry; biology education can establish fish pond; physics education can engage in electronics and electrical works. A lot of money could be generated through these ventures which could be a solution to poor funding for the institution.

Science education could be use to solve problem of corruption through emphasis on moral and peace education; teaching should not be only on principle and method of teaching science but on individual duties to neighbours and immediate community (Rukuni, 2013).

Meeting the challenges of tertiary institution through technical education

With standard research work, technical education can produce more technical personnel that will help mount the already collapsed industries. This can be achieved through the relevant skills acquired to solve the nation's erratic power supply by demonstrating their skills in accordance with the objectives/ goals of Technical Education which are specifically to technology education that is offered at some higher institutions:

- The production of high level and middle-level manpower as appropriate in areas necessary for agriculture, industrial, commercial and economic development.
- The identification and solution of the technological problems and needs of industrial; and

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- The production of technicians and technologies and similar business related personnel for direct employment in industry. pp 30-31 (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2004, pg.).

Technical education can also reduce the high rate of poverty in the country because more youths would have possessed the relevant skills that will discourage them from scanning for a white collar job and be self-reliant. In fact, if technical education programs are properly funded, it will in return help to generate more money back to government purse because goods produced from the available funds and materials can be sold at both local and international levels respectively. The program can also build into the young Nigerians coming with the skills for maintenance culture which the country is lacking right now. Skills' acquisition can help in the formulation of ideas, their integration, and the interaction of persons and ideas to give solutions to possible emerging challenges for national development (Ogundele & Shehu, 2013).

Most importantly, students who are idle or restless can be engaged with series of skills ranging from welding, lubrication of vehicles, spraying of vehicles, machining, servicing, joinery, block making, electrical installation, electronic computer diagnosing to painting and decoration in college before graduation. These skills if introduced to them will not create room for cultism, crime, examination malpractice, and arm-robbery among them. More so, the time allocated for theoretical and literature work could be shortened to give more room for practical know-how.

CONCLUSION

In the light of the above submission it is obvious that Nigerian tertiary institutions are faced with the challenges of insecurity, examination malpractices, and cultism among many others. Science and Technical education have been seen as strong tool to overcome these challenges through skill acquisition and entrepreneurship education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the fact that Science and Technical Education can help in meeting up with the Nigerian Tertiary Institutions' Challenges, the followings are recommended:

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- Funding of Science and Technical Education programs in Nigerian tertiary institutions should not be left for government alone, but stake holders and private/corporate organizations should join hands in funding Nigerian tertiary institutions.
- Technical education programs should be adequately funded and free for all categories of students, youths, and adults, in order to reduce the rate of unemployment in Nigeria.
- Science education must be taken seriously by the Nigerian government at all levels of education by giving scholarship for any outstanding students in science education.
- Science education curriculum should be revised to include skill acquisition programme and entrepreneurship education in all tertiary education.
- Any corrupt individual in tertiary institution should be dealt with like an arm rubber; the individual may be lecturer, chief executive of institution or anybody.

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**STUDENTS' ENTRY QUALIFICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL ENGLISH IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN KWARA
STATE**

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KEYWORDS: Students' entry qualification, academic performance, English language and General English

ABSTRACT

The paper employed descriptive survey study of students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English in the Colleges of Education in Kwara State, Nigeria. One hundred and eighty- six students were sampled for the study. Descriptive Statistic and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were used to analyze the data collected. The results showed correlation between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English. The paper concluded that early good academic performance could enhance future academic performance. Some recommendations were suggested at the end of the study.

INTRODUCTION

Akale (1991) averred that students' academic performance is the level of knowledge, skills or accomplishments in an area of endeavor such as in English language. Brown (1999) referred to it as how students deal with their studies and how they cope with it or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers.

Ayodele (2002) pointed out that students performance in English language at the Senior School Certificate Examinations have been persistently poor in the past 20 years. Iiyas (2013) on students' academic performance in General English among students in Colleges of Education in Kwara State revealed that the inability of Colleges of Education students to take a meaningful note from lecture has been a reflection of their poor English background.

On the basis of students' entry qualification, Momoh-olle (1992) and Sear (1983) were of the opinion that students' academic performance is very complex to predict. Despite the complexity associated with students' entry qualification in determining future academic performance of students, some have investigated the issue.

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Momoh-Olle(1992) revealed a cogent statistical relationship between students' entry qualification and their academic performance in education theory, language and vocational studies. Ojetunde (1988) articulated a high positive correlation between entry qualification and success.

Gbore (2013) was of the opinion that there was moderate correlation coefficient between SSCE and academic performance of the University undergraduate students which tossed the same direction with the findings of WAEC (1992) that a positive and significant relationship existed between candidates' performance in the SSCE and academic performance in the Universities' undergraduate levels.

Idika (1997) noted a non-significant difference between final performance of WASSCE Technical and GCE holders in their Technical Education programmes. Majasan and Bakare (1979) revealed something close to the findings of Idika; they keenly noted that entry qualification was poor predictor of academic performance and that the degree of performance cannot be linked to the quality of grade obtained in the entry qualification. The study used under-graduates in the University with GCE certificates.

A study by Muraina, et.al (2010) and Fowowe, et.al (2010) indicated that entry qualification cannot serve as a predictor of the students' academic performance in higher level of education. Okwilagwe (2001) also argued that there was a very low correlation coefficient between SSCE and academic performance of the Universities' undergraduate students.

Peers and Johnston (1994) also confirmed the validity of the number and grades of passes in the Scottish Certificate of Education in predicting first year and the final year University performance. Gay (1996) also indicated that high school grades could be used to predict the College grades. However, these findings were contrary to O'Rourke, Martin and Hurley's (1989) where the scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) was unable to predict examination performance as effectively as the Leaving Certificate Examination (LCE) pointed out.

Adeyemi (2008) supported earlier findings on the complexity of students' entry qualification. To him performance varies considerably from one subject to the other. Thus, scholars' conclusions on this issue are

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based on data collected and so many other factors such as students' attitude (Ali, 1983), institutional factors (Pidgeon, 1970) and home background (Olanipekun, 2012).

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English in Colleges of Education in Kwara State.

Research Question

Is there any difference in the performance of student base on entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English?

This research work employed descriptive survey method where students' scores in General English along with their entry qualification in English language, were collected and analyzed for the purpose of this study.

The sample population comprises of students from Colleges of Education in Kwara State. Pro-forma was used to collect students' scores from year 1 to year 3 (final year) students of 2011/2012 with a total number of one hundred and eighty six students that were randomly selected.

Research hypothesis and question were tested and answered using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient and descriptive statistic. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient is used to determine the degree of relationship between two set of variables (Okoro, 2002), this could be supported by (Owie, 1996) that, Correlation Co-efficient Method was used to compute the strength of association between variables. Descriptive statistic summarizes a relatively large array of data into meaningful forms such that they could be more easily interpreted (Nkemakolam, 2002).

RESULTS

The result in Table 1 reveals that there is a strong correlation between students' entry qualification in English language and students' academic performance in General English with correlation coefficient of

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.220. This means that early good academic performance could influence students' academic performance in the College. The hypothesis is thereby rejected.

Table 2 also revealed that students performed better at their students' entry level in English language than in General English when they get to College of Education as the mean scores in the entry qualification is higher than that of General English in the Colleges of Education. In this sense, the research question is answered.

DISCUSSIONS

The relationship between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English in Colleges of Education in Kwara State.

As seen from the findings of this research, there is a correlation between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English of students in Colleges of Education in Kwara State. This therefore posited that there is tendency for students' entry qualification in English language to act as a predictive virile instrument for future academic performance of students in General English.

This Gbore (2013) also pointed out when he was of the opinion that there was moderate correlation coefficient between SSCE and future academic performance of students. The finding also agreed with the findings of WAEC (1992) that a positive and significant relationship exists between candidates' performance in the SSCE and academic performance in tertiary institution. Ojetunde (1988) also articulated a high positive correlation between entry qualification and success. Ubokobong (1993) keenly unfolded those students with high number of credit in Nigeria secondary school examinations as those who performed well in higher institutions

However, Idika (1997), Majasan and Bakare (1979) did not agree with the above findings as revealed in their research when they keenly noted that entry qualification was poor predictor of academic performance and that the degree of performance in the Colleges cannot be linked to the quality of grade obtained in the

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entry qualification. Adeniyi & Solomon (NY) were of the opinion that there were no significant differences between students' entry qualification and their final academic performance in NCE programmes. This they ascertained through the mean scores of students admitted through Pre- NCE programmes and that of their JAMB counterparts.

It is therefore plausible to unfold that students' academic performance is one of the current educational problem of public interest based on poor level of students' performance especially in public examination and at schools and various higher institutions (kolawole,1998, kolawole and Dele ,2002) in which English language is not an exemption. This Ivowi ,Okebukola and Oladotun (1992) gave credent to when they averred that the problem of under achievement among school children has persisted in many subjects areas such as English language. However, students still perform better in entry qualification in English language than in General English in the Colleges of Education in Kwara State as obtainable form this research.

CONCLUSION

At this juncture, it is jussive to assert that students' entry qualification is an instrument used in predicting higher education. However, while some scholars' works agreed with the outcome of this finding some findings are at variance. It should therefore be noted that the validity of data collected and the institutions under experiment or the environment could go a long way in influencing the summations of various scholars on a subject like.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teachers of English at all level should endeavor to create in students the urge and the necessary curiosity in learning English language.
2. Students should also desist from all forms of examination malpractices. They should learn to read and face their books, not 'face book' and face examinations without internal, external or foreign assistance, either from their teachers or 'machineries' since early good academic performance could influence later academic performance.

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Table 1: Correlations between General Eng. And Entry Qualification in English language

		General English		Entry Qualification	
General Eng.	Pearson Correlation	1.090			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.220			
Entry Qualification	N	186		186	
	Pearson Correlation	.090		1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.220			
	N	186		186	

Table 2:

Mean scores of students in General Eng. And Entry Qualification in English language

	Mean	Std. deviation	N
General Eng.	45.40323	6.0837186	

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EntryQualification

49.25815.25028186

TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND POVERTY REDUCTION: THE CASE OF NIGERIA.

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KEYWORDS: Technical and Vocational Education, skill acquisition, Poverty, Informal sector, Funding, and Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Despite the contributions of technical education to national development, the leaders of Nigeria have not given this sector the attention it deserves. In spite of the strong emphasis on skills development for poverty reduction found in national policies, programmes and projections, it is not clear how the Government of Nigeria plans to realise its ambitions in this direction. The government at several fora had come up with high sounding proposals and development plans aimed at stemming the scourge of poverty and unemployment in Nigeria like the case of national policy geared towards technical education, but all efforts, as it were, failed to yield the desired result. This is because the relationship between skills development and poverty alleviation is neither simple nor automatic. It is against this background that this paper seeks to evaluate governments' efforts and commitments to technical and vocational education in Nigeria and the possible way forward. The paper makes a campaign for a prodigious investment in skill acquisition if Nigeria will ever achieve its vision 2020 goal; realize economic growth and development evidenced with employment opportunities and an increasing life expectancy. A case is also made for the

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informal sector, realising that the productive capacity of this economic unit is sub-optimal as a result of lack of both pre and post training opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

The need to promote technical and vocational education and to imbue graduates with the mindset of enterprise and innovativeness is gathering momentum among nations of the world. There is a fresh awareness among policy makers in many African countries and the international donor community of the critical role that technical and vocational education and training (TVET) can play in national development. According to Bhuwanea (2006), in recent years, concerns have been raised by most African countries about the move towards making TVET complementary to post-basic education. Prior to the present dispensation, Nigerians have historically considered technical and vocational education and training (TVTE) as an education programme meant for low level, low brilliant and less privileged or second class citizens (Okoro, 1993, and Eze and Okorafor, 2012). Iheonunekwu, Nwamuo and Eze (2011) noted that from all ramifications and to a number of reasons, Vocational Education is for people who are not intelligent enough to do academic work. However, in the recent time, the campaign for technical education and skill acquisition is gathering momentum in the country.

Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) systems play a crucial role in the social and economic development of a nation. Owing to their dynamic nature, they are continuously subject to the forces driving change in the schools, industry and society. The major educational reforms according to Daniel (2001) have, however, been on vocationalisation. It is in line with this, that different countries have come up with different framework towards repositioning their vocational and technical programmes. Technical education facilitates the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge, it is therefore a planned program of courses and learning experiences that begins with exploration of career options, supports basic academic and life skills, and enables achievement of high academic standards, leadership, preparation for industry-defined work, and advanced and continuing education (CTE, 2009). Cinterfor/ILO (2006) stated that VTE can be a tool to counteract at least in part, the harmful effect of unemployment by promoting greater job turnover and guarding against the risks of obsolescence.

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However, in view of the benefits accruing to Technical and Vocational education (TEV) and the global challenge of the time, Nigeria therefore has joined her world counterparts in formulating policies geared towards ensuring a national system of vocational education. A system that ensures that, young people see vocational education as challenging and worthwhile. Although, in the recent time, the nations' emphasis on technical education appears to be gathering momentum, yet it is not clear how the government of Nigeria plans to realise its ambitions in this direction realising the fact that under-funding has been the bane of vocational and technical education in Nigeria. According to Fafunwa (2010), Nigeria has money but lacks the ability to use it judiciously. Dike (2009) stressed that vocational education holds the key for the solution of Nigeria's developmental problems, yet it is the worst applied instrument for national development. Considering Vocational and Technical Education as the key for national development (Dike, 2009), it is imperative for this sector to be adequately funded to make it result- driven.

Unfortunately, Nigeria does not seem to give technical and vocational education the attention they deserve and this appears to be one of the reasons for rising unemployment and poverty in the society. It is against this background that this paper seeks to evaluate government efforts and commitment to funding technical education in Nigeria with the aim of making recommendations for the way forward. A case is also made for the informal sector, for a scheme to formalize what may be called the training side of the informal sector by way of partnership with the formal sector.

Conceptual Issues

The concept of technical and vocational education varies from country to country thus, are interchangeably used as vocational education and training (VET), technical and vocational education (TVE), technical and vocational education and training (TVET), vocational technical education (VTE), or vocational and technical education and training (VOTEC). They all mean the same thing.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) opined that vocational technical education is an aspect of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relative to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Manfred and Jennifer (2004) advocated that

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vocational technical education comprises all more or less organized or structured activities that aim at providing people with the knowledge, skills and competencies necessary to perform a job or a set of jobs whether or not they lead to a formal qualification. These definitions show that the relationship between VTE and employments is undeniable. Thus, any education that is geared towards teaching technical skills and attitudes suitable to such skills can be regarded as technical education.

Others have noted that skills development appears to be a much broader concept than technical and vocational education and training (TVET), (Working Group for International

Cooperation in Skills Development, 2002: 11). With these qualifications in mind, therefore, skills development is not equated with formal technical, vocational and agricultural education and training alone, but is used more generally to refer also to the productive capacities acquired through all levels of education and training, occurring in formal, non-formal and on-the-job settings.

Poverty affects many aspects of human conditions; hence there has been no universal concern on the definition. Poverty according to Ozoike (2002) is a condition below that of ease and comfortable living in any area of life; physically, mentally, socially and financially. The concept of poverty includes material deprivation, (e.g food, shelter) and access to services (e.g health, education). It tends to encompass a range of non-material conditions such as a lack of rights, insecurity, powerlessness and indignity (Vandenberg, 2006).

Skill development and poverty reduction

There is still a strong sense that the capacities acquired through skills training or skills development are linked to particular livelihoods, occupations and work – whether in industry, commerce, agriculture or micro-enterprise. Yinka (2013) quipped that skill training is critical for sustainable industrialisation and poverty reduction in terms of creating a critical mass of technically an entrepreneurially qualified people. United Nations emphasized human development, measured by life expectancy, adult literacy, access to all three levels of education, as well as people's average income which is a necessary condition of their freedom of choice. The UNESCO International Project on Technical and Vocational Education (UNEVOC)

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(2006), emphasized that since education is considered the key to effective development strategies, technical and vocational education and training (TVET) must be the master key that can alleviate poverty, promote peace, conserve the environment, improve the quality of life for all and help achieve sustainable development. The above, therefore, lend credence to the fact TVET has the potential to curb high rates of unemployment in Nigeria especially among youths and women.

TVE Funding in Nigeria – An Evaluation

It is difficult to deny government's role in the funding of Vocational and Technical Education especially after independence. The Federal Government therefore had substantially improved expenditure in this area in the third and fourth National Development Plan period in addition to establishing such agencies as the ITF and the erstwhile Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF) to assist in the development of technological education in the country. Offiong, A. Anthony (2013). However available statistics show that we are not there yet.

While the allocation to education in Nigeria's 2013 budget proposal presented to the joint session of the National Assembly on Wednesday, October 10, 2012 by President Goodluck Jonathan tops those of other sectors, the amount is still far below the standard set by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO). The proposed allocation of N426.53 billion to the sector takes only 8.67 percent of the proposed total budget of N4.92 trillion, whereas the UNESCO recommended for the allocation of 26 percent of the total sector to the sector which is very vital to national development. Ifeoma (2004). An insignificant proportion of Nigeria's financial resources are spent on education. Education budgets as percentages of total national budgets were 8.43% in 2012 and 8.67% in 2013. These fell below those of other developing countries. Ghana, South Africa, Cote d'Ivoire, Kenya and Morocco had 31%, 25.8%, 30%, 23% and 17.7% respectively of their annual budget for education (Abayomi 2012). The United Nations recommends that 26 per cent of the total expenditure be devoted to education.

If the above is the situation for education in Nigeria, then, under-funding is still the bane of Vocational and Technical Education in Nigeria as could be seen in the inadequacy of infrastructure, human resources and equipment in many institutions at the secondary to tertiary levels.

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The need for adequate funding of VTE

Poverty could be reduced when TVET are well funded which will invariably develop the nation. The apparent neglect of technical education is socially and economically injurious because it is robbing the nation the contributions the graduates would make on national development. According to Manfred and Jennifer (2004), industrialized countries are transforming themselves into knowledge society by investing more on human resources. This implies that productivity and competitiveness of Nigeria in the economic world order is dependent on a well-educated, skilled and adaptable workforce. The importance of proper funding of Vocational and Technical Education has been acknowledged by many educationists like Adesina (1977), Ukeje (1977), Akpan (2010). They all agreed that since the programme is capital intensive, proper implementation and actualization of its set goals will not be achieved without adequate funding.

At present, most of our institutions running TVET courses do not have reliable learning workshops as they are equipped with conventional machines which are not in line with the trend of development and the ones they will be exposed to in the standing manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Also, graduates lack the requisite skills today as a result of inadequate funding of TVET because instructors, technicians and craftsmen that possess the dexterity of industrial technical acts are not available in the schools due to poor remuneration occasioned by poor funding of the education sector. There is, therefore, the need for effective funding of technical education in the county otherwise Nigeria will continue to wear the toga of poverty and remain a laggard in preparing its labour force for the 21st century economy.

Informal sector and the economy

The informal sector refers to the very large micro and small enterprise economy in urban and rural areas, outside the formal sector. Enterprises are often unregistered and untaxed. It is not an exaggeration to state that the large gaps left by the formal training and employment systems are filled by informal arrangements. In addition to employment in the informal sector, formal enterprises also rely heavily on informal, on-the-job training.

Informal skill acquisition is also associated with a sense of economic independence and security of income. In this context, it is evident that any effective strategy for poverty reduction through skills development

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cannot afford to neglect the informal sector. The informal sector and the local apprenticeship system present a development paradox: they are crucially important to employment generation and to the transfer of skills across generations. Yet, government response has generally been more negative than positive.

Training in the Informal or Unorganized Sector

The supply of training outside the formal economy is widely acknowledged to be the main pathway for skills acquisition and utilization in many countries. And what has been said above about the enabling economic environment applies directly to this sector. Policy makers are now much more aware of the scale of such training, as compared to formal TVE or TVET, and they are attracted by the sheer size of the youth population that is involved in acquiring skills in this part of the private sector. There is the need to co-opt the informal sector into skill acquisition in the tertiary institutions realising the fact that lack of access to basic education grossly affects their contribution to the economy. The irony is this. In some cases, our tertiary institutions do take their students who offer entrepreneurial courses to technicians, mechanics, fashion designers, vulcanisers, computer 'engineers' etc in the informal sector for practical training and skill acquisition but unfortunately, some of these supposed instructors are not well educated thus, giving rise to communication problem and inefficient delivery. Schemes to formalize what may be called the training side of the informal sector abound, including of the informal apprenticeship system. These can involve upgrading masters, organizing access to theory related to the practical skills being acquired, promoting certification of informally acquired skills, even the proposed funding of the apprentices' first year. (Johanson, 2009: 53)

Funding of Technical and Vocational Education in Nigeria – The Way Forward

Globally, the drive to mobilize finance for TVET is much weaker than efforts to raise resources for academic schooling or higher education. The problem of financing vocational-technical education appears intractable. And, according to Onwueme (1995), "if vocational technical education is considered crucial for our technological needs, then a reappraisal of national priorities is required so as to give vocational technical education the place it deserves." However, this demands conscious efforts from all stakeholders rather than mere rhetoric. Rather than solely relying on the government for funding and capacity building

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through skills acquisition both in the formal and informal windows, an attempt will be made to highlight for other possible options.

1. Public- private partnership: Constitutionally, local government authorities are responsible for funding primary education, while states fund secondary education. Tertiary institutions are funded by the proprietors including the federal, state and private owners. However, the resources required to transform Nigeria education sector cannot be provided by government alone. There is therefore, the need to solicit Public-Private Partnership (PPP) because Vocational and Technical Education is capital intensive which requires more workshops, equipment and other facilities which the state may not be able to fund alone. Any new thinking and focus for public-private model will enhance the contributions of private initiatives, investors and technocrats to the effectiveness of TVE in Nigeria towards revamping the economy.

2. Partnership with International Donors: In today's increasingly integrated world, harnessing opportunities from well-coordinated activities of the international donors such as International Development Partners (IDPs) are critical to strategic investment in TVE. As NGOs, their aim is to provide affordable health care, clean and reliable water, education, agriculture among others to low-income countries. The world has changed fundamentally since the adoption of the Millennium Declaration. It is faced with new challenges and opportunities, many of which require collective action. Most importantly, it will have to be based on a strong commitment to engage in collective actions with a clear distribution of tasks between developed and developing countries. IDPs work with local civil societies, organisations and government authorities in developing countries. Therefore, partnering with international donors for greater TVE funding is another avenue that could be explored to generate fund for TVE in Nigeria. The above will serve as a way of supplementing the assistance which the nation's education sector has been enjoying from International Organisations such as World Bank, UNESCO among others.

3. Tax rebates and credit schemes: In most regions other than Latin America, Tax Rebates or Tax Credit system is more frequently used. In Tax Rebates, a portion of the tax is returned to the firm as subsidy for training. In Singapore and Tunisia, the rebate is on the basis of costs incurred. In Nigeria, this can be in the form of grants to set up training systems. This will help enterprises who are into training and skill development on employees overcome teething problem arising from funding.

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4. **Vocational training funds:** In many countries where employers are active participants in VET, a training fund for financing vocational training has been set up. Tax contributions from the employers collected through payroll levies as well as subsidies from the government are transferred to the Training Fund. In Nigeria, this should not be the same as Education Trust Fund but a separate fund that is legally reserved for VET. Management of funds can be handled by the Ministry of Education, the employers association and the workers' unions. This is a useful way securing cooperation as well as formulation of appropriate training policy for both the formal and informal sectors.

5. **Internally Generated Revenue Opportunities:** Training and vocational Institutes can generate income from the sale of services to public and private enterprises or individuals. Even in the area of technical education, students can be made to engage in product manufacturing for their assessment under the guidance and supervision of their teachers. By this approach, technical education institutions in Nigeria are likely to be revenue yielding to the favour of their continued and productive existence. A management committee could then be set up to liquidate these products to the public in a widely publicized open day in order to generate revenue for the school. Also, school halls could be rented out for public functions like, weddings, church activities, conduct and marking of external examinations and other social meetings. And again, some TVETs offer non-training services such as consultancies. Fees from this could be paid to the government or the training institution. In the informal sector, the apprentice or the recipient of such services pays their master or the Training Institute.

6. **Paid educational leave:** Another pattern of financing vocational and industrial education in some countries is the provision of paid educational leave. Employers continue to pay wages to employees while they receive part time or full time vocational education. Therefore paid educational leave also becomes another way of distributing costs between the employers, workers and tax payers (Woodhall, 1987). The interesting thing about this is that the failure of our technical schools and tertiary institutions to produce technically and entrepreneurially qualified people arising from funding problem can be compensated for through on-the-job training opportunities.

7. **Corporate Social Responsibility:** In addition to corporation tax, business organisations do take greater roles in the society to achieve several economic, education and social objectives as part of their corporate social responsibilities. They do this as a way of giving back to the public and to project their

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goodwill and therefore, training and technical institutions can woo corporate bodies to harness such financial assistance. The fund can go through the government or directly to technical institutions.

CONCLUSION

Vocational education has always been given the shorter end of the stick when it comes to statutory allocation of finances by the government. This notwithstanding, the resources required to transform TVET cannot be provided by government alone if Nigeria will ever achieve economic growth and development evidenced with employment opportunities and increasing life expectancy. There is therefore, the need to solicit for other sources of funding because of the capital intensive nature of Vocational and Technical Education. Diversifying financing will create greater opportunities and improve the quality of training. Governments have to realise that funding from public revenue is not the only way to finance investment in vocational education and training. There should be a determination to involve employers, international donor agencies, individuals and the corporate body. Also, there is the need to co-opt the informal sector into skill acquisition in the tertiary institutions, realising that lack of access to basic education grossly affects their contribution to the economy. In this context, it is evident that any effective strategy for poverty reduction through skills acquisition and development cannot afford to neglect the informal sector otherwise the nation's vision 2020 remains elusive and the resultant effect will sink the nation in the mud of poverty and technological backwardness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In a bid to improve on the funding status of Vocational and Technical Education in Nigeria the paper recommends the following:

1. All stakeholders in education, industry and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) should jointly fund and train/develop the students for the acquisition of employable skills to meet the demand of industry and the sophisticated technology in this technological era.
2. There is the need for the government to streamline bureaucratic process and create enabling environment for greater private sector participation in funding of TVE.

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3. Institutions involved in Vocational and Technical Education should intensify more effort to realize internally generated revenue through consultancy services, rental services of school hall and showcasing their products for public sale.
4. When funds are released for capital and non-capital projects, monitoring and impact assessment procedures must necessarily be carried out to avoid such funds going down the drain.
5. Support should be sought from Development Partners and other International donors e.g. World Bank, UNESCO.
6. There is the need to separate TVE fund from the general education in state allocations.
7. Financial support should also be sought from corporate organisations under their corporate social responsibility policy.
8. Governments at all level must be pressured to devote the recommended 26% of their budgets to education by UNESCO. Out of this, we should demand that at least about 50% should be allocated to Technical Vocational Education.
9. In the case of the informal sector, there should be schemes to formalize what may be called the training side of the informal sector. These can involve organizing access to theory related to the practical skills being acquired, promoting certification of informally acquired skills through diploma and certificate courses in the tertiary institutions as a way integrating both the formal and non- formal TVET.
10. Also, it is important that the two TVET systems that is, formal and non-formal are piloted by a single national coordinating body in order to facilitate articulation between the two systems and enhance coherence and better management of the entire TVET system.

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THE ROLE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION IN MEETING THE CHALLENGES OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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KEYWORDS: learning, science and technology, development strategies, economic growth, social wellbeing

ABSTRACT

There is increasing realization that learning and applying science and technology to development strategies could produce major improvements in economic growth and social wellbeing in Nigeria. This paper considered the aims and objectives of science education with emphasis on education not schooling. In

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addition the constraints to the realization of the goals (such as poor achievement in science and lack of interest, poor teaching methods, inadequate funding, lack of science teachers) were considered. The input of Science Education towards our economy, food, medical and communication was also x-rayed. The paper recommended that enough funding, provision of competent teachers and availability of committed stakeholders in science education should be in place for it to sincerely and genuinely serve as a vehicle for national development in Nigeria among others.

INTRODUCTION

The important of science education in the development of a nation cannot be over emphasized. It is the foundation of practical changes and development of any society. There has been an increased attention in science education and learning in developing countries of the world in order to produce more and better trained scientist and technologists, in order to thrive technologically in today's world – global village. According is Iwuala (1990), a close look at human history will show that science and technology, whether in pre-historic rudimentary forms, or in the modern day sophisticated and complex forms, have continued to keep pace with the challenges and ever- growing complexities of man.

Science according to Aniodo (2002), in Egbo and Aniodo (2010) is an organized knowledge that has been gathered through many years of careful observations, experiments and reasoning. It also means the systematic study of the empirical world in order to understand it.

One of the aims and objectives of tertiary education as outlined in the education policy document (FME; 2004) is to produce manpower in science, technology and mathematics so as to increase agricultural and economics development in Nigerians". In order to achieve this objectives, manpower development in higher institutions of learning should be well focused and directed towards the achievement of these aims:-

- i) To contribute to the national development by intensifying and diversifying their prograammes for the development of high level manpower according to the needs of the economy with emphasis on science, technology and mathematics
- ii) To produce manpower capable of applying the acquired knowledge in improving and solving their environmental problems thus making it more useful and convenient for man.

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- iii) To produce manpower capable of effectively utilizing scientific knowledge and methods in solving real life problems such as food, shelter, health, water resources, energy etc.

In transforming there aims and objectives into reality, such curricula were redesigned to reflect science, technology and mathematics at all levels of nations school system.

Goals of Science Education

These objectives of tertiary education can be fully achieved through emphasizing the goals of science of education stated in the National Policy on Education, thus;

- i. to cultivates inquiry, knowledge and rational mind for the conduct of a good life and democracy
- ii. to produce scientist for national development
- iii. services studies is technology and the cause of technological development and
- v. to provide knowledge and understanding of the complexity of the physical world, the forms and the conduct of life (FRN, 2004).

It simply means that science and technology education, if properly taught, will instill in the future scientist the scientific attitudes of honestly, suspended judgment, humility, curiosity, objectively to mention but a few. They will also develop in them the scientific process skills of observation, experimentation, manipulative skills, formulating hypothes and models which consist the vehicles or process through which the **learner scientist** becomes scientifically and technologically literate, self employed and self sufficient (Maduabum 1989). Imperatively self sufficiency will raise living standard of the citizenry. With the learner scientist being scientifically and technologically self employed, they can contribute their quota to the national development. The nation will also be scientifically and technologically developed hence meeting the challenges of tertiary institution of tertiary institutions towards national development.

Teachers' Role in Meeting the Challenges.

Teachers (Lecturers) need to make science effective and relevant to a diverse fraction of population and nation at large. To do this, the following facts need to be critically enforced on the students in order for

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science teaching and learning to make any meaningful impact in the national development. These are; Research in learning, retaining information, understanding basic concepts, affecting beliefs and improving teaching and learning.

Research in Learning

In a traditional science class, the teacher stands at front of the class lecturing to a largely passive group of students. These students then go off and do back-of-the chapter home-work problems from the textbook and take exams that are similar to these exercise and pass without any knowledge of research. It has been noted by Hasteners and Swackhammer (1992) that new graduate “scientist” after years of extraordinary success in class, when given research projects to work on were clueless about how to proceed. Or worse – often it seemed that they did not even really understand the concept at all.

Teachers should therefore teach and make sure that any graduate of science should be drilled practically to be able to undertake research works in order to contribute to the nations cry for technological advancement.

Retaining Information

Teachers should not be surprised to find out that students are able to take away only a small fraction of what is presented to them from lectures. They take in information and retain such longer when they are involved and see those things done. (Hake 1998) therefore teachers should ensure that science is taught with practical and demonstration lessons.

Understanding Basic Concept

There are fundamental concepts in science that can be applied very widely. This has inspired science education researchers to study how well students are actually learning the basic concepts in their science courses. The oldest and the most widely used assessment tool in Physics for example is the Force Concepts Inventory (FCI) Hestenes (1992). This tests student’s mastery of the basic concept and their application to real – world context. Hake (1998) found out that students who mastered many basic concepts are assets and catalysts to the technological development of a nation. Teachers should ensure pedagogical approaches involving more interactive engagement of students to help them master the basic concepts.

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Affecting Belief

Students believe certain things about what science is and how one goes about learning the discipline. Beliefs about science lies on a spectrum that ranges from “novice” to “expert” Hake (1999). It is the implicit belief that science is difficult. Traditional science instruction concentrates on teaching factual knowledge with the implicit assumption that expert – like ways of thinking about the subject comes along naturally or are already present. The teacher therefore has to involve cognitive science which holds that students need to develop expert ways of thinking by means of extended, focused mental **effort**. Basic biology tells us that everything that constitutes understanding “science and other thinking scientifically” resides in the long – term memory, which is developed via the construction and assembly of component protein. A person who does not go through this extended mental construction cannot achieve mastery of a subject.

Improving Teaching and Learning

Scientific knowledge is dynamic and ever changing. It is often said that the only thing that is permanent in nature is change itself (Anidoh 2008).

The traditional lecture method of teaching science should as a matter of fact be replaced with experimentation, demonstration and inquiry base methods which give the students opportunity to see, do, and interact with one another and with the environment. Secondly incorporation of desirable cognitive activities into normal course activities should be one of the keys for them to be relevant and make meaning contribution to the technologically changing world.

Challenges of Tertiary Institutions in Meeting the Demands of the Nation Technologically.

The institution in the nation are facing a number of challenges towards meeting the demand of Nation’s scientific technological demands such problems are as follows:

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Inadequate Funding of Education:

The information published by Academic Staff Union of the Universities (ASUU) on government funding on education and cited in Nwabuisi (2008) in Eze and Oluba (2010) is as follows; in 1999, the budgetary allocation was 11.12%, in 2000, it was 8.36%; in 2001, 7.0%; in 2002, it was 5.9% and in 2003, it was 1.83%. There is a big decrease in the amount budgeted for education and this goes a long way to account for inadequacy of funds to equip our institutions for maximum technological harnessing. Most of our laboratories are shadows of the real thing. Teachers/Lecturers do not enjoy financial rewards from the Government commensurate with their contributions to development (Madukwe 2001) hence the current ASUU strike nationwide.

Lack of Laboratory Facilities:

One of the roles of science education towards national development is to sustain the growth, and also improve the efficiency of the national economy. If our laboratories are not adequately equipped with modern facilities, there will not be any meaningful research work done and thus we will continue to be dependent on other thus affecting our economy negatively.

Shortage of Well – Qualified and Enthusiastic Science Teacher

Madukwe (2001), in Oluba and Eze (2010) opined that any country that is desirous development whether scientifically, technologically or general should pay utmost attention to its teachers.

One of the goals of science education according to Ugwu and Ozioko (2010) is to promote improvisation, innovative thinking, creativity and resourcefulness and use of knowledge and skills acquired to provide national needs and solve personal and societal problems. This will remain an illusion if there are no well qualified and enthusiastic sciences teachers for the transfer of such knowledge.

Lack of Meaningful Research

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One of the major problems of undertaking meaningful research is lack of fund to equip the laboratories where the desired meaningful research can be carried out. With the shabby state of most laboratories in our institutions of higher learning, most works that should involve research are done theoretically.

Over Emphasis on Cognitive Development

There is over-emphasis on the acquisition of certificate rather than in actual acquisition of knowledge and skills. This has resulted in the pursuit of certificate at all cost through any means available. This has resulted in the student's interest in passing the exam without paying attention to the actual knowledge involved which can be transferred to national development. The opinion of Maduabum (2001) in Eze and Oluba (2010) is a contrary one which says that **“ours is a country with no education system but certification system”**. In which University science graduates are turned out from institutions which are better described as simple, glorified secondary schools having learnt about science not science its self”.

CONCLUSION

Science education plays very important roles in triggering off technological advancement and hence national development, a nation without strong science education base remains a consumer nation and underdeveloped. In view of this, the institutions of higher learning as channels through which this is achieved should be given a face lift in terms of funding, research, to mention but a few, for the nation to be technologically and scientifically viable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the challenges identified, the paper therefore recommends thus;

1. There is urgent need for the government to give priority attention to education during budgeting such that enough funds will be injected to the education sector, science and science education in particular.
2. Stakeholders in the education sector in Nigeria should pay serious attention to the development of science education by ensuring that enough fund is allotted to schools for equipping the laboratories and that such funds are judiciously used. They should also ensure implementation of science and technology programmes.

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3. Government and infact the governing councils of various institutions of higher learning should ensure that they employ only well qualified and enthusiastic science teachers who will inculcate into the students scientific values and consciousness.
4. Government should join force with stakeholders to make sure that everything needed by these institutions to establish a research base should be put in place in all institutions of higher learning in the nation.
5. Laws should be enacted by the government that is addition to paper qualification a practical session/written work should be the basis for employment in both private and public sectors of the work force of the nation.

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SUPERSTITIOUS BELIEFS OF ADAMAWA STATE STUDENTS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTION AS MEASURE OF LEVEL OF SCIENTIFIC LITERACY IN ADAMAWA STATE

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KEYWORDS: scientific literacy, cultural beliefs, superstition, technological literacy, public understanding of science.

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to determine the superstitious beliefs of Adamawa state students in tertiary institution as indicator of level of scientific literacy in Adamawa State. As public understanding of science increases, science education curriculum as bedrock for national development can move a nation economically, socially, politically and culturally forward which become a basis for sustainable development. The target population of the study comprised all students in tertiary institutions in the state. Two selected institutions were used as the sample of the study, made up of 800 students. Data collected using questionnaires were analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics in order to answer the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypothesis. The major findings of the study showed inclination to superstition in women more than men; and the more the educational level, the less inclination to superstition. Based on the findings, it was recommended that government and other stakeholders should invest more in science education while curriculum planners and implementers should ensure that science in schools is taught in a way that helps to change the mindset and psyche of our people. This is the only way scientific knowledge can benefit society and bring about sustainable development.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past fifty years, the concept of scientific literacy was introduced to the science education community by (Hurd, 1958). There has been considerable debate over the various meanings entailed by science (Shamos, 1995; Laugksch, 2000; Fensham, 2002; Roberts, 2007). Scientific literacy and several closely related terms, like science literacy or public understanding of science are very much a part of the landscape of science education writing and research of the past half century. No ultimate consensus has been reached on the definition of the concept.

However, according to Hurd, (1998), scientific literacy is seen as a civic competency required for national thinking about science in relation to personal, social, political, economic problems and issues that one is likely to meet throughout life. In a much earlier analysis of this concept, Roberts (1983) suggested that scientific literacy has so many interpretations that it now means virtually everything to do with science

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education and it had come to be an umbrella concept to signify the purposes of teaching science in schools. During the early 1960s, scientific literacy was primarily a concept about curriculum goals. It suggests in very broad terms what the overall character of school science should be about and what it should emphasize. This means that scientific literacy as a concept may vary from day to day, but the fact remains that the concept still occupies a central position in aims and objectives for many contemporary curriculum reform projects (e.g. All American Advancement in Science, AAAS, 1989, 1993, 2001; Turkey Ministry of Education, TME, 2006). Since the 1960s educational reform, it has become a continuous worldwide movement in order to promote students literacy in different disciplines.

Universities, as other schools, are one of the places that prepare students for the real world and real life. In realizing this aim, universities must help their students gain scientific literacy abilities and grow scientifically literate citizens (Miller, 1998). This is necessary because of the challenge of living in a modern world. In addition, a scientifically literate individual has access to a wide range of employment opportunities and is better prepared to respond to the introduction of new technologies. Moreover, he/she is better able to cope with the demands of everyday life in an increasingly technology-dominated society (Osborne, 1998).

Amplifying these views, Okoronka (2007) opined that in the new millennium, we have to teach science to our children who represent the future in order to equip them. He further stated that there is a new but fast growing trend of teaching science to make for a scientifically literate society in which every citizen will be made to imbibe and appreciate the science culture. He suggested that this would imply that the 21st century science teacher must brace up to the challenges of not only teaching the few would be future scientists but also teaching the larger number of non-scientists whom the demands of our age have imposed on him to expose to the rudiments of science. He concluded that this is the only way to make every member of society live meaningfully within our scientifically and technologically situated age.

Superstitious beliefs have been found in a diverse range of cultures for thousands of years (Jahoda, 1969) and polls show that these beliefs continue to thrive in modern times. The clearest demographic correlate of superstitious beliefs is gender. According to Vyse (1997) most superstitious beliefs are more often held by

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women than men. In some studies, a low educational level has been connected to superstitious beliefs (Otis & Alcock, 1982; Za'rour, 1972), but in general, the results have been inconsistent (The National Science Foundation, 2006; Vyse, 1997). Science education curriculum at the primary and secondary school level have a major goal of inculcating scientific literacy into learners.

The objective of this study therefore is to determine the superstitious beliefs of Adamawa state students in tertiary institutions as indicator of level of scientific literacy in Adamawa State. The study equally determined whether there were gender differences and stereotypes in the superstitious beliefs of respondents as well as the relationship between superstitious beliefs and level of education. To achieve these objectives a research question was raised and two null hypotheses stated to guide the study as follows:

Research Question

(i) What are the superstitious beliefs of Adamawa state students in tertiary institutions on communication, sex, weather and environment?

Null hypotheses

Ho1 There is no significant difference between the superstitious beliefs of University students and College of Education students.

Ho2 There is no significant difference between male and female students inclination to superstitions

METHOD AND INSTRUMENTS

This study adopted survey research design to determine the superstitious beliefs of students of Adamawa State tertiary institutions. This is because survey research enables specific issues to be investigated through information gathering on people's opinion and belief over a large population. The population for this study comprised of all students in the tertiary institutions in Adamawa State who are indigenes. Two institutions were purposively selected as sample namely: Adamawa state University, Mubi (ADSU) and College of Education, Hong (COE). This is because the population of students in ADSU and COE is made

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up of more indigenes than other tertiary institutions in the state. Data were collected using questionnaire adapted from Uwalaka and Mutsuo (2002) which contained 25 items of a four point Likert scale format of Strongly agree, SA (4), Agree, A(3), Disagree, D(2) and Strongly Disagree, SD(1). The SA and A were collapsed together as A while the D and SD were collapsed into D.

RESULTS

Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 show the percentage responses of the respondents on superstitious items on communication, sex, weather and environment respectively.

Table 1: Summary of Percentage Responses on Superstitious beliefs of Students in tertiary institution on communication

Items	Respondents		
	Agree (AG)%	disagree (DA)%	Total %
The white man is using “juju” in GSM network	62.8	37.2	100
The internet has some sort of rituals in the working process	59.6	40.3	100

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It is believed that space satellites are using spirits and rituals in transmitting information	48.8	51.2	100
If a person bites his tongue while eating, it means somebody is calling him	53.7	46.3	100
If an owl cries it means an old person has died	47.0	53.0	100

Table 1 indicates that 62.8% of the respondents believe that the white man is using juju in GSM networks, followed by 59.6% which believe that the internet has some sort of rituals in the working process: The least belief from the above Table was if an owl cries it means an old person has died' with 47.0% agree and 53% disagree. From the analysis, it is clear that the students are still inclined to superstitions beliefs on communication.

Table 2: Summary of Percentage Response on superstitious beliefs of students in tertiary institutions on Sex.

Items	RESPONDENTS'		
	Agree (AG)%	Disagree (DA)%	Total %
Bareness is as a result of evil spirit.	57.33	42.65	100
If a man eat food from a cooking pot, he will not bear a child	57.2	42.8	100
A woman who is not circumcised will be promiscuous	62.2	37.8	100
When a lizard cross over a woman legs, it means she will soon get pregnant	59.7	40.3	100
when a woman hates to get married, it means evil spirits have married her	40.8	59.2	100

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Table 2 indicates that 62.2% of the respondents agree that a woman who is not circumcised will be promiscuous, followed by 59.7% which agree that when a lizard crosses over a woman legs, it means she will soon get pregnant: The least belief from the table was when a woman hates to get married, it means evil spirits have married her, with 40.8% agree and 59.2% disagree. From the analysis, it is evident that the students are inclined to superstitious beliefs on sex.

Table 3: Summary of Percentage Response on superstitious belief of students in tertiary institutions on weather.

Items	RESPONDENTS'		
	Agree (AG)	Disagree (DA)	Total
It is bad to light torch and point it to the sky at night	56.4	43.6	100
When there is an eclipse of the moon, people should sacrifice a 'he goat' and beat drums to avert an impending danger	28.5	71.5	100
People should not count the stars at night	66.2	33.8	100
People should not sweep at night	82.6	17.4	100
When a thunder strikes a person dead, it indicates that the person's hands are not clean.	51.3	48.7	100

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Table 3 indicates that 82.6% of the respondents believe that people should not sweep at night, followed by 66.2% which believe that people should not count the stars at night, followed by 56.4% who believe that it is bad to light torch and point it to the sky at night and 51.3% who believe that when thunder strikes a person dead, the persons hands are not clean. The least belief from the Table was when there is an eclipse of the moon people should sacrifice a He Goat and beat drums with 28.5% agree and 71.5% disagree From the analysis, it is evident that the students are still inclined to superstitions beliefs on weather .

Table 4: Summary of Percentage Response on superstitious belief of students in tertiary institutions on environment.

Items	Respondents		
	Agree (AG)%	Disagree (DA)%	Total %
When you push a firewood with your leg while cooking then the people to eat the food will fight	67.33	32.65	100
When a dead child is buried facing upward, it closes the mothers womb.	37.2	62.8	100
People should not talk or sing while taking bath	72.8	27.2	100
Evil spirits call people and they die if they answer	49.7	50.3	100
When a dog leaves the owners house to a neighboring house then the owner will die.	50.2	49.8	100S

Table 4 indicates that 72.2% of the respondents believe that people should not talk or sing while taking bath, followed by 67.33% which believe that when you push a firewood with your leg while cooking, then the people to eat the food will fight the least belief from the Table was that when a dead child is buried facing upward, it will closes the mother's womb with 37.2% agree and 62.8% disagree. From the analysis, it is clear that the students are inclined to superstitious beliefs on environment.

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Table 5: Z-test for Comparison of Superstitions Inclination between University and College of education Students

Level of Education	Number (N)	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard deviation (SD)	Z-crit	Z-cal	Degree of freedom (DF)
University Students	374	43.80	7.245	0.121	1.96	766
College of Education students	394	43.96	7.835			

Table 5, shows that the superstitious inclination of college of education students and University students does not differ significantly. Calculated z-value from Table 6 is 1.96 which is greater than critical value of 0.121 considering 95% level of significance and 766 degree of freedom. Therefore, the hypotheses that states that there is no significant difference between the superstitious beliefs of University students and College of Education students, is not rejected.

Table 6: Z-test for Comparison of Superstition Inclination in Male and female respondents

Gender	Number (N)	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard deviation (SD)	Z-crit	Z-cal	Degree of freedom (DF)

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Male	392	41.56	7.056	1.960	10.141	766
Female	376	46.06	7.151			

Table 6, showed that calculated z-value was 10.141 which is greater than the z-critical value 1.96, considering 5% error level. Therefore, it can be inferred (with at least 95%, confidence) that inclination to superstition in females is more than males. Therefore the second null hypothesis is not rejected which states that there is no significant difference between male and female Adamawa students superstitious beliefs.

DISCUSSION

Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 indicate the percentage responses of the respondents on superstitious items on communication, sex, weather and environment respectively. From the analysis it is evident that Adamawa state students in tertiary institution believe most on superstitions on weather, followed by sex followed by environment and lastly communication. This finding is in agreement with research finding by Patel (1984) found that, majority of Indians had belief in superstition of their immediate environment

The mean inclination to superstitions in COE students is slightly more than that of University students. The z-test indicated that there is no significant difference between University students and College of education students' inclination to superstition. This finding is similar to that by Patel and Sanithi (1984) that superstitious beliefs are prevalent among people of all levels of formal education. Another finding of the study is that inclination to superstitious was more in female students than there male counterparts. This is in agreement with Shanooshii (2003); Zebb and Barbara (2001) and Peltzer (2002). Who found that intentionally or unintentionally women incline to superstitions more than men because they rely on their feelings more than men and incline more to tradition.

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Implication and conclusion

The findings of this study imply that the superstitious beliefs of students tend to persist even after they have finished secondary education and entered into tertiary institutions. This further implies that the aims and objectives of science education implemented through the teaching of physics, chemistry, mathematics and biology in secondary schools are not being attained. This calls for more concerted effort on the part of stakeholders in science education (government, science and mathematics teachers, science and mathematics textbooks authors) to adopt techniques and measures that will make science more authentic to the learner in confronting problems within his/her immediate environment. This will enable the average science student to be able to relate and use the scientific theories, principles and laws to explain events and phenomena in the immediate environment. After all, science education is supposed to help change the mindset and psychology of people. This is the only way scientific knowledge can benefit society and bring about sustainable development.

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SUSTAINABLE MEDICAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH

**PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS: A CASE STUDY OF THE GOVERNMENT
SECONDARY SCHHOOOL, OGBIA, BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA.**

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KEYWORDS: Dental fluorosis, Fluoride, dental caries

ABSTRACT

Background: The prevalence of dental fluorosis in certain parts of the globe has been found to be increasing. In contrast to these prevalence reports in these areas, there is little or no systematic epidemiological study evaluating dental fluorosis in Bayelsa state, Nigeria. We thus studied the prevalence of dental fluorosis among school children in Ogbia town, Ogbia local government of Bayelsa state, Nigeria and evaluated the role played by potential risk factors.

Method: A cross-sectional survey of 242 school children (106 males, 136 females) within the age group of 10 – 17 years using a multistage random sampling technique was done. A pre-tested questionnaire was used to assess exposure to various fluoride sources. Dental professionals examined all the children to determine the absence or presence of dental fluorosis, with the Dean's Index used for grading of the degrees of dental fluorosis. Bivariate associations were tested using Chi-squared tests and linear logistic regressions were used to determine the association between selected risk factors and the occurrence of dental fluorosis.

Result: The mouth prevalence of dental fluorosis among our study sample was 19% and the Community Fluorosis Index was 0.57. The principal factor associated with the presence of dental fluorosis was sachet water (OR: 2.00, 95% CI: 0.97 – 4.09, $p = 0.04$). No significant association was found between dental fluorosis and the consumption of sea fish, the use of fluoride supplements and the use of fluoride toothpaste.

Conclusion: Dental fluorosis is thus, not a public health problem in Ogbia town, Bayelsa state although, sachet water is a risk factor associated with the occurrence of dental fluorosis. Measures should thus be

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taken to review the fluoride content of sachet water produced in the area of this study. Also, similar in-depth studies using similar criteria for assessing dental fluorosis prevalence needs to be carried out in other parts of Bayelsa state and Nigeria as a whole.

INTRODUCTION

Fluoride is often called a double-edged sword because deficiency of fluoride intake leads to dental caries while excess intake leads to dental and skeletal fluorosis. (Esa & Razak, 2001).

There has been a decline in dental caries prevalence and incidence during the last twodecades, both in economically developed and in economically developing countries. This decrease is considered to be largely due to the widespread use of fluoride. Concurrent with the decline in caries, an increase in the prevalence of dental fluorosis has been documented, in communities with and without fluoridated drinking water. (McGrady et al, 2012; Buzalaf, Cury, & Whitford, 2001; [Mascarenhas](#), 2000).

Dental fluorosis is a developmental disturbance of dental enamel caused by successive exposures to high concentrations of fluoride during tooth development, leading to enamel with lower mineral content and increased porosity. The clinical appearance of mild dental fluorosis is characterized by bilateral, diffuse (not sharply demarcated) opaque, white striations that run horizontally across the enamel. These may be invisible to the individual and the clinician but often can be seen after the enamel has been dried. The opacities may coalesce to form white patches. In the more severe forms the enamel may become discolored and/or pitted. Upon eruption into the mouth, fluorosed enamel is not discolored; the stains develop over time due to the diffusion of exogenous ions (e.g., iron and copper) into the abnormally porous enamel. (Buzalaf, Cury, & Whitford, 2001).

The severity of dental fluorosis depends on when and for how long the overexposure to fluoride occurs, the individual response, weight, degree of physical activity, nutritional factors as well as bone growth. The recommended level for daily fluoride intake is 0.05 – 0.07 mg F/Kg/day, which is considered of great help in preventing dental caries by acting during remineralization. (Abanto et al, 2009).

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Abanto et.al (2009) stated that some 10% of children in optimally fluoridated (1.0 ppm) areas were affected by mild or very mild fluorosis in the permanent teeth and that less than 1% were so affected in low-fluoride areas. These degrees of prevalence were recorded prior to the availability of fluoridated dental products when fluoridated drinking water was the only significant source of fluoride intake, although this was still the view of a study conducted in the United States on the prevalence of adolescent fluorosis among adolescents aged between 10-17 years, which showed that the main dietary source of fluoride was drinking water however other sources included the widespread use of fluoride drugs, fluoride tablets, mouth rinses, fluoride tooth pastes as well as various processed foods and beverages (Eugenio et al, 2010; WHO, 2002; Mascarenhas, 2000). Children within the age bracket of 10 – 17 years usually represent a population at risk for dental fluorosis as the period of teeth calcification from infancy to 6 years of age constitutes the vulnerable period for the onset of dental fluorosis (Gopalakrishnan et al, 1999) with the period of greatest susceptibility being the time of mineralization of the secondary upper central incisor teeth at about 22 – 26 months of age. (WHO, 2004)

Many studies have also identified fluoride supplements as risk factors for dental fluorosis, both in fluoridated and non-fluoridated areas. In fluoridated areas the risk of dental fluorosis from use of fluoride supplements is almost 4 times higher than in non-fluoridated areas. (Buzalaf, Cury, & Whitford, 2001).

The prevalence of dental fluorosis has been increasing in a number of countries in recent years (Esa & Razak, 2001), it has been observed that there is insufficient or no data as regards the prevalence of dental fluorosis in Bayelsa state. With the presence of what looks like a white-mottled appearance (which is suggestive of dental fluorosis) on the teeth of students in the Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state, it is thus suspected that dental fluorosis may be prevalent in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state.

Thus, this makes it necessary to determine whether or not this mottled appearance is due to dental fluorosis as well as to determine the presence of any associated risk factors.

This research work when completed will provide useful information about dental fluorosis in Ogbia local government area. It will educate communities in Ogbia as well as various health parastatals in Bayelsa state

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and in Nigeria at large on the prevalence of dental fluorosis in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state as well as possible ways to prevent future occurrences of dental fluorosis.

METHODS

We performed a cross-sectional survey of school children attending Basic Junior Secondary School and Government Secondary School, Ogbia within the age group of 10-17 years (JSS 1 – SS 3) during the month of February 2013.

Children in this age group were selected because they represent a population at risk for dental fluorosis; the period of calcification of teeth from infancy to 6 years of age constitutes the vulnerable period for the onset of this condition.

Ogbia town was chosen as the area of study because of unpublished reports indicating that dental fluorosis was prevalent in the area. The principal sources of drinking water in this area include sachet water (commonly known as pure water), tap water as well as water from boreholes.

The Taro Yamen's formula was used to calculate the sample size and a simple random cluster sampling technique was used to select our study sample after consultation with the principals of both schools as to the population of the study area. Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Principals of the participating schools and age eligibility requires that the subjects fall into the appropriate age bracket at the time of sampling.

The data were collected and recorded, based on a structured close-ended pre-tested questionnaire to obtain information on the age, gender, ethnicity and the religion of the respondents. Information on the source of drinking water, sea-fish intake, the use of fluoride supplements as well as the use of fluoride-containing toothpaste by the students was also gotten. These factors have been identified as potential risk factors for dental fluorosis in previous studies"

The printed questionnaires were administered to the students on the day of the dental examination, with clear instructions to submit the completed form as a pre-requisite for oral examination.

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Oral examination

The oral examination of each student was carried out by a dental specialist in the concerned classroom with the subject seated in a chair in bright daylight and the teeth were not dried prior to the examination for fluorosis.

The presence and severity of dental fluorosis was recorded and the Dean's index (Dean H.T., 1942) was used to determine the grade of dental fluorosis, thus:

- *Unaffected*: The enamel is translucent. The surface of the tooth is smooth, glossy, and usually has a pale creamy white colour.
- *Questionable*: The enamel shows slight changes ranging from a few white flecks to occasional white spots. This classification is utilized in those instances in which a definitive determination of the mildest form of fluorosis is not warranted and a classification of unaffected is not justified.
- *Very mild*: Small opaque paper-white areas are scattered over the tooth surface, but do not involve as much as 25% of the surface.
- *Mild*: White opaque areas on the surface are more extensive, but do not involve as much as 50% of the surface.
- *Moderate*: White opaque areas affecting more than 50% of the enamel surface.
- *Severe*: All enamel surfaces are affected. The major aspect of this classification is the presence of discrete or confluent pitting.

Statistical Analysis

We estimated a sample size of 242 subjects for the present study.

The prevalence of dental fluorosis was estimated by summing the occurrences of dental fluorosis showing definite signs of the condition. This implies adding up the occurrences from very mild fluorosis to severe fluorosis.

Community Fluorosis Index (CFI) was derived by multiplying the numerical weight (statistic consideration: p) and the frequency of fluorosis and dividing the result by the total sample.

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A community fluorosis index of greater than 0.6 had been used in previous studies to identify areas where fluorosis was a public health problem. (Saravanan S. et al, 2008)

The association of dental fluorosis (dependent variable) with select individual risk factors (predictor variables) was studied using chi-square tests. Linear logistic regressions were used to determine the association between selected risk factors and the occurrence of dental fluorosis.

A p-value of <0.05 was used for entry of the variables in the multivariable models. Odds ratios (and their 95% CI) for the association of the predictor variables with the dependent variable were computed.

All analyses were performed with the Epi Info statistical software and p-value of <0.05 was taken to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS

Altogether, 242 respondents were used in this study. The modal age was 13, n=58 (24%); 56.4% of the respondents were female, most of the respondents are of the Ijaw-speaking tribes of Nigeria: n=173 (71.5%) and majority of the respondents, n=232 (95.9%) are Christians. The demographic data of the respondents are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Data of Respondents (Subjects)

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. AGE			
10	7	2.90	1.20 – 5.90
11	9	3.70	1.70 – 6.90
12	36	14.90	10.60 – 20.00
13	58	24.00	18.70 – 29.90
14	47	19.40	14.60 – 25.00
15	44	18.20	13.50 – 23.60

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	16	19	7.90	4.80 – 12.00
	17	22	9.10	5.80 – 13.40
2. GENDER				
MALE	106		43.60	37.20 – 50.10
FEMALE	136		56.40	49.90 – 62.80
3. ETHNIC GROUP				
IGBO	63		26.00	20.60 – 32.00
IJAW	173		71.50	65.40 – 77.10
YORUBA	6		2.50	0.90 – 5.30
4. RELIGION				
CHRISTIANITY	232		95.90	92.50 – 98.00
ISLAM	7		2.90	1.20 – 5.90
OTHERS	3		1.20	0.30 – 3.60

N= 242

AGE RANGE: 10 – 17 YEARS; MODAL AGE: 13 (n = 58, 24.00%)

MEAN AGE: 13.85 ± 1.71; VARIANCE: 2.94

SOURCES OF DRINKING WATER AS RISK FACTORS OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS

In all, the consumption of five different sources of drinking water was determined. 122 (50.4%) of the respondents drink borehole water, 149 (61.6%) of the respondents drink sachet water (popularly known as pure water), 159 (65.7%) of the respondents consume tap water, 20 (8.3%) get their drinking water from wells and 20 (8.3%) also get their drinking water from the river. This is outlined in table 2.

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Table 2: Sources of Drinking Water as a Risk Factor Of Dental Fluorosis

WATER SOURCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVALS
1. BOREHOLE			
• YES	122	50.40	43.90 – 56.90
• NO	120	49.60	43.10 – 56.10
2. SACHET WATER			
• YES	149	61.60	55.10 – 67.70
• NO	93	38.40	32.30 – 44.90
3. WELL WATER			
• YES	20	8.30	5.10 – 12.50
• NO	222	91.70	87.50 – 94.90
4. TAP WATER			
• YES	159	65.70	59.40 – 71.70
• NO	83	34.30	28.30 – 40.60
5. RIVER WATER			
• YES	20	8.30	5.10 – 12.50
• NO	222	91.70	87.50 – 94.90

OTHER RISK FACTORS OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS

In this study, the presence of three other risk factors were used in determining the prevailing risk factor(s) associated with dental fluorosis in Government Secondary School, Ogbia town. 224 (92.6%) of the

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respondents use a fluoride-containing toothpaste, 143 (27.3%) of the respondents eat sea fish often and only 66 (27.3%) of the respondents use fluoride supplements. These are shown in table 3.

Table 3: Other Risk Factors of Dental Fluorosis

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. USE OF TOOTHPASTE			
• YES	224	92.60	88.50 – 95.50
• NO	18	7.40	4.50 – 11.50
2. FLUORIDE SUPPLEMENTS			
• YES	66	27.30	21.80 – 33.30
• NO	176	72.70	66.70 – 78.20
3. CONSUMPTION OF SEA FISH			
	143	59.10	52.60 – 65.30
	99	40.90	34.70 – 47.40

MOUTH PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS

After oral examination of the 242 subjects involved in this study, it was found that 150 (62%) of the subjects were not affected by dental fluorosis, 46 (19%) of them had questionable fluorosis, 15 (6%) of the subjects had very mild fluorosis, 9 (4) of them had mild fluorosis, 6 (2%) had moderate fluorosis and 16 (7%) of the subjects had severe fluorosis. This is shown in figure 1. In calculating the prevalence of dental fluorosis the Dean's Index was used with the prevalence of dental fluorosis considering only cases with definite signs of fluorosis ranging from very mild fluorosis to severe fluorosis. The attainment of the Community Fluorosis Index was based on Dean's (1942) Index score (0 – 4.0 for dental fluorosis. This is shown in table 4.

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FIGURE 1: PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS AMONG STUDENTS AGED BETWEEN 10 – 17 ATTENDING GOVERNMENT SECONDARY SCHOOL, OGBIA.

Table 4: Dean’s Index to Determine Prevalence of Dental Fluorosis and Community Fluorosis Index In Students of Government Secondary School, Ogbia.

	FREQUENCY OF FLUOROSIS	PERCENTAGE (%)	WEIGHT OF FLUOROSIS	FREQUENCY*WEIGHT OF FLUOROSIS
UNAFFECTED	150	62	0	0
QUESTIONABLE	46	19	0.5	23
VERY MILD	15	6	1	15
MILD	9	4	2	18

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MODERATE	6	2	3	18
SEVERE	16	7	4	64
TOTAL	242	100		138

NOTE: THE PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS CONSIDERS ONLY CASES WITH DEFINITE SIGNS OF FLUOROSIS RANGING FROM VERY MILD FLUOROSIS TO SEVERE FLUOROSIS(REFERENCE ON INDEX).

FROM TABLE ABOVE:

PREVALENCE OF FLUOROSIS = SUMMATION (FREQUENCIES OF VERY MILD, MILD, MODERATE AND SEVERE FLUOROSIS)

$$= 15 + 9 + 6 + 16$$

$$= 46 (19.0\%)$$

COMMUNITY FLUOROSIS INDEX

THIS IS EQUAL TO:

$$= \frac{\text{SUMMATION (FREQUENCY OF FLUOROSIS * WEIGHT OF FLUOROSIS)}}{\text{TOTAL SAMPLE}}$$

$$= \frac{138}{242}$$

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= 0.57 (BORDERLINE FOR PUBLIC HEALTH SIGNIFICANCE)

COMPARISON BETWEEN FLUOROSIS AND ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS

The Chi-squared test as well as bivariate associations was used to determine a relationship between fluorosis and the risk factors stated in this study. This is shown in table 5.

Table 5:Odds Ratio Estimation For Prevalence Of Fluorosis And Risk Factors In Government Secondary School, Ogbia.

RISK FACTOR p-value	ODDS RATIO FOR DENTAL		CONFIDENCE INTERVAL	
	FLUOROSIS	PREVALENCE	INFERIOR	SUPERIOR
TAP WATER	1.41	0.70	2.85	0.21
RIVER WATER	0.45	0.10	2.01	0.22
BOREHOLE WATER	0.57	0.30	1.10	0.06
SATCHET WATER*	2.00	0.97	4.09	0.04
FLUORIDE TOOTHPASTE	2.00	0.43	8.82	0.30
FLUORIDE SUPPLEMENTS	1.38	0.69	2.75	0.23
SEA FISH CONSUMPTION	0.90	0.46	1.68	0.41

***STUDENTS THAT CONSUMED SATCHET WATER (PURE WATER) HAD 2 TIMES MORE RISK TO SUFFER DENTAL FLUOROSIS THAN THOSE WHO DID NOT CONSUME IT. (Chi^2 : 3.64;p-value: 0.04.**

THIS IS THE SAME CASE WITH FLUORIDE TOOTHPASTE ALTHOUGH THE p-Value DOES NOT SHOW STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE (p-value: 0.30)

DISCUSSION

The low prevalence and Community Fluorosis Index suggests that dental fluorosis is not a public health problem in the study area.

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The overall prevalence of fluorosis of 19% is less than what was recorded by Gopalakrishnan et al (35.6%). This finding was the same for the community fluorosis index which was lower than previous findings: 0.57 as against 0.69 (Gopalakrishnan et al, 1999). This thus shows that dental fluorosis is less of a public health problem in our study area than in other regions (Chandrashekar J. et al, 2004) although the number of severe cases (n=16 [7%]) evokes some concern as it may have been due to a chronic ingestion of excessive fluoride by these students.

On examination of the subjects, the major complication of dental fluorosis was the presence of white opacities (89.13%) while the remainder (10.87%) presented with pitting/chipped-off enamel which were all seen as severe cases of dental fluorosis.

Sachet water commonly called pure water (in this part of the world) was found to be a statistically significant risk factor associated with dental fluorosis with an odds ratio value of 2.00 (Confidence Interval: 0.97 – 4.09, Chi²: 3.64, p-value:0.04). Unfortunately, there are no prior reports to associate with this finding.

It was also observed that fluoride-containing toothpaste was a major risk factor associated with the occurrence of dental fluorosis with an odds ratio value of 2.00 (although this result was not statistically significant, p-value: 0.30). This however, is supported by previous findings in which it has been reported that excessive fluoride intake due to inadequate use or swallowing of fluoride-containing toothpaste is also responsible for the development of dental fluorosis. (Abanto et al, 2009). Other risk factors tested in this study were however less likely to cause dental fluorosis.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, dental fluorosis is not a public health problem among students of Government Secondary School, Ogbia town; although, the number of observed severe cases of the disease should be treated as urgent cases of public health intervention.

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Sachet water (pure water) is a significant risk factor of dental fluorosis among students of Government Secondary School, Ogbia.

It is recommended that further in-depth research using similar criteria for assessing the prevalence of dental fluorosis in other parts of Bayelsa state and Nigeria as a whole be done. A review of the fluoride content of sachet water by its manufacturers is also advised and oral health education on the principles guiding the usage of fluoride-containing toothpaste should be looked into to be carried out.

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ASSESSMENT OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULACE OF IKIBIRI COMMUNITY, YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS.

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KEYWORDS: Oral health problems, Causes, Solutions

ABSTRACT

Background: This research work was aimed at assessing the oral health problems of the elderly populace of Ikibiri community, Bayelsa state as well as determining possible solutions to these problems.

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Method: A descriptive study design was carried out on 100 respondents comprising of elderly individuals of Ikibiri community, Yenagoa local government area of Bayelsa state between the ages of 60 - 110 years. Interviewer - based questionnaires assessing the presence of specific oral health problems as well as delivery of oral health services were used as our instrument for data collection.

Results: Bleeding gums (52%), toothache (44%), and oral sores (42%) were found to be the major oral health problems being experienced by the population under study and these were mostly attributed to the absence of a dentist (95%), absence of a dental clinic (94%) as well as the absence of oral health education to the community (87%).

Conclusion: Oral health problems are undoubtedly present among the elderly individuals of Ikibiri community, Yenagoa LGA, Bayelsa state which was attributed to the absence of dental personnel, dental facilities and oral health education. It was however recommended that Ikibiri community be provided with dental personnel and facilities as well as the provision of oral health education to the entire populace of Ikibiri; which would indeed reduce the burden of oral health problems among the elderly in this community.

INTRODUCTION

Oral health is a standard of health of the oral and related tissues which enables an individual to eat, speak and socialize without active disease, discomfort or embarrassment and which contributes to the general well being of an individual, thus preserving the highest levels of self esteem of such an individual, as there is increasing recognition that oral health has a significant impact on physical, social and psychological wellbeing of an individual. (Danfillo, 2009; Olusile, 2010; Saimadhavi et al, 2013). Generally, oral health in Africa has been characterized by low to very low caries prevalence and severity, inadequacy of oral health care personnel when matched with population needs, low priority given to oral health as well as poor working conditions. (Danfillo, 2009).

In Nigeria, there abounds a low level of oral health awareness, a high prevalence of periodontal disease leading to tooth loss which increases with age, very low to moderate prevalence of dental caries as well as the occurrence of other conditions such as oral cancers, dental fluorosis e.t.c. Nigeria also manifests an apparent lack of coordination for the provision of preventive dental services with little or no access to

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modern dental treatment within her rural areas and therapeutic dental services mainly available in the urbanized areas with the occasional visits of dentists to the rural areas. (Akpata, 2004; Taiwo et al, 2004; Taiwo and Omokhodoin, 2006; Sofola, 2010). In addition, it has been reported that factors affecting the oral health of the elderly populace in India include almost non-existent or limited preventive dental care, grossly insufficient dental personnel, poverty, illiteracy as well as lack of social security. (Shah, 2001).

It has been reported that the elderly make-up an important part of the general population as a result of the concomitant increase of the elderly population which is largely due to increasing life expectancy in most parts of the world and this increasing life expectancy has been associated with better nourishment, hygiene and healthcare of the elderly populace. The world's population of those aged 60 years and above increases by about a million every month and that by the year 2035; it is projected that the elderly will constitute one in every four persons. (WHO, 2003; Owotade et al, 2005; Pestic, 2007). A number of surveys have reported significant oral health impairment as well as poor oral hygiene among the elderly especially among the institutionalized which has been attributed to several factors including age-related changes that affect the oral health. Likewise, older adults are more vulnerable to diseases of the oral cavity due to an increase in chronic conditions as well as physical and mental disabilities. Thus, old people are a peculiar group in terms of service provision. (Owotade et al, 2005; Bhardwaj, 2012).

Oral diseases which the elderly are particularly prone to include root caries, attrition, attrition, missing teeth due to earlier neglect, edentulism, poor alveolar ridge quality, mucosal lesions, oral ulcerations/sores, dry mouth (xerostomia) amongst others including oral cancers whose incidence is highest in India, with 13.5% of all body cancers being oral cancers. Most of these diseases are indeed a sequelae of neglect in the early years of life of these individuals which includes poor knowledge of how to prevent oral diseases, tobacco smoking, consumption of cariogenic diets, betel nut chewing, to mention but a few. (Bhardwaj, 2012; Edwards and Kanjirath, 2010; Shah, 2001). The presence of these oral diseases as well as coexisting medical problems usually increases in magnitude the declining immunity associated with old age.

Due to poor systemic health, the elderly patient does not pay sufficient attention to oral health and it has indeed been reported that elderly people are least likely to seek dental care except in emergency situations

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as oral health is perceived to be a less important need when compared with physical health in general. Furthermore, financial constraints, lack of family support, misconceptions of dental treatment, low level of oral health awareness and transportation facilities adversely affect access to dental services when it concerns the elderly. (Bhardwaj, 2012; Owotade et al, 2005; Sofola, 2010). From studies carried out in the South-East Local Government Area in Ibadan, it was gathered that there was a high level of unmet dental needs as well as lack of perceived need among the elderly individuals from this area which thus contributed to their poor dental clinic attendance despite having good attitudes towards oral health. (Taiwo J.O. et al, 2007; Taiwo J.O. et al, 2012). In all these, reports State that experiences from developed countries show that the prevalence of chronic diseases and high levels of disability among the elderly and indeed for the entire populace can be reduced through health promotion and appropriate prevention strategies designed to improve quality of life. (Bhardwaj, 2012; Olushile, 2010; Sofola, 2010).

It has been observed that little or no reports exist concerning the oral health needs of the elderly populace in Ikibiri Community Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State amidst the fact that they are faced with different types of oral health problems of which most of them are not aware of thus the desire to identify the oral health needs and feasible strategies for solving them in this community. This study is significant in that it would provide pertinent information about the oral health problems of Ikibiri community as well as means that could be employed in controlling dental problems and promoting oral health and thus the general health of the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community, Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

METHODS

We employed a descriptive study design in determining the oral health problems of the elderly populace of Ikibiri community, Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Interviewer - based questionnaires assessing the presence of specific oral health problems as well as delivery of oral health services were distributed among 100 respondents gotten by a convenience sampling technique comprising of elderly individuals of this community ranging between the ages of 60 - 110 years. Permission to carry out data collection was gotten from the Chairman of the Community Development Committee of Ikibiri Community and the decision by the respondents to be involved in this study was completely voluntary.

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Data gotten from the respondents was analyzed using the Epi Info 3.4.3 statistical software and the relationship among certain oral health problems was determined.

RESULTS

Altogether, 100 respondents participated in this study. The modal age group was between ages 60 – 70 years, n=56 (56%); 58% of the respondents were females and the major occupation the respondents were involved in was farming (60%). The demographic data of the respondents is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF RESPONDENTS

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
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1. AGE			
• 60 – 70	56	56.00	45.70 – 65.90
• 71 – 80	25	25.00	16.90 – 34.70
• 81 – 90	15	15.00	8.60 – 23.50
• 91 – 100	3	3.00	0.60 – 8.50
• 101 – 110	1		
		1.00	0.00 – 5.40
2. GENDER			
• MALE	42	42.00	32.20 – 52.30
• FEMALE	58	58.00	47.70 – 67.80
3. OCCUPATION			
• CIVILSERVANT	13	13.00	7.10 – 21.20
• FARMER	60	60.00	49.70 – 69.70
• FISHING	11	11.00	5.6 – 18.80
• RETIRED	13	13.00	7.10 – 21.20
• SELF EMPLOYED	3	3.00	0.60 – 8.50
4. MARITAL STATUS			
• MARRIED	63	63.00	52.80 – 72.40
• DIVORCED	1	1.00	0.00 – 5.40
• SINGLE	4	4.00	1.10 – 9.90
• WIDOW	27	27.00	18.60 – 36.80
• WIDOWER	5	5.00	1.60 – 11.30
5. RELIGION			
• CHRISTIANITY	91	91.00	83.60 – 95.80

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• ISLAM	1	1.00	0.00 – 5.40
• OTHERS	8	8.00	3.50 – 15.20

N= 100; AGE RANGE: 60 – 110; MODAL AGE GROUP: 60 - 70

ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS OF RESPONDENTS

In all, 52% of the respondents said they were experiencing bleeding gums, 44% were experiencing some form of tooth ache, 42% had sores/injuries in their mouths and 34% of the respondents had dry mouth (xerostomia). This is outlined in Table 2.

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TABLE 2: ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS OF THE RESPONDENTS

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. BLEEDING GUMS	52	52.00	41.80 – 62.10
2. TOOTHACHE	44	44.00	34.10 – 54.30
3. SORES/ INJURIES IN THE MOUTH	42	42.00	32.20 – 52.30
4. DRY MOUTH	34	34.00	24.80 – 44.20

CAUSES OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULACE OF IKIBIRI COMMUNITY

In our survey, it was gathered that the absence of a Dentist (95%), the absence of a dental clinic (94%) as well as the absence of oral health education were major causes of the oral health problems being experienced by the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community. This is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: CAUSES OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULACE OF IKIBIRI

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. ABSENCE OF A DENTIST	95	95.00	88.70 – 98.70
2. ABSENCE OF A DENTAL CLINIC	94	94.00	87.40 – 97.80
3. ABSENCE OF ORAL HEALTH EDUCATION	87	87.00	78.80 – 92.90

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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PRESENCE OF BLEEDING GUMS AS AN ORAL HEALTH PROBLEM AND THE PRESENCE OF OTHER ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

An interesting relationship was found to exist between the presence of bleeding gums and the presence of toothache and oral sores. It was observed that as the number of cases of bleeding gums were increasing, the number of cases of toothache also increased ($r=0.31$, $p\text{-value}=0.002$) and the number of cases of oral sores increased as well ($r=0.25$, $p\text{-value}=0.01$). This is outlined in Table 4.

TABLE 4: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PRESENCE OF BLEEDING GUMS AS AN ORAL HEALTH PROBLEM AND THE PRESENCE OF OTHER ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

Variable	Correlation Coefficient	Standard Error	p-value
Toothache	0.305	0.094	0.001649*
Dry Mouth	0.093	0.101	0.360543
Oral Sores	0.253	0.096	0.010229**

p-value is set at <0.05

*Significant relationship between Bleeding gums and Toothache ($p=0.002$, $r=0.31$)

**Significant relationship between Bleeding gums and Sores in the mouth ($p=0.01$, $r=0.25$)

METHODS OF ORAL HYGIENE USED BY THE RESPONDENTS

Amongst the respondents, 51% use toothbrush to clean their mouths. 28% use chewing stick, 14% use only water to rinse their mouths, 4% use charcoal to clean their mouths, 2% use saltwater and 1% of the respondents use sand as an oral hygiene method. The distribution of what the respondents use in maintaining their oral hygiene is shown in Figure 1.

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FIGURE 1: METHODS OF ORAL HYGIENE USED BY RESPONDENTS

THE ACTION OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

Out of the total population of the respondents, 38% of the respondents went to the chemist to buy drugs to use in order to treat the problem, 28% of the respondents do nothing i.e. they do not do anything to treat themselves when they have oral health problems. 21% of the respondents treat themselves traditionally and only 13% visit the dentist to receive treatment when they have oral health problems. This is shown in Figure 2.

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FIGURE 2: THE ACTION OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

DISCUSSION

An important criteria for successful aging apart from the availability of health promotion and appropriate prevention strategies designed to improve quality of life, is also the maintenance of a functional, natural and healthy dentition throughout life, including all the social and biologic benefits such as aesthetics, comfort, the ability to chew, taste and speak. As the elderly populace increases, there would be an increasing demand on dental services by such individuals. (Owotade et al, 2005).

From the results of this study, the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community certainly experience oral health problems. It was seen that the age group of 60 – 70 years had the highest population in this study and

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accounted for 56% of the respondents, this is in line with the findings of Owotade et al (2005). Majority of the respondents are farmers which accounted for 60.0% of the population, this is in line with the fact that the occupation of the people of Ikibiri community in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria is farming. 63.0% of the respondents are married and christians were accounted for the highest number of respondents. This may be due to the fact that the south – south region of Nigeria is dominated by Christianity.

The major oral health problem among the elderly in Ikibiri Community was bleeding gums (52.0%), which may be due to poor oral hygiene status (Akpata, 2004) as well as poor oral health education and awareness among the elderly populace of this community which agrees with the reports of Sofola (2010). 44% of the respondents had toothache as an oral health problem which may have been due to the lack of appropriate dental awareness, lack of dental health facilities as well as dentists in the community. Sores/injuries in the mouth were oral health problems affecting 42% of the respondents which may have been due to poor oral health practices. Dry mouth recorded a 34% occurrence among the respondents as an oral health problem and may be due to various medications being taken by the elderly in this community.

The possible causes of oral health problems among the elderly in Ikibiri community indicated that almost all of the respondents (95%) attributed it to the absence of a dentist. 94.0% of the respondents were of the opinion that the absence of a dental clinic was a major cause and a contributing factor to the prevalence of oral health problems in the community and 87.0% of the respondents agreed that the absence of oral health education was a cause of oral health problems in Ikibiri Community.

The elderly populace of Ikibiri Community had various practices when they had oral health problems, which included going to the chemist to buy drugs to use (38.0%), treating themselves with local herbs at home (21.0%), doing nothing (28.0%) and going to visit the dentist to obtain dental treatment at the State capital Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Furthermore, out of all the respondents, 51.0% used tooth brush to clean their mouths, 28.0% used chewing stick, 14.0% used only water to rinse their mouths, 4.0% used charcoal to clean their mouths, 2.0% used salt water to clean their mouths and only 1.0% used sand to clean the mouth which goes to show the extent of poor knowledge of oral health and oral hygiene practices and may

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explain further the presence of oral health problems being experienced among the elderly populace of this community. This agrees with the reports made by Sofola (2010) who said that: “when there is low oral health awareness, there is a direct effect on the illness seeking behaviour of the individual and population”.

The significant correlation between bleeding gums, toothache and oral sores may have been due to the occurrence of periodontal diseases which is capable of causing these oral health problems. This surely, can be attributed to the poor oral hygiene practices of the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the study carried out in Ikibiri community Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria, there is the presence of oral health problems among the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community which require urgent steps and strategies to be put in place in order to reduce the occurrence of oral health problems and also promote the oral health status of the elderly populace in this community.

The following steps and strategies are thus recommended to be put in place to reduce the occurrence of these oral health problems. Viz:

1. Provision of dental health personnel and services at Ikibiri community, which would enable the elderly to have access to oral health services.
2. Oral health education programmes should be carried out from time to time not just in Ikibiri Community but also in other communities in different Local Government Areas in Bayelsa and in Nigeria as a whole in order to provide proper education to the elderly and the entire populace on oral health and oral health promotion.

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ERADICATING STRESS AMONGSTUDENTSINHIGHERINSTITUTION (OYOSTATECOLLEGE OFAGRICULTURE, IGBOORA, OYOSTATE)

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KEYWORDS: stress, students, parents, challenges

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to determine how to eradicate stress among students in higher institution. The study adopted a design in which 200 students from Oyo state College of Agriculture, Igboora were the respondents. Data collected were analysed using Anova. Students face harsh realities of life which challenges them not only cognitively but emotionally and psychologically as well. Hence, stress is not uncommon among students in higher learning institutions. By understanding how these students cope with stress, the parents, lecturers, advisers, administrators can assist in managing it.

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SUSTAINABLE TROPICAL AGRICULTURE DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH

**PRESERVATION OF ANIMAL SEMEN: AN IMPORTANT ASPECT IN MAINTENANCE OF
REPRODUCTIVE AND FERTILITY PARAMETERS**

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Knowledge for Global Development

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ABSTRACT

Semen extender is graded on its capability to protect spermatozoa, conserving motility and fertility over time by stabilizing the plasmalemma, providing energy substrates and preventing deleterious effects of changes in pH and osmolarity. The present article is constructed to provide the readers with a holistic review on various efficacious semen extenders used for preservation under experimental conditions.

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IRRIGATION SCHEDULING FOR SOME SELECTED VEGETABLES CROP AT THE GALMA PILOT IRRIGATION SCHEME

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ABSTRACT

The possibility of improving efficient use of water and energy by applying the right amount of water to cropland at the right time and thereby increasing the extent of irrigation to other areas is not only relevant but calls for urgent attention. The study aims at determining irrigation scheduling for vegetable crops at Galma Pilot Irrigation Scheme of the Ministry of Water Resources, Zaria Kaduna State. The moisture contents at field capacity and wilting point were obtained from the soil water characteristics software named hydraulic properties calculator (HPC) using the details of the particles size analyses and bulk density obtained from the study area. The crop water requirement for each vegetable crop was estimated based on average of ten years weather data. Water application depth and irrigation interval were calculated based on the initial stage, crop development stage, middle stage and late stage. The irrigation interval for the initial stage for the different crops ranges between 3 – 5 days, crop development stage 4 -6 days, mid season stage 4 – 8 days and 4 -8 days at maturity. The water application depth ranges from 13 -20mm at the initial stage for the different crops, 14 – 22mm at the development stages, 19 -35mm at the middle stage and maturity stage.

KEYWORDS: Irrigation, vegetable crops, water application, maturity, moisture content

Background of the Study

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Vegetables are among the most important food of mankind as they are not only nutritious but also indispensable for the maintenance of health. From the point of view of the agriculturist also, it is of great importance as the is assured of high returns from its cultivation even on a small scale. The present vegetable production in the World is around one million tons per year, 70% of which is produced during the cool season (Ali, 2000). Production of summer vegetables is constrained by lack of suitable and high-yielding varieties, high rainfall, humidity and temperature, while vegetable production in winter is favored by suitable climate (Ali, 2000).

The farmers' irrigation are characterized by poor water management irrigation is applied at very high moisture content. The implication of this practice will be over irrigation, which will lead to water wastage and may likely affect the crop grown. Doorenbos and kassam (1979) warned that over irrigation of vegetables lead to poor yield. Over irrigation can also result in waterlogging of the farm, leading to build up of the water table and soil salinity. Adequate irrigation scheduling therefore needs to be designed for vegetable crops so as to improve their growth and yield.

Statement of the Problem

The Galma pilot scheme is a division of Zaria irrigation scheme in Kaduna state which is located 16km along new Zaria – Jos road. The purpose of establishing the pilot scheme was to train local farmers on when and how to irrigate their farmland. It was also meant to assist in putting the vast fertile land along the river Galma under crop production. Check basin is the most common method of irrigation observed by farmers growing vegetables like Carrot, Spinach, onion Lettuce, Cabbage in the scheme etc. The problem encountered in the scheme is the lack of trained personnel to effectively guide farmers on how to schedule Irrigation on their farmland.

Justification of the study

Most famers that produce vegetables depend on traditional methods of production. It is generally recognized that such production techniques do not put into consideration the amount of water applied to the crop, how frequent and how much water could be used by the crop. This has brought the need to effectively

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design the irrigation scheduling for Galma irrigation scheme which is required to reduce the excess water being wasted and put more in to production.

Objectives

To develop irrigation scheduling for some selected vegetable crops at Galma irrigation scheme these crops include: Carrot, Cabbage, Onion, Spinach and Lettuce.

The specific objective include;

1. To determine appropriate water application depths for selected vegetables in the study area.
2. To determine appropriate irrigation intervals for the selected vegetables in the study area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Irrigation Scheduling

Irrigation Scheduling is a process of determining when to irrigate, and how much water to apply per irrigation. Irrigation scheduling is important in achieving higher yields, good quality of farm products, water and energy conservation and to lower production cost. Some irrigation water is stored in the soil to be removed by crops and some is lost by evaporation, runoff or seepage. The amount of water lost through these process is affected by the irrigation system design and irrigation management. Prudent scheduling minimizes runoff and percolation losses, which in turn usually maximizes irrigation efficiency by reducing energy and water use (Robert, 1996). Irrigation scheduling is carried out, either to maximize yield per unit depth of water applied, or to maximize yield per unit area of land. Scheduling for maximum yield per land area becomes imperative when water supply is readily available and irrigation cost are low, while scheduling for maximum yield per unit depth of water is justified when irrigation water is limited in supply and cost of irrigation increases with use.

The factors that affect irrigation interval include water supply, climatic setting, crop and crop stages, irrigation system, soil, weather and the economics of irrigation interval based on fixed number of days requires the simplest and cheapest approach, often handled by unskilled workers. Plant water use change with crop stage and weather, and so it is not constant throughout the growing season. Fixed interval

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treatment can be either too wet or too dry at different plant stages for precise scheduling, information on the rate of water applied and crop water use are require.

Selected Vegetable

1. **Cabbage-** (*Brassica Olera Cea Ver Capitata*): cabbage is sown thinly in nursery bed or in boxes. Seed germinates 4-10 days after sowing. It is then transplanted on a bed when seedlings are 8-10cm in height. Depending on the variety, cabbage is ready for harvest in 12-18 weeks. (Sekyere, 1997).
2. **Carrot-** (*Daucus*): Carrot grows well on a light soil and seeds are sown on beds 1cm deep. Seeds germinate in 7 -14 days. Carrot is harvested 10-14 weeks after planting. (Sekyere, 1997).
3. **Lettuce-** (*Lactuca Sativa*): Lettuce seeds are sown sparsely in nursery beds or boxes. They are transplanted and the crop is ready for harvest in 6-10 weeks. (Sekyere, 1997).
4. **Onion-**(*Allium Cepa*): Onions are very sensitive to both temperature and length of day. Onion is sown in a nursery bed and gemimates in 7-21 days. They are transplanted when seedlings are 5-8cm tall and spaced at 10cm away. Bulbs mature in 3-4 months. The crop may be harvested green in 6-8 weeks after transplanting or left till leaves turn brown. (Sekyere, 1997).
5. **Spinach-** (*Basella Aba*): Spinach is sown in situ in rows at a distance 60cm by 30cm. leaves are harvested when young.

The selected vegetables have different growth stages, rooting zones and water requirement. Summary of these are shown in table 1

The Check Basin Irrigation System

Slobbers (1971) reported that the most common irrigation method in many parts of the world especially in food plains is the check basin method. It is used in both small sizes to grow vegetables and large sizes to grow cereal crops. The distinguishing features of the various uses of the check basin method of irrigation

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involve the size and shape of the basin and whether irrigation is accomplished by intermittent or continuous pounding of water in the basins. The basin size is highly dependent on the prevailing slopes.

According to Michael (1978) check basin irrigation is suited for smooth, gentle and uniform land slopes and for soil having moderate to low infiltration rates. It is also suitable in very permeable soil but the basins must be covered with water rapidly to prevent excessive deep percolation losses at the upstream end. The design of check basin is often limited by sized and height of practical basin ridges used to confine water in the basin.

Design Daily irrigation Requirement

James (1988) defined Design Daily Irrigation Requirement (DDIR) as the rate at which an irrigation system must supply water to achieve the desired level of irrigation. In some situations, the largest daily irrigation requirement is associated with land preparation (like rice paddy formation) and not evapotranspiration (ET) The DDIR for an irrigation system depend on the crop, climate, and soil of the farm. Farm located in climates with high daily ET rates and low precipitation have the largest DDIR.

Generally, DDIR_s for crops grown in soils with low water holding capacities such as sand are higher than those for crops grown in finer textured soils with higher water holding capacities. This is because the interval between irrigations increase with water holding capacity and the average daily irrigation requirement is smallest for longer irrigation intervals. DDIR Is expressed as (James, 1988):

$$DDIR = \frac{AD}{11_{min}} \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where:

Ad = Allowed depletion of soil water between irrigations (mm);

11_{min} = Minimum irrigation interval during irrigation season (days).

Approaches to Irrigation Scheduling

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The requirement regarding the number of irrigations and their timing vary for different crops. Under field experimental conditions the criteria of soil water availability plays an important role in scheduling of irrigation. This leads to the concept of evapotranspiration, maximum allowable deficiency (MAD), irrigation frequency etc, which can be used as the criteria for irrigation timing.

Irrigation should be scheduled by observing soil moisture level, and not by observation of the crop (Michael, 1978). A summary of the common irrigation scheduling techniques as presented by Rujov et al (1973) includes:

- a. Measurement or observation of water deficit in plants,
- b. Monitoring soil moisture content until the critical point is reached,
- c. Irrigation scheduling on evapotranspiration rates,
- d. Calculating irrigation schedules or irrigation guides.

Crop Coefficient

The crop coefficient K_C , relates the actual rate at which a crop uses water (ET) to reference evapotranspiration (ET_0). Burman et al, (1983) defined K_C as the ration of ET occurring for a specific crop at a specific stage of growth to the potential ET at that time. James (1988) stated that values of K_C for field and vegetable crops generally increase gradually from an initial low value to a peak plateau and then declines as the plant progresses to its maturity stage. Coefficient K_C and growth stage information for several other field vegetable crops are available in Doorenbos and Pruitt (1977).

Reference Crop Evapotranspiration (ET_0)

ET_0 may be either potential ET or reference ET. Potential ET is the maximum rate at which water, if available, can be removed from soil and plant surface, and varies from day to day (James, 1988). Doorenbos and Pruitt (1977) defined reference crop ET as the, "ET from an extensive surface of 8-15cm tall, green grass cover of uniform height, actively growing, completely shading the ground and not short of water". Potential ET varies from crop to crop, while reference crop ET is defined for a specific crop. Therefore, reference crop ET is preferred over potential ET (James, 1988).

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Several methods have been developed for computing ET_0 . One of such method is the hargreaves ET_0 equation, expressed as (Allen et al 1998).

$$ET_0 = 0.0023 (T_{\text{mean}} + 17.8) (T_{\text{max}} - T_{\text{min}})^{0.5} R_a \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where:

T_{mean} = Mean of the daily maximum (T_{max}) and Minimum temperatures (T_{min}).

R_a = extra terrestrial radiation for daily periods ($MJm^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) as detailed by allen et al 1998.

Crop Evapotranspiration (ET_C)

The term crop evapotranspiration refers to the rate of evapotranspiration of a disease-free crop growing in a field under optimal soil condition including sufficient water and fertilizer, and achieving full production potential of the crop under the growing environment (Doorebos and Pruitt, 1977).

$$ET_C = K_C \times ET_0 \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where:

K_C = crop coefficient

ET_0 = reference crop evapotranspiration (mm/day)

Maximum Allowable Deficiency (MAD)

The concept of maximum allowable deficiency, MAD is also one of the criteria for estimating the amount of water that can be used without adversely subjecting the crop to water stress. MAD gives the critical water content at which irrigation is required. It is defined as the ratio of readily available water to the total available water. That is

$$MAD = \frac{RAW}{TAW} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Where

RAW = readily available water (mm)

TAW = total available water (mm)

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Readily available water is defined as the amount of water between field capacity and critical soil water content. Total available water is the amount of moisture held between field capacity and wilting point. MAD depends on soil type as well as crop type. See table 2

Irrigation interval

Michael (1978) defined irrigation frequency as the number of days between irrigation during the period without rainfall. Irrigation frequency depends on the crop consumptive use and also on the amount of moisture stored in the root zone. It is function of crop, soil and climate. The stage of growth of crop with reference to the critical periods of growth is also kept in view while designing irrigation frequency is expressed as (Robert and Juanita 1989):

$$\text{Interval} = \frac{\text{RAW}}{\text{CRW}} \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where;

RAW= readily available water (mm) also known as net depth.

CRW= Crop water requirement (mm/day)

Irrigation period

According to Michael (1978) Irrigation period is the number of days that can be allowed for applying one irrigation to a given area during the peak consumptive use period of the crop being irrigated. It is the basis for irrigation system capacity and equipment design. The irrigation system must be so designed that the irrigation period is not greater than the irrigation interval.

Available Moisture

The major role of soil in supporting agriculture is their function as a reservoir of water and nutrients for plant use. The difference in moisture content of a soil between its field capacity and wilting point is termed the available moisture. This represents the moisture, which can be restored for subsequent use the plants. After irrigation, soil moisture is expected to be restored to field capacity.

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Field capacity is defined as the moisture content after drainage of gravitation water has become very slow and the moisture content has become relatively stable. The field capacity varies from one soil type to another. For sandy soil, it attains field capacity within one day; loamy soil about 2 days, whereas clay soil at 3 or more days after thorough wetting. Wilting point is the moisture content at which plants can no longer obtain enough moisture to meet their evapo-transpiration requirements, and remain wilted unless soil moisture is restored. For permanent

Water Application Efficiency

An ideal irrigation is assumed to be the one, which supplies enough water to wet the soil uniformly to field capacity throughout the root zone with negligible losses. Water application efficiency is the ratio of water that is in root zone of soil to the amount of water applied (Michael, 1978). It is expressed as,

$$E_A = \frac{R_S}{W_F} \dots\dots\dots 6$$

Where;

- E_A= water application efficiency (%)
- W_S= quantity of water stored in the root zone of plant (mm).
- W_F= quantity of water delivered to the field (mm).

Generally, water application efficiency decreases with increasing amount of water applied. Lower application efficiencies below 100% are due to run – off losses from the field and deep percolation below the root zone (Michael, 1978).

Water Application Depth.

Stewart et al. (1990) reported that at the beginning of the growing season, the amount of water given per irrigation application also called the water application depth is small and given frequently. This is due to the low evapotranspiration of young plants and their shallow root depth. During the mid – season, the irrigation depth should be larger and given less frequently due to high evapotranspiration and maximum

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root depth. In principle, the amount of irrigation water given in one irrigation application is the amount of water used by the plant since the previous irrigation.

Table 1 growing stage, root zone and water requirement of the selected vegetables.

Crop	Initial Length	Development length	Mid length	Late length	Total	Root depth (cm)	*Water requirement (mm)
Cabbage	40	60	50	15	165	0.5	380-500
Carrot	20	30	30	20	100	0.5	380-500
Lettuce	20	30	25	10	85	0.4	200-300
Onion	25	30	10	5	70	0.4	350.500
Spinach	20	20	15	5	60	0.4	250-380

Source: (Allen et al, 1998) * (Robert, 2003)

Table 2: MADvalues for the selected vegetables

Crop	MAD
Cabbage	0.45
Carrot	0.45
Lettuce	0.30
Onion	0.30
Spinach	0.30

Source: Allen et al (1998)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

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The Galma pilot irrigation scheme is a division of Zaria Irrigation Scheme in Kaduna State which is located 16km along the new Zaria – Jos road. It is on latitude 11° 05' North and longitude 7°44' east, and covers an area of about 250ha. Over 350 farmers are allocated with various sizes of farmland for both dry and raining season farming yearly. The different crops under cultivation are: wheat, okra, hot pepper, tomatoes, sweet potatoes, spinach, garden egg, carrot, onion, maize etc. the source of water for the scheme is Shikka Dam and the Galma river (Musa, 2008).

The climate of Galma is marked by wet and dry a season which is sub – divided into three;

- i. The cool, dry season from October to February
- ii. The hot, dry season from March to May and
- iii. The warm wet season from June to September.

The rainy season usually starts in the month of May and ends in October. Mean monthly temperature normally ranges from 30°C – 35°C and a mean relative humidity ranging from 30 – 70% annually.

Soil Physical Properties

Ogbe (2008) provided the details of the soil particle size analysis and bulk density of the study area. These details were used to determine moisture content at field capacity and wilting point with the help of the hydraulic properties soil characteristic software (Sexton, 1994) see table 3

Determination of Crop Evapotranspiration (ET_c)

An average of 10 year weather data was used to determine the reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) using the Hargreaves equation (Eq. 2) The weather data was obtained from the institute for Agricultural Research (IAR). Ahmadu Bello University, Samaru Zaria. The data are temperature, sunshine, relative humidity and wind speed. Hargreaves equation was used to determine the ET_0 because there were missing data. Crop evapotranspiration was determined by multiplying the average of the year reference evapotranspiration by the crop coefficient of the various stages of development of each crop given in. (Eq. 2.3)

Water application depth

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The water application depth (dg) was calculated from the net depth of application using E.q. 8 (Michael, 1978).

$$dg = \frac{dn}{Ea} \dots\dots\dots 7$$

Where:

- dg = gross depth (water application depth)
- dn = net depth of application
- Ea = Application efficiency
- MAD (FC – PWP) Rz

$$dn = \frac{MAD (FC - PWP) Rz}{100} \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where:

- MAD = Maximum Allowable Deficiency
- PWP = Permanent Wilting point (%)
- FC = Field Capacity
- Rz = Root zone depth (mm)

Irrigation interval

The Irrigation interval was calculated based on the stages of development of each vegetable, that is initial stage, development stage, middle stage and last stage. The irrigation interval was obtained base on soil, plant and climatic characteristics as recommended by Robert and Juanita (1989).

$$\text{Interval} = \frac{RAW}{CRW} \dots\dots\dots 9$$

Where;

- RAW = Readily available water (mm) also known as net depth.
- CRW = Crop water requirement (mm/day)

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Table 3 Average soil properties at different depths

Source: Ogbe (2008), *Saxton (1994)

Depth (mm)	Clay %	Silt %	Sand %	Texture	Bulk density g/cm ³	*Field capacity (% vol)	*Wilting point (% vol)
0.0 – 200	11	53	36	Silt loam	1.40	25.7	9.1
200 – 400	12	53	36	Silt loam	1.62	24.6	9.7
400 – 600	11	47	42	Loam	1.59	20.8	6.9
600 – 800	11	43	46	Loam	1.60	19.7	6.8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

In order to ensure optimum water management and efficiency in operation, an effective and suitable irrigation schedule for farmers that is practical under local condition should be designed. The results discussed in this chapter are centered on irrigation interval and water application depth for vegetable crops in Galma Irrigation Scheme.

Crop water requirement of the selected vegetables

Table 4 shows the average daily crop water requirement for the four growth stages season for the crops under study (Eq. 3). The crop water requirements were low at the initial stage of the crop that is just after planting. The values increase to a peak at the mid season stage of the crops. This because crop coefficient for the vegetable crops generally increase gradually from initial low value to a peak and then decline as the plant progresses to its maturity. See table 4

Water Application Depth

Farmers cultivating in Galma irrigation scheme do not have suitable means of measuring the amount of water they apply to their crop. Table 4.3 shows the water application depth required to bring the soil to field

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capacity at the different growth stages. Stewart et al. (1990) recommends 60% water application efficiency for surface irrigation system. This accounts for the amount of water that would be lost in the course of application. The water application depth was found to range from 13 – 20mm at the initial, 14 – 22mm at the development stage, 19 – 35mm at the middle stage and late stages. The water application depth for lettuce, onion and spinach were the same at different stage of development because soil is silt loam and they have the same rooting depth. Also cabbage and carrot have the same application depth at the different stages of crop development because the soil varies from silt loam to loam and have the same rooting depth. The water application depth increases from initial to late stage because the root zone depth keeps increasing. See table 5

Irrigation Interval

Table 6 shows the irrigation interval for the selected vegetables at the four stages of development. The irrigation interval for the initial stage for the different crop range between 3-5 days, crop development stage 4 – 6 days, mid season stage 4 – 8 days and maturity stage 4 – 8 days, for good crop growth and development the vegetables should be irrigated frequently at the beginning of the growing period because of their shallow root depth. This implies that, applying the same water application depth at the initial stage, can result in damage to crops, leading to building of water table and soil salinity. Since the water application depth is small, at the initial stage, the irrigation should be applied within a short interval. If farmers irrigate every seven days, it means at all growth stages, the crops will suffer moisture stress except for crop that the interval is less than 7 days.

Comparison between farmers' fixed schedule and design schedule

The irrigation interval observed by the farmers at the study area is 7 days. This interval was observed by the farmers irrespective of the growth stage of crop. Farmers have no knowledge of the water use that need to be applied to bring the soil to field capacity.

Growth stages of the selected vegetables where the computed interval is 8 days, the water use that needs to be applied to bring the soil to field capacity is higher compare to the farmers' water application depth at fix interval farmers schedule will result to water and yield may be affected

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Growth stages of the crop where the computed interval was less than 7 days, shows that the water use that applied to bring the soil to field capacity is less than the farmers water application depth at fixed interval. In this case water and energy will be wasted by the farmers schedule see table 7

Table 4 Average value of crop water requirement at various growth stages (mm/day)

Crop	Initial	Development	Middle	Late
Cabbage	2.6	3.9	5.0	4.4
Lattuce	2.6	3.5	5.1	5.1
Carrot	3.1	3.7	5.2	4.0
Onion	3.1	3.7	4.7	4.0
Spinach	3.1	3.5	4.8	4.1

Table 4.3: Irrigation water application depth at different stages of development for each application.

Crop	Initial stages(mm)	Development stages (mm)	Middle stage (mm)	Late stages (mm)
Cabbage	20	37	58	58
Carrot	20	37	58	58
Lettuce	13	23	32	32
Onion	13	23	32	32
Spinach	13	23	32	32

Table 4.2 Irrigation interval (days) at different stages of development.

Crop	Initial stage	Development stage	Middle stage	Late stage
Cabbage	5	6	8	8
Carrot	4	6	7	8

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Lettuce	3	4	4	4
Onion	4	4	4	4
Spinach	4	4	4	5

Table 7 comparing the farmer's water application depth at irrigation interval of 7 days with the computed interval.

Crop	Stage of development	Farmer's irrigation interval depth (day)	Water use /application interval (days)	Computed irrigation interval (days)	Water application depth (mm)
Cabbage	Interval	7	30	5	20
	Development	7	42	6	37
	Middle	7	54	8	58
	Late	7	50	8	58
Carrot	Initial	7	35	4	20
	Development	7	42	6	37
	Middle	7	58	7	58
	Late	7	53	8	58
Lettuce	Initial	7	30	3	13
	Development	7	48	4	23
	Middle	7	58	4	32
	Late	7	53	4	32
Onion	Initial	7	37	4	13
	Development	7	42	4	23
	Middle	7	57	4	32

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	Late	7	43	4	32
Spinach	Initial	7	37	4	13
	Development	7	42	4	32
	Middle	7	55	4	32
	Late	7	50	5	32

Summary

The study was conducted at Galma pilot schem, a Division of Zaria irrigation scheme in Kaduna State. The irrigation scheduling method observed by the farmers growing at the study area is fixed schedule and the irrigation method adopted by farmers is surface irrigation basically check basin. The soil of the study area was found to be silt loam at a depth of 400mm and loam at depths from 400mm to 600mm. an average of

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ten years weather data was used to compute reference crop evapotranspiration and crop water requirement for the selected vegetable crops was calculated. The irrigation interval and water application depth were calculated based on the growth stage of the selected vegetable crops. These depends on soil type, root depth and climatic data.

CONCLUSION

Irrigation scheduling is important in achieving higher yields, good quality of farm products and to lower production cost.

Farmers in Galma Irrigation Scheme should be effectively guided on how much water to be applied per irrigation and when to irrigate their farmland based on the growing stages of crops. This is because crop water use changes with crop stage and weather.

To maximize yield per unit area of land, appropriate water application and appropriate irrigation intervals must be considered. By virtue of the results of this finding, farmers in Galma Irrigation Scheme should be trained on how to irrigate their farmlands

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Further study need to be carried out for other crops in the Galma Pilot Irrigation scheme.
- ii. Similar study need to be carried out in other locations with soil of different properties.

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Appendix A1.

Values of crop water requirement, reference evapotranspiration and root zone of lettuce throughout the growing period.

Stage	Day	Month	ET _O (mm/day)	K _C	ET _C (mm/day)	RZ (mm)
Initial	1	11	5.4	0.5	2.7	150
	2	11	5.1		2.5	
	3	11	5.0		2.5	
	4	11	5.2		2.6	
	5	11	5.3		2.7	
	6	11	5.0		2.5	
	7	11	5.2		2.6	
	8	11	5.1		2.6	
	9	11	5.2		2.6	
	10	11	5.1		2.6	

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	11	11	5.1		2.5	
	12	11	5.0		2.5	
	13	11	5.1		2.6	
	14	11	5.0		2.5	
	15	11	5.1		2.6	
Development	16	11	5.2	0.7	3.7	300
	17	11	5.1		3.6	
	18	11	5.2		3.6	
	19	11	5.1		3.6	
	20	11	5.1		3.6	
	21	11	5.2		3.6	
	22	11	5.2		3.6	
	23	11	5.1		3.6	
	24	11	5.1		3.6	
	25	11	5.1		3.6	
	26	11	5.1		3.6	
	27	11	5.0		3.6	
	28	11	4.9		3.5	
	29	11	5.1		3.4	
	30	11	5.0		3.5	
Mid	1	12	4.9		3.5	
	2	12	4.9		3.4	
	3	12	4.8		3.4	
	4	12	4.8		3.2	
	5	12	4.6		3.2	
	6	12	4.6		3.2	
	7	12	4.6		5.1	
8	12	4.6		5.0		

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	9	12	4.7	1.1	5.1	400
	10	12	4.6		5.1	
	11	12	4.7		5.1	
	12	12	4.6		5.2	
	13	12	4.5		4.9	
	14	12	4.7		5.2	
	15	12	4.6		5.1	
Last	16	12	4.5	10	4.9	400
	17	12	4.5		4.5	
	18	12	4.7		4.7	
	19	12	4.7		4.7	
	20	12	4.4		4.4	
	21	12	4.5		4.5	
	22	12	4.7		4.7	
	23	12	4.6		4.6	
	24	12	4.5		4.5	
	25	12	4.6		4.6	

Appendix A2.

Values of crop water requirement, reference evapotranspiration and root zone of carrot throughout the growing period.

Stage	Day	Month	ET _o (mm/day)	K _c	ET _c (mm/day)	R _z (mm)
Initial	1	11	5.4		3.2	
	2	11	5.1		3.2	

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	3	11	5.0	0.6	3.2	150
	4	11	5.2		3.2	
	5	11	5.3		3.2	
	6	11	5.0		3.2	
	7	11	5.2		3.2	
	8	11	5.1		3.2	
	9	11	5.2		3.2	
	10	11	5.1		3.2	
	11	11	5.1		3.2	
	12	11	5.0		3.2	
	13	11	5.1		3.2	
	14	11	5.0		3.2	
	15	11	5.1		3.2	
	16	11	5.2		3.2	
	17	11	5.1		3.2	
	18	11	5.2		3.2	
	19	11	5.1		3.2	

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	20	11	5.1		3.2	
Development	21	11	5.2	0.75	3.2	300
	22	11	5.2		3.2	
	23	11	5.1		3.2	
	24	11	5.1		3.2	
	25	11	5.1		3.2	
	26	11	5.1		3.2	
	27	11	5.0		3.2	
	28	11	5.9		3.2	
	29	11	5.1		3.2	
	30	11	5.0		3.2	
	1	12	4.9		3.2	
	2	12	4.9		3.2	
	3	12	4.8		3.2	
	4	12	4.8		3.2	
	5	12	4.6		3.2	
	6	12	4.6		3.2	

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	7	12	4.6		3.2	
	8	12	4.6		3.2	
	9	12	4.6		3.2	
	10	12	4.6		3.2	

	11	12	4.7		3.5	
	12	12	4.6		3.5	
	13	12	4.5		3.3	
	14	12	4.7		3.5	
	15	12	4.6		3.5	
Middle	16	12	4.5	1.15	5.2	500
	17	12	4.5		5.1	
	18	12	4.7		5.4	
	19	12	4.7		5.4	
	20	12	4.4		5.1	
	21	12	4.5		5.2	
	22	12	4.6		5.3	
	23	12	4.5		5.2	
	24	12	4.6		5.2	
	25	12	4.6		5.3	
	26	12	4.4		5.3	
	27	12	4.5		5.0	
	28	12	4.6		5.2	
	29	12	4.8		5.3	

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Last	30	12	4.5	0.9	4.2	500
	31	12	4.3		4.3	
	1	1	4.5		4.0	
	2	1	4.4		4.0	
	3	1	4.2		4.0	
	4	1	4.2		3.8	
	5	1	4.3		3.7	
	6	1	4.4		3.9	
	7	1	4.4		4.0	
	8	1	4.4		4.0	

Appendix A3.

Values of crop water requirement, reference evapotranspiration and root zone of spinach throughout the growing period.

Stage	Day	Month	ET _o (mm/day)	K _c	ET _c (mm/day)	R _z (mm)
Initial	1	11	5.4	0.6	3.2	150
	2	11	5.1		3.0	
	3	11	5.0		3.0	
	4	11	5.2		3.1	
	5	11	5.3		3.2	
	6	11	5.0		3.0	
	7	11	5.2		3.1	
	8	11	5.1		3.1	
	9	11	5.2		3.1	
	10	11	5.1		3.1	

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	11	11	5.1		3.0	
	12	11	5.0		3.0	
	13	11	5.1		3.1	
	14	11	5.0		3.0	
	15	11	5.1		3.1	
Development	16	11	5.2	0.7	3.7	300
	17	11	5.1		3.6	
	18	11	5.2		3.6	
	19	11	5.1		3.6	
	20	11	5.1		3.6	
	21	11	5.2		3.6	
	22	11	5.2		3.6	
	23	11	5.1		3.6	
	24	11	5.1		3.6	
	25	11	5.1		3.6	
	26	11	5.1		3.6	
	27	11	5.0		3.5	
	28	11	4.9		3.4	
	29	11	5.1		3.6	
	30	11	5.0		3.5	
Middle	1	12	4.9	1.05	5.2	400
	2	12	4.9		5.2	
	3	12	4.8		5.0	
	4	12	4.8		5.1	
	5	12	4.6		4.9	
	6	12	4.6		4.8	

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	7	12	4.6		4.9	
	8	12	4.6		4.8	

	9	12	4.7		4.9	
	10	12	4.6		4.8	
	11	12	4.7	0.9	4.2	400
	12	12	4.6		4.1	
	13	12	4.5		4.0	
	14	12	4.7		4.3	
	15	12	4.6		4.2	
	16	12	4.5		4.0	
	17	12	4.5		4.0	
	18	12	4.7		4.2	
	19	12	4.7		4.2	
	20	12	4.4		4.2	

Appendix A4.

Values of crop water requirement, reference evapotranspiration and root zone of Onion throughout the growing period.

Stage	Day	Month	ET _o (mm/day)	K _c	ET _c (mm/day)	R _z (mm)
Initial	1	11	5.4		3.2	
	2	11	5.1		3.0	
	3	11	5.0		3.0	
	4	11	5.2		3.1	
	5	11	5.3		3.2	
	6	11	5.0		3.0	

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	7	11	5.2	0.6	3.1	150			
	8	11	5.1		3.1				
	9	11	5.2		3.1				
	10	11	5.1		3.1				
	11	11	5.1		3.0				
	12	11	5.0		3.0				
	13	11	5.1		3.1				
	14	11	5.0		3.0				
	15	11	5.1		3.1				
	16	11	5.2		3.1				
	17	11	5.1		3.1				
	18	11	5.2		3.1				
	19	11	5.1		3.1				
	20	11	5.1		3.1				
	Development	21	11		5.2		0.75	3.9	300
		22	11		5.2			3.9	
		23	11		5.1			3.9	
		24	11		5.1			3.9	
		25	11		5.1			3.8	
		26	11		5.1			3.8	
27		11	5.0	3.8					
28		11	4.9	3.7					
29		11	5.1	3.8					
30		11	5.0	3.7					
1		12	4.9	3.7					
2		12	4.9	3.7					

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	3	12	4.8		3.6	
	4	12	4.8		3.6	
	5	12	4.6		3.5	
	6	12	4.6		3.5	
	7	12	4.6		3.5	
	8	12	4.6		3.4	
	9	12	4.7		3.5	
	10	12	4.6		3.5	

POULTRY LITTER AS A FEED SUPPLEMENT FOR LIVESTOCK? BACKGROUNDS AND VEIWS OF SOMEGHANAIAIAN LIVESTOCK FARMERS

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KEYWORDS: Poultry, litter, ruminants, feed, supplement, Ghana.

ABSTRACT

Cattle, sheep and goats play important role in human development due to good source of protein derived from their meat products. These animals also provide finance, traction power and serve as a hedge against risk in many Sub-Saharan countries including Ghana. The demand for protein from these sources over the years has increased geometrically than the supply as a result of partly low or unavailable feed for these animals. Data on poultry litter was collected from twenty-five livestock farmers who are into sheep, goats and cattle production by simple random selection with structured questionnaire and analysed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 16). It was found out that most of them used cassava husk for feeding their animals and all the 25 (100%) respondents did not know about poultry litter as feed supplement for their animals. Most of them have heard about irradiation as an important tool for decontaminating food products. Logit regression result showed that the number of animals the farmers has affects the decision on the use of irradiated poultry litter as feed. It is recommended that farmers are educated on the benefits of poultry litter as security for them during lean season when there is scarcity of feed.

INTRODUCTION

Protein constitutes an integral part of human development. It can be derived from both plants and animals. When it comes to animals, cattle, sheep and goats cannot be left out. Cattle, sheep and goats, also provide finance, traction power and serve as a hedge against risk in many Sub-Saharan African countries including Ghana. The demand for services and protein from these sources over the years has increased geometrically more than the supply as a result of low or unavailability of feed for these animals. One of the cheapest ways of accessing feed which is high in protein is poultry litter. Poultry litter is a mixture of poultry excreta, spilled feed, and materials used as bedding in poultry operations. Traditionally used as fertilizer but it is now used as livestock feed supplement as a cost-saving measure compared to other feed stock materials. Poultry litter is a low energy feed, similar to average hay in energy value but high in protein and minerals. Though this is known to contain some pathogens, carefully treated litter can be made free of these

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pathogenic microorganisms which may eventually affect these animals and therefore used successfully as feed supplement for ruminants.

Fig 1 A poultry farm showing birds in a deep litter system

Chemical composition of poultry litter though varies it is rich in crude protein which could be as high as 31% and thus its utilization as animal feed ingredient, apart from reducing environmental pollution is assumed to have the advantages of providing a low cost feed ingredient according to [1]

A research conducted by [2] on inclusion of different proportions of poultry litter in the rations of yearling Hararghe Highland goats concluded that poultry litter could replace favourably conventional crude protein sources such as noug seed cake by up to 28% in the ration of goats.

The findings from [3] in their research on poultry litter as a source of protein revealed that goats fed on a commercial goat diet gained faster and had greater feed efficiency when compared to the poultry litter-based diet. However, it was observed that goats were sorting the poultry litter-based diet. Feeding ruminants with poultry litter is not only palatable but increases live weight and carcass quality. Beef cattle

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can consume 3 kg of poultry manure daily, additionally, when fed with 23.5 kg daily of corn silage prepared by adding 30% broiler manure, 1190 g of daily live weight gain can be achieved[4].

The practical potential of ensiling broiler litter with forages or high-moisture grain was demonstrated in several experiments carried out by Virginia scientists [5] and [6] and discovered that broiler litter ensiled with high-moisture (26.3%) maize grain was more palatable, measured by feed intake, and gave better performance than soybean used as protein supplement. Similar results were obtained ensiling broiler litter with forage maize. The palatability, live weight gain and carcass quality of finished cattle fed maize-forage broiler-litter silage were much better than that of cattle fed maize-forage silage plus soybean meal.

It also been found by [7] that partial and total supplementation of forage-maize silage with soybean meal and dried poultry waste was effective, as demonstrated by satisfactory digestibility of nutrients in all groups, either with or without soybean-meal supplementation. An experiments by [8] with a 6-month-old lambs, reported that lambs fed with a mixture of 235 g of poultry litter and 190 g of wheat meal performed as well as those fed with 365 g of wheat meal per day.

Many studies have been carried out on the effect on beef quality when poultry waste is fed to beef cattle for instance ([9] and [10] found slightly lower carcass grades, while [11] reported a significant difference in dressing percentages in favour of steers fed poultry litter (control 49.9%; litter (maize cobs) 53.6%, litter (groundnut hulls) 55.6% and litter (rice hulls) 53.0%). Nevertheless, most experiments have not recorded significant differences in the carcass or its quality according to ([12], [13], [14] and [15])

A paper by [16] on poultry litter as cattle feed that, industrial chicken feed (and therefore chicken faeces) contains rendered tissue from ruminants such as cattle and sheep, among other mammals which is commonly used for poultry feed concluded that feeding poultry litter to cattle increases the risk of the cattle becoming infected with mad cow disease (Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy) which devastated the British beef industry in the early 1990s. It is also explained that poultry litter may contain a range of disease-causing bacteria which ruminants can transmit to humans, such as campylobacter, salmonella and E. coli, as well as veterinary drug residues, heavy toxic metals and even rocks, nails and glass

Fig 2 Poultry litter

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Researches done in other places as shown in the literature reviewed meant that poultry litter inclusion in the feed for livestock helps to increase crude protein to some extent despite the potential side effects it can cause. Therefore identifying the costs as well as the benefits derived in monetary terms in order to quantitatively determine its economic importance as feed supplement for sheep, goats and cattle as well as individual farmers involved in its use is paramount issue to be considered. This is what this piece of research seeks to address.

METHODOLOGY

Materials and Methods

This research employed a structured questionnaire which captures important information on the backgrounds, including age, occupation, marital status, educational levels, number of children their knowledge on feed supplement and the irradiation of poultry litter, the cost of feed in the use of the litter and their general knowledge on irradiated poultry litter as a feed.

Research Setting

The research was supposed to be conducted across large study areas but due to financial constraint it was done in some part of the Greater Accra, Central, Eastern and Volta region of Ghana.

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Sampling Technique, Size and Data Collection Method

Data was collected using simple random techniques. Twenty-five (25) of them who have been persistent in animal rearing over the past years were interviewed. These farmers are into animal production such as sheep and goats (Small ruminants) and cattle (Large ruminants). Data was collected by means of structured questionnaire. The Logit regression model was used to establish relationship between the likelihood of irradiation of poultry litter as feed and the various factors affecting it. The decision of a farmer to use irradiated poultry litter is complex situation and can be modeled as two mutually exclusive processes. The first is the decision to adopt the technology and the second the level of intensity or extent of use of that technology, given that adoption has taken place [17], [18] and [19]. This research emphasises is on the likelihood of adoption of the proposed irradiated poultry litter. Theoretically, the Logit model is expressed as:

$$\mu = B_n \sum_1^n X_n + e \text{ Where: } \mu = \text{Likelihood of Adoption,}$$

Adopter is a farmer who answered yes to the question on whether they will use irradiated poultry litter for their animals, B_n = estimated parameters; X_n = Set of independent variables ([19]; [20] and [21]) e = the error term

Hypothesis statements.

The following hypotheses are stated:

H₀: Factor under consideration has no effect on irradiated poultry litter

H_a: Factor under consideration has an effect on irradiated poultry litter

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 16) and Microsoft excel and presented in tables and graphs, percentages and frequencies. Data was gathered on background information such as Age, Sex, Marital status, Number of children, Educational Background, Religion, Occupation, other economic activity, Poultry litter/ feed status including the type of feed, Amount spent on feed, hours animals graze, the animals they own, the number slaughtered, the amount sold, the knowledge about poultry litter, the source of information, whether they have ever used poultry litter, where it was obtained, what they think about the use of poultry litter, what they know about irradiation, their source of information, cost effectiveness of irradiating poultry litter and their view concerning irradiated poultry litter

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as feed supplement. Also regression analyses was used to ascertain the factors that will contribute to the adoption of irradiated poultry litter with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

Introduction:

This section presents the results from the data collected from the farmers who availed themselves for interaction and interviewed with respect to poultry litter. Their backgrounds and their views on poultry litter have been presented some in charts, others in tables and others in quotations.

District

Twenty-five respondents were interviewed to gather information on what they know about the use of poultry litter as feed supplement 16 (64%) from Ga East District, 4 (26%) Cape Coast Metropolitan Assembly and another 4 (26%) from Akwapim South and 1 (4%) Kpando District See fig. 1 below for detail on the specific areas where data collection was done.

Age, Sex and Marital Status of Respondents

Out of 25 respondents 3 (12%) are 37 years old and another 3 (12%) 43 years old and 2 (8%) 48 years. Others have different ages below 37 years and above 65 years. The mean age of respondents is 44.1 years and Std Dev. 10.6 years. Seventeen (68%) are males and 8 (32%) females with 22(88%) married and 3 (12%) single. Marital status is also known to contribute significantly to the adoption of an innovation because, the couples normally adopt new technology more than an individual (single) person due to the fact that they are more futuristic and think mostly about their children's well being for the years ahead than the unmarried

Number of Children

On the number of children of the respondents, 6 (24%) have 3, 5 (20%) have 4, another 4 (16%) have 5, 2 (8%) have 1 child, 6 or 7 children while 1 (4%) has 2 or 8 and 2 (8%) have no child. The mean number of children is 4 and Std. dev. of 2. It known that couples with more children always want to find means of taking care of them for future reasons. That is to care for them during their old ages. They are therefore likely to adopt an invention which positively affects them and their children.

Education, Religion and Occupation of Respondents

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Nine (36%) respondents out of the 25 completed JHS, 6 (24%) MLSC, 3 (12%) completed SHS and another 3 (12%) Primary school. Two (8%) attended Tertiary institution, 1 (4%) Arabic school and another 1(4%) had a Non-formal education. Nineteen (76%) are Christians and 6 (24%) Muslims. For their occupations, 24 (96%) are into sheep and goat production with 1 (4%) as a cattle rearer. Apart from these 9 (36%) are into some part time trading, 4 (26%) driving, 3 (12%) masons, 2 (8%) are into other forms of farming. Others are into different outfits such as Security jobs, Hairdressing, Medical Lab job, Plumbing works among others. Religion and occupation correlate somehow especially in African and Asian countries, For example moslems normally embrace sheep, goats and cattle rearing, the situation is not different from Christians however moslems abhor pig production. Though this project is focused on the ruminants, it is worth mentioning since some do not involve themselves directly but employ other people for such jobs. See figures below.

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Type of Feed

As to the type of feed they employ in their animal production, 9 (36%) said cassava husk and free range system, 4 (16%) employ free range system, 3 (12%) grass and cassava husk, with another 3 (12%) who use

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cassava husk, grass and plantain husk. Other three (12%) also use free range, cassava husk and grass, while 1 (4%) use cassava husk, grass and plantain husk, and a handful also use cassava husk only. In Ghana most small scale production of sheep and goats use household food remnants and cassava husk and plantain to feed their animals. Some also use grass especially those who practice free range system of animal husbandry. More so, the fact that farmers spend about GH¢10.00 per week on feed and also about 8 hours on free range feed hunting show that introducing a feed which cost less and yet with high protein content will be welcome news to them.

Weekly Expenditure on Feed and Number of Hours Animals Graze (Free Range)

Six (24%) spend GH¢10.00 on feed, 2 (8%) GH¢15.00 another 2 (8%) spend GH¢5.00. Fourteen (46%) did not disclose the amount they spend on feed. For those who employ free range system 4 (16%) use 2 hours in doing it, another 4 (16%) use 6 hours and 3 (12%) use 8, others use similar times

Total Number of Animals, Number Slaughtered and Sold last year

Out of 25 respondents, 3 (12%) have 5, 8 or 13 animals. Two (8%) have 7, 14 or 28 animals while 1 (4%) 3, 9, 10, 16, 20, 23, 37, 54 and 105 animals. Four (16%) slaughtered 1, 2 or 4 animals, 2 (8%) slaughtered 3, 5, and 10 animals, 1 (4%) respondents slaughtered 11 and 3 (12%) did not respond to the question. Four (16%) sold their animal at GH¢ 100.00, another 4 (16%) at GH¢150.00, 3 (12%) GH¢120.00, and another 3 (12%) GH¢130.00 and 2 (8%) sold at GH¢ 60.00 and GH¢ 80.00, 1 (4%) sold his animal for GH¢1000.00 and 6 (24%) did not respond to the question. The fact that some slaughtered some 105 animals means some huge income generation therefore special attention needs to be attached to animal production in these areas

Table 1 Mean, Std. Dev., maximum and minimum values of some variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Weekly feed Expenditure in Cedis	9.30	4.0	2.0	15.0
Number of hours animals graze	4.40	2.50	0.5	8.0
Number of animals	18.0	22.0	3.0	105.0

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Number slaughtered	4.0	3.0	1.0	11.0
Amount sold	112.1	29.0	61.0	150.0
Age in years	44.2	10.6	18.0	65.0
Number of children	4.0	2.0	1.0	8.0

Knowledge on Poultry Litter

All the 25 respondents, representing 100% said they do not know anything about poultry litter as far as feed supplement is concerned. Also all the 25 respondents representing 100% said they will go for cheap conventional feed. It is interesting to know that none of the selected farmers heard about poultry litter as a feed. This is not a surprise at all since a crude survey conducted in an environment of scientists only a handful of them know about the litter as feed for animal production. This means that more education should be done on this and research work like this should be published in the national papers and other journal for the end users to apply in their production areas.

What Do You Think About Poultry Litter?

Out of 25 respondents, 9 (36%) said with education they will feed their animals with poultry litter, 6 (24%) said they will like to feed their animals with poultry litter if it will cost less, 4 (16%) will not feed their animals with poultry litter, 2 (8%) said it is not safe for their animals, Others have different views. Though the respondents' do not know about poultry litter as feed some are aware of radiation as an important tool for decontaminating food products. This means it will not be difficult introducing it to their system.

Surprisingly they are ignorant of the fact that poultry litter can be used as feed for their animals upon careful explanation, they agreed that it is comparatively cheaper than the feed they know suggesting that they may go in for it.

Do You Know Irradiation and Where You Heard It?

Out of 25 respondents, 22 (88%) said they do not know about irradiation and 3 (12%) said they know something about it. Two (8%) respondents said they saw it from the internet, 1 (4%) said he heard it from school and 22 (22%) did not respond also, 20 (80%) out of 25 respondents said they will use irradiation for their poultry litter and 5 (20%) said they will not apply it

Do You Agree that Poultry Litter Is Cheap?

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Though not yet applied 13 (52%) out of 25 respondents anticipated poultry litter as cheap feed compared to others, 10 (40%) said they don't think it is cheap because the time and inconveniences one has to go through in order to access it and 2 (8%) did not respond, 15 (60%) said they will recommend it to others 6 (24%) said they will not while 4 (16%) said they are thinking about it.

General Comment about Poultry Litter

Most of the respondents were hearing it for the first time. Somebody said "it's a surprise to me", another said it was news to him. Others said they don't know anything about it. One for instance said he needs education on it. One respondent also said he needs education because he doesn't see how poultry litter can be used as feed. Yet others were hopeful that it will be good. For instance, 2 respondents said they will give it a try. One respondent said that due to irradiation he knows that it will be safe for the animals but may be expensive. Another also said he is not sure it will provide a pathogen free supplement and enhance animal's health. Again, one answered that it will help during the dry season. However, others think it will be expensive, one showed the willingness to try even though he thinks it will be expensive. Some respondents answered that they will try it. One respondent said that due to irradiation he knows that it will be safe for the animals but may be expensive. Another also said he is sure it will provide a pathogen free feed supplement and enhance animal's health. Again, one answered that it will help during the dry season. Two did not comment on it at all

The logit regression equation result reveals that only the number of animals the farmers have affects the decision on the use of irradiated poultry litter. The a priori expectation of the regression results was not met. Meaning as the number of the animals increases there is a reduction in the level of acceptance of the use of irradiated poultry litter. The implication to this that, as the farmers' number of animals increases the edge to use more irradiated poultry reduces which implies farmers tend to shun the poultry litter with larger number of animal because of the volume of litter they have carry which in their perception is not an easy task to discharge. See below table for regression results.

Table 8 Logit regression model 1

	B	S.E.	Sig.
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Hrs	-0.01	0.666	0.988
An	-0.374	0.22	0.09
Sxd	2.429	3.036	0.424
Msd	-15.93	2.72E+04	1.00
Ag	0.065	0.217	0.764
Dfofr	0.891	4.388	0.839
Dkird	4.226	70.137	0.952
Constant	16.992	2.72E+04	1

Independent Variables: Hrs, An, sxd, msd, Ag, dfofr, dkird Cox & Snell R square = 0.57, Nagelkerker R square = 0.81

Definition of Variables

Dpli = Dummy for poultry litter irradiation, 1 for yes and 0 otherwise as dependent variable

Dkird = Do you know of irradiation dummy, 1 for yes and 0 for no, Hrs = Number of hours animal graze, An = Numbers of animals (sheep, goats and cattle), Sxd = Sex dummy, 1 for male and 0 for female, Msd = Marital status dummy, 1 for married 0 for otherwise, Ag = Age of respondent, Dfofr = Dummy for free range, 1 for preference, 0 for otherwise, Edudm = Education dummy, 1 for JHS and 0, otherwise as independent variables

Some Points for Discussion

The study shows that the average age of the respondents is 44 years with average number of children 4 means that the future for animal rearing is still bright since relatively young people are engaged in the venture. Though age of farmers is observed not as a determining factor when it comes to adoption of farm inputs and technology, it has been proved by studies ([22] that younger farmers are reported to have a higher likelihood of adopting new technologies due to their longer time horizon ([23] and their zeal to acquire and use farm information ([24] and [25] than older farmers. Older farmers may have more skills in assessing innovation but somehow less inclined to adopt new farm practices than younger ones because they are less receptive to change ([26] Also the fact that most of them have at least JHS and higher education levels show that information dissemination to these farmers will be relatively easier since education has been proved to enhance adoption of innovations and inventions which is contrary to the study done by [27] that, low productivity in Ghana has been attributed partly to low skilled labour force,

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illiterates and semi-illiterate farmers who have persisted in the use of traditional farm implements and methods in farming. Schooling facilitates learning which creates the enabling mental atmosphere for the acceptance of new practice ([28]). Higher education enhances farmers understanding to follow and use technology earlier than others who are not ([29])

The logistic regression results show that only the number of animals the farmers have is significant factor that affect the adoption of irradiated poultry litter. Factors such as sex, marital status, number of hours of grazing, age as well as education do not that affect the use of irradiated poultry litter. Since the number of animals one possesses is the only significant factor that affect the use of the technology, farmers with large number of animals are encouraged to use it because it is cheaper.

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POIKILOTHERMS: THEIR EVOLUTIONAL PATTERN

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KEYWORDS: Fish, Evolution

ABSTRACT

The study of fossil fish is known as Paleoiichthyology. Fossil fishes are the prehistoric aquatic creatures those which share their record of existence from primitive era. These were the primitive vertebrates having fossil records. These include the fishes which have now become extinct and have their existence from the Cambrian to Tertian period. The prehistoric fishes are early fish that are known for their existence once upon a time only from fossil records. They are the earliest known vertebrates, and include the first and extinct fish that lived through the Cambrian to the Tertian era. The study of prehistoric fish is called Paleoiichthyology.

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ADVANCES IN SOCIAL SCIENCES

GREEN MARKETING: A TOOL FOR SUSTAINABILITY DEVELOPMENT IN INDUSTRIAL POLLUTION.

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KEYWORDS: Green marketing, Environmental Sustainability, Pollution.

ABSTRACT

Environmental issues influence all human activities while the problems of industrial pollution are enormous. Present-day environmentalist tends to focus on a philosophy of sustainability aiming at combining ecological and economic concerns that is having significant economic concerns and impacts on key organizational processes. Green marketing seeks to satisfy the needs and wants of individual consumers while simultaneously seeking to improve environmental quality of life for the society as a whole. The main objective of this study is to establish the roles of government and private organizations in environmental sustainability in Nigeria. A survey research design was employed for this study. One hundred and twenty (120) individuals were selected randomly from top and senior managers of manufacturing companies in two locations in Ibadan metropolis: Oluyole Industrial Estate and New Ife Road Industrial Area. This comprises 80 respondents from Oluyole and 40 respondents from New Ife Road Industrial areas. The major instrument used was questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed with a four-point Likert rating scale showing the responses and their points as: strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The questionnaire was administered to all the key management personnel of the companies. The results of this study have confirmed to some extent that industrial activities affect the environment. The result confirmed that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution at various business organizations while government gives inadequate attention to industrial pollution. All respondents confirmed that relationship exists between green marketing and industrial pollution in Nigeria.

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Introduction

Nowadays, the concept of “green marketing” is becoming more and more popular. Although, it has not taken its firm root in Nigeria but it began in Europe in the early 1980s when specific products were identified as being harmful to the earth’s atmosphere. Terms like phosphate free, recyclable, refillable, ozone friendly and environmentally friendly are some of the things consumers most often associate with green marketing. While these terms are green marketing claims in general, green marketing is a much broader concept that can be applied to consumer goods, industrial goods and even services. Thus, green marketing incorporates a broad range of activities, including product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising.

The evolution of the green challenge has brought about a change in the relationship between marketing and the physical environment. Traditional marketing attempts to identify and meet latent, current, or future consumer needs by manipulating the marketing mix – product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence and procedure/process. These objectives have been historically been identified with efforts to increase consumption of material goods and services, practices not particularly compatible with the notion of a sustainable society.

Industrial pollution is pollution which is directly linked with industry, in contrast to other pollution sources. This form of pollution is one of the leading causes of pollution worldwide, for example, in Nigeria, the industrial pollution control law termed “National Effluent Limitation Regulation” and “Pollution Abatement and Facilities Generating Wastes Regulation” was enacted in August 1991 and came into operation in 1995.

Environmentalists have criticized various aspects of the consumption culture, particularly its wasteful and pollutive production and disposal processes. Green marketing can accommodate these concerns in a way that remains attractive to consumers by addressing the environmental and consumer advantages inherent in the product. Companies are becoming more environmentally responsible as part of an overall commitment to Total Quality Management or sustainable development. Sustainable development involves meeting the needs of the present consumers without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

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The discovery of a major toxic waste dump at Koko, a small port town in the Bendel State in 1987 now in Delta State led to the establishment of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) in 1998. In 1992, the Agency's mandate was expanded by law to cover conservation of natural resources and biological diversity. These represented the efforts made by successive administrations to ameliorate environmental problems in the country. The Obasanjo administration instituted on 29 May, 1999 created for the first time in the history of the country, a Ministry of Environment in June 1999. Naturally, FEPA was absorbed and its functions taken over by the new Ministry. The primary mandate of the Ministry is to protect and improve water, air, land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria as mandated by section 20 of the National Constitution. The Ministry is also to ensure the sustainable utilization of the environment and its resources by evolving tools for poverty alleviation, ensuring food security, foreign policy and international development and good governance.

Although, global issues such as climatic change and ozone depletion dominate the headlines, the green agenda contains a vast array of issues, each of which creates marketing opportunities and threats for different businesses. So, why concern over the thinning ozone layer has posed a major threat to some manufacturers, the ensuing warnings about the increased risk of skin cancer has provided a grim opportunity for the manufacturers of skin-care products. The most immediate issues for marketers are typically internal ones relating to the product and the company itself, and externally to customers. Beyond this, the analysis of the environment broadens out externally through different, but interwoven, levels of environment. Each level has important implications for marketing but dealing with each level are more difficult strategic challenge due to increasing breadth and complexity and their proximity to the company itself.

The pursuit of sustainability is the underlying principle of green marketing, and a company can justifiably claim green credentials if it is demonstrably and consistently moving towards sustainability. Achieving sustainability is not a pre-requisite for a valid claim to be green, just as one hundred percent customer satisfaction is not a pre-requisite to claim a marketing orientation.

The objective of this paper is to identify forms of industrial pollution and identify the roles of government agencies and private organizations in environmental sustainability in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

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Prothero (1990) define green marketing as “the holistic management process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying the needs of customers and society, in a profitable and sustainable way.” Peattie and Charter (2000) in their one-chapter contribution opined that “green marketing’s key concepts of sustainability and holism are both apparently simple, but can be extremely difficult to translate into action. White (2010) recalls the definition offered by the American Marketing Association (AMA) in three ways: retail, social and environments definitions. The retail definition defines green marketing as the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. The social marketing definition on the other hand is the development and marketing of products designed to minimize negative effects on the physical environment to improve its quality. The environments definition defines green marketing as the efforts by organizations to produce, promote, package and reclaim products in a manner that is sensitive or responsive to ecological concerns.

Ward (2011) defines green marketing as “the process of selling products and or services based on their environmental benefits.” Kotler (2001) sees green marketing and industrial pollution control as the engine that regulates the marketing activities with the perception of consumer in relationship to need satisfaction. Mintu and Lozada (1995) define green marketing as “the application of marketing tools to facilitate exchanges that satisfy original and individual goals in such a way that the preservation, protection and conservation of the physical environmental is upheld.” Coddington (1993) defines green marketing as “marketing activities that recognize environmental stewardship as a business development responsibility and business growth responsibility.”

All the definitions enlarge the traditional objective of business to maximize profits by including some notion of maintaining integrity of the natural environment.

What constitutes a green product?

What constitutes a green product is relatively difficult to answer and not a simple one. Would it be the one that has achieved sustainability or a product that is better than its competitors? Or is it the one that is less harmful or the one produced by a company with an accredited environmental management system? There has not been a widespread agreement on what exactly makes a product green. Some general guidelines include that a green product:

- Does not present a health hazard to people or animals;
- Is relatively efficient in its use of resources during manufacture, use and disposal;

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- Does not incorporate materials derived from endangered species or threatened environments;
- Does not contribute to excessive waste in its use or packaging; and
- Does not rely on unnecessary use of or cruelty to animals.

Such polarized distinctions are inappropriate for a performance continuum, and the reality of eco-performance as reflected in Charter's (1992) concept of greener rather than green marketing. For the marketing strategist, it is vital to understand the potential impact of the green agenda on the business and its customers and also the strength and weaknesses of the company's economic performance. The concept of green marketing was developed in 1980 and early 1990s to reinforce the existing societal marketing concept. The concept is aimed at addressing the roles expected of a marketing organization to carry out its marketing activity that ensure the safety of the consumer. The difference between green marketing concept and societal marketing concept lie in:

- An emphasis on the physical sustainability of the marketing process as well as its social acceptability.
- A more holistic and interdependent view of the relationship between the economy, society and the environment.
- A treatment of the environment as something with intrinsic value over and above its usefulness to society.
- A focus on global concerns, rather than those of particular societies.

Literature Review

Industrial pollution is a pollution which can be directly linked with the industry. Industrial pollution is a serious problem for the entire planet especially in nations which are rapidly becoming industrializing like China, Japan and other developing countries like Nigeria.

Kotler (2001) sees green marketing and industrial pollution control as the engine that regulates the marketing activities with the perception consumer has in relationship to need satisfaction. He opines that the derived utility or satisfaction from products means less if the environment is not safe from pollution and the marketing of products that is not environmentally safe.

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According to the National Implementation of Agenda 21 on the Review of Progress made since the United Nations Conferences on Environmental and Development, 1992, “Nigeria for instance has about 5,000 registered industrial facilities and some 10,000 small scale industries operating illegally within residential premises. In places like Kano, Kaduna, Ibadan and Lagos, coloured, hot and heavy metal-laden effluents especially from the textile, brewery and paints industries are discharged directly into open drains and water chemicals, constituting direct dangers to water users. Stack fumes have industries emit nauseating gases and particulars with grave respiratory and cardiac ailment consequences”.

Municipal solid waste heaps dot several parts of our major cities blocking motor roads, alleys and pavements. These are particularly serious in Lagos, Ibadan, Enugu, Kaduna, Aba, Port Harcourt and Owerri and Warri. These unsightly dump sites are characterized by:

- Various non bio-degradable household petrochemical products such as polythene bags, plastic containers Styrofoam packages and tyres,
- Crankcase oils discharged by mechanical workshops, industries power stations and commercial houses are discharged carelessly into drains and surface waters, thereby contaminating surface and underground waters,
- The siting of public buildings and residential quarters on flood-prone areas as well as unsettled and improperly reclaimed dump sites.

According to UNDP (2001), only fifty seven percent of Nigerians have access to improved water sources, which includes household connections, public standpipes, and boreholes with hand pumps, protected dug wells, protected springs and rainwater collection. According to UNEP (1993: 17-18), pollutants arise from the dirt and grease that is removed from raw natural fibres, as well as from process chemicals and dyestuffs that are lost during operations.

There are various forms of industrial pollution, but the most common ones are:

- Air Pollution
- Water Pollution
- Soil (Chemical) Pollution.
- Other Common Effects

Air Pollution

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Air pollution is defined “as that form of industrial pollution activity that is depleted into the air that can result into air pollutant which is harmful to human existence.” Industrial pollution is one of the major causes of air pollution. The emissions from various industries contain large amounts of gases such as carbon dioxide, sulphur and nitrogen, among others. These gases, when present in elevated levels in the atmosphere, often result in various environmental and health hazards such as acid rain, and various skin disorders in individuals. It is the introduction of particle matters, chemical into the atmosphere through the activity of the industries which are dangerous to human health. (<http://www.ehow.com/about/5155119/effect-industrial-pollution.html>)

Water Pollution

Pollution emitted from the industries is also one of the major factors contributing towards water pollution. Dumping of various industrial waste products into water sources, and improper contamination of industrial wastes, often result in polluting the water. Such water pollution disturbs the balance of the ecosystem inside, resulting in the death of various animal and plant species present in the water.

Soil Pollution

Soil pollution is defined as a phenomenon in which the soil loses its structure and fertility due to various natural and artificial reasons. Dumping of industrial wastes is one of the prime factors contributing towards soil pollution. Industrial wastes contain large amounts of various chemicals which get accumulated on the top layer of the soil, resulting in loss of fertility of the soil. Such loss of fertility ultimately results in changes in the ecological balances of the environment due to reduction in plant growth.

Other Common Effects

Other form of industrial pollution includes damaging of buildings and structures, increasing the risk of various occupational hazards such as asbestosis, pneumoconiosis among others.

Justification of the Study

This paper will give wider knowledge of how to understand and design products that are presumed to be environmentally safe and give guidelines to manufacturers on green products.

Methodology

A survey research design was employed for this study. One hundred and twenty (120) individuals were selected randomly from top and senior managers of manufacturing companies in two locations in Ibadan metropolis: Oluyole Industrial Estate and New Ife Road Industrial Area. This comprises 80 respondents

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from Oluyole and 40 respondents from New Ife Road Industrial areas. The major instrument used was questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed with a four-point Likert rating scale showing the responses and their points as: strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The questionnaire was administered to all the key management personnel of the companies.

Table 1: Result of One-way ANOVA for Questions 1 to 7.

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Q1 Between Groups	11.267	1	11.267	21.237	.000
Within Groups	62.600	118	.531		
Total	73.867	119			
Q2 Between Groups	.417	1	.417	3.026	.085
Within Groups	16.250	118	.138		
Total	16.667	119			
Q3 Between Groups	.938	1	.938	9.077	.003
Within Groups	12.188	118	.103		
Total	13.125	119			
Q4 Between Groups	.417	1	.417	3.026	.085
Within Groups	16.250	118	.138		
Total	16.667	119			
Q5 Between Groups	.417	1	.417	.715	.399
Within Groups	68.750	118	.583		
Total	69.167	119			
Q6 Between Groups	1.667	1	1.667	26.222	.000
Within Groups	7.500	118	.064		
Total	9.167	119			
Q7 Between Groups	1.350	1	1.350	16.857	.000

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Within Groups	9.450	118	.080		
Total	10.800	119			

Source: Author's Computation

Table 1 was obtained through the one way ANOVA with the means as (ms= 11.267; 0.417; 0.938; 0.417; 1.667 and 1.350) for the treatment comparison between groups and within the groups. The results supported the findings in table 2 that indicated significant differences in the respondent's opinion in the seven questions. Questions 1, 3, 6, and 7 have significant level of $P < 0.05$. These show that there are significant differences in the respondent's opinion from Oluyole Industrial Estate and New Ife Road Industrial Area. Questions 2, 4, and 5 have significant differences of $P > 0.05$ as indicated in the table which shows that they were not significant.

Table 2: Frequencies of Field Responses

Table 2.1: Q1 – Industrial activities of my organization affects the environment.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	6	4.0	5.0	5.0
Disagree	4	2.7	3.3	8.3
Agree	30	20.0	25.0	33.3
Strongly Agree	80	53.3	66.7	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	
Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

From the table, it shows that 8.3% disagreed while 91.7% agreed that the activities of their organizations affect the environment.

Table 2.2: Q2 – Industrial pollution has impact on organization.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	20	13.3	16.7	33.3
Strongly Agree	100	66.7	66.7	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	

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Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The table above shows that all the respondents agreed that industrial pollution has impact on organization. This is 100%.

Table 2.3: Q3 – Adequate attention is given to industrial pollution on monthly basis.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	15	10.0	12.5	12.5
Strongly Agree	105	70.0	87.5	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	
Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The table shows that all respondents agreed that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution on monthly basis. This is 100%.

Table 2.4: Q4 - Adequate attention is given to industrial pollution in my organization.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	20	13.3	16.7	16.7
Strongly Agree	100	66.7	83.3	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	
Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The table shows that all the respondents agreed that they give adequate attention to industrial pollution in their organizations. This is 100%.

Table 2.5: Q5 – Adequate attention is given to industrial pollution by the government.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	20	13.3	16.7	16.7

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Agree	10	6.7	8.3	25.0
Strongly Agree	90	60.0	75.0	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	
Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

Table 2.5 shows that 25% respondents strongly disagreed that government give adequate attention to pollution while 75% respondents strongly agreed that government give adequate attention to pollution.

Table 2.6: Q6 – My organization takes measure to control industrial pollution.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	10	6.7	8.3	8.3
Strongly Agree	110	73.3	91.7	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	
Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

Table 2.6 shows that all respondents agreed that their organization take necessary measures to control industrial pollution. This is 100%.

Table 2.7: Q7 – There is relationship between green marketing and industrial problem.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	12	8.0	10.0	10.0
Strongly Agree	108	72.0	90.0	100.0
Total	120	80.0	100.0	
Missing System	30	20.0		
Total	150	100.0		

Source: Author's field survey 2010

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Table 2.7 shows that all the respondents agreed that there is a relationship between green marketing and industrial pollution. This is 100%.

Table 3: Responses through location

Table 3.1: Q1 -Industrial activities of my organization affects the environment.

			LOCATION		
			OLUYOLE	NEW IFE ROAD	TOTAL
Q1	STRONGLY DISAGREE	Count	0	6	6
		% within Q1	.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	DISAGREE	Count	0	4	4
		% within Q1	.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	AGREE	Count	20	10	30
		% within Q1	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%
	STRONGLY AGREE	Count	60	20	80
			75.0%	25.0%	100.0%
	Total	Count	80	40	120
		% within Q1	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

Table 3.1 shows that only ten respondents from New Ife Road disagreed that their industrial activities affect the environment while none respondent from Oluyole disagree. All the respondents from Oluyole Industrial area agreed that their industrial activities affect the environment while 30 respondents from New Ife Road agreed to the question. There was a significant difference in respondents from the two locations.

Table 3.2: Q2 -Industrial pollution has impact on organization.

			LOCATION		
			OLUYOLE	NEW IFE ROAD	TOTAL
Q2	AGREE	Count	10	10	20
		% within	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
	STRONGLY AGREE	Count	70	30	100

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	% within Q2	70.0%	30.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	80	40	120
	% within Q2	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

Table 3.2 shows that all (100%) the respondents in the two locations agreed that industrial pollution have impact in organization. There were no significant differences in the two locations.

Table 3.3: Q3 – Adequate attention is given to industrial pollution on monthly basis.

		LOCATION			
		OLUYOLE	NEW IFE ROAD	TOTAL	
Q3	AGREE	Count	5	10	15
		% within Q3	33.3%	66.7%	100.0%
	STRONGLY AGREE	Count	75	30	105
		% within Q3	71.4%	28.6%	100.0%
Total		Count	80	40	120
		% within Q3	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The table shows that all the respondents in the two locations agreed that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution on monthly basis. This is 100%. There were no significant differences in the two locations.

Table 3.4: Q4 – Adequate attention is given to industrial pollution in my organization.

		LOCATION		
		OLUYOLE	NEW IFE ROAD	TOTAL
AGREE	Count			
	% within Q4			
STRONGLY AGREE	Count	10	10	20
	% within Q4	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	70	30	100
	% within Q4	70.0%	30.0%	100.0%

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	80	40	120
	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The above table shows that all the respondents in the two locations agreed that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution their organizations. This is 100%. There were no significant differences in the two locations.

Table 3.5: Q5 – Adequate attention is given to industrial pollution by the government.

			LOCATION		
			OLUYOLE	NEW IFE ROAD	TOTAL
Q5	DISAGREE	Count % within	10 50.0%	10 50.0%	20 100.0%
	AGREE	Count % within Q5	10 100.0%	0 .0%	10 100.0%
	Strongly Agree	Count % within	60 66.7%	30 33.3%	90 100.0%
	Total	Count % within	80 66.7%	40 33.3%	120 100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The table above shows that 10 respondents each from the two locations disagreed that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution by the government which is 16.7%. The respondents in the two locations strongly agreed that government give adequate attention to industrial pollution which is 83.3%. There were no significant differences in the two locations.

Table 3.6: Q6 – My organization takes measure to control industrial pollution.

			LOCATION		
			OLUYOLE	NEW IFE	TOTAL

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			ROAD		
Q6	AGREE	Count	0	10	10
		% within Q6	.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	STRONGLY AGREE	Count	80	30	110
		% within Q6	72.7%	27.3%	100.0%
Total		Count	80	40	120
		% within Q6	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The above table shows that all the respondents strongly agreed that their organizations take adequate measure to control industrial pollution. There were no significant differences in the two locations.

Table 3.7: Q7 – There is relationship between green marketing and industrial pollution.

			LOCATION		
			OLUYOLE	NEW IFE ROAD	TOTAL
Q7	AGREE	Count	2	10	12
		% within Q7	16.7%	83.3%	100.0%
	STRONGLY AGREE	Count	78	30	108
		% within Q7	72.2%	27.8%	100.0%
Total		Count	80	40	120
		% within Q7	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%

Source: Author's field survey 2010

The table above shows that all the respondents strongly agreed that there is strong relationship between green marketing and industrial pollution. There were no significant differences in the two locations.

Discussion of Findings

The main objective of this study is to establish the roles of government and private organizations in environmental sustainability in Nigeria. The results of this study have confirmed to some extent that industrial activities affect the environment. The result also confirmed that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution at various business organizations. It was also confirmed that government give

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inadequate attention to industrial pollution while all respondents confirmed that relationship exists between green marketing and industrial pollution in Nigeria.

Conclusions and Recommendation

Green marketing is based on the premise that businesses have a responsibility to satisfy human needs and desires while preserving the integrity of the natural environment (www.insead.edu/Management-courses). The results of this study revealed that industrial activities affect the environment and that adequate attention is given to industrial pollution by industrial organizations. It is also revealed that governments at the three tier level give inadequate attention to industrial pollution. It is also concluded that there is relationship between green marketing and industrial pollution in Nigeria.

The following recommendations are made:

- There is the need by government at all levels to ensure environmentally sound waste management including elimination of litter on Nigerian streets and provide basic sanitation.
- There is the need to minimize waste generated at all levels to ensure clean and environmentally sound approach which will reduce the volume of wastes destined for disposal particularly in the face of increasing population and the concomitant value attached to land.
- There is the need by the government to control chemical hazards through pollution prevention, emission inventories, product labeling for safe handling of consumers.
- Environmental audits of existing industries should be carried out by government to improve hazardous waste management.
- Industries should give proper consideration to pollution that may be caused during manufacturing or as post-consumer wastes.
- There should be consumer education about environmental implication of different materials and process of manufacturing companies.
- Government should encourage industries to produce bio-degradable packaging materials.
- Government should devote reasonable amount of the budget to addressing municipal solid waste management and ensure safe and healthy environment.
- Government should provide sound collection, handling, transportation and disposal of environmental waste.

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ACHIEVEMENTS AND SUSTENANCE OF POVERTY ERADICATION IN BORNO STATE, NIGERIA.

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KEYWORDS: Achievements, Sustenance, Poverty, Eradication.

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the activities, operations and achievements of Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programmes under the present administration of Governor Kashim Shettima. Several relevant authorities concerned were consulted to get the required information. Those consulted include: staff of Borno State Ministry of Poverty Alleviation, Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, programme vital dossier on the activities of youth job creation and empowerment. Other sources contacted on the programme were the Borno Radio Television (BRTV) and Nigeria Television Authority, Maiduguri (NTA) news propaganda on the activities and achievements of the Borno State Poverty Alleviation Schemes as well as trainees (employed youths under the programme). The study, however, incorporated several related literature and empirical studies to complement the work. The finding of the study strongly endorsed the paper hypothesis and claims effectiveness of the Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme towards job creation and youth empowerment as undisputable. Therefore, the programme is a success and serves as a role model to other sister states to emulate. The researcher however, made some suggestions of how to maintain the existing tempo of success and achievements for year to come.

Introduction

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Reflections on decades of practically widespread poverty amongst youth, according to the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), United Nation Development Programme (UNDP) and other related Non Governmental Organizations report on the status of poverty in Nigeria is highly traumatizing and alarming. The situation further aggravated recently to become one of the major challenges facing Nigeria is its continuing vigorous population growth and poor economic prospects which prevent it from meeting the increased needs of its people. However, the study observes that structural weakness and extremely limited diversification of the economies prevent job creation in sufficient number to absorb the growing annual young entrants into the labour market. Thus, the same identified Non Governmental Organization reports that about 70% of Nigerians wallow in absolute poverty (Tafida, 2012). Nigeria was also ranked 139 out of the 157 countries on the human poverty index out of the 108 developing countries, Nigeria was also ranked 80th. (UNDP, 2007). Similarly, NEEDS (2005) reported that out of 6 of every 10 Nigerians live on less than one dollar a day.

This alarming poverty profile in Nigeria contradicts the abundant natural resources which the country has been endowed with. In view of that, different programmes have been put in place in Nigeria by different administrations to reduce poverty to the barest minimum. Some of these programmes were Directorate for Foods, Roads and Rural Infrastructural (DEFRI), 1986), National Directorate for Employment (NDE), 1986), Better Life For Rural Women Programme (BLP), 1987), People's Bank of Nigeria (PBN), 1989), Community Banks (CB), 1990), Family Support Programme (FSP), 1994), Family Economic Advancement (FEAP), 1997), Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), 1999), Upward Review of Salary (URS), 1998-1999), Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP), 1999-2000), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), 2001) and currently Women and Youth Empowerment Scheme (W-YES) in addition to the establishment of these programmes at the Federal, States and Local Governments levels, the International Communities have also contributed immensely in improving services among others. Yet, all programmes and policies introduced at different times by successive governments in partner with various non governmental organizations/bodies where temporally appreciated in changing the conditions of the absolute poor and required more efforts to salvage the Nigerian youths future from going down. (Tafida, 2011; Obadan, 1996; Aliu, 2001) Some of the programmes seemed to have only benefited those who were already economically buoyant and political associates of those in power.

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It was observed that the twin phenomena of rapid population growth and manifestation of poverty characterized by joblessness amongst youth in Nigeria are the key problems the government of various level have over the years battling to solve but, the situation as at the time of compiling this study remain the same that requires urgent attention so as to avoid what is called “revolution” to manifest in Nigeria as predicted and uttered by the former President Olusegun Obasanjo during west African Regional Conference on Youth Unemployment and Poverty held in Dakar, Senegal. Obasanjo, has expressed fears that Nigeria will witness a revolution soon unless government takes urgent steps to check growing Youth Unemployment and Poverty (cited in Daily Trust, Monday, 12th November, 2012).

Poverty has been a serious challenge to government and continuing debates on the issue has not resolved the confusion surrounding the concept. Therefore, the concept poverty has been understood and used differently by different scholars, governments and organizations. Though, this study adopted the United Nations (UN) Copenhagen Submit definition of Poverty to comprehend the paper. United Nations described poverty as “..... a condition characterized by severe deprivation of basic human needs, including food, safe drinking water, sanitary facilities, health, shelter, education and information” (*cited in think quest team, 2006, 00282*).

In fulfillment of his electioneering campaign promises to lead by examples to fight poverty and to sustain socio-economic and political development and change the fortunes of Borno State Youth to reflect modern day standard of living, the Borno State Governor Shettima despite the meager resources earned from Federal revenue allocation coupled with global economic recession occasioned by precarious challenges, the state government pensively declared state of emergency to all sectors of human endeavour to alleviate sufferings of all Borno State citizens irrespective of demographic affiliation but much emphasis is being given to the area of jobless youth in order to make them self-reliant in future. The Borno State Government adopted a tigerish reform approach which covers area such as jobs creation and poverty eradication; provision of decent and affordable housing for all citizens; standardizing quality of education and agriculture; improving health care delivery services and provision of clean drinking water and drilling of boreholes resuscitation of the state moribund firms; electrification of rural areas so as to curtain the trend of rural-urban drift among youths to mention but a few are the fundamental priority sector of this administration currently receiving attention day and night to achieve success (Survey, 2012).

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The desire to create jobs for the teeming youth and encourage them to engage in entrepreneurship development for sustainable livelihood and self-reliance, Governor Shettima in his effort to improve the living conditions of his people, has initiated multifarious policies and programmes of skill acquisitions and youth empowerment to fight poverty through intensive trainings of thousands of unemployed youth in various capacity of skills development. Sources from Borno State Ministry of Poverty Alleviation and Agriculture as well as State owned medium BRTVNews, English bulletin of September, 2012 confirmed that the youth empowerment programme on interlock production has officially began production activities with approximately 2000 youth spread across 15 wards of the Maiduguri Metropolis and environs and similar activities will soon be established in other local government areas of the state.

According to the officials of the ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, Governor Shettima has paid a Fadama Phase III Counter part fund in partner with the World Bank aimed at promoting and improving agricultural activities to enhance food security and generate jobs for the unemployed youth, thereby, minimize poverty amongst the youth and make them self-reliant in the near future to complement the Federal Government's Seven Point Agenda and meet the Millennium Development Goal (MDG's) and Vision – 2015 target. The Fadama project, if properly implemented can put smiles on the faces of many young farmers in the state (Survey, 2012). In order to ensure judicial implementation of the Fadama III programme. The commissioner of Agriculture and Natural Resources had recently constituted a technical committee to ensure proper implementation of the scheme to boost agricultural activities in the state (BRTV News, English bulletin of 31st January, 2013). Borno State Governor Kashim Shettima in his effort to eradicate poverty and minimize joblessness in the state, the governor had recently signed a tripartite treaty of understanding with Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and A.I Development Services Limited for establishment of north-east entrepreneurship development in Maiduguri, Borno State to give loans and credits for small scale farmers and non farmers, while creating jobs opportunity for teeming jobless youths. The reports revealed that both management of CBN and A.I. Development Services Limited has assured Governor Kashim Shettima for creating approximately 5,000 job opportunities to ease the problems of unemployed youths and poverty in Borno State (BRTV news, Kanuri bulletin of 18th Jan, 2013; NTA News, Hawarra bulletin of 16th, Feb, 2013).

As part of Borno State Government desire to promote the education sector, the commissioner and executive chairman of Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Borno State, Professor, Tijjani Abba Ali on 6th

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of January, 2013 gave audience or briefed newsmen in Maiduguri revealed that Borno State Government has paid its counterpart funds from 2007 to 2012 for effective implementation of UBE programme in the state. The chairman authoritatively disclosed that about one thousand, two hundred nursery, primary and junior secondary schools were renovated across the state. He further confirmed to the media that all the classrooms were equipped with furniture and teaching aids to create conducive and enabling environment for imparting sound knowledge to the young ones. (BRTV news, English bulletin of 6th January, 2013; UBE office, Borno State Branch, January, 2013) Equally, an authoritative source from Borno State Ministry of Education and staff of tertiary institutions in Borno state has revealed that Governor Kashim Shettima has settled all tertiary institutions long outstanding salary demands. The academic staff union Polytechnics (ASUP), Ramat Polytechnic Maiduguri Chapter, Chairman confirmed the Government's claims that all staff of tertiary institutions in Borno State are beneficiaries of CONTISS II since March, 2012. (Survey, 2012; 2013). Similarly a source from Borno State Ministry of Education vindicated that Governor Kashim Shettima's administration has renovated an approximately 450, primary and secondary schools across the state. (NTA Maiduguri, *Promotional Jingles* reports of December, 2013). In the same vein, Borno State Government under the leadership of Governor Kashim Shettima has approved the establishment of Borno State University to ease the difficulty being experienced by indigene of Borno State in getting admission into Universities and to accommodate many qualified indigene lecturers to nurture the State University for smooth take off. In addition, the Governor also promised that the Borno State University will assume full academic activities before the end of this year, 2013. (BRTV News, English bulletin of 27th and 30 December, 2012) The Borno State Government as part of its efforts to standardize the education sector and motivate both students and staff, recently increased the boarding secondary schools feeding system from monthly ₦20, 000,000, to ₦100, 000,000 so as to improve the quality and quantity of students' food to benefit from the dividends of democracy under the administration of Kashim Shettima (Borno State Ministry of Education, 2013; BRTV News, English bulletin of 15th December, 2012). Similarly, a source from Borno State Ministry of Education revealed that separate 25 housing estates was approved to be built for secondary and primary schools staff (*Borno State Ministry of Education, 2013; Survey, 2013*). In a related development, the Borno State Government under the leadership of Governor Kashim Shettima in his desire to provide decent and affordable houses for all citizens of Borno State, he granted an approval for 2,500 housing estate to minimize the problems of housing being experienced by

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people of Borno State (Borno State Ministry of Housing and Rural electrification, 2013; BRTV News, English bulletin of January, 20th, 2013; Survey, 2013) In addition to these, according to BRTV news, English bulletin, of 26 Jan, 2013, reported that Governor Kashim Shettima has also approved the building of 2 storey of 30 blocks of 6 units and 3 bedroom flat, tagged “Legacy Garden Housing Estate” with a view to enrich the cultural heritage and structural face of Borno State. The State Government has since inaugurated a committee for projects led by Borno State Government House Chief of Staff and Borno State Deputy Governor for the latter respectively. The Members of the Committee charged with the responsibility of supervising the projects and ensure speedy completion without delay. (BRTV News, English bulletin of 14th January, 2013).

In response to address the problems of youth unemployment, the Borno State Government under the leadership of Governor Kashim Shettima has put several plans on ground in all sectors of human endeavour to fight poverty as noted in 2013 budget breakdown. He added that emphasis would be given to entrepreneurship development to makes the youth self-reliant to minimize poverty, hunger and diseases that engulfed the entire society. (BRTV news, English bulletin of 18th January, 2013) This manifests the degree of commitment of the present administration of Governor Kashim Shettima’s efforts to fight poverty, develop the state and make youth self-reliant and improve standard of living of the people..

It is against this backdrop that this study intends to examine the activities, operations and achievements of Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme.

Objectives

- i. To thoroughly examine the practical activities and achievements of Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme and policies towards uplifting the living standards of youth and make them self-reliant.
- ii. To suggest ways to improve the performance of Poverty Eradication programme in Borno State.

Hypothesis

That Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programmes under the administration of Governor Shettima is like a long awaited messiah for the unemployed youth is indisputable.

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Methodology

Plethora of empirical studies on poverty alleviation and related areas were thoroughly examined and found relevant, the researcher also made a series of consultations with the staff of the Ministry of Poverty Alleviation Programme and Ministry of Agriculture as well as recently employed youth under the scheme are the subjects extensively discussed. Several documents in relation to the programme activities examined and used in this paper to complement the work. This paper serves as a public mirror to understand the facts behind the operations; progress and achievements of the Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme. The study however, declined the use of statistical data and analysis throughout the work, due to the methodology the study adopted and to avoid the work being voluminous.

Discussion

The hypothesis advanced in this paper were upheld by the responses of the staff of the Ministry concerned, programme documents searched and comments of unemployed youth under the scheme as well as the BRTV and the NTA News propaganda on the activities and achievements of the Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme. It has clearly shown that Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme and policies under the administration of Governor Shettima is a divine blessing for BornoState citizens.

This is evident from the programme schedules, strategies and plans of the activities glanced was convincing to agree that the programme meant for job generation and youth empowerment. In support of the paper hypothesis, Sekuk (2004) in Anyanwu (2010) reveals that career youth development through skills acquisition training which helps to enhance youth to aspire to enter occupations based on their interests, abilities, talents, aptitudes, etc. Evidence on the effectiveness of the programme was cited in the work of Alimi (2012:2) that agriculture and other related facilities and equipment worth millions of Naira was procured by Borno State Government with a view to make farming inputs sufficient to train youth in various capacities and improve agricultural sector and ensure food security.

He further reported that over 5,000 youth officially are said to have registered and one third of them are already engaged in the programme of training. Another from the youth employed under the scheme favourably support the study hypothesis that they have finished their fish pond 6 months period of management training skills. According to them, one third of them has been permanently absorbed in the Mainstream of the Civil Service work and others were rewarded with some amount of not less than N200,000. Other separate group of youth recently employed under the scheme to manufacture interlock

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brick which was officiated on 3rd November, 2012 revealed that they had already benefited a one month allowance of N10, 000 each (Survey, 2012). This implies that the responses of the youth graduated and currently on apprenticeship under the scheme was a clear backing of the entire programme activities, policies and operation. Therefore, Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme under the administration of Governor Kashim Shettima is a blessing to Borno State youth. The need for youth entrepreneur programme to achieve objectives, Chigunta, (2002) strongly suggests that the design of the programmes should recognize the capabilities of the different youth groups and how to impact on their ability to set up, run, manage and expand a business.

Sekuk, (2009) added that for the youth programmes to be successful, the youth should be enlightened and be given necessary guidance in making appropriate choices. She said this will help them avoid waste of time, money and other problems that could lead them to undesired experience. Therefore, career education becomes necessary so that frustrations experienced by youth and their attending wrong decisions can be curbed. (Anyanwu, 2010), Chigunda (op.cit) in reaction to the poor achievements of most of the youth poverty eradicating programmes, he posits that there are no proper policy programme linkages; youth policies are not properly integrated with key macro economic and sectoral policies; there is a document welfarist perception of youth; and the policies lack effective implementation mechanism.

Anyanwu, (2010) reveals on the continued collapse of Federal Government skills acquisition programmes without positive impact on the youth give rise to organized poverty, marginalization and unemployment that influenced them to roam about the streets in search of vanity. This is why Akinola (2001) stated that these youth without jobs engage in all types of social vices at the expense of general public. In support of Akinola (2001), Thom and Thom (2008) confirmed that as soon as there is a little problem within the social structure, these youth turn themselves into hooligans as a result of idleness arising from unemployment. For it is said, an idle mind is the devil's workshop. Addendum to the opinions of Anyanwu (2010), Akinola (2001) and Thom and Thom (2008), White and Keyon (2000) stated that with the exception of just a few countries and programmes, continued assistance for business development expansion after a year or so of operation remain almost absent.

The researcher, however, attributed most of the collapse and failure of youths related programmes in Nigeria to lack of patriotism, poor funding, political dichotomy (political party differences) poor programme policy, poor supervision, coordination, evaluation and insincerity on the part of those who

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manage the affairs of the youth programme as well as lack of financial management culture from the programme beneficiaries (youth) (Survey, 2012). Similarly, NEEDS (2005) observed that discrimination of people in terms of opportunity and prosperity, poor resource management and lack of focus in delivering public services, corruption in public services, and poor working environment are some of the factors serve as hindrance for economic development in Nigeria (*Cited in National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy 2005; P. 16*).

On the other hand, the need for effective poverty alleviation programme to minimize the level of poverty is necessary. This is evident from the works of World Bank, IMF, UNDP and UNICEF reports which show that over 40 percent of the population of Sub-Saharan Africans are living in absolute poverty or on purchasing power parity (PPA) of less than one US Dollar per day. Similar demand for youth skill acquisition programme to train jobless youth to be self-reliant was supported by the Managing Director of the Zambia Seed Company that “if we want to make any meaningful impact on youth unemployment, we must change the curricula in our schools.

The thrust should be to train people to go into industry on their own as opposed to go and get paid employment. Employment nowadays is getting scarce. People are being retrenched, left, right and centre as companies and industries are re-adjusting. Therefore, the concept of training people for employment is out. We should be training people to go and do something on their own” (Chigunta, 2002: 15).

In consistent to the opinion of Zambian Seed Firm Managing Director and in conformity to his administrations, top agenda to create job and eradicate poverty, the Borno State Governor, Kashim Shettima has recently inaugurated an independent adhoc committee led by Alh. Garba Ngamdu with a mandate to man or oversee all Borno State Youth training and skills acquisition related programmes and task to initiate more other jobs opportunities to incorporate or employ the remaining jobless youths to better their conditions and make them self-reliant. The committee was also charged with the responsibility of identifying the exact number of the applicants seeking for jobs across the state (Reported by BRTV News, Hawarra, Kanuribe bulletin of 2nd December, 2012). These have demonstrated the zealous efforts and commitment of Governor Kashim Shettima to mitigate poverty, create jobs and enhance quality of life among the youths in BornoState.

In view of the National Poverty Eradication Programme failure, several scholars and observers noted that all these programmes failed not because of poor theoretical articulation but due to faulty

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implementation and prevailing socio-economic and political conditions. Scholars added that the conduct and behaviour of the political elites and the advocates of these programmes are in sharp contrast to what the programmes are advocating. On the expulsion of poverty onto our society, UNEP (2002) declares that rapid urban population growth exceeds the capabilities of municipalities to improve adequate environmental infrastructure and social services. It also observes that inadequacy of all these services results into widespread poverty and poor living conditions in Nigeria (Ali, 2011:91).

Schnurr, (1997) and Chigunta (op.cit) argued that the youth policies are often highly politicized and based on stereotypical notions of disaffected youth. In supporting the contention, Fowler and Collins (1991) opined that youth related programmes and policies are designed with youth as ‘subjects’ and not ‘objects’ of policy. Mhone, *et al.*, (1999) in Chigunta (op.cit) further observes that, creating an enabling environment for domestic and foreign private operators is evidently desirable and necessary in much of Sub-Saharan Africa in order to minimize the youth’s suffering. Tendler, (2002) argues that under the current dominant economic model, states have abdicated responsibility for employment creation. In the same vein, UN report (1999) also adds that most of the Africa’s youth policies lack clear definition areas that are critical to youth employment creation and development.

It should therefore, be noted that for any youth programme to achieve success Mhone, *et al* (op.cit) argues that a more plausible approach is to examine the nature of the existing economic context and the programme and reflect the demand and skills of those seeking jobs. Therefore, careful programme policy selection on employee wishes is necessary to achieve objectives. Schnurr, (op.cit) suggests the need to understand the full complexity of underemployment among young people in order to create flexible system to respond to their needs. Todaro and Longman (1977) supports these views and maintain that too much emphasis cannot be placed on the expansion of the modern day industrial sector to solve the unemployment problems, but ability to understand areas where the employee wishes to practice and invest its talents, is the key success of youths programme intended (Chigunta 2002). On the other hand, NEEDS (2005; 6) argued that incorporating private sector to government activities, creating a system of incentives that reward hard work and arrest corruption, while enhancing educational sector and providing special programmes for the most vulnerable members of society could help establish ground for effective empowerment of people to achieve Millennium Development Goals. NEEDS (2005: 19) admitted that for Nigeria to achieve economic development and to eradicate poverty, must divorce the practice of human,

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economic and political discrimination, eliminate a syndrome of in appropriation of public sector, open enabling environment for private sector growth and arrest the problem of flimsy economic management. NEEDS, cautioned that if such an abnormalities would continue to grow, will undermine the goals and objectives of Kuru declaration of 2001 (Cited in NEEDS 2005:19-20). On the other hand, Anyanwu, (op.cit) technically supports the study hypotheses that for national and state poverty alleviation programmes to achieve success there is need for integrating technical and vocational training to be pressing priority to generate jobs for youth and make them self employed to meet the requirement of the Federal Government to achieve Vision 2015 target in advance. Therefore, universities, polytechnics and colleges of education are advised as a matter of urgent importance to generalize practical entrepreneurship training course to all students from all fields of study and learn how to run a business independently before graduation, (Anyanwu, 2010;80).

The researcher is optimistic that the Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme under the present administration of Governor Shettima will be fruitful and a role model to other sister states. Thus, urging the state governments and those managing the activities of the programmes to take all necessary measures and actions to implement the programmes objectives judiciously to eliminate poverty in BornoState.

Equally, Thom and Thom (*op.cit*) further encouraged youth not to depend on government or company jobs, rather acquire skills that can earn them a living and equally make them employers of labour. As part of effort to achieve objectives of the programme, sources from NTA Maiduguri quoted Commissioner of Agriculture and Natural Resources, on the achievement of the Ministry indicates that Borno State has procured thousands of hectares of land, fertilizers, tractors and other farm related materials. He further added that many officials of the Ministry were sent abroad, particularly Egypt to inspect and oversee the assembling of farm implements already procured by BornoState government. While several students were also sent for different Asian Tiger Nations to study various agriculture related skills acquisition courses in order to be self-reliant in the future.

In its effort to upgrade the healthcare sector in Borno State, Governor Kashim Shettima as reported by BRTV Kanuri news Bulletin of 2nd February, 2013, that a 250 bed hospital equipped with Modern day medical facilities worth millions of Naira was recently commissioned by the Vice President of Nigeria, Architect Mohammed Namadi Sambo and renamed it after late General Mamman Shuwa, while Mai Umar Moduganari bye pass constructed by the Borno State Government to ease traffic congestions in

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the state was equally commissioned by Namadi Sambo(BRTV News,English bulletin of 2nd and 3rd of February,2013). The Vice President in his remark commended Governor Kashim Shettima for fulfilling his electioneering campaign promises. He called on other Governors to emulate, while pledges Federal Government support to Governor Kashim to achieve its transformation agenda. (*NTA Government House, Maiduguri Diary of 11th February, 2013.*)A week after commissioned of the 250 bedroom hospital, BRTV News,English bulletin of 19th January,2013 reported that Governor Kashim Shettima has approved an immediate recruitment of 500 Nurses to actualize the dream of enhancing the health sector.

In a related development, there is no gain saying in the fact that "what a man does, a woman can do better". This adage has gained ground in Borno State when the wife of Governor Kashim Shettima had recently officiated an humanitarian/philanthropic programme in which she rendered cash and kind assistance to various groups of less privileged (destitute) members of the society, such as widows, orphans and Tsangaya pupils, among others, with a view to alleviate their sufferings and integrate them in the society so as to become useful and hopeful members through empowering them by learning skills of various types. (BRTV News, English bulletin of 4th February, 2013; BRTV News Kanuri bulletin of 3rd February, 2013; BRTV News Kanuri and English bulletin of 17th and 26th January, 2013; Daily Trust of Wednesday, February,6th 2013.p.V11).Furthermore, the wife of Borno State Executive Governor, Hajiya Nana Kashim as part of her commitment to resuscitate the health sector and give the women and children a new lease on life. She initiated a healthcare programme through her (SWOT) foundation to address the long standing problems of infant mortality and poor state of medical facilities as well as non availability of drugs in the state hospitals. A reliable source obtained at Maiduguri Yerwa Clinic shows that Borno State Government has procured sufficient free drugs and medical facilities to enable health personnel to carry out their diagnostic practice or responsibilities, while renovation work at the clinic was in progress as at the time of compiling this report, February, 2013 without hindrance in order to meet the Millennium Development Goals target (Survey, 2012; 2013: BRTV News, English bulletin of 19th and 21st of January, 2013).These manifest the degree of commitment of present administration's efforts to Fight Poverty and make youth self-dependent.

Conclusion

It could be said that the demand for effective poverty eradication programme with sound policy of entrepreneurship development to train jobless youths in various skills acquisition is a key for achieving

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sustainable livelihood or economic dependence among the youth. Therefore, the importance of poverty alleviation programmes in empowering youths cannot be over-emphasized in our contemporary world. It has been observed that ineffective youth poverty alleviation programme could generate negative action from youth and thereby render the programme abortive. The finding of this paper vindicated that the way and manner the Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme is organized, is quite convincing and encouraging. Though, the study further appeals for proper implementation of the programme objectives. The target of Governor Shettima administration is to complement the effort of the Federal Government of Nigeria, Vision 2015 and Global Millennium Development Goals (MDG's) target, respectively. Therefore, individual and group cooperation is highly needed to achieve success in this regard.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this paper, the following recommendations are made to improve and achieve the goals and objectives of the programmes.

1. That the Borno State Government should continue to provide funds and necessary logistics to the poverty alleviation programme in order to achieve a great success.
2. That the Borno State Government should acknowledge that the programme requires honest persons to oversee the activities and affairs of the programme in order to ensure complete success of the programme and avoid unnecessary diversion of resources meant for the scheme.
3. That the Borno State Government should look for a way to initiate additional programme of door to door within the Maiduguri Metropolitan Council that touches every house without discrimination. The mini programme should be similar to the recent distribution of mosquito nets where each and every household was a beneficiary. The government should start with a token item as a litmus test and observe for sometime and see whether to go ahead or suspend the programme for appropriate strategies.
4. That the coordinator of Borno State Poverty Alleviation Programme should consider the demand and wishes of those recruited under the scheme as to area they want to specialize in out of the various acquisition capacities available at a time.
5. That the researcher commended Borno State Government and fishery/fish pond training unit coordinator for retaining some of the trainees that have excelled and provision of capital to those that are to be on their own.

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6. That Borno State Government should revisit and review the secondary and tertiary institution academic curricula to incorporate skills training on jobs for students of all levels. Every student should be made to specialize in one trade or job of interest before graduation. Based on this, students of all fields should be engaged in industrial attachment (SIWESS) exercise as part of their various courses.
7. There is need to invest in research to get the exact information on specific needs of youth growth in both the rural and urban areas so that they could be incorporated in the planning and provision of services to improve their welfare, to establish sufficient grounds for an egalitarian society in the future.
8. That the researcher highly commends Governor Kashim Shettima for his foresight to establish Borno State University and promised to start full academic activities this year, 2013.
9. That the researcher suggest for further study on the subject, hence government is a continuous process.
10. That as part of effort to standardize the education sector, government should independently sponsor some qualified indigenes for abroad to study post graduate (Masters and PhDs) in relevant fields of human endeavors.
11. That the researcher on the basis of the study outcome commends Governor Kashim Shettima for his commitment and determination towards developing the State and uplifting the living standards of Borno State citizens.

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FINANCIAL REPORTING AND THE COMPUTERISED ACCOUNTING INFORMATION SYSTEM: BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES

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KEYWORDS: Financial Reporting, Accounting Information System, Accounting Process

ABSTRACT

This paper examined the importance of computerized accounting information system as an effective tool for accurate and reliable financial reporting. An accounting information system is a system of collection, storage and processing of financial and accounting data that is used by decision makers. Furthermore, in the computerized system of accounting, the computer handles every step in the accounting process from recording the financial transaction to preparing the financial statements. Also, the various benefits, implications as well as the challenges of the computerized accounting information system were accentuated. The paper also recommends a full fledge incorporation of the computerized system of accounting into the curriculum of learning of Accounting students across tertiary institutions.

Introduction

Accounting is an important part of every company. Businesses are required to keep books on their credits and debits. As many professional accountants and auditors state - accounting is a language of business which is accepted in all developed and developing countries. Every company applies accounting because it is generally accepted that companies have to reveal certain financial and management information to the government and public users and of course because accounting is an indispensable tool in business

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decision-making process. The days of painstakingly entering data by hand and calculating totals made accounting slow and often resulted in errors. As computerized accounting systems emerged through the advancement of technology, accounting was simplified and became more accurate. With the development of information technologies there were developed many computer products (software) that make accounting as easy as ABC for those who uses them.

Accounting

As many professional accountants and auditors state - accounting is a language of business which is accepted in all developed and developing countries, but what exactly is accounting? Well, accounting has been defined by many authors in various ways. According to Osmond, (2011), accounting is the way business owners manage their company's financial information in orders to make better decision regarding their companies. Meigs & Meigs (1986) also defines accounting as the art of measuring, communicating and interpreting financial activities.

History of Accounting

Osmond, (2011), states that; Accounting is several centuries old and that Luca Pacioli, an Italian friar from San Sepulcro, is the father of accounting. Pacioli is credited with developing the double entry bookkeeping system in 1494 using debits and credits to manage a company's financial information. His system included ledgers and journals where financial information was kept relating to business transactions. Pacioli's accounting system is still in use today, even by the various computerized accounting programs in the industry.

Emergence of Computerised Accounting System

Till 1970th-80th the most common used system in accounting was "general ledger". It was a book with assigned pages for each account, such as cash, receivables, payables, stockholder equity. Everyday transactions were entered by hand into a journal. After each transaction entry had to be posted in a proper general ledger account on the assigned page . Next step was an input of the numbers from general ledger into financial statements and preparing tax returns. All these processes were inefficient, slow, and manual. Even a minor mistake or inaccuracy in these processes led to long time spent for recalculation.

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Through the 20th century, developments in computing, data modeling, and telecommunications influenced accounting processes significantly. The first mention of the term “systems” regarding accounting emerged in the 1920’s and was used widely in mass-media. At the same time many scholars considered that development of computerized accounting systems technologies had begun even earlier. For example in 1890s, to meet needs of cost accounting, calculating machines, such as Hollerith device, were created.

Invention of accounting software revolutionized accounting processes. Multiple developments forerun present-day technologies. A countess Ada Lovelace computing machine was the first machine created and used for accounting. The IBM 9Pac was one of the first programming systems that preceded the invention of many modern accounting systems. SAP software was created in 1973 and provided opportunities not only for automated financial transactions but also for supported executive decision making. Before the invention of Peachtree program, all accounting computerized programs were unavailable for broad public. Peachtree was the first program sold in stores and accessible for everyone.

In 1983 company Intuit introduced a computerized computing program for personal finance Quicken. After that TurboTax for calculation of federal and income taxes and QuickBooks for small business accounting purposes were presented to wide public. At this point of the development of accounting technologies manual journal entries were left in the past and computer technologies made profession of accountant easier.

The last decade of 20th century brought significant changes to data communication. It became faster, more reliable, and less expensive.

Manual versus Computerized Accounting

Accounting is an important part of every company. Businesses are required to keep books on their credits and debits. Weber, M. (2011) emphasizes that every company applies accounting because it is generally accepted that companies have to reveal certain financial and management information to the government and public users and of course because accounting is an indispensable tool in business decision-making process, it has led to the development of information technologies and many computer products (software

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in terms of accounting packages) that make accounting as easy as ABC for those who use them. Accounting can be divided into two basic categories: those which apply manual accounting and those which prefer computerized accounting systems. Whereas computerized accounting has been defined by Alan & Frank (2005) as a total suit of components that together comprises all inputs, storage, transactions, processing, collecting and reporting of financial transaction data, manual accounting on the other hand implies that employees perform the whole accounting cycle manually on a periodic basis: they calculate trial balances, journalize transactions, prepare financial statement reports and other routines.

Whether manual or computerized, accounting in itself is known to have a cycle that includes the following steps: journalizing the transactions, posting them to ledger accounts, preparing trial balance, making adjustment entries, preparing adjusted to end-of-period trial balance, preparing financial statements and appropriate disclosures, journalizing and posting the closing entries, and preparing after-closing trial balance at last, Weber M. (2011). From the first look, it is not very difficult and it is so indeed, but when there are thousands or millions of transactions to be handled, the situation dramatically changes. Lots of transactions that must be processed in the accounting cycle make this process routine and even a little mistake or inaccuracy can cause all the cycle from the very beginning to fail which will therefore require an extra effort to find and correct the mistake.

Manual accounting uses several paper ledgers and journals where accountants record financial information. The general ledger includes miscellaneous transactions and the aggregate balance of all subsidiary ledgers and journals. Whereas Manual accounting is very detailed, since accountants must carefully enter information into physical books, Computerized accounting uses software programs designed from traditional manual accounting systems and involves the use of computers, spreadsheets and programs designed to record and report financial information electronically, (Osmond, 2011).

Manual accounting implies that employees perform the whole accounting cycle manually on a periodic basis: they calculate trial balances, journalize transactions, prepare financial statement reports and other routines. Computerized accounting implies that the only thing that employees do is recording transactions into the computer which processes the other steps of accounting cycle automatically or by a request.

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Computers provide accurate calculations and smart reports but it takes much time, resources and effort too and it's difficult to assess which accounting type is more fast and economic. If manual accounting requires qualified accountants to keep a record of business transactions, computerized requires accountants which can use specific software and thus they cost more. Computer software calculates faster but it does not know what you need until you can clearly explain what exactly you need. In addition good computerized accounting system can cost thousands and even millions dollars, depending on the complexity and the size of organization. Computerized accounting provides better internal control report system for any given period of time (computer can control thousands indicators simultaneously and create notifications to the appropriate departments or workers if some indicators do not correspond to the normal state), while manual control takes more time. Among the advantages of manual accounting there are: comparatively cheap workforce and resources, reliability, independence from machines, skilled workers availability; the disadvantages include: reduced speed, increased effort of accountants, relatively slower internal control reporting, routine work and some others.

Among the main advantages of computerized accounting there are: high speed and mobility of reporting, reliability, no routine work, increased accuracy, internal control system of increased productivity, easy back up and restoration of records; the disadvantages include: extremely high costs on developing, introducing and using the system, special trainings for personnel, increased personnel costs, dependence on machines etc. Obviously both computerized and manual accounting have advantages and disadvantages

Components of Computerized Accounting System(CAS)

A good computerized accounting system or will have a clean, easy-to-use interface. From this interface, you should be able to enter data, export data into other formats, and perform data validation operations. On the back end, databases will drive your CAS, responding to queries about the information stored therein. Your CAS should have elements including:

- Accounts Payable: Allows you to manage invoices and bills that you must pay.
- Accounts Receivable: Allows you to manage payments, billing, and income.
- Payroll: Handles employee payroll within the accounting system.

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- **Benefits Management:** Allows for employee budget management, accrued vacation time reporting, and other budget reporting.
- **Budgeting:** Lets you create and manage a budget.
- **Assets:** Lets you manage fixed and fluid assets, calculate depreciation, and perform other asset management.
- **Reporting:** Integrates your data with existing reporting standards, so that you can comply with regulations that affect your business.
- **Project Reporting:** Let you manage the assets and workflow for multiple projects at one time.
- **Supply Chain Management:** Allows you to track inventory, suppliers, goods pricing, and other supply side services.

Accounting Software

Accounting software is application software that records and processes accounting transactions within functional modules such as account receivable, payroll and trial balance. It functions as an accounting information system. It may be developed in-house by the company or organization using it, may be purchased from a third party, or may be a combination of a third-party application software package with local modification. It varies greatly in its complexity and cost.

Accounting software is typically composed of various modules, different sections dealing with particular areas of accounting. Among the most common are:

Core modules

- **Accounts receivable**—where the company enters money received
- **Accounts payable**—where the company enters its bills and pays money it owes
- **General ledger**—the company's "books"
- **Billing**—where the company produces invoices to clients/customers
- **Stock/inventory**—where the company keeps control of its inventory
- **Purchase order**—where the company orders inventory
- **Sales order**—where the company records customer orders for the supply of inventory
- **Book keeping**—where the company records collection and payment

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Non-core module

- Debt collection—where the company tracks attempts to collect overdue bills (sometimes part of accounts receivable)
- Electronic payment processing
- Expense—where employee business-related expenses are entered
- Payroll—where the company tracks salary, wages, and related taxes
- Reports—where the company prints out data
- Purchase requisition—where requests for purchase orders are made, approved and tracked
- Reconciliation—compares records from parties at both sides of transactions for consistency
- Journals
- Departmental accounting
- Support for value added taxation
- Calculation of statutory holdback, vendors may use differing names for these modules.

Some of the Accounting Softwares are:

- **FreshBooks**The mission of FreshBooks, an online accounting software package, is to manage your books at a level detailed enough to satisfy an accountant. FreshBooks does more work than invoices. You can track expenses and income, get tax reports ready for your accountant, and calculate sales tax. It also backs up all your income online. It is one of the favourite online accounting software programs.

- ***QuickBooks Simple Start Edition***

QuickBooks Simple Start is an easy accounting software solution for your business. It is best used for small businesses with few employees. It organizes your business's finances, tracks your sales and expenses, and provides help for you at tax.

- ***QuickBooks Pro***

QuickBooks Pro 2012 has all the features of QuickBooks Pro 2011 with some of them improved and some new features. Some of the features carried over from the 2011 version are customer snapshot,

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batch invoicing, accounts receivable and payable functions, the ability to email customers invoices and other correspondence, payroll management, and report functionality. Improved features include worksheet formatting and memorized transactions. New features are industry-specific report templates, invoices, billing, and other tasks in a calendar template.

- ***QuickBooks Premier 2012***

QuickBooks Premier 2012 is one of the top of the line of the QuickBooks line of accounting software. It includes everything that QuickBooks Pro 2012 has in it plus a number of more advanced features. One of the most important advanced features, is its inventory control center that lets you track your inventory. In addition, QuickBooks Premier can cost each complete job, customize reports, track balance sheets by class, bill clients progressively by job phase, and much more

- ***AccountEdge Accounting Software***

AccountEdge accounting software is the "jack of all trades" accounting software package. This software has innumerable features. One good feature is that it has a banking program that allows you to receive your clients' banking data. You get comprehensive general ledger and asset management functions. The software produces compliant financial accounts in the chart of accounts.

- ***Sage Peachtree Accounting Software***

The Peachtree Accounting Software package is a complete accounting solution for your small business. If you have a microbusiness or a very simple small business that doesn't have to handle payroll or inventory, Peachtree is probably a more vigorous software package than you need. If you have a more complex small business, Peachtree could be for you as it handles everything from job costing to inventory to vendor management. Reporting functions are excellent and Online banking is available. Peachtree is a more sophisticated accounting software packages to use or to learn.

Financial Reporting and its Qualities

According to the Babylon dictionary (1997), financial reporting is the process of preparing and distributing financial information to users of such information in various forms. Emphasis is made that the most common format of formal financial reporting are financial statements, which are actually prepared in

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accordance with rigorously applied standards defined by professional accounting bodies developed according to the legal and professional framework of a specific locale.

A financial statement also known as a financial report is a formal record of the financial activities of a business, person, or other entity, Babylon dictionary (1997). A financial statement also often referred to as an “account”; expression of one’s responsibility over a particular activity.

Financial reporting is largely an effort to assess financial performance, that is, how well or how poorly an entity performed with money entrusted to it, (Sacco, 1998). Financial statement comprises of statement of comprehensive income (Profit and Loss A/C), statement of financial position(Balance Sheet), cash flow statement, notes to the accounts, five-year financial summary, etc.

The Influence of Computerized Accounting System on Financial Reporting

The presentation of scheduled reports can be simplified and prepared at regular interval with ease (McRae, 1998). With the application of computerization, generation of financial reports will be easy since information can be easily generated and updated on a timely basis. With the substantial increase in the number of transactions and increase in the need for real time information, maintenance of accounting data on a real time basis has become essential. This is achievable using computerized systems hence promoting the quality of financial reporting. Carol (2002) says that computerizing business general ledger, payroll and other accounting tasks increases office efficiency.

Computerized accounting systems have also been credited for their quick processing speed and large storage capacity. Using computerized accounting systems ensure up to date account balances are available at any time to aid management in decision making (Lancouch 2003). Computerization saves time on transaction hence leading to quality of financial reporting for instance timely, accurate and reliable information can be generated (Lewis 1999)

Benefits of Computerized Accounting over Manual Accounting Accuracy

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There is an old proverb that begins with the statement “to err is human.”. Humans do commit errors. An absent decimal point or the addition of one too many zeros can drastically alter the accuracy of a financial report. Computerized accounting systems, on the other hand, are designed to minimize the existence of such blunders. Additions, subtractions and other calculations are performed by the machine. This ensures that only the correct total are listed at the end of the general ledger.

Automation

A computerized accounting system eliminates many cumbersome and time consuming manual processes. In addition to calculations being automated, many accounting software programs allow various reports, such as year-end reports, to be generated at the touch of a button. An additional benefit to automating the accounting process is the ability to expediently share information. Information regarding business accounts can be independently entered into an automated system by multiple authorized parties. In addition, accounting documents, such as financial statements, can be emailed from one colleague to another in just a few moments.

Compatibility

The implementation of a computerized accounting system also allows various businesses to more easily share financial information. For example, if a company with manual accounting procedures purchases another organization with manual accounting procedures, it may take weeks or even months to completely integrate the financial data of the two firms. On the other hand, if both companies utilize compatible computerized accounting systems, all data can easily be integrated because one program is able to speak to the other.

Furthermore, Accounting software help you to maintain lists of customers and vendors in a database designed for finances.

Accounting software contains record formats that let you type in or import relevant customer and vendor details, things like contact information, credit terms and limits, credit card numbers, and price levels. You can usually set up custom fields to track any additional information you'd like to. Customer records can

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also contain descriptions of jobs you're working on for that company; they may even display a history of your transactions with them. Also, accounting software keeps you in the know about whom you're buying from, to whom you owe money, and how much you spend to pay certain suppliers..

With accounting software, payroll processing will involve little more than entering the hours everyone worked and printing paychecks or authorizing direct deposit.

Accounting program also save your time and money by its electronic banking and billing capabilities. The computerized accounting system transmits and retrieves some financial transaction information electronically. For example, you can email invoices to customers and clients directly from the system. It can also share bank accounting information with most banks, making it easy to make payments and transfer funds electronically.

Challenges encountered with the use of computerised accounting systems

Despite the numerous benefits of Computerised Accounting Systems that can be listed they are not without challenges. The impediments to implementing a CAS include: lack of time (Proudlock et al. 1999), owner-manager's view that the CAS is costly (Head 2000), perception that the technology is not suited to the nature of the business (ABS 2000), and lack of IT expertise (ABS 2000; Burgess 1998). Other specific challenges include:

- **Hardware security risks:** The Computer hardware refers to electrical, mechanical and up to electronic components. Conditions such as high environmental humidity, dust, vibration, etc may damage the computer hard disk. Such condition may affect accounting data seriously or can lead to loss of vital information.
- **Software security risk:** Smoothly processed computerised accounting work requires the operating system to function well. Any damage or impairment to the software can make the process of computerisation a futile effort.
- **Risk associated with the Network Environment:** Conditions such as password theft, hacking into damage can hamper the effectiveness of the computerised accounting system.
- **Lack of adequate skills and technical-know-how** could frustrate the computerisation process.

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However, these challenges can be overcome by taking appropriate measures in the form of in-built security on the computer system as well as proper orientation and training for the users of the computer system

CONCLUSION

The study of accounting information system is very important to stay abreast of the changing environment as a result of the complexity of the modern-day information system. Computerised accounting system is important for timely and reliable financial reporting.

Recommendations

The accounting students in the 21st century need to be dynamic, moving along with the current advances in the profession. It is recommended that Computerised Accounting system should be included in the curriculum of learning of tertiary institutions. This becomes imperative as it is an effective tool for timely and accurate financial reporting.

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APPLICATION OF FORENSIC AUDITING IN FRAUD CONTROL IN NIGERIA MONEY DEPOSIT BANKS

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KEYWORDS: forensic auditing in fraud, control, Nigerian banks, forged cheques

ABSTRACT

The study examines the application of forensic auditing in fraud control in Nigerian banks. Nigerian banks over the past decades suffered from the menace of frauds which resulted to distresses and liquidations which hamper the roles of banks in the economy. The external auditors failed to detect the frauds in the course of carrying out their work. Regulatory evidences have shown that bank frauds increase on daily

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basis. Analysis of the types of frauds and forgeries perpetrated show that the most common types are: ATM fraud; fraudulent transfers/withdrawals; internet banking; lodgement of stolen warrants; presentation of forged cheques; suppression of customer deposit. The study analysed the trend in fraud cases from 2001-2012, included are the amounts involved in frauds, the most frequent types of fraud, and the losses sustained by banks. The analysis revealed that there are up and down movements in fraud cases. Since banks continually lose huge sums of money as a result of the inability of the auditors and the supervisory regulators to curtail the trend, there is therefore the need to devise different means of tackling frauds in the banks. The study therefore suggests employment of forensic auditing in Nigerian banks by amending the existing statutes, in such a way that forensic auditors are included in the audit team. Through this, auditors will have more tools to effectively deal with challenges in detecting fraud.

INTRODUCTION

The rise in corporate crimes has forced the developed and developing economies to look for possible way of tackling the scandals. Nowadays, fraud has become a norm in most organisations and as result of its widespread, conventional auditing and investigations have become unproductive in its prevention and detection. Oyejide (2008) opines that fraud is a subject that has received a lot of attention both globally and in Nigeria specifically. Fraud is something that internal and external auditors are supposed to guard against through their periodic audits. However, the auditors can only check for the compliance of a company's books to Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP), auditing standards, and company policies.

According to Owolabi (2010) bank failures are as old as banking industry itself. The Dictionary of Economics and Commerce confirmed that 200 banks failed in England between 1815 and 1850 just a period of 35 years, and one of the reasons attributed to the failure is fraud. Therefore, fraud is not limited to one economy but is a general problem. The origin of bank failure in Nigeria can be traced to the 1930s bank failure and crises. Nwankwo (1992) stated that "the crises of confidence in Nigerian banking industry is not a new one, it has been with us for quite a long time. It occurred in the 1930s when all indigenous banks, except one (National Banks), collapsed. It occurred again during the banking boom and crash of the late 1940s when all but four indigenous banks escaped the liquidators' hammers". Also between 1952 and 1954, 16 out of 21 indigenous banks failed. In the late 1990s, 26 failed banks were liquidated at once while

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others went through various surgical operations ranging from, restructuring, renaming, acquiring and complete sales to new investors (Owolabi, 2010). As a consequence of capital inadequacies, Nigerian banks experienced liquidity problem which led to the raising of minimum capital base of N25 billion in 2004. The recapitalization brought the number of banks to 25 in 2006, a considerable reduction from the 89 which existed in 2004. In 2009, Nigerian banks witnessed sacking of the management of five banks; Intercontinental, Oceanic, Union, Afri, and First Inland banks over alleged fraudulent mismanagement and lack of corporate governance which tremendously heightened public anxiety about the health of these banks and to some extent created doubts about the audit function being performed in these banks. Fraud constitutes a problem to banks in their operations and their roles in the economy at large. Evidence therefore shows that out of the 25 big banks operating in Nigeria after recapitalization, three international accounting firms have been their auditors.

The above scenario shows that audit failure prevailed over the years. The audit failure encompasses internal and external audits. The frauds were perpetrated under the supervision of the management and internal auditors of the banks. There is no doubt on the fact that the independence of internal auditors is not guaranteed as they work as employees of the organisation as also noted by Okoye and Gbegi (2013). The idea of external auditor was given birth to, yet frauds exist in banks. The frauds committed are of different types and magnitude. Among them are; Telling fraud, Falsification of accounts, Forged cheques with forged signatures, Printing of bank documents illegally, Clearing fraud, Computer Fraud, Foreign exchange fraud, Theft of cash, Opening and Operating of fraudulent loan accounts, Armed Robbery attacks, Fictitious Bank branches, Miscellaneous and other types of fraud, Fraudulent Withdrawals, ATM Withdrawals (Kanu and Okarafor, 2013).

In relation to external auditors' work, the statutory regulations such as Companies and Allied Matters Act 2004 (as amended), Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) Act 2007, Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 1991, and Banks Ordinance 1991 have not spelt out fraud detection as part of auditor's duty rather than management. Conventional auditing has become ineffective in its preventive role, and lack of integrity which is an essential quality of an auditor. This means there is need to devise different

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means of tackling fraud taking into consideration the types of frauds, perpetrators, the mode of perpetration, and the duties of external auditors as enshrined in the governing statutes.

Forensic auditing is a field of accounting that is attracting attention as a result of persistent occurrence of frauds. Crumbley (2003) defined forensic accounting as an accounting analysis that can uncover possible fraud that is suitable for presentation in court. This means the primary aim of forensic auditing is fraud detection. Several studies centred on the detective role of forensic accounting and fraud prevention in Nigerian deposit banks. However, little or no attention has been given to its possible application in Nigerian banks especially taking into cognizance the factors that may hamper its application, and acceptance. It is against this background that the study seeks to examine the possible application of forensic auditing in reducing fraud Nigerian banks.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE CONCEPT OF FRAUD

Different scholars have varied definitions of fraud. Adewumi (1986) defined fraud as a conscious premeditated action of a person or group of persons with the intention of altering the truth and or fact for selfish personal monetary gain. It involves the use of deceit and trick and sometimes highly intelligent cunning and know-how. Watoseninyi (1996) views fraud as irregularity involving criminal deception to obtain an unjust or illegal advantage. He further explains that fraud is the deviation of a person's or organisation's money or goods for satisfaction of personal or selfish desires using criminal deception techniques which are identified to include defalcation by way of misappropriation of money or goods or manipulation of accounts. From the legal point of view, fraud situates itself as generic term which embraces all multifarious means, which human ingenuity can devise, that are resorted to by one individual to get an advantage over another by false pretences (Nigerian Criminal Code, 1990). According to Chambers Universal Learners' Dictionary (1985), a person who pretends to be something that he is not is fraud, a snare, a deceptive, trick, cheat and a swindler. The defunct Common Law Manual (Masango, 1998) argues that fraud is an unlawful making, with intention to defraud, a misrepresentation which causes actual prejudice or which is potentially prejudicial to another. It identifies essential elements as follows: unlawfulness, misrepresentation (which could be in the form of words, conduct, or failure to disclose);

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prejudice (which could either be actual or potential), and intention. The United States Association of Fraud Examiners (1999), in a rather conservative fashion, identifies fraud as the fraudulent conversion and obtaining of money or property by false pretences; included are larcenies by bailee and bad cheque.

In the context of the banking industry, Gold-Irokalibe (1995) opines that banking fraud or malpractice is an action or conduct by which the perpetrator aspires to gain a rather dishonest advantage over another in pecuniary. Ihiagarajah (2008) views bank fraud to any of a number of actions carried out with the intent of defrauding a financial institution. Similarly, the concept has been stated to mean the use of fraudulent means to obtain money, assets, or other property owned or held by a financial institution (Wikipedia, 2013). One thing stands out from the various definitions above which is the fact that fraud vary widely in nature, character and method of perpetration.

COMMON TYPES OF FRAUD IN NIGERIAN BANKS

Attempts to classify fraud have been a difficult task to fraud specialists. One school of thought differentiates fraud according to occupation and non-occupation (Singleton, Singleton, and Balogna, 2006), while Comer (2006) classified it on the basis of whether it is public or private sector fraud. However, another school accorded fraud in terms of industry in which the fraud was committed, such as bank fraud or insurance fraud (Skalah,Alois, and Sellar, 2005). Watoseninyi (1996) opines that fraud can be classified based on the method or instruments used; those involved in the fraud; and the victim of the fraud.

For the purpose of this study, the table below shows the types of fraud in Nigerian banks

Table 1: Common types of fraud in Nigerian banks

S/no	Fraud type	No. of bank fraud	Ranking
1.	Cashiering fraud	401	8 th
2	Falsification of accounts	300	11 th
3	Forged cheques with forged signatures	2254	3 rd
4	Printing of bank documents illegally	54	15 th
5	Clearing frauds	338	10 th
6	Computer fraud	356	9 th

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7	Telex fraud	56	14 th
8	Foreign exchange fraud	31	17 th
9	Cross firing of cheques and kite flying	36	16 th
10	Theft of cash/suppression of lodgement	786	6 th
11	Suppression of entries cash/cheque	1301	5 th
12	Opening and operating of fraudulent account	235	12 th
13	Over-invoicing for service to the bank	79	13 th
14	Robberies (armed)	472	7 th
15	Fictitious bank branch	2	18 th
16	Miscellaneous fraud	1361	4 th
17	Fraudulent withdrawals	4994	1 st
18	ATM withdrawal	4647	2 nd
Total		17703	

Source; adapted from Akindele (2011)

Analysis of the types of frauds and forgeries perpetrated shows that the commonest types are: ATM fraud; fraudulent transfers/withdrawals; lodgement of stolen warrants; presentation of forged cheques; suppression of customer deposit. A further analysis of the types of frauds and forgeries perpetrated in 2010 shows that the perpetration of ATM frauds and granting of authorized credits accounted for the largest proportion. A total of 357 members of staff of banks were reported to be involved in frauds and forgeries in 2010 (Omoh, 2011). Sometimes, employees monitor customers' signatures as they always come to perform one transaction or the other. Once they become conversant with the signatures, having access to the account is no longer a problem. Fraudsters perpetrate the above frauds in different ways best known to them.

The NDIC report (2011) shows that the largest number of the reported cases were through the ATM transactions, fraudulent transfers/withdrawals through insider facilitation, internet banking, and suppression

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of customer deposits. Details of the nature of the frauds show that ATM-related frauds topped with 738 reported cases, followed by fraudulent transfers/withdrawal of deposit (331 cases), presentation of forged cheques (280 cases) and outright theft (240 cases). Other cases include suppression of customer deposit, 219; fraudulent conversion of cheques, 123; non-dispensing of money, but registered by electronic journal, 112; and internet fraud, 108. In 2012, there were about 2352 reported fraud cases. 498 were attributed to staff participation which shows an increase of 141 from 357 cases in 2010. This indicates that staff members commit internal frauds mostly. This could be controlled by putting proper internal control measures in place.

The consequences (the amounts involved, and the losses sustained by banks) of the frauds committed are presented in the table below

Table 2. Fraud cases in banks from 2001-2012

Year	Amount of bank funds involved (N'M)	Actual/expected losses sustained by banks (N'M)
2001	11,243.94	906.3
2002	12,919.55	1,299.69
2003	9,384.67	857.46
2004	11,754	2,610
2005	10,606.18	5,602.05
2006	4,832.17	2,768.67

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2007	10,105.81	2,870.85
2008	53,522.86	17,543.09
2009	41,265.50	7,549.23
2010	21,291.41	11,679
2011	2,840	4,071
2012	1,797	452
Total	191,563.09	58,209.34

Source; extracted from NDIC report (2001-2012)

The data in table 2 are presented in the chart below:

Source; plotted from table 2

Note: Series 1 represent amount involved in bank frauds

Series 2; actual/expected losses sustained by banks

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Horizontal axis; years (2001-2012)

Vertical axis; amount involved

The chart above shows the amounts involved in bank frauds and the losses suffered by banks as a result of the frauds from 2001-2012. As depicted in the chart, there is rise and fall in the amounts involved in the two cases. The chart shows that the worrisome fraud occurred in 2008 amounting to N53,522.86 billion which resulted to N17,543.09 billion loss. In 2009, there was reduction in the fraud from N53,522.86b to N41,265.50b (N12,257.36b difference), resulting to a reduction in losses by N17,535.54b. More so, between 2009 and 2010, a reduction in the amount involved in fraud was recorded, but there was increase in the losses suffered.

Nigerian banks started using e-banking effectively in 2008. Looking at the types of fraud prevalent in the banks between the periods under review, such as, fraudulent withdrawals, ATM fraud, forged cheques with forged signatures, miscellaneous fraud e.t.c, there is indication that e-banking has brought about fast growth in fraudulent activities. The reduction in the bank frauds in the years 2009 and 2010 on the other hand, could be attributed to the measures taken by Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in sanitizing the banking industry in 2009. This brought an iota of sanity into the banking industry.

The NDIC has said that three banks were in unsound condition in 2010. The NDIC in its 2010 report noted that the financial condition of 15 of the 24 banks operating in the country were rated as sound/satisfactory compared to 13 of the previous year, six were rated as marginal as against one in the previous year whilst only three banks remained in the unsound category compared to the 10 in 2009. The level of soundness and the industry performance improved during the period ended December 2010 when compared to its performance in 2009. The various statistics were indications that the nation banking industry benefited immensely from the stringent regulators action and restructuring efforts that took place in the industry during the year under review.

The total cases of frauds in 2011 involved the sum of N28.4 billion and caused a loss of about N4.071 billion to the industry. Though the value of fraud and forgeries in 2011 was lower than 2010 (N21.29

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billion), the expected loss was higher in 2010 (N11.68 billion). The NDIC reported that various Money Deposit Banks in the country reported some 3,380 fraud involving the sum of ₦17.97 billion with expected/contingent loss of about ₦4.52 billion in 2012. The expected/contingent loss had increased by ₦455 million, representing 10.9 per cent as against ₦4.072 billion reported in 2011. Notwithstanding the 43.7 per cent increase in the number of reported fraud cases from 2,352 in 2011 to 3,380 in 2012, the amount involved decreased by 36.4 per cent from ₦28.40 billion in 2011 to ₦18.04 billion in 2012. The report noted that in terms of level of soundness, 10 banks were rated sound, nine satisfactory and only one was rated marginal. According to the report, the industry can be considered to be relatively stable in 2012. It noted that there was no unsound bank in the banking industry as at December 31, 2012. If banks can continue to operate the same way they did from 2009-2012, then they may not experience much problems in the future.

CONCEPT OF FORENSIC AUDITING

The concept forensic auditing and forensic accounting are used interchangeably. The concept has been enunciated by several authors and scholars. According to Dahli (2008), forensic comes from the Latin word 'for public' and specifically to 'forum'. The forum was where the Ancient Romans were taught to do business and settle disputes among other things. He further buttressed that forensic relates to the application of knowledge to legal problems such as crimes. This definition traces the history of forensic accounting and its application in litigation support. Forensic is as old as history but its usage got little attention in the past. It is now becoming prominent because of increase in financial scandals. Joshi (2003) ascribed the origination of forensic accounting to Kutilya, the first economist whom he said mentioned 40 ways of embezzlement centuries ago. However, he stated that the term forensic accounting was coined by Peloubet in 1946, when he defined forensic accounting as the application of accounting knowledge and investigative skills to identify and resolve legal issues. Crumbley (2003) defined forensic auditing as an accounting analysis that can uncover possible fraud that is suitable for presentation in court. A forensic accountant uses his knowledge of accounting, law, investigative auditing, criminology, and psychology to uncover fraud, find evidence and present such evidence in court if required. According to him forensic accounting is different from the old debit or credit accounting as it provides an accounting analysis that is suitable to the organization, which will help in resolving the disputes that arise in the organization. Forensic accountants

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are often retained to analyze, interpret, summarize and present complex financial and business related issues in a manner, which is both understandable and properly supported. Albretch and Albretch (2001), described forensic auditing as the utilization of specialized investigative skills in carrying out an enquiry conducted in such a manner that the outcome will have application to the court of law. They further stated that the primary aim of forensic auditing is fraud detection, unlike the traditional auditing that focuses on review of internal control system, error identification and prevention. Forensic auditors are experienced auditors, accountants, and investigators of legal and financial documents that are hired to look into possible suspicion of fraudulent activity within a company; or are hired by a company who may just want to prevent fraudulent activities from occurring. It demands reporting, where accountability of the fraud is established and the report is considered as evidence in the court of law or in administrative proceedings. Forensic accountants may be involved in recovering proceeds of crime and in relation to confiscation proceedings concerning actual or assumed proceeds of crime or money laundering. In the United Kingdom, relevant legislation is contained in the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002. In India there is a separate breed of forensic accountants called Certified Forensic Accounting Professionals. In other countries, some forensic accountants are called Certified Fraud Examiners (CFE), Certified Public Accountants with AICPA's Certified in Financial Forensics (CFF) Credentials, Chartered Accountants (CA), Certified Management Accountants (CMA) or Chartered Certified Accountants. Also known as investigative accounting, [forensic accounting](#) is a detailed examination and analysis of financial documents and records for use as evidence in a court of law. The term forensic accounting can refer to anything from the execution of a fraud analysis to the recreation of true accounting records after the discovery that they have been manipulated.

Forensic accounting in its present state can be broadly classified into two categories encompassing litigation support and investigative accounting. These two major categories form the core around which other supporting services that traditionally come within the sphere of investigative services revolve - including corporate intelligence and fraud investigation services.

A good forensic accountant is much more than just a good accountant. To discharge his functions effectively, a forensic auditor needs to possess certain qualities and skills. Crumbley (2003) identified the following as qualities of a forensic auditor; a good knowledge of financial and managerial accounting,

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corporate financial management, advanced computer skills, a good knowledge of the environment experience, strong communication skills, and a naturally suspicious state of mind. On the other hand, Singleton, et al (2006) opine that the forensic auditor if he is to succeed in his work, should have knowledge and understanding of fraudulent financial transactions, legal processes, and high acumen of fraud and criminological concepts, and above all investigative skills.

ADVANTAGES OF FORENSIC ACCOUNTANTS

Forensic accountants are of benefits in the following areas;

Objectivity and credibility - there is little doubt that an external party would be far more independent and objective than an internal auditor or company accountant who ultimately reports to management on his findings. An established firm of forensic accountants and its team would also have credibility stemming from the firm's reputation, network and track record.

Accounting expertise and industry knowledge - an external forensic accountant would add to the organisation's investigation team with breadth and depth of experience and deep industry expertise in handling frauds of the nature encountered by the organisation.

Provision of valuable manpower resources - an organisation in the midst of reorganisation and restructuring following a major fraud would hardly have the full-time resources to handle a broad-based exhaustive investigation. The forensic accountant and his team of assistants would provide the much needed experienced resources, thereby freeing the organisation's staff for other more immediate management demands. This is all the more critical when the nature of the fraud calls for management to move quickly to contain the problem and when resources cannot be mobilised in time.

Enhanced effectiveness and efficiency - this arises from the additional dimension and depth which experienced individuals in fraud investigation bring with them to focus on the issues at hand. Such individuals are specialists in rooting out fraud and would recognise transactions normally passed over by the organisation's accountants or auditors (www.buzzle.com).

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Disadvantages/challenges of Forensic Auditing

The increased use of forensic accountant breeds the following challenges/disadvantages:

Confidentiality Issue: Since the scrutiny of a company's financial records is done by an external forensic accountant, the chances of leakage of confidential matter are always there. It is true that their code of ethics clearly mentions that forensic accountants and other members involved in the scrutiny must not engage in disclosing confidential data to outsiders, but the possibility of disclosure cannot be nullified.

Increased Chances of Threats and Negative Publicity: If the analysis of a company's financial statements points out the involvement of a particular person in fraudulent activities, there is a significant chance that the person will try to threaten the company to safeguard himself from the trial. Also, any trial that confirms a fraud happening in the company comes under public eye and gains negative publicity, which directly affects the reputation and investor relations of the company.

Costs a Lot of Money: Forensic accounting can be an expensive affair because the procedures which accountants use involve high-end accounting software. If study results have to be presented in a trial, the overall expenditure goes up even further, because the fees of forensic accountants are quite high. This can be a matter of concern for the organization.

Losing Employee Trust: It is quite obvious for employees to feel offended when they come to know that their job is under scrutiny by a third person. If no fraud is identified, employees are left with the feeling that the employer does not have faith in them. Lost trust can be difficult to regain in such cases.

Limited Use of Services: Federal regulations limit the use of services from a single accounting firm. Suppose a company has tied up with one firm for auditing, it cannot ask the firm to provide other services to it. Therefore, a company has to reach out to several firms for carrying out its accounting tasks (www.buzzle.com).

Stringent rules on customers: limited services may be provided to customers as a result of stringent rules on operations. Employees may not want to take the risk of providing some services to customers at the

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expense of their job. As a result, customers would find banking operations to be difficult which at the end of the day will make customers run away from banking. Also, Lack of trained professionals poses serious harm to the field.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The importance of forensic auditing cannot be underestimated as a result of global persistent perpetration of fraud in organisations. This indeed has made researchers and management of companies to look into other means of tackling and reducing the menace of fraud.

The following recommendations are therefore made;

1. The service of forensic auditors should be employed in Nigerian banks. This could be done by amending the existing statutes, thereby making forensic auditors one of the audit team.
2. Forensic auditing should be taught in tertiary institutions to better train accountants in the field.
3. There should be ethical campaign among employees towards developing high moral standards.
4. Practicing Accountants should also specialize in forensic auditing.
5. Fraud perpetrators should be properly sanctioned without any favour.

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ACCOUNTING: BEYOND PRACTICE BRIDGING THE GAP THROUGH TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

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KEYWORDS: Policy formulations, Nigeria, budgeting and budgetary control, environmental impact

ABSTRACT

The awareness about the fact that the frontier of accounting is increasingly expanding beyond professional practice is inchoate in Nigeria. The role of accounting extends further to research and policy formulations for Governments and corporate organizations as it assumes a multi-dimensional sine qua non in budgeting and budgetary control, environmental impact measurement, forensics and other socio-political and economic policy measures. This awareness level should be increased substantially through tertiary education. There is a unilateral stereotype of the profession (in Nigeria) especially among students always tending to practice as the core of the accounting profession hence the purpose of this article is to unmask the ills of the propaganda for professional practice as the core of the accounting profession in Nigeria; and to emphasize the three parts of the profession (research, policy and practice) according to Guthrine et al (2011). There is little awareness about the benefits of undertaking research and/or policy based orientation in Nigerian institutions limiting students' focus to becoming only professional practitioners. With this comes low number of senior academics in the field of Accounting experienced in most tertiary institutions.

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Tertiary institutions should be the “place of orientation” for the three aspects of accounting; nurturing and developing students’ interest, so this paper strongly rejects the overbearing clamor for professional practice as the core of the profession. This paper is based on the authors’ assuming opinions, observations and perspective with respect to realities in the academic environment hence subjective.

INTRODUCTION

Most common definitions of accounting start with the term “*art*” “*system*” or “*science*”. Accounting is a means to an end; through provision of relevant information for decision making. This definition implies that accounting is more relevant in practice. However, an art or a system or a science can be improved upon. If this is the case experience gained from doing something over again can lead to efficiency of the learning curve theory process, but cannot adequately help innovations with respect to better or improved methodology owing also to the fact that human resource most times enjoy and are satisfied with satisficing rather than optimizing.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Nigeria, there is literature silence on the three aspects (parts) that constitute the profession of accounting. Also, despite the parts, there is a stereotype to limit it only to professional practice. Corporate organizations pay way more than what is obtainable in academics hence also, another stereotype is the tendency only to allot slot for young academics with good grades. Like an experience my friend had (asking him to go back to the classroom, because he made a first class and because he explained issues well).

Social status is the final paradox we will address here. In the academia academics with professional membership enjoy a more dignified position, because of their affiliation with professional bodies.

Uche (2007) opines that despite recent advances in the study and knowledge of the accounting profession, there has been very little research along these lines in developing countries.

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IMPERATIVE OF RESEARCH IN ACCOUNTING

Research is what brings about innovation and that is why most organizations have a department or unit called the Research and Development (R&D) or any other related nomenclature.

Mainoma and Aruwa (2008) quoted this definition of research from (PICPA, 2006): “research may be defined as a purposive, systematic, and scientific process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, organizing, presenting and interpreting data for the solution of a problem, for prediction, for invention, for the discovery of truth, or for the expansion or verification of existing knowledge, all for the preservation and improvement of the quality of human life”.

I would like to emphasize “*...for the expansion or verification of existing knowledge...*” from that definition.

If we continue to rely on practice without innovation, we would become very good at what we do, however, how do we verify that our approach is truly explicit?

How relevant/important is membership of professional accounting bodies to students, graduates, post-graduates and post-doctoral students in/of Accounting other than those interested in accounting professional practice?

In Nigeria, Accountants have been viewed majorly as professional practitioners. This view is corroborated with the number of Professors of/in Accounting in Nigeria.

During informal interviews, counseling sessions and interactions with prospective students and students, when they are asked why they (want to) study Accounting, the most common responses are “*it is a professional course*”. And one tends to wonder what course is not professional knowing that there understanding is limited to the fact that after their degree all they hope for is to be a member of a professional body and engage in practice.

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However, contrary to popular inchoate view, Accounting is not just about professional practice; it is three dimensional: research, policy and practice (Guthrine et al, 2011). These differences should be emphasized in clear terms to intending students to enhance their understanding of the field.

Many academics preach professional practice as the core of the Accounting profession to students. This is a limited view of the profession. Accounting has evolved with three wings.

In a typical Nigerian corporate, a degree with a professional qualification is adequate for career progression. Consider this: “At the international level, research is generally a requirement for accounting academic career progression, and an important contributor to the development of knowledge and scholarship” (Wright and Chalmers, 2010).

If we insist on professional practice alone ignoring research and policy based accounting how do we develop the accounting profession?

“ICAN membership has little content of membership of the academia thus the symbiosis of research and practice is non-existent. Compared to ANAN with over 90 percent of 13 professors of Accounting in Nigeria and largely made up of accounting graduates as members”. (Mainoma and Aruwa, 2008)

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ACADEMIC ACCREDITATION

For Departments of Accounting in tertiary institutions in Nigeria to be accredited by the National Universities Commission, (NUC) the Federal regulatory body is not as much burdensome as that by professional bodies. Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) for instance will insist that as a prerequisite for accreditation, some senior members of the Department especially the Head of Department (HOD) are members of the Institute; calling for social inequality in the academia as non-members are not allowed to handle key courses and hold substantial positions.

Also according to Mainoma and Aruwa (2008) “since many of the students intend to pursue careers in the accounting profession, there is collaboration with professional bodies to align courses of study with what is obtainable in the Institutes. This strategy of indirectly imposing the Institute’s requirements on the university is done through accreditation of universities’ accounting programmes”.

It is good to have a blend of professionals and researchers in the academic environment but to insist, we have reservations.

This places a moral burden on staff members who want to be only researchers forcing them to join the body. Even with our accreditation, this is a submission by Parker et al (2011): “After more than 50 years of producing university accounting graduates, we are still being told that universities produce narrowly educated and focused graduates who can produce bank reconciliations, but cannot think critically”. This is a shame on our Universities. In Nigeria you can find graduates of Yoruba studies and Engineering working in the Operations Department of Deposit Money Banks. This is because firm now realize they can do the same things Accountants can do since they believe Accountants are just to post figures. The place of Accounting has degenerated too much in Nigeria. With the advent of technology, all an employee requires is adequate knowledge of Information Technology (IT) gadgets for posting. But is that what Accounting is all about?

Accounting is critical and requires a certain degree of knowledge base to apprehend its workings. The fact that anyone can prepare Bank reconciliations does not imply the person is an Accountant and that is what professional bodies are causing. Medical Doctors, Chemical Engineers and others from any field who can

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sit to pass their examinations are accorded professional membership status. Anyone can sit to pass a 3-hour paper but without the basic knowledge of the course his/her efficiency can be in doubt to a great extent. This is not to assert that all Accounting major Graduates are the best suited for the job.

CURRICULAR AND EXEMPTIONS

Professional bodies cajole Department of Accounting in most tertiary institutions in Nigeria to align their course content with theirs to enable their students assess and maximize course exemptions to become professional members.

“The pressure to satisfy the Institute’s requirements is manifested indirectly through the students’ desire to receive not just a degree, but a degree that also includes an exemption from their specific courses or stages”. (Mainoma and Aruwa, 2008)

This is good and acceptable but my questions are: are all graduates of Accounting meant to be members of professional bodies to be relevant in the accounting profession?

Is there no place for students who aspire to be scholars in the field of Accounting? Must those students too be “forced” to join the status quo to be relevant?

For students who want to become professional practitioners, their choice of institution is based on the Department’s chumminess with professional accounting bodies so as to maximize enough exemptions to become professional members.

According to Guthrine et al (2011) “the accounting profession is made up of three parts – research, policy and practice. I strongly believe that if these three aspects are differentiated in personalities and harmonized institutionally, then accounting profession in Nigeria will grow wider and faster”.

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The questions of discuss is whether all the Staff members of the Department of Accounting should be members of professional bodies or Accounting Practitioners per se and should membership of a professional body in Accounting be the yardstick for relevance and researching in the field of accounting?

UNDERSTANDING THE TRIPARTITE

Recall the three parts of the accounting profession-research, policy and practice by Guthrine et al (2011). Richard Laughlin's chapter (Accounting Research, Policy and Practice: Worlds Together or Worlds Apart?) in the publication *Bridging the Gap between Academic Accounting Research and Professional Practice (2011)* questions the relationship not as a 'gap' that needs to be 'bridged', but rather in a more open ended way considering whether accounting research, policy and practice are 'worlds together or worlds apart' and what the answer to this question implies for the elements that constitute the profession. In conclusion, he indicates that not bringing these worlds together runs the risk of losing the societally-sanctioned status of being seen as a profession with all the associated privileges and respect. His chapter makes clear that it is accounting research, policy and practice that constitute the accounting profession. Put simply and directly, all three elements need to work together and, through discourse, agree and accept, at an institutional level, the respective roles, responsibilities and interrelationships (with the other elements), if the profession is to continue to survive and prosper and offer the services it should in societies throughout the world.

This indicates that there is a wide gap and this is what obtains. I don't disagree with the facts that an Accountant should be chartered but is this core of the profession? Is it only by being chartered that an Accountant gains relevance in the profession? If we insist that all Accountants should be chartered as it is now then no one will ever think of research in the field and the profession will invariably not grow.

The Institute of Chartered Accountants in Australia in their report in 2011 expressly advanced the willingness of Accountants in the country to choose either to be Policy makers, Researchers or Practitioners. This they believe will ensure continuous and steady development of the profession and its contribution to society which is every Accountant's dream/goal.

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DISPARITY IN PAY

A tweet by *Accounting Today* from this link viewed on 10th June 2013 <http://www.accountingtoday.com/news/Management-Accounting-Salaries-Reach-Highest-Level-67211-1.html> reads: Professionals holding the Certified Management Accountant credential continued to enjoy greater earning power. CMA holders reported an average annual salary of \$115,290, or 25 percent more (compared to \$92,570) than those without certification. The average annual total compensation for CMAs was \$139,578, a difference of more than \$34,000 (or 32 percent) compared to their noncertified peers. The certification advantage is evident at all stages of one's career as certified professionals in all five of the survey's age categories reported higher earnings. "As the profession grows, accountants must find ways to differentiate themselves in order to stand out," said IMA president and CEO Jeff Thomson in a statement. "The findings of this year's salary survey point to the value of certification, not only in terms of earning power, but the value to employers who need highly qualified accounting talent."

In Nigeria too, an Accountant engaged in professional practice has the opportunity to earn more than a researcher or an academic.

This is a good incentive for gaining professional membership status. However how can a researcher engaged in practice have the required time for adequate research?

A researcher is not motivated solely by pay. Researchers want to see that their efforts are utilized properly.

RECOMMENDATION

My first submission is the establishment of a Nigerian Accounting Research Centre made up of equal number of practitioners and pure academics. I imply "pure" as academics whose desire is to research into the development of Accounting in Nigeria. It is the responsibility of the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) to cater for the needs of Accounting in Nigeria; however, the creation of an independent research centre will further enhance the development of the profession, because I strongly believe Accounting is research based.

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I tend to think that practitioners are stereotyped to the way things are done over time. They enjoy no incentive to change their methods or approach. But my concern is this: these methods were formulated, created, devised, put together by some people. Why then should we continue to rely on such *always* without verifying if they are still relevant?

I suggest that since practitioners are overburdened with getting their work done, the responsibility invariably falls on the researchers to find better or improved ways of doing things. Parker et al (2011) recounts that practitioners are seen as not being interested in any challenge or debate or challenge to the status quo; they are reluctant to disclose their data, so they want us to help them but they will not let us into their firms (Bricker and Previts, 1990).

If new approaches emerge, practitioners should be willing to accept them and not insist on their approaches which they are already used to.

In Court proceedings I hear of the use of former similar cases as yardstick for a case in hand, however, when the previous cases fall short of just a single proof, it is dropped. I think Accountants should take a cue from that and be ready to drop any approach adjudged stale.

Most suggestions a graduate or a student of accounting get in Nigeria is: “if you become chartered you will be hot-cake, your services will be required everywhere with good pay”. I mildly decline this. Is this profession just about the pay? Is there no desire to lift the profession? People in the past made sacrifices to make this profession get to where it is today, but all a practitioner cares about is using the profession to maximizing his financial gains. Is that solely right?

CONCLUSION

In developed economies, the roles of Accountants are explicitly spelt out so that there is not a thin line between the professional and the researcher. However in Nigeria, these roles are merged into one person. This strains the Nigerian Accountant as he/she has to multitask at every point which makes him/her

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versatile. However, with the development in technology it is imperative to define the roles to ensure effectiveness and efficiency.

As an Accountant in Nigeria you are expected to be a researcher in the field of accounting even elsewhere, a policy maker and a practitioner: how possible is that?

This paper hence examined the rationale and assesses the implications for the individual involved, the Department and the University as a whole keeping in mind that Students generally would like to attend tertiary institutions that will enable them assess as much exemptions as possible from professional bodies. It is a known fact professional bodies require Departments to align their curricula to enable their graduates obtain exemptions from some papers. This is welcome development, but there should be a line (which is rather than thin) which differentiates a researcher from a policy maker to a practitioner.

Recently I heard of ICAN'S resolve to sponsor Doctor of Philosophy candidates in Accounting and I am impressed.

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ACCOUNTING RESEARCH AND PROFESSIONALISM: REDEFINING THE TERTIARY INSTITUTION CURRICULUM

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KEYWORDS: Accounting profession, information and communication technology

ABSTRACT

One of the defining characteristics of a profession is the existence of a related academic discipline, which engages in teaching and research activities that support the profession. The accounting profession and the accounting research environments are two worlds apart. Obviously the explosive development in the information and communication technology has not significantly impacted on the improvement in the

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accounting profession particularly in the academia in terms of accounting research activities. The teaching and research activities have been an improvement of the role professional accountants had been playing in the last four decades. This study specifically examined the accounting education system, the accounting curricula, the professional accounting bodies and their requirements, accountants in a computerised work environment and the relevance of accounting research. It thus proffered a redefining of the curriculum and possible strategies, issues and changing skills set for accounting graduates, accounting academia and higher education providers, by identifying major challenges and strategies for addressing them. It therefore recommended that computerised accounting training be incorporated into the curriculum and also develop students to undertake academic accounting research. Accounting educators and researchers should collaborate to help improve what is taught and improve the quality of accounting graduates. Equally there should be constant review of the accounting education curricula to keep it abreast of development in the ever growing globe. This paper contributes to knowledge in the disciplines of accounting research, information and technology, and accounting information systems.

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THE IMPACT OF ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING SYSTEM (ERPS) IN THE ACCOUNTING DOMAIN

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KEYWORDS: Enterprise Resource Planning System, financial, marketing, manufacturing, human resources

ABSTRACT

This paper assessed the impact of Enterprise Resource Planning System (ERPS) in relation to the accounting field. ERPS is seen as database business management software that supports all business activities such as financial, marketing, manufacturing, human resources and costing activities. It elucidated the importance of ERPS as one which gives a company an incorporated real-time view of its major business processes, which are linked together by ERP applications software and a common database maintained by a database management system. It also revealed that ERPS enhances information flow between all business activities carried out within an enterprise. It considered the effect of ERPS which, if incorporated into courses taught in tertiary institutions, will help educate students on its importance in corporate

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organizations. This paper is basically a theoretical discourse. Relevant literatures were reviewed on the meaning, characteristics, functions, relevance and effect of ERPS in accounting. The study examined some accounting theories in relation to ERPS such as agency theory and green accounting theory. It gave the benefits to be derived in the implementation of ERPS. ERPS software modules were also discussed. It concluded by stating that the aptitude science and education has in making tertiary institutions meet the challenges, particularly in accounting, cannot be overestimated. The paper recommended, among others, that the Nigerian tertiary institutions incorporate ERPS into their curricula as this is not yet a common practice. This study contributes to the academic research in accounting; particularly in the areas of financial accounting, cost accounting, auditing and accounting information system.

Introduction

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) System is database business management software that supports all business activities such as financial, marketing, manufacturing, human resources and costing activities. ERP system gives a company an incorporated real-time view of its major business processes such as production, inventory and order processing management, which are linked together by ERP applications software and a common database maintained by a database management system. ERP system came into view in the 1990s as one of the fastest growing and possibly, one of the most important developments in information technology. Morris, J. J., (2009) stated that ‘these systems, which consolidate all of the back office processing needs of a typical business into one common system, affect all functional areas, especially the accounting function.’

ERP system has undergone certain evolutionary changes. Gartner Group first made use of the acronym ERP which served as an expansion of Material Requirements Planning (MatRP) which later metamorphosed into Material Requirements Planning and then Computer Intergrated Manufacturing. Despite these changes, ERP system is still seen as one which links up and breaks the barrier affecting the flow of information between various activities performed within an organization. O’Leary (2002) observed that ‘this common system design allows firm to capture information once and then share it cross functional areas enabling *information congruence*.’

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On the other hand, accounting can be defined as the process of recording, measuring, summarizing, interpreting and communicating financial information to users of financial statements to enable them make wise or rational decision. The art of accounting in its sphere of influence makes it paramount to put in place necessary systems that can help weave together organizational activities to enable the dissemination of right and appropriate information to corporate stakeholders to enable them make rational decisions. It therefore becomes important to examine how ERP system, a sub-set of Management Information Systems assists in achieving the goals of an entity, particularly, in relation to accounting.

Objectives of the Study

This paper generally assesses the impact of ERP system in relation to the accounting field. Specifically, it addresses the following issues:

- i. Elucidating on the meaning of Enterprise Resource Planning System
- ii. Assessing the characteristics, benefits and relevance of ERP system in an organization.
- iii. Examining ERP software modules that are employed in linking up organization activities.
- iv. Evaluating challenges faced in the implementation of ERP system
- v. Assessing the effect of ERP system particularly in the accounting field.

Definition of Enterprise Resource Planning System

Various authors have examined the meaning of ERP system; some of which are:

- Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is business management software that allows an organization to use a system of integrated applications to manage the business. (www.netcoach.eu.com)
- ERP could be described as a database software package that supports all of a business's processes and operations including manufacturing, marketing, financial, human resources. (Harold A., n.d)
- Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is a cross-functional enterprise system driven by an integrated suite of software modules that supports the basic internal business processes of a company. (www.techrulez.info)
- ERP is an industry term for the broad set of activities that helps an enterprise manage the

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important aspects of its business. (Margaret R., 2012)

Hence, it can be deduced that the main focus of ERP system is to have a built-in system which serves the whole organization.

Characteristics of Enterprise Resource Planning Systems

The characteristics of ERP System include the following:

- i. It is an integrated system that works in real time, without depending on periodic changes.
- ii. It has a consistent sense throughout each module.
- iii. Installation of the system and data incorporation is without complex application, given that the adoption is not done little by little.
- iv. It has a common database which supports all applications.

Major financial accounting processes in ERPS are in the areas of General ledger, Bank ledger, Accounts payable, Account receivable, Vendor invoice and Customer invoice processing. Other accounting ERP functions comprise of asset accounting, fiscal year change, depreciation and automatic clearing (Accounting with Enterprise Resource Planning Systems).

However, it's important to note that the development of ERP system is still budding. This is because it is not yet made so popular in the country. This can be deduced from the statement made by Dr Evans E. W., Executive Director, First Bank of Nigeria Plc (2004) in his write-up on *The Nigerian Software Industry and National Economic Development* stated that 'the market for ERP is still nascent'. He accentuates on the need to place emphasis on training IT professionals both at the tertiary and non-tertiary levels.

Emphasis on training to produce an army of highly trained and skilled IT professionals in terms of tertiary and non-tertiary IT training at various levels. Need to encourage some new areas of IT that are either forgotten or glossed over in our country namely: proper IT project management skill, software assessment, certification skills, software quality assurance and metrication and modern software engineering practices.

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Agbo Joel C. O. also noted that

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are potentially powerful enabling tools for educational change and reform processes through improving both access to education and the quality of that education. ICTs help expand access to education, strengthen the relevance of education to the increasingly digital workplace and raise educational quality by helping make teaching and learning into an engaging, active process connected to real life when used appropriately.

Importance of Enterprise Resource Planning System

ERP system cuts across all business activities, thus giving room for information congruence in all areas. Some of its values are given below:

- ✓ ERP Systems are highly integrated system that not only involves the accounting transactions, but transactions made in all areas of the company. [With Enterprise Resource Planning Systems (ERP) Theory and Practice FASTER Module 7]
- ✓ Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are potentially powerful enabling tools for educational change and reform processes through improving both access to education and the quality of that education. ICTs help expand access to education, strengthen the relevance of education to the increasingly digital workplace and raise educational quality by helping to make teaching and learning into an engaging, active process connected to real life when used appropriately. (Agbo Joel C. O.)
- ✓ ERP system makes clear key performance indicators needed to achieve organisational goals. Margaret R., (2012) stated that 'ERP software applications can be used to manage product planning, purchase parts, maintain and keep track of inventories, interact with suppliers, provide customer service, and track orders'.

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Source: Perky Global Limited (2012)

Challenges facing the Implementation of Enterprise Resource Planning System

In order to assess the challenges facing the implementation of ERP system, studies carried out by certain researchers are examined below:

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- ❖ Chapman & Chua (2000, p. 207) stated that ‘... there is virtually no published material that studies accounting and this [ERP] technology. The need for research into these issues is great since ERP-type technologies are rapidly spreading and at the same time evolving.’

Duplaga & Astani (2003) interviewed representatives of 30 manufacturing companies in the upper Midwest region of the United States and was able to obtain the following results:

- ❖ Lack of ERP training and education for affected employees
 - ❖ Lack of clear goals for ERP effort.
 - ❖ Lack of companywide support and involvement
 - ❖ Lack of in-house expertise in ERP
 - ❖ Lack of data accuracy
 - ❖ Lack of project management strategy to manage processes
 - ❖ Lack of software vendor support
 - ❖ Lack of top management commitment and support
 - ❖ Unsuitability of hardware and/or software
 - ❖ Lack of communications to users.
-
- ❖ Joffrey S. W. (Dr.), (2012) also noted that ‘the major impediment to successful implementation of ERP systems is usability and under utilization.’
-
- ❖ Umble et al. (2003) in his study discovered certain factors that led to the failure in implementing ERP. They include the following:
 - ✚ Top management not been committed to the system
 - ✚ Organization is not committed to change
 - ✚ Strategic goals are not clearly defined
 - ✚ Inadequate education and training
 - ✚ Multi-site issues are not properly resolved
 - ✚ Performance measures are not adapted to ensure that the organisation changes
 - ✚ Technical difficulties can lead to implementation failures.

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 Data accuracy is not ensured.

Hence, it becomes necessary to promote the adoption of ERP system as this will boost the overall effectiveness of business entities. One major way to achieve this is impacting the knowledge to students in tertiary institutions.

Accounting Theories in Relation to Enterprise Resource Planning System

Some of these theories are examined below:

Agency theory:

Agency theory assumes that the interests of owners and managers or board members (principals and agents, respectively) are not, ex ante aligned (Jensen, M.C., & Meckling, W.H., 1976). An agency relationship is said to exist between the principal (the owner or shareholder) and the agent (Moldoveanu, M., & Martin, R., 2001). However, there is the problem of information asymmetry because the agent has access to information which the principal does not have, therefore the principal is unable to keep an eye on the actions of the agent. There are two methods used in practice to address the problem. (Morris J.J., n.d) However, the second method which is to provide information systems that allow the principal to better monitor the actions of the agent has been seen to be viable. Thus, one major software application which helps to bring about information congruence is Enterprise Resource Planning System.

Structuration theory:

This deals with the concept of duality of structure for insights into the processes by which new accountants' practices and positions come into view. Ariela C., (2002) gave three levels and dimensions of structuration. The levels include: action, structure and modalities while the dimensions consist of signification, domination and legitimation. These are perceived to be fundamental analytical devices that enable proper comprehension of such transformation. He also provided a framework which conceptualise change in accountants' expertise as a structuration process and ERP systems as modalities of structuration that offers new interpretive schemes, norms, co-ordination and control facilities.

ERP Systems Software Modules

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ERP software is usually made up of an entity's software modules which are designed to meet organizational specific requirements. Each ERP module is focused on one area of business processes, such as product development or marketing. Some of the more common ERP modules include those for product planning, material purchasing, inventory control, distribution, accounting, marketing, finance and HR. (Spar Associates, Inc.)

Some of these modules are examined below:

Finance Modules

An ERP (enterprise resource planning) finance module is a software program that gathers financial data and generates reports such as ledgers, trail balance data, overall balance sheets and quarterly financial statements. (Margaret Rouse, 2012)

In ERP, a system such as accounting information system is built as a module integrated into a suite of applications that can include manufacturing, supply chain, human resources. These modules are integrated together and are able to access the same data and execute complex business processes. With the ubiquity of ERP for businesses, the term 'accounting information system' has become much less about pure accounting (financial or managerial) and more about tracking processes across all domains of businesses.

ERP Finance Module covers the following areas: general ledger, cash management, fixed assets, receivables and payables, costing, cost management, activity-based costing, budgeting.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Module:

CRM is both a business strategy and a set of discrete software tools and technologies, with the goal of reducing costs, increasing revenue, identifying new opportunities and channels for expansion, and improving customer value, satisfaction, profitability, and retention (Gary B. G. & Greg A, 2002). ERP system covers certain areas such as sales and marketing, customer contact, recruitment, service, commissions, training of employee, employee benefits, payroll and retirement.

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Inventory Module:

ERP inventory module entails all stock related functions of an enterprise. Thus, it takes into consideration all activities such as identifying inventory requirements, inventory processing, setting goals, providing replenishment techniques and monitoring consumption of stock items.

Features of Inventory module include the following:

- Stock valuation such as First-In-First-Out, Last-In-First-Out and Weighted Average Price.
- Quality Control based on Quality Control parameters
- Transfer of stock
- Consolidation of all warehouses
- On-line status of stock item such as quantities of stock in hand, available stock, stock ordered and reserved.

Sales Module

Sales is a core aspect of the activities embarked upon in an organisation. Hence, businesses are now focusing on a closer relationship with their customers across the supply chain. Sales module involves activities such as price control, order control, handling of sales enquiry and sales contract. When all these are effectively handled, a company will be able to compete well with other companies.

Purchases Module

Purchases Module is a very important constituent in a business entity. It is fully integrated with other modules in ERP. It communicates with other modules to ensure a constant flow of information. (resource) It also offers complete purchasing control to generate and track purchase orders (Seradex). Some business functions supported by this module are: On-line requisition, purchase performance, purchase orders, supplier quote appraisal, supplier scheduling, supply chain planning, vendor and contract management.

Production Module

ERP Production module gives an entity all it needs to carry out its manufacturing processes efficiently and effectively. This include setting up machines for the fixed asset section, bringing the planning process to

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production orders, storing the total planned duration of the specific assembly and the actual time taken. Production module helps to perform the following functions: quality control, bill of materials, engineering, product life cycle, assembly management, minimum and maximum production quantities and standard labour.

It must be noted however, that each of these module are closely connected to each other. This is to ensure free flow of information between various functions within an organisation.

Source: Perky Global Limited (2012)

Impact of Enterprise Resource Planning System in the Accounting Field

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- It enables accountants to spend less time on data collection and computation, but rather influences rational decisions from the results obtained.
- With successful implementation of ERP system, accountants tend to focus more on the role of internal reporting.
- ERP system also changes accountants focus on external reporting.
- ERP system helps to generate virtually any desired historical based report, therefore enhancing the process of business planning.
- ERP system generates data for cross-functional analysis, thereby enabling accountants to be involved in cross-functional analysis.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The aptitude science and education has in making tertiary institutions meet the challenges cannot be overemphasized. This is because organizations are now looking for better and effective ways by which business activities can be carried out. This, of course does not leave out our higher institutions of learning as this is a platform for which students are being impacted with necessary skills to enable them be at their best in whichever field they find themselves. ERP system, which is seen as database business management software, supports all business activities within an organization and thus enhances information flow between all business activities carried out within an enterprise. This paper therefore examined the meaning, characteristics, importance and challenges facing the successful implementation of ERP system. ERP software modules and their areas of application are also considered. The impact of ERP system in the accounting field was also dealt with.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are proffered:

- ✓ Communication skills should be improved upon. For instance, management should be able to understand technical reports provided from the results obtained.
- ✓ Nigerian tertiary institutions should incorporate ERPS into their curricula as this will help prepare the minds of students in their formative period.

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- ✓ Training of employees on the use of ERP software as this is necessary for the successful implementation of the system in corporate organizations.
- ✓ Management should be committed to the adoption and implementation of ERP system.

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OSUN STATE YOUTH EMPOWERMENT SCHEME: A KEY TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.

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ABSTRACT.

Wide-spread poverty and insecurity emanated from gross unemployment of youths seemed threatening the realisation of individual and societal socio-economic progress as well as the nation's sustainable development and nascent democracy. Youths in their numerical, energy, and creative strength are the most reliable change agents. Unemployment in any form globally propels youth restlessness, crime and associated vices and the attendant threats to nation building, peace and security. In a bid to tackle unemployment and other fundamental problems, the State Government of Osun under the visionary leadership of Mr. Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola embarked on six action-packed people programmes that guarantee development with citizens' participation in the Education, Rural and Urban Renewal, Infrastructural Development, Agriculture, Health, Entrepreneurship and Job creation christened Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme (OYES) to fast track development and banish hunger and poverty. This paper examined the challenges and prospects of OYES vis-à-vis its implications in the development of the State. Structured questionnaires were administered to gather relevant information from total sample of 120 OYES cadet members in three local government areas in the State. Data collected were analyzed using correlation analysis. The results of the study showed: that there is significant relationship between youth

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empowerment and State development; that the general objectives of OYES are achievable. On the basis of the results of the study, the researcher recommended that one, governments' empowerment programmes should be encouraged, centered on participatory approach. Two, government should reach out to more youths, regardless of their ethnic, cultural, religious, educational background and geographical or political affiliation, and three, that the programme should be legislated so that new/succeeding government would not obstruct its continuity for sustainable development.

KEYWORDS: Empowerment, Youth, Development, Sustainable, Unemployment, OYES.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria as well as many other countries in the world is facing the worst burden of youth unemployment. Many Nigerians youths roam the streets in rural and urban centres without gainful job and the danger of this situation has far reaching implications on the social wellbeing and security of the country because the idle mind is the devil's workshop. *"The implications of youth unemployment are of social, economic, political. It can be argued that youth unemployment is potentially dangerous as it portends disturbing signals to all segments of the society. The rate of youth unemployment is high in the state of Osun, and it seems to have remained so even during the economic boom while its problems could be traced to many well-known factors among which are: Non-availability of jobs both in the private and public sector of the economy, lack of required skills among job seekers and absence of loan facility to those who deserve it for self-employment among others (Ogbonnaya, 2010)."*

Ujah and Komolafe (2012) stipulated that "economic growth drop to 7.6% in 2011, unemployment rose to 23%". Those who suffer most from this problem are millions of youths who resorted to criminal means for survival through cybercrime, armed robbery, prostitution, militancy, kidnapping, political thugs, etcetera.

The Bureau of Statistics according to Osun Defender (2012) reported that the overall national unemployment rate has been on the steady increase since 2005. For instance, it increased from 11.9% in 2005 to 21.1% in September, 2011 while unemployment rate in the State of Osun had double from 6.30% in 2007 to 12.6% in March, 2009. The determination to arrest the ugly trends necessitated the current effort

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by the Governor of State of Osun, Ogbeni Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola to not only empower 20,000 youths in Community Development Programmes (CDP) but also embarked on developmental projects aimed at taking the State and citizenry out of poverty to socio-economic prosperity. Past government administrations instituted State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (SEEDS) in the State of Osun even before the administration of the incumbent governor, yet unemployment was still on high side. This study therefore investigated the phenomenon and provided possible solutions.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this research work is to:

- Discuss the challenges, prospects of Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme (OYES) and deployment of volunteer youths in various segments of the programmes.
- Clarify youth empowerment as means of facilitating development in the State of Osun.

Literature Review

Youth empowerment is a process whereby young people gain the ability and authority to make decisions and implement change in their own lives. It ranges from economic empowerment to social ideological, educational, technological and political empowerment (Omotere, 2011). In Nigeria, youth empowerment occurs in homes, at schools, through Youth Organisations, Government programmes, reality TV shows, orientations and seminars, and Community Organising Campaigns. The term ‘youth empowerment’ combines two important words (“youth” and “empowerment”) which must be defined differently. Youths are individual persons between the ages of 18-30 years. It is a means of encouraging young people to gain the practical skills, knowledge and exposure that will allow them to face and address overcome obstacles in life. The Leadership (2012) submitted: “Although Nigeria is often referred to as the richest country in West Africa, unemployment has been a major problem in the country since 1980, when the nation’s economy took a nosedive. The menace has been described as a time bomb that might explode anytime if no serious attention is paid in engaging the growing army of unemployed youths that have taken over the streets of the nation.”

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Youth empowerment is the outcome by which youths, as change agents, gain the skills that impact their own lives within and outside host communities. Omotere (2011) noted that ‘youth empowerment at the individual level is exercising power over one’s life by being skilled, critically aware, and active in creating community change. Youth empowerment at the organisation level is the implication of culture, vision, and system that support youth empowerment at individual level. Skill development: This is the process of strengthening the skills of youth so that they know how to effectively make decisions positively and interact with their peers. Critical awareness: This is the process of providing youths with the information and resources necessary for analyzing issues that affect their lives and environments as well as strategize on ways to act as change agent. Opportunity: This is the process of providing youth the platforms for decision making and engaging them in community development/change.

The Concept of Osun Youth Empowerment

The inauguration of OYES was a demonstration of one of Governor Rauf Aregbesola’s campaign promises to make the State of Osun an industrial haven in which youths as leaders of tomorrow would be catered for in the area of skills acquisition, poverty alleviation, job and wealth creation. Fulfilling his promise to create 20,000 jobs within 100 days in office as governor, OYES a palliative livelihood for 20000 out of 250000 unemployment youth applicants, mainly graduates, was launched by the State Government in the year 2011 under the administration of Governor, Ogbeni Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola as a planned action aimed at tackling the problems of unemployment and physical development in the Virtuous State (State of Omoluabi) in order to rescue the State of Osun from poor governance and install progressive governance. The State did not only target the youths who are seen as engines of economic and social development but also primary school children who are enjoying free feeding (O-Meal) and the aged people (Agba Osun) for free Medicare and N10000 monthly stipend .

Youth empowerment can be defined as the process whereby the creative potentials of the young people between the ages of 18 and 30 years old are developed to gain the ability and authority to make decisions and implement pragmatic changes affecting their lives. Therefore it was joyous and memorable when on the 26th of November 2010 the Ibadan Division of the Court of Appeal adjudged

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Mr Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola the duly elected Governor of Osun State in the Gubernatorial and House of Assembly elections held on April 14, 2007.

OYES objectives.

Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme is a voluntary and interventionist community services organisation (CSO) with the following aims. (i) To help channel the lateral potential young people into productive social and economic activity, whilst at the same time being mindful of their current livelihood conditions and capabilities. (ii) To restore sense of community, individual, self-esteem and worth to our youth, 20000 of who were selected impartially as pioneer members. (iii) To create a moral and ethical overhaul by remolding the value of our youths towards making them pursue honour and integrity/virtuousness and (iv) To give the candidates entrepreneurship opportunities through new skills training.

Systematic empowerment

Having identified the implications of youth unemployment and the importance of youths on the state development, the State Government of Osun had systematically empowered the youths and adults of Osun through saleable/practicable skills acquisition embedded in OYES schemes to address youth unemployment in the State for future developmental purposes using the following modalities:

Attitudes Re-Orientate Training: - This meant to expose the youth to leadership skill, discipline and imbibe them with the virtue spirit that will make them free from any misdemeanor in discharging of their duties.

OYES-tech- Information technology (IT) has become phenomena in the world today and which had created much opportunities for the jobless in Nigeria is that of technology. Hence the OYES officials decided to educate cadet members with computer technology training ranging from computer repair, dismantling and assembling of GSM-handsets and related devices, training of computer packages such as Corel draw, micro soft office, power point, page maker and many more. The Corp members also choose the time convenient for them in the tutorial.

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O-poultry- The state of Osunwell imbibed the Corp members into poultry farming such as catfish rearing in the State so that the Corp members will be self-reliant after their graduation instead of seeking white collar jobs endlessly without success.

O-beef/O-ram programme is designed for the Corp members to exploit cattle rearing business because of the economic advantages that pervaded the business and for economic sustenance.

O-reap. This is also designed for rural enterprise and agriculture programme. The cadet members were trained in the agro-allied production ranging from animals husbandry, fishery, yams; cassava and cocoa plantations, maize, beans, vegetables, etcetera as well as the processing of agricultural product into semi-finished or finished goods for both industrial customers and private consumers usage.

O-meal- This is another people's programme by the State government of Osunto feed the public primary schools pupils in the state free of charge. OYES cadets would be major suppliers of raw food items from their agro-allied businesses.

O-power- This acquisition of skill is for the Corp members deployed to learn the process of generating electric power supply in the State. It will be enable the trainees to study and create alternative (Bio-Gas) to the epileptic power supply that pervaded the state.

O-tour- Is a deployment of OYES Corp members into the tourism centres so as to be creative in nature and try as much as possible to promote tourism orientation and make Osun a most tourism centre like that of Dubai.

O-clean Plus (Sanitation Czars). This is for environmental sanitation of the State to promote all-round cleanliness, good health of the people because health is wealth, and also to attract foreign investors.

Green Gang- Some of the corps was also deployed to the green gang for State security purpose both at the daytime and night for the protection of citizenry and government installations.

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Traffic Marshall- likewise some of the OYES Corp members were deployed to Traffic control system in the state of Osun because of the over conjunction of the Traffic law abiding with the assessment of vehicle document for road worthy.

Public Work- the state of Osun deployed some of the OYES cadets to the public works such as road repair and maintenance

Paramedics. For good health and cleanness in case of accident, hospitalization; some of the youth corps were also trained and deployed into this segment to deal with cases on citizen health.

Teacher corps. Some of the cadets having teaching qualifications were deployed to the teachers' corps segment so as to train and educate pupils and students at different level of primary and secondary schools to give them sound educational background.

Sheriff corps is equivalent to the Federal Government Road Safety Corp to address issues on high roads. The cadets are also involved in educating the motorist to be conscious when driving and be traffic law abiding.

OYES is economic empowerment, par excellence, which reduces social inequalities, improves standard of living as well making the youths better-off and reduced crimes that are often associated with idle hands.

Youths in the development of State

Sustainable development, according to Oyeshola (2008), *“describes a process in which the natural resources base is not allowed to deteriorate. It emphasizes the hitherto unappreciated role of the environmental quality and environmental inputs in the process of raising real income and quality of life. It is a new way of life and approach to social and economic activities for all societies, rich and poor which is compatible with the preservation of the environment.”*

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Youths occupied a prominent place in any developing or developed nation. “Apart from being the owners and leaders of tomorrow, they outnumber the middle-age. Besides numerical superiority, youth have energy and ideas that are State potentials (Anasi, 2010). Federal Government of Nigeria (2001) on National Youth Development Policy asserted that: “*Youths are the foundation of a society; their energies, inventiveness, character and orientation defines the pace of development and security of a nation. Through their creative talents and labour power, a nation makes giant strides in economic development and socio-political attainments. In their dreams and hopes, a nation finds her motivation; on their energies, she builds her vitality and purpose, and because of their dreams and aspirations, the future of a nation or state is assured*”

The above statement acknowledges the role of youth in the peace, security and building of a nation. As the most active segment of any society, youths are the determiners of peace and stability of a nation. Conversely, the degree of disorderliness and instability in society is also determined on the part of youth. Peace is a precursor of development. The absence of peace means that no meaningful development can take place. The National Youth Policy (2001) affirms that the extent of the youth’s responsible conduct and roles in society is positively correlated with the development of their country.

Youth empowerment and national development

National-building is associated with national integration, national consciousness, national unity, construction and modification of socio-political and economic structures so as to move with the global trends.

It is concerned with the overall development of a nation socially, economically and politically. This view is corroborated by Ona (2012) who submitted that “nation-building is a multi-faceted, complex process of building the socio-political and economic dynamics of a political society in such a way as to facilitate the policy’s continued independence sustenance, development and growth. As a vibrant group, the educated and empowered youths can easily be mobilized positively. They can form formidable pressure groups to press home desirable changes in the political leadership at any tier of the government. They can use their energy, determination and enlightened position to disseminate information to others so as to create political

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awareness and consciousness against evil and selfish political machination. If youths are empowered, one can predict with some degree of certainty a more transformed Nigerian nation, most probably devoid of corruption, nepotism, political manipulation which has for long characterized Nigeria's political landscape."

Youth employment in agriculture not only ensures food sufficiency but also reduces unemployment rate, idleness and poverty. Ifaturoti(2012) observed that unemployment compounds the problems the youths are facing in Nigeria; by being idle, they are prone to such vices as prostitution, armed robbery and rape."

Prospects of OYES Scheme

OYES was inaugurated purposely for the development of the state of Osun which cannot be achieved in a day but through a gradual process which could take a couple of years to be achieved. Ifaturoti (2012) recounted the prospects of Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme as follows: "Full infrastructural maturity of the on-going vocational training programmes for the cadets. Partnerships with banks for the provision of credit facilities so that the cadets can engage 'gainfully' in small scale businesses and activities. Access to donor or development funds and increased global recognition. Creation of substantial volume of permanent employment for the pioneer OYES cadets. The development programme targeting to bring 500,000 youths of the State of Osun into the scheme to boost employment among the youngsters to the highest stage. With aggressive agricultural practice, roads networks construction, rural and urban renewal, establishment of community development associations (CDAs), provision of electric power transformers, tourism and formal launching of Omoluabi Garment Factory in September 2013 which has capacity to engage 3000 workers signal a brighter future, job security and sustainable development, not only for the people but also the state in particular.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher used structured questionnaires and personal interview to obtain relevant data.

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It is generally believed that the larger the sample size, the smaller the sampling error and also that a good sample is a good representation of the population from which it was drawn. Sample of 120 OYES corps in the population with equal and independent chances of being selected were randomly selected for this research.

Hypotethesis i.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between challenges and prospects of youth empowerment in the State development.

Hi: There is significant relationship between challenges and prospects of youth empowerment in the State development.

Hypotethis ii.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and the State development.

Hi: There is significant relationship between youth empowerment and the State development.

Data Presentation, Analysis and interpretation

The researcher prepared and distributed 120 structured questionnaires among the cadets in three Local Government Areas (LGAs). The OYES cadet members were randomly selected based on their availability. A total of 105 filled questionnaires were recovered from the respondents in three local government areas as follows: Olorunda 36, Ede North 35, and Egbedore 34 respectively but only 105 copies were recovered. The questionnaires served as the basis for data analysis.

ALTERNATIVE	RESPONDENT EDE NORTH LG	RESPONDENT OLORUNDA LG	RESPONDENT EGBEDORE LG	PERCENT
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STRONGLY AGREE	17	16	13	43%
AGREE	12	14	15	39%
DISAGREE	3	2	2	7%
INDIFFERENT	3	4	4	11%
TOTAL	35	36	34	100%

Table 1: Youth empowerment reduced unemployment in the State of Osun.

Sources: Field survey, 2013.

From the table 1 above, it could be seen that 43% of the respondents strongly agreed, 39% agreed, 7% disagreed, while 11% were indifferent that there are challenges facing the implementation of OYES in the State of Osun. 35 respondents in Ede North, 36 in Olorunda, 34 in Egbedore local government areas respectively responded to the questionnaires administered.

Table 2: Youth employment scheme facilitates development in the State of Osun.

ALTERNATIVE	RESPONDENT EDE NORTH LG	RESPONDENT OLORUNDA LG	RESPONDENT EGBEDORE LG	PERCENT
STRONGLY AGREE	15	13	12	39%
AGREE	13	16	17	43%
DISAGREE	4	5	2	10%
INDIFFERENT	3	2	3	8%
TOTAL	35	36	34	100%

Sources: Field survey, 2013.

Table 2 above showed that 39% respondent representing various local government areas strongly agreed; 43% agreed. Summarily 82 percent of the cadets agreed that peoples-oriented programmes especially

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OYES scheme facilitated development in the State of Osun. However 10% of the respondents disagreed while 8% were indifferent to the question.

Testing of Hypothesis

For the reason that one hypothesis may be accepted or rejected does not indicate that as for this research study and OYES is concerned, they are only show to be correct and reasonable. Since the acceptance or rejection of hypothesis is based on the result of a sample taken from the respective population or a certain number of people, so at this junction the researcher needed to calculate the relationship between two (2) variables through correlation coefficient techniques in order to know and show how they are related.

X--- Represent responses

Y--- Represent percentages

N--- Represent number or the respondents

Hypothesis II

This hypothesis was designed for the cadet members to know whether youths empowerment facilitate development of State of Osun.

Table 3 was designed to test this hypothesis correlation coefficient for hypothesis

N	X	Y %	XY	X ²	Y ²
Strongly agree	40	39	1560	1600	1521
Agree	46	43	1978	2116	1849
Disagree	11	10	110	121	100
Indifferent	8	8	64	64	64
ΣN=4	Σ105	Σ100	Σ3712	Σ3901	Σ3534

$$R_{X-1} = \frac{N\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2 (N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2)}}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{4(3712) - (105)(100)}{\sqrt{4(3901) - (105)^2(4(3534) - (100)^2)}} \\
 &= \frac{14848 - 10500}{\sqrt{(15604 - 11025)(14136 - 10000)}} \\
 &= \frac{4348}{\sqrt{4579 \times 4136}} \\
 &= \frac{4348}{\sqrt{18938744}} \\
 &= \frac{4348}{4351.87} = 0.9991
 \end{aligned}$$

Interpretation: There is positive strong correlation and it shows that youth empowerment is significant to development in the State of Osun.

Summary of Findings

The findings revealed that the Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme (OYES) has succeeded in empowering the beneficiaries in terms of skill acquisition for self-employment. Although the programme is still ongoing, there are still more to be expected. OYES in all ramifications is a successful project which has empowered 20,000 youths (Batch 1) that had hitherto lost all hopes of survival. OYES has contributed tremendously to fostering state development. Moreover, the scheme did intervene in the plight of the youths by providing them opportunities for acquisition of vocational/entrepreneurial skills of varied kinds which made them not only to be self-reliant but also empowered them to be more efficient in the discharge of their responsibilities to their individual family members, communities and Nigeria at large. The

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investigation revealed that the beneficiaries, more so among university and polytechnic graduates, were able to set up their own businesses such as O-tech, O-beaf, O-power (Bio-gas), O-Reap, O-meal and Green gang after graduating from the training schemes. There was an improved sense of commitment among the participants in OYES projects. This was evidenced by their prompt, enthusiastic response on experiences gathered during the training periods, the new change in their socio- economic status as a result of the skill acquired, and the fact that most of them were not only self-employed but also employers of labour. The then voluntary scheme turned to permanent self-sustained opportunity.

Conclusion

This study attempted capturing the role of youth empowerment scheme in the development of the State of Osun. The future belongs to the youths who make productive use of their knowledge, skills and character to positively affect the development of the state. This can only be through skill acquisition and positive orientation seminars. From all indications, youth unemployment is a menace in Nigeria and constitutes a real danger and a threat to the state development of Osun. Against this background, there is the need by government at all levels and other stakeholders to embark on massive youth empowerment schemes for the envisaged development of the community around them and that of the nation. If a state requires developingsocio-economically and politically it needed to advance natural and human resources availability in a multidimensional way.

The findings revealed that the Osun Youth Empowerment through its various trainings did re-orientate cadets' attitudes towards self and societal development; inculcate in trainees the appropriate entrepreneurial skills and attitudes for creativity, innovation and enterprise which enabled them tackled unemployment and contributed to the economic wellbeing of their communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Excessive reliance on the government for the provision of every required socio-economic resources and the jobs creation has been the bane of development efforts in Nigeria. Government alone cannot provide all facilities due to her limited resources and population explosion. Government must as a matter of urgency place her priority right; create an enabling environment for the private sector/peoples' participation programmes in building the State to an enviable level.

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There is a growing need for creativity in the modern society. The State Government of Osun should ensure continuity and improve on distribution of updated Tablet of Knowledge (Opon Imo) to public tertiary institutions and secondary schools students who as from year 2015 would write compute-base-test (CBT) examinations in West African Examinations Council and University and Tertiary Matriculation Examinations because education is the best pivotal legacy on which sustainable development rest.

Government should reach out to more youths, regardless of their ethnic, cultural, religious, educational background and geographical or political affiliation, and that the programme should be legislated so that new or succeeding government would not obstruct its continuity for sustainable development.

Zonal youth/leadership development centres should be established in the state/country for leadership/entrepreneurial/vocational training which would enable the youths and adults who are interested in manpower development effort of the State to promote sustainable self-empowerment to gainfully discover their potentials and cultivate a habit of excellence as unique brands, establish and manage their own businesses to take them out of crimes and become productive, self-reliant and development conscious.

Other States and the Federal Government should emulate State of Osun's hands-on approach to youth's empowerment and peoples' programmes to check the rate of unemployment and fast-track national development.

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APPENDIX
OYESsegmentation and deployment

s/n	Local Office	Government	Nominal Roll Strength	Percent age Strength	Green Gang 3000	Sanit ion Czars 3000	Sheriff Guard	Traffic mgrs	Teachers Corps 5000	Public Work 4000	Paramed ics 2000	Task force 1000	Total	
													Gr and	Wei

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0	2	3	4	Watt	Other	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		gth
1	BOLUWADURO	488	2.6	39		39	77	20	31	128	103	51		488	173
2	BORIBE	640	3.4	48		54	101	20	47	168	135	67		640	230
3	IFEDAYO	818	4.3	57		72	129	20	66	215	172	86		818	295
4	IFELODUN	761	4.0	15		105	120	20	60	200	160	80		761	235
5	ILA	609	3.2	49		48	96	20	44	180	128	64		609	220
6	IREPODUN	650	3.4	40		51	180	20	48	171	72	68		650	160
7	ODO-OTIN	600	3.2	48		47	95	20	43	158	126	63		600	217
8	OLORUNDA	1099	5.8	60		87	200	138	79	289	131	116		1099	270
9	OROLU	686	3.6	54		108	254	20	31	181	44	72		686	129

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10	OSOGBO	1260	6.6	50	147	199	200	50	332	150	133	1260	250
11	ATAKUMOSA EAST	363	1.9	29	28	57	20	18	96	76	38	363	123
12	ATAKUMOSA WEST	488	2.6	39	38	77	20	31	128	103	51	488	173
13	IFE CENTRAL	663	3.5	53	52	105	20	50	174	140	70	663	243
14	IFE EAST	343	1.8	27	27	54	20	16	90	72	36	343	115
15	IFE NORTH	495	2.6	39	39	78	20	32	130	104	52	495	175
16	IFE SOUTH	391	2.1	31	31	62	20	21	103	82	41	391	134
17	AREA OFFICE	382	2.0	15	30	129	20	15	101	31	40	382	61
18	ILASA EAST	551	2.9	44	43	87	20	38	145	116	58	551	198

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19	OBOKUN	626	3.3	50	49	99	20	46	165	132	66	626	228
20	ORIADE	453	2.4	36	36	72	24	28	119	95	48	453	159
21	ILASA WEST	610	3.3	49	49	98	20	45	163	130	65	619	224
22	AYEDADE	658	3.5	52	52	104	20	49	173	139	69	658	240
23	AYEDIRE	445	2.3	35	35	70	20	27	117	94	47	445	156
24	EDE NORTH	692	3.6	55	54	173	20	53	182	82	73	692	150
25	EDE SOUTH	596	3.1	47	47	174	20	43	157	45	63	596	135
26	EGBEDORE	656	3.5	52	52	149	20	49	173	93	69	656	154
27	EJIGBO	521	2.7	41	41	82	20	35	137	110	55	521	136
28	IREWOLE	726	3.8	58	57	115	20	56	191	153	76	726	227
29	ISOKAN	478	2.5	38	37	75	20	30	126	101	50	478	169

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30	IWO	790	4.2	63	62	125	20	63	208	166	83	790	292
31	OLA-OLUWA	435	2.4	36	36	72	20	28	119	95	48	453	159
	TOTAL	19000	100	1345	1653	3508	918	1221	5000	3350	2000	20000	6000

OYES volunteers were massively deployed into the streets for their respective duties, the teachers Corp was later added in response to a desperate emergency.

DEPLOYMENT AREAS OF OYES IN THE STATE OF OSUN

(Culled from OYES First Anniversary Programme. Saturday 5th May, 2012)

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**APPRAISAL OF BANK'S LOAN DISBURSEMENT TO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES
IN NIGERIA AFTER BANK RECAPITALIZATION**

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, access to finance has been identified as a key element for SMEs to succeed in their drive to build productive capacity, to compete, to create jobs and to contribute to poverty alleviation in the country. Without finance, SMEs cannot acquire or absorb new technologies nor can they expand to compete in global markets or even strike business linkages with larger firms. Despite these, SMEs traditionally have faced difficulty in obtaining formal credit or equity from commercial banks. This study showed a downward trend despite recapitalisation by Nigeria commercial banks, it therefore conclude and recommend that there is more to Banks performance on stimulation of economy through SME than mere recapitalisation.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, finance has been recognised as an essential tool for promoting small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The Federal and State governments in Nigeria have recognized that for sustainable growth and development the financial empowerment of the SMEs is vital, being the repository of the predominantly poor in society. An important role of banks is to design ways of providing loans to informationally opaque small business (Berger, Klapper, and Udell 2001). However, a number of factors may affect the banking system's ability to provide credit to small borrowers in the future. There is evidence of bank consolidation across many countries of the world through mergers and acquisitions. These mega banks may be oriented towards transaction lending and providing capital markets services to large corporate clients and often less quantitative and qualitative relationship with small business. Re-capitalization of banks in Nigeria is intended among others to help mobilize domestic savings, deepening and broadening intermediation, Improve allocation of resources and helping to mobilize foreign savings.

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Credit is the largest element of risk in the books of most banks and failures in the management of credit risk, by weakening individual banks and in some cases the banking whole, have contributed, to many episodes of financial instability. An increasing amount of research on credit risk is being carried out within financial firms, central banks, regulators and universities. However, in most developing countries like Nigeria, manufacturing SMEs are operating in an environment with weak institutions for technical and financial supports (Oyeyinka, 2002). They face severe legal and regulatory constraints and little institutional support is available for them for innovation. Hence, important technical affiliations, network capacity and ownership are crucial factors in the economic performance and innovative behaviour of these industries in such an environment.

Research Problems/Purpose: Despite recapitalisation of Nigeria banking industry and consequent declaration of large profit by the banks the real sector had not really felt their impact. This paper intends to analyze the accessibility of SMEs to bank loan and to ascertain whether recapitalisation offers an effective means of solving the problem of funding small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria, and determine the relationship between Bank recapitalisation, Bank loan disbursement to SME and their contribution to GDP.

The objectives are:-

- (i) To determine the effectiveness of banks in their role as economy stimulator; and
- (ii) Whether the recapitalisation improves loan disbursement to the economic engine rooms - the SME's.

Hypothesis:-

The study will investigate and hypothesis whether increased Bank capital base can influence adequate loan facilities to SME.

Literature Review

Small businesses do not conform to any neat parameters because much of their activities depend on the industry in which they operate also the personalities and aspirations of those in charge of these businesses. These factors vary from manufacturers to retailers; and high start-ups that are funded by venture capitalists

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to self-financed tradesmen and women for the purpose of making a living. (David.S and Nicholas, 2006). Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) occupy a place of pride in virtually every country or state. SMEs have aptly been referred to as "the engine of growth" and "catalysts for socio-economic transformation of any country." SMEs represent a veritable vehicle for the achievement of national economic objectives of employment generation and poverty reduction at low investment cost as well as the development of entrepreneurial capabilities including indigenous technology. SMEs in Nigeria can be Organized and Unorganized Enterprises. The organised enterprises have paid employees with a registered office while the unorganised enterprises are mainly made up of artisans who work in open spaces, or operate in temporary wooden workshop or structures, and mostly employ low rate or no salary paid workers. The major activity involved in this sector include; soap and detergents, fabrics, textile and leather, local blacksmith, tinsmith, ceramic, clothing and tailoring, timber and winning, bricks and cement, food processing, wood furniture, beverages, bakeries, electronic assembly, agro processing, chemical based products and mechanics (Sanni 2007).

Financial systems, the world over, play fundamental roles in development and growth of the economy. The effectiveness and efficiency in performing these roles, particularly the intermediation between the surplus and deficit unit of the economy, depends largely on the level of development of the financial system. It is to ensure its soundness that the financial sector appears to be the most regulated and controlled by the government and its agencies (Ogujiuba, Ohuche, Adenuga 2004). Stiglitz and Weis (1981) observe that small and medium scale firms with opportunities to invest in positive net present value projects may be blocked from doing so because of adverse selection. Adverse selection problems arise when potential providers of external finance (banks) cannot readily verify whether the firms have access to quality projects. Nonetheless, the liquidity ratio of the financiers plays a major role. Through the new minimum capital requirement, the number of banks in the country has been successfully reduced from eighty-nine to twenty-four. They are, therefore, better placed now to meet the funding needs of their clients in SMEs. In the past, the financial intermediation role of the banks became heavily impaired while the macroeconomic activities seriously slowed down. It was against this background, that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) announced a major reform of the Nigerian banking industry. The recapitalization of the capital base of banks constituted the first phase of the reform policy in the banking sector of the Nigerian economy. Recapitalization in Nigeria comes with amendment to the existing banking laws. In July

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2004, the new governor of the CBN announced the need for banks to increase their capital base to N25 billion all banks are expected to comply by December 2005 (Adegbaju A. and Olokoyo F, 2008) with a view to provide verile banking system and support for economic growth and development.

In 2001, a study identified poor access to finance as the most critical constraint on small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. In fact, 50 percent of the surveyed enterprises received external finance while 79 percent indicated lack of financial resources as a major constraint (see Guardian. Nov, 26, 2001). The foregoing study confirms the risk-averse behaviour of banks in funding SMEs in Nigeria. Somoye & Ilo, (2009) also discussed the impact of lending on bank performance. They pointed out that the Nigerian government, through the CBN, set the lending rate for financial intermediaries at their various prevailing levels in the banking industry. To buttress their argument, they argued that the CBN set the rate to favour specific sectors in order to encourage or discourage lending to various sectors of the economy. However, the banks' desires to achieve favourable return on investment notwithstanding, the environmental factors play a vital role in banks' lending behaviour.

In recent year's banks in developed countries have launched a number of initiatives that both improve the profitability of lending to SMEs and also provide SMEs with better access to finance and to financial products that are better tailored to their needs (Aladekomo, 2003). A number of leading banks have demonstrated that providing financial services to SMEs can be turned into a highly profitable business. Although the business environments in developing countries and developed countries differ in many respects, the problems of servicing SME customers are similar, namely high-perceived risk, problems with information asymmetry and high administrative costs. Therefore, recent innovations in developed countries to improve SMEs access to credit can provide valuable insights for developing country banks to become more SME-oriented and to increase the volume and the quality of their services to this sector. Economic growth indices in Nigeria reflect the effective production capacities of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) not only on how they are funded, but the practical utilization of their operational philosophy and how this is integrated towards service delivery and uplifting society. As a result, several microlending institutions were established to enhance the development of SMES. Such micro credit institutions include the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), National Economic Reconstruction Fund (Nerfund), the Nigeria Agricultural and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB), the Microfinance Bank (MFB), and the Nigerian Export and Import Bank (NEXIM), and the liberalization of the banking sector. Howbeit, up till 2005 the number of

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banks operating in the country is about 89 with more than 50% having capital base of less than US\$10 million and about 3,300 branches. This compared to 8 banks in South Korea with about 4,500 branches or bank in South Africa with larger assets than all the 89 banks shows that the banking system is very marginal relative to its potentials and in comparism with other countries.(Ogujiuba, Ohuche, Adenuga 2004). Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), of whatever configuration, are an asset in the production chain of any economy, because of their impact on issues of job creation, provision of a wide variety of good services, income generation and efficient sources for micro – financing.

Despite their proactive nature, growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), have been lighted, because of inadequate access to finance, production schedules and marketing. This undoubtedly is a reflection of the changes in the monetary policies of our Nation. The comfort is that the governments (local, state and federal) are neither relenting nor giving up in their bid to revamp and invigorate the fortunes of SMEs as to enable them play the expected role in Nigeria's economic growth and development. This is evidenced by the government's recent establishment of as well as the mandate given to the Bank of Industry (BOI) and the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), the facilitation of the Bankers' Committee's institutionalisation of the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS), the federal government's drive and focus on realizing the objective of NEPAD, the government's endorsement and support of multilateral agencies and loans, and the government's backing of international development finance facilities such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) facilities and the likes. Given the crucial role SMEs play in the industrial and economic growth and development of developing countries like Nigeria, the various governments in Nigeria cannot afford to relax in their efforts towards making the SME subsector very vibrant and productive(Onugu,2005).

SMEs Experience in Accessing Financial Resources

Due to the inability of SME's to raise their own finance and access financial services from formal sources (UNCTAD, 2001). This category of SMEs usually look to the banking sector and other financial intermediaries for instruments to finance working capital and to provide credit for short-term liquidity management. However, they often fail to access the financial resources in the required amounts because banks evaluate them on the basis of a checklist, as listed below:

- ✓ Audited finance statement for the last three years including management accounts;

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- ✓ Project proposal highlighting strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats;
- ✓ Financial projectors;
- ✓ Monitoring costs;
- ✓ Credit or default risk because of the problem of information asymmetry;
- ✓ Enforcement costs.

Unfortunately, financial and accounting records are rarely in place, and where they are available, their accuracy is usually doubted. In instances where bank financing is provided, it is in most cases in amounts that are insufficient and at a high cost in relation to the term to maturity of loans they also apply simple and relatively backward technology in production and, therefore, the quality of their products are usually poor. There is a general lack of professionalism within this category of SMEs in terms of strategic planning procedures, decision-making processes and business planning, and management in general(Kasekende,2001).

Banks Position in Financing SMEs

Consequently, commercial banks and investors have been reluctant to service SMEs because:- (1) SMEs are regarded by creditors and investors as high-risk borrowers due to insufficient assets and low capitalization, vulnerability to market fluctuations and high mortality rates; (2) Information asymmetry arising from SMEs' lack of accounting records, inadequate financial statements or business plans makes it difficult for creditors and investors to assess the creditworthiness of potential SME proposals and (3) High administrative/transaction costs of lending or investing small amounts do not make SME financing a profitable business.

The absence of collateral or foolproof steps for its enforcement warrants special mention since it has been an important factor-inhibiting bank lending to SMEs particularly as banks do not just rely on their borrowers' past financial statements or projected earnings as the bases for their credit decisions. As a result, commercial banks are generally biased toward large corporate borrowers, who provide better business plans, have credit ratings, more reliable financial information, better chances of success and higher profitability for the banks. When banks do lend to SMEs, they tend to charge them a commission

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for assuming risk and apply tougher screening measures, which drives up costs on all sides.

Research Methodology

For the purpose of determining the relationship between Bank loan to the SMEs and its impact on the general economic development, secondary data was sourced from CBN statistical bulletin on: (i) Total Commercial Bank Loan, (ii) Loan to SMEs; and Gross Domestic Product (at current price). These are presented in Tables I & II i.e from 2000 to 2009 and the percentage composition in the pre-recapitalisation era was compared to post-recapitalisation era.

Ratio of Loans to SME's by Commercial Banks (₦)

Table 1: Pre-Recapitalization

Period	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs	Total Commercial Banks Loans	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs as %tage of Total Credit	GDP	%tage Growth of GDP
2000	44.54	508.30	8.76	4582	-
2001	52.43	796.16	6.59	4725	0.03
2002	82.37	954.63	8.63	6912	0.32
2003	90.18	1210.03	7.45	8487	0.19
2004	55.00	1519.24	3.62	11411	0.26

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin

Table II: Post-Recapitalization

Period	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs	Total Commercial Banks Loans	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs as %tage of Total Credit	GDP	%tage Growth of GDP
	Enterprises (N' Million)	(N' Million)	% of Total Credit		

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2005	50,67	1,899.35	2.67	14572	0.22
2006	25,71	2,524.30	1.02	18566	0.22
2007	41,10	4,813.49	0.85	20657	0.10
2008	76.56	27,568.41	2.7	24296	0.15
2009	63.30	35167.20	0.72	24712	0.02

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

A study of the figures in Table 1 and 11 i.e. pre and post recapitalisation periods respectively showed that though the volume of total credit and loan disbursement to SMEs improved tremendously in the post recapitalisation era as expected but that is in absolute figure when relatively of loan to SME to total credit is factored in percentages, loan disbursement to SMEs in the pre recapitalisation era is better. Highest proportion was 3.62% in pre-recapitalisation.

There was increase in GDP in the post-recapitalisation era, but given the proportion of loan disbursement to SMEs (i.e. lack of fund) how much of this increase in GDP could be attributable to the contribution of SMEs. (economic growth engine) Very small! Amazingly, the GDP itself is growing but the percentage growth is falling, more so after recapitalisation, which means money is not flowing to where it is needed for real economic growth.

The results above confirmed the risk-averse behaviour of banks in funding SMEs in Nigeria after the recapitalisation. The analysis of the access to credit market for small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria has established two important facts: (i) macroeconomic instability and uncertainty in the business environment has forced banks to lend short to SMEs; (ii) such overdrafts and short term loans are made available at high interest rates of over 26% and they are also relatively heavily collateralised. In a situation in which SMEs are mainly dependent on bank loans, this situation could be dangerous. The implication is that many SMEs do not have access to bank loans with grave implications for their growth and general economic development.

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Despite efforts to encourage adequate fund flow to SMEs, the result has not been enthusiastic; the margin of loan to SMEs during post consolidation era is falling, i.e the economic engine house is grinding down. The growth in GDP could be concluded to be majorly a contribution of trading and services sectors and not manufacturing or real sector (SMEs) where the bank could have concentrated after such a good recapitalisation outing.

The Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS)

The Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme facilitated by the CBN, was initiated by the Bankers' Committee (all the banks in Nigeria) as another means to funding small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. The scheme requires all banks to set aside 10 percent of their profit before tax annually for equity investment in small and medium enterprises. The scheme is to promote indigenous entrepreneurship, develop local technology, generate employment, facilitate the flow of funds from banks for the establishment of new, viable SMEs, ensure output expansion, re-distribute incomes and promote industrial linkages. The Scheme involves equity participation of banks in enterprises that they have appraised to be viable. The banks partner with the entrepreneurs for social and economic development.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Recapitalisation has in no way persuade banks to lend more to SMEs, if anything the bank are cost and risk implication conscious hence money seems to be flung elsewhere, perhaps where they can generate return quickly without minding the consequence on real sector growth it therefore behoves the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have to improve their management systems and adopt modern management techniques if they are to benefit from the opportunities offered by the formal sector. They need to improve their financial records and accounting systems. Proper records need to be kept and maintained and the books of accounts have to be clear and should reflect a realistic picture of their operations and financial conditions. A good system and books of accounts are not only helpful to the banks; they are also crucial in managing and monitoring business as well as guiding tax authorities.

Well-functioning and sustainable mechanisms for SME financing require institution building and a market approach. Lending institutions must improve their ability to provide financial services to SMEs through commercial

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mechanisms that lower costs and minimize their risk exposure. Only in this way will financial institutions find SME lending to be more profitable, and thus be encouraged to construct lending programmes targeted at SMEs.

Part of the reluctance of banks to lend to SMEs is the banks' inability to properly evaluate the position of SMEs because of the lack of reliable financial information. Banks and regulatory authorities at times demand more information than what is publicly made available or required. In addition financial analysts, rating agencies or business intelligence providers can generate additional information, which is available to creditors and investors, at additional cost.

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PRACTICAL APPROACH TO (FINANCIAL) RESOURCEFULNESS: A NECESSITY FOR SUSTAINABLE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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KEYWORDS: Education, Public Institutions, Government, Universities in Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Education is an expensive social service and requires adequate financial provision from all tiers of Government for a successful implementation of the educational programmes. However, the situations in Public Institutions signify continual inadequate fundings from the Government. The ongoing industrial action embarked upon by the Academic Staff Union of Universities in Nigeria is a typical effect of the inadequacy. Nevertheless, the educational institutions on their own can bring about some positive changes through financial resourcefulness. The study was designed to figure out the pragmatic approaches needed for sound management and strategic entrepreneurship, researching and leveraging that would lead the institutions into financial adequacy. The study intends to bring out the right orientation towards our academic researches and prescribe a reasonable approach that is adaptable to the Business Model Innovation defined by Henry Chesbrough and Richard S. Rosembloom from Harvard Business School. The effect of the model is that researches would be information-based, and oriented towards the addressing the nagging societal needs, producing things of value which may lead to financial resourcefulness.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an expensive social service and requires financial provision from all tiers of Government for a successful implementation of the educational programs. (National Policy on Education [NPE], 1977). Even though this statement is clearly written in the document of the Nigerian national Policy of Education, the poor funding of schools and institutions today is a clear evidence of its poor implementation. Dilapidated conditions of public schools, shortage of teachers, poorly-equipped libraries, bad roads and infrastructures, delays in the payment of teachers' salaries and allowances. The incessant industrial strikes embarked upon by the teachers' associations are direct reactions to their poor working conditions. If the Government of a nation cannot properly harness her resources to finance education then it is a big challenge to the owners of private institutions to ensure that they do not fall into such a mistake.

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Parents want to see good teachers – highly trained teachers, Good Hostels, and facilities, and good infrastructure, beautiful environment conducive for learning. For a University not to lose her credibility these items must not just be provided but should be maintained and sustained. Since education is a dynamic process, her monetary affairs should not be hampered by any factor because any shortage or mismanagement of such would make the University to lose its essence and credibility.

Nigeria as a nation is slow in terms of development. We don't have good roads and infrastructure, poor in science and technology and we have very poor economic power. These factors militate against the smooth running of educational system in the country. Education is expensive, bad economy is additional burden!

Now, education is expensive and it has to be provided for. This calls for financial resourcefulness on the part of educational stakeholders. The work cannot be done by the stake holders alone, the teachers have to rise to the task. All avenues of providing money for education should be explored. Money is needed to train and retrain teachers, to buy materials and equipment, to furnish laboratories and workshops, to expand the scope of existing programmes, to create new programmes and generally to supply the day-to-day needs of an institution.

Nigeria's poor economy, coupled with marketing competitiveness among private institutions would not make the tuition fees to be enough as the only source of financing Higher Institutions. Therefore, the school managements need to combine both the intellectual and tangible resources of the institution to buoy the system out of debilitating poverty. Her pecuniary resources, her intellectual acumens, her corporate rights and privileges need to be channeled towards fruitfulness and growth.

By carefully studying the Nigerian economic system, looking for the challenges, the factors that pose as impediments to its growth, the abandoned or neglected actions/policies that would have made the country rich economically, the pitfalls to avoid, the areas that need fortification; we can easily establish a strong economic system that will be sustainable.

1.1 Facts That You Need To Know about the Nigerian Economy

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- Nigerian Population - 169 millions.
- 70% of the population lives in poverty.
- Nearly 61 percent of the population or about 100 million people live on less than \$1 a day.
- About 35 millions youth are jobless.
- Second highest rate of maternal mortality in the world - WHO
- 90% of the Raw materials used are imported
- Nigeria is Oil-rich.
- Ravaged in Political turmoil and Corruption.
- About 120 million of the population don't have access to electricity

1.2 Financial Resourcefulness

What is Financial Resourcefulness?

- **Financial:**- Pecuniary resources (monetary affairs);
- **Resourcefulness:** - Fertility in expedients; Skill or ingenuity in meeting any situation.
- **Financial Resourcefulness** can be defined as making skillful use of our funds, revenue, income, intellect, power, strength and position in such a way that will bring multiplication of wealth and progress.

Why Financial Resourcefulness in Higher Institutions?

- High interest rates.
- High cost of materials/facilities.
- Expansion.
- Meeting Competitive challenge among other Universities.
- Reformation and Transformation.
- Preparation for sophisticated investments.
- Privatization and Concessioning.
- Financial back-up in form of Reserve.

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What Financial resourcefulness is NOT!

- Not by receiving Foreign aids.
- Not donation(s) from philanthropist(s).
- Not submission of papers to international or local journals.
- Not tuition fees – other institutions have tuition fees as well.
- Not by spending many hours in the laboratory.
- Not personal achievements or compliments.

1.3 **Philosophy of Nigerian Education**

Financial resourcefulness is attainable if we can go back to the landmark which the Nigerian pioneers of educational system had made. This landmark is evident in the five main national objectives as they are itemized in the philosophy of Nigerian Education. Nigerian Education is to be for the building of;

- 1) a free and democratic society;
- 2) a just and egalitarian society;
- 3) a united, strong and self-reliant nation;
- 4) a great and dynamic economy;
- 5) a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens.

(NPE, 1977)

The last three (3) objectives are the factors that bring financial resourcefulness because they indirectly bring about job creation and wealth generation. When these objectives are achieved we will have a country with stable and dynamic economy. Wealth generation does not come directly but it comes when we meet the societal needs.

‘Wealth, like happiness is never attained when sought after directly. It always comes as a by-product of providing a useful service’ – Henry Ford.

University education is meant for national development through researching in the areas that the society need. This is clearly written in the NPE (1977) section 5 No. 35: “If university research is to assist national development, it should be relevant to the nation’s development goals. To ensure this relevance:

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- (a) Government will direct the National Universities Commission, the National Educational Research Council, and other appropriate bodies to identify the areas of need and priority. Universities can base their research programs on these.
- (b) Government will support closer links between the universities, industry and the various Research Councils.
- (c) Government will encourage locally-based industries to develop direct links with research institutes and universities to facilitate research into their products and problems.
- (d) Universities will be required to keep both government and industry better informed about their research results.
- (e) Government will ensure effective utilization of the results of universities' research and promising research results which at first look unprofitable but are likely to pay off in the long run will be taken up and developed by government.

University → **Research** → **Industry** → **Production**
 ← ← ←

University education is meant to practically tackle the societal needs by recommending research-based solutions to the government for execution. What this will normally lead to are;

- Rise in the number of the university patents.
- Creation of spin-out factories.
- Recognition of the university as a high-ranking institution.
- Financial enrichment.
- Increased level of cooperation and collaboration with other companies/universities of related achievements in form of MOU.

The financial resourcefulness of a university depends much on how seriously the management of the institution is ready to apply the intellectuality and the technicality of the institution to solve the societal/community needs. If our researches are not relevant to the community need, we should bury such because the community would neither recognize it nor buy it.

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1.4 Research, Innovation and University System

For a university to be financially resourceful, it is not enough for researchers to approach research in the old manners of going to the laboratory to perform experiment with the mind that sometimes in the future useful products might come out of them. This linear or supply-push approach to innovation is well past its sell-by date. The scientific researches truly bring to light certain facts that are explained in empirical forms but they do not lead to a wholesome innovation. This may probably be because the long-hour stays in the laboratory is out of mere curiosity – curiosity of finding new things. If we are to continue with this approach and expect all industrial ideas to come directly from universities, we would not even have the tin-opener.

The linear model approach to innovation had been used by the past scientists – laws of motion was discovered by Isaac Newton but there is a complex interchange between laws of motion and creation of automobiles. There is a complex interchange between Faraday's laws of electricity and the creation of electric generator. Likewise there is a complex interchange between Maxwell's equations of electromagnetism and the discovery of radio. In fact most of the discoveries were made by enthusiastic amateurs like D.E. Hughes and Thomas Edison who are just interested in finding solutions to human needs. In Nigerian universities, we have many researchers boasting of having written many papers but we have very few innovators. We have to take note of this; Researches gulp money, innovations refund money; researching on its own do not create jobs, innovation does; research do not generate wealth, innovation does; research do not raise the Gross Domestic product of a nation, innovation does. In fact, it is through innovation that we can put our raw materials into effective usage for manufacturing.

Nigerian educational system had over-stayed on the linear approach to innovation to the extent that the nation is being overwhelmed by bursting challenges such as lack of employment, poverty, slowness of economic development, lack of indigenous technology, and so on. Nigeria has to be delivered out of the shackles of poverty and the universities have important roles to play. We should know that the funding agencies of various researches would expect result in form of wealth creation. By following this linear approach to innovation we would not be able to meet up with this challenge or if at all, it would be on timescales longer than that of the relevant product. Most of the funding agencies are from the developed

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nations – USA, UK and ASIA. These countries also adopt linear model to innovation which definitely will not yield any immediate result but their consolation is that at least they have vast numbers of innovations that they sell within and also exported to other countries and so they have robust economies, and science and innovation to them is yielding dividends.

Every country has its own peculiarities. Nigerian researchers should not continue with their long-hour stays on Lab benches trying to find out problem that yet, not exist or remote when there are nagging or debilitating issues at hand. They should train their faculties to be innovative as well. Their analytic approach to education should be synchronized with creative intelligence. That is the essence of university education and that is the only way financial resourcefulness can be achieved.

This does not mean that we are relegating the conventional model of researching. Of course, a university campus is a great place to garner new ideas, if you have run out of them yourself. Certainly, when you have built something bigger, more powerful than you have ever done before and it does not work, it is a great place to find the scholarship that will tell you where you went wrong. But this is all part of the university's vital role in thriving modern industrial economy. However industrial ideas (innovations) should come from our universities too. What we need is an understanding of the real value of both the seasoning of academic scientific creativity in industrial innovation and the ability to call on a university's specialist expertise with ease. This requires that the universities adopt funding strategies of meeting the needs of the society in a new, changed or different ways. This method is far more effective than the one many of us have at present; it is referred to by business schools as the 21st century innovation game.

Universities should channel investments not to where immediate highest short-term profit could be maximized, but where investment is needed for long-term robust and sustainable job-driven growth could be expected. Not seeking short-term highest return on investment, but long-term university monitored economic approach.

1.4.1 Why Must We Not Settle for a Low Key Investment?

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Nigeria is a developing country and although her economic growth rate had been slow, the developed world had recently discovered that it is a promising land. Countries like US and China are interested in the country, more importantly after the economic crash of 2008. They have seen Nigeria as one of the emerging markets where they can invest at low interest rate and harvest bountifully at high margins. These countries are wealthier and more advanced in technology and so, they can produce in large quantities. Why should they take the glory of production alone?

1.4.2 Why are the advanced countries interested in Nigeria?

- Nigeria is blessed with mineral resources.
- We are not technologically advanced.
- We have comparatively very large population (cheap labour is available) (about 169 million).
- Most of our resources are been exported for manufacturing.
- Nigeria market is an emerging market not yet subject to the rules of the advanced markets; hence they see it as centre for competitiveness.
- Nigeria is at the verge of transition from developing country to a civilized country. In fact they knew that our slowness of advancement is as a result of poor leadership and not because we did not have the potentials.

Globalization would bring advancement to the country in the next 15 years, technology will be transferred in the country (majorly for profit making) and the indigenous companies and institutions need to measure up to the standard.

The Universities need to take businesses beyond the border of 'Let us survive' to the level of the national development. The country is full of business opportunities, it only requires discernments of sound entrepreneurs to identify the areas of needs and recommend to the University for researching and leveraging. The University has the advantage of deploying intellectuals of various expertises to examine critically the proposed areas, authenticate the values of the areas proposed, identifies the customers, devised the cost of production and develop strong capacity for take-off. This method is referred to as Business Model Innovation and it has been recommended as 21st Century innovation game.

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1.5 Business Model Innovation

Business model innovation is the creation, reinvention or enhancement of a business model (describes the logic and principles that a firm uses to generate revenue) so that it satisfies customer needs (values proposition) in a new, changed or different way.

Henry Chesbrough and Richard S. Rosenbloom from Harvard Business School put forward an excellent definition for a business model innovation.

“The functions of a business model are to;

- Articulate the value proposition, that is, the value created for users by the offering based on the technology;
- Identify a market segment, that is, the users to whom the technology is useful and for what purpose;
- Define the structure of the value chain within the firm required to create and distribute the offering;
- Estimate the cost structure and profit potential of producing the offering, given the value proposition and value chain structure chosen;
- Describe the position of the firm within the value network linking suppliers and customers mentors and competitors;
- Formulate the competitive strategy by which the innovating firm will gain and hold advantage over rivals.

This approach is a nimble approach to innovation and it can be adapted to any business anywhere in the world.

The flow chart for the Business Model Innovation as designed by Alex Osterwalder is shown below.

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Flow Chart For Business Model Innovation

Fig. 1. Business Model Innovation

The Business Model Innovation attaches much importance to the **value** that the company wants to create. The value is to be determined by joint efforts of **interdisciplinary partners** forming a network. This partner network must comprise of highly informed economists, sound entrepreneurs, scientific researchers and legal advisers. They are to develop the value proposals as they would be presented to the **targeted customer** (presentation is better done by the marketers). The objective of the marketer is to make the **potential customer** know the value in terms of comparative advantage derivable from patronizing the company.

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The partner network form the major man-power resources of the company, they are to formulate the facilities and the materials needed for creating the product that would measure up to the standard of value planned. The entire cost of procuring facilities/equipments, of providing network of interdisciplinary experts so as to get the product of equivalent value is the **cost structure**.

The mutual understanding between the company and the customer will bring about patronization that is backed up with legal agreement. This relationship is to bring **Revenue Streams** to the company.

The Cost Structure and the Revenue Streams makes it easy for the company to do self-evaluation.

Revenue - Cost of Production = Profit/Loss

If it is positive it is success.

If it is negative it is failure.

However, profit or loss should not be based on the returns from the single transaction as the facilities continually would produce virtually an unending result!

1.5.1 Practical Application/Adaptability of Business Model Innovation to Business Demand

The CEO of Fan Milk Plc lamented that Nigeria, after 50 years of independence could not supply his company with Cow Milk to the extent that the company has to continually spend money to import this material from Brazil. He further said that it takes 300,000 diary cows to produce the milk that his company requires continually and regularly. He then wondered why Nigeria is enriching other countries and left herself fallowed. In conclusion, he said and I quote, “What Nigeria needs to do is to leverage on the areas where she has competitive advantages and stop unnecessary imitation of foreign countries”.

To a University that wants to be financially resourceful, the statement from the CEO above is a mine of information and the required innovation of providing raw cow milk is adaptable to the Business Model above.

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Partner Network: Students in the faculty of Agriculture particularly the Animal Science Students, Researchers from this field, Expert on the field, Economists' crew, Entrepreneurs, Legal Practitioners and as many others as the service may require.

Core Capacities: Calves for nurturing and experimentation, Facilities (Physical) for researching and experimentation, Landed Properties, Dairy Cows, Human Resources

Value Configuration: Production of raw milk from within the country, Relief from Importation of raw milk at high expense rate, Accessibility of raw milk by the company.

Cost structure: To be determined by the partner network in a progressive manner

Customer relationship: To be designed by the marketers (Business Administrators) and Legal Personnel.

Targeted Customers: Fan Milk PLC, Ibadan. Oyo, Nigeria, Eleyele Industrial Layout, P. O. Box 1617

Distribution Channels: To be determined by the Partner network e.g. by Self-delivery

Success/Failure: Self-evaluation

Value Proposition: Proposals to be made by the marketing body of the Partner network.

Revenue Streams: From the customer to the producer.

When a University embarks on a project like this successfully, she has succeeded in solving one of the problems in the country and therefore contributed to national development. As a consequence, the University would be financially enriched. This is just an example out of many. There are hundreds of raw materials that are being imported from foreign countries when in actual fact; they can be made available within. Prof. Peter Onwualu, the Director-General of the Raw Materials Research and Development Council (RMRDC) has confirmed that 90% of the raw materials used in the country were imported by

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manufacturers. One of the ways of raising the GDP of the country is by reducing substantially the volume of imported raw materials.

Onwualu said the reduction in the importation of raw materials would lead to the creation of jobs as well as the generation of wealth within the economy. He said that it would also improve the standard of living in the country. According to him, when such raw materials are harnessed, new processing industries will come up and new products will come into the market to help the people to make more money (Manufacturers Association of Nigeria [MAN], 2012).

Summary

Educational system of which university education is of paramount importance is the subject of national development. University education is meant for changing the community for the better by providing continuously, adequate manpower resources through proper training and researching. However, if this will be successful, there should be adequate funding for sustainability and growth. Therefore, University system needs to adopt Business Model of Innovation so as to produce those things that are marketable and relevant to the national development. This model therefore, requires co-operations and collaborations among experts of various endeavour: academic, professional, skilled, semi-skilled and the unskilled for singularity purpose of raising the economic growth of the nation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The Office of the Development and Strategy should document the Industries in the country with raw materials they import and where they are imported from so as to make presentation to the Partner Network.
- The University should establish Innovation and Entrepreneurship Group.
- There should be a policy that upholds continuity of projects even after the incumbent administration has left for sustainable development
- There should be incentives for scientific researchers that procure solutions to the nagging needs of our immediate environment/Community most especially in the area of economic development.

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TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS

AN EXPLORATION OF THE CRITICAL METHODS FOR IMPROVING DESIGN STAGE COST ESTIMATES OF BUILDING PROJECTS: A THEORETICAL LITERATURE-BASED STUDY

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KEYWORDS: Design stage cost estimate, factors, methods, budgetary tool, cost certainty

ABSTRACT

Accuracy of early cost estimates is a major concern for clients and cost engineers. Several researchers have long expressed their concern about cost estimating inaccuracies by recognising that the accuracy achieved in cost estimating has been less than desirable. The essence of having accurate design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool is defeated if the factors that affect design stage cost estimating accuracy and the critical methods for improving the subject are not given adequate consideration in the estimation process. Hence, project objectives regarding cost, time and quality targets are threatened. This paper first identifies various factors affecting design stage cost estimating accuracy in construction practice. Also, it provides a review of the influencing methods for improving design stage cost estimating accuracy of building projects by demonstrating the theoretical context. The study is a literature-based theoretical exploration, and a preliminary part of an on-going doctoral research on the budgetary reliability of design stage elemental cost plan aimed at assessing the risk impacts on the variability between design stage elemental cost plan and tender sum. The outcome of the doctoral research will provide the platform at exploring causes of variability with a view to developing a predictive model which will help construction industry practitioners in New Zealand in coming up with a reliable and objective elemental cost plan that guarantees cost certainty. This particular study is a first step towards a comprehensive empirical research of securing design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool that guarantees cost certainty for building projects.

INTRODUCTION

The reliability of final tender sums depends on the accurate projections of baseline cost estimates developed at the design development stage of project development. However no matter how much care and effort is put into the preparation of design stage cost estimates, significant deviations are usually observed between these cost estimates and the final tender sum. This makes accurate predictions challenging for construction industry practitioners. The major attributable factors for the variability between the design

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stage cost estimate and final tender sum are risk elements that are inherent in construction project developments.

(Odeyinka et al., 2010) explained that the budgeted cost established at the pre-contract stage forms the basis of the final tender sum otherwise known as the contract sum, and this is the amount arrived at for the entire project. (Potts, 2008) suggested that most clients work within tight pre-defined budgets which are usually part of a larger overall scheme. If a budget or design cost estimate is exceeded, the whole scheme may fail. Pre-contract estimating produces the original budget and this forecasts the likely expenditure for the client. (Odeyinka et al., 2012) submitted that this budget should be used positively to make sure that the design stays within the scope of the original scheme. Moreover, from a pre-tender view, it can be justifiably concluded that design stage cost estimate anticipates and predicts final tender sum. Thus, budgetary reliability or performance depends on the degree of variability between the design stage cost estimate prepared by the quantity surveyor and final tender sums submitted by the contracting firms. Similarly, it is concluded further that the observable deviation between the design stage cost estimate and final tender sum is due to the factors which are not only hard to predict but also difficult to manage. Hence, many budget overruns are due to circumstances observed as factors affecting the design stage cost estimating accuracy and an important issue is the ability to predict such factors and the impact they have on the project (Odeyinka et al., 2010). The concern of this research is to identify various factors responsible for the variability between the design stage cost estimate and final tender sum. Also, the conjecture of the study is to examine the critical methods for improving the design stage cost estimating accuracy of building projects.

The overall aim of this study is to signify the design stage cost estimating as a function of those factors that affect its accuracy in the estimation process, with a view to providing a review of the influencing methods for improving design stage cost estimating accuracy of building projects by demonstrating the theoretical context. This paper is intended as a preliminary literature review, prior to full research project aimed at developing a predictive model that will assist construction industry practitioners to have a better and reliable prediction of a final tender sum of building project from the design stage cost estimate.

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Design Stage Cost Estimating

Traditional construction management practice divides the project procurement process into two: (1) the design phase, and (2) the construction phase. Cost estimating has tended to follow, very closely, this division (Ogunlana, 1989). However, it is pertinent to strengthen this division with conceptual planning phase which practically precedes these two foregoing phases whereby conceptual cost estimating is performed under inadequate information circumstances and incomplete work scope definition meant for crucial project decisions like funding approval. This contribution was further strengthened and opined in (Liu & Zhu, 2007) that a typical project under conventional procurement system can be divided into five stages: (1) the conceptual stage, (2) the design stage, (3) the tender stage, (4) the pre-construction stage, and (5) the build stage. According to them, specifically at the design stage, estimates start with preliminary estimates; cost estimates are continuously adjusted as design evolves; as design progresses, more detailed estimates are produced. The main objective for cost estimation here is evaluating the design feasibility within budget constraints.

Design stage cost estimating has significant relevance to design stage cost planning as both sit between the conceptual planning phase and tender action phase of development process, hence both are performed between the outline proposal / scheme design stage and detailed design / tender action stage in accordance with RIBA Plan of work specified in (Kirkham, 2007). Design stage cost estimating is the principal responsibility of the client's cost consultant: the quantity surveyor (for building projects) or the design engineer (for civil engineering works) (Ogunlana, 1989) in contrast to a definition credited to the *Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors 2006* that a Quantity Surveyor is an expert professionally trained and experienced in the financial management of construction schemes regarding building, civil and heavy industrial engineering works, respecting the schemes in prospect and work in progress.

At this point, it is extremely significant to consider design stage cost estimation as a function closely intertwined with the design process as reported in Oyediran (1992) cited in (Adafin, 2000). The building design process is a complex interaction of skills, judgement, knowledge, information and time, which has as its objective the satisfaction of the client's brief (Kirkham, 2007) or demand for shelter within the overall needs of the society. The quantity surveyor, as a member of the design team is charged with

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providing information on costs so that the designers could know the cost implications of their decisions. Hence, according to Oyediran (1992) cited in (Adafin, 2000) there is therefore the need for integration of cost information and design variables; this calls for a team approach in building design and the adoption of the *Royal Institute of British Architects' (RIBA) Plan of work* for project development. However, (Ogunlana, 1989) stressed that the design team is not constrained to conform rigidly to the plan of work in practice. Meanwhile, the RIBA Plan of work is therefore devised to take cognizance of this team approach. Also, the plan of work is a systematized procedure for taking design decisions with accompanying data to be incorporated at various stages of the design evolution (Oyediran, 1992 cited in Adafin, 2000); this clearly reflects chronological development of project and the way in which the design stage estimates relate to the plan of work and cost planning process as reported in (Seeley, 1996) and (Kirkham, 2007) meant for design team operation as stated below:

- Briefing: this comprises inception and feasibility stages;
- Sketch plan: also comprises outline proposals and scheme design stages;
- Working drawings: this involves (i) detailed design stage, (ii) production information stage, (iii) bills of quantities stage, (iv) tender action stage
- Site operation: this constitutes (i) project planning stage, (ii) operation on site stage, (iii) completion, and (iv) feedback

The conclusion drawn from this submission indicates that design stage cost estimate shares similar meaning with conceptual cost estimate except that the former takes place at various stages of design process, commencing from outline proposal to detailed design stage of development process. While the latter takes place at the early or conceptual planning stage of project development and is undertaken by the cost consultant. Therefore, design stage cost estimate is a forecast of the probable cost of a proposed building project and is produced only when some level of design information and project scope definition is available during the design stage, but tender documents are not available. The traditional estimating methods such as (1) functional unit, (2) superficial, (3) cube, (4) elemental cost analysis, (5) approximate quantities, (6) elemental estimating, (7) storey-enclosure, and (8) interpolation as documented in (Haron et al., 2001; Soutos & Lowe, 2005) cannot adequately deal with risk, and in trying to aid this area, several techniques of cost modelling such as (1) regression analysis, (2) montecarlo simulation, and (3) neural

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networks, were among those cost estimation techniques developed and integrated for conceptual and design stage cost estimation which utilize the latest advancement in science and technology (Sonmez, 2004; Soutos & Lowe, 2005). Meanwhile, contractors are only engaged in tender-based cost estimating, likewise the cost consultant at tender action stage as soon as the tendering process is set in motion.

Accuracy in Design Stage Cost Estimating

The view in construction management literature is that the accuracy of estimates should improve as design progresses. Thus, the estimator has more information on which to base predictions and project is better defined than at the early stages of design (Ogunlana, 1989). Ideally, the study in this section should reflect precisely cost estimating at detailed design stage of project development as this clearly demonstrates improvements by showing less values of error than at the previous conceptual and scheme design stages. Also, detailed design stage reflects the stage at which cost checking confirms full cost plan produced by the quantity surveyor, hence final cost plan at this stage could be compared with the final tender sum or contract sum.

With reference to Morrison (1984), (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) defined accuracy of quantity surveyors' estimates as the deviation from the lowest acceptable tender received in competition for a project. Following (Lee et al., 2011) the accuracy of a design stage cost estimate can equally be defined as the difference between the actual cost and design cost estimate; the actual cost being the contract sum, while the design cost estimate represents the cost estimate prepared specifically at detailed design stage of project development, and can be measured by the error rate calculated from Equation (1):

$$\text{Error rate (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Actual Cost} - \text{Design Cost Estimate}}{\text{Actual Cost}} \right) \times 100.$$

According to (Barzandeh, 2011) the accuracy of a design stage cost estimate can be assessed in different ways depending on whether the figure for comparison is the tender, end product or final account. It is the degree to which a measurement or calculation deviates from its actual cost; therefore, estimating accuracy is an indication of the degree to which the final account or contract sum of a project may vary from the single point value used as the design stage cost estimate of the project. (Oladokun et al., 2011) evaluated

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estimating accuracy in terms of biases in estimates (error level) and measures of consistency (the degree of variation). They analysed data from 82 building projects in Nigeria. Prepared design cost estimates (QSEs) and contract sums (CSs) of the projects were obtained from the database of the quantity surveying firm (source of the data). The data also included project type, sectors from which the projects emanated, and year of estimates/awards. The deviation of design cost estimates from contract sums (estimate bias “Error”) was calculated in percentage form using the formula below:

$$\text{Estimate bias (Error)} = \frac{(QSEs - CSs) \times 100}{CS} \quad (1)$$

Positive value of Estimate bias/Error (%) indicates overestimation of cost for QSEs while negative value implies an underestimation of cost for QSEs. Also, the consistency in the estimate was determined by calculating the coefficient of variation (CV) for all building projects in different categories using the following formula (Aibinu et al., 2011; ; Aibinu & Pasco, 2008; Oladokun et al., 2011):

$$CV = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation} \times 100}{\text{Mean Error}} \quad (2)$$

Ideally, in purely deterministic world Skitmore and Picken (2000) concluded that costing the construction implication of design decisions is supposed to be accurate, taking into consideration the effects of time for completion, construction quality, and resale or letting values. However, this is not so in practical situation as noted in (Aibinu et al., 2011; Aibinu & Pasco, 2008; Oladokun et al., 2011; ; Pasco & Aibinu, 2008) because estimates are often prepared within a limited time-frame and without the aid of a finalised project design. Meanwhile, (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) opined that design stage cost estimating is usually carried out by consultant quantity surveyor on behalf of his client and is an attempt to forecast contractor’s tender sum before the design is finalized or before tenders are received. It is therefore important that estimates have to be as accurate as possible since they form the basis for tender comparison or negotiation, and underestimation may lead to difficulty in award decisions, or in some cases unrealistic negotiation

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targets. To this end, they further maintained that Quantity Surveyors are tasked to improve on the accuracy of their design stage cost estimates in order to ensure clients' satisfaction.

Factors Affecting the Accuracy of Design Stage Cost Estimating

Accuracy of early cost estimates is a major concern for clients and cost engineers. Though, several researchers have long expressed their concern about cost estimating inaccuracies by recognising that the accuracy achieved in cost estimating has been less than desirable (Ashworth and Skitmore, 1983; Ogunlana and Thorpe, 1987) cited in (Jafarzadeh, 2012). The essence of having accurate design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool is defeated if risk estimates are not incorporated or not properly evaluated if incorporated. Hence, project objectives regarding cost, time and quality targets are threatened as contingency is proportional to the risk present in a construction project.

In contrast to CIOB (1997) that the definition of construction cost estimating is the technical process of predicting costs of construction; Ashworth and Skitmore (1983) argued, as revealed in (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) that cost estimating cannot be a precise technical and analytical process but is, to an extent, a subjective process. This argument as viewed by (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) tends to suggest that estimators consider factors relevant to the successful execution of a project. Most important factors affecting contractors' cost estimate according to (Enshassi et al., 2005) in their case study, are: client's financial status, type of current contractor workload and project location. In addition, based on Akintoye's (2000) findings, the most important factors identified as influencing project cost estimating practice include (1) complexity of design and construction, (2) scale and scope of construction, (3) method of construction, (4) tender period and market condition, (5) site constraints, (6) client's financial position, (7) buildability, and (8) project location. He further concluded that those factors have a direct effect on productivity levels on site and performance of the construction project. In his work, he analysed 24 factors that influence project cost estimating practice, but his work and that of (Enshassi et al., 2005) only concentrated/focused on contractors. Meanwhile (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008), in their study, reported seven most important factors that affect the accuracy of pre-tender cost estimate in Nigeria based on the construction industry experience of consultant quantity surveyors, which include (1) expertise of cost consultants, (2) quality of information and flow requirements, (3) project team's experience of the construction type, (4) tender period

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and market conditions, (5) extent of completion of pre-contract design, (6) complexity of design and construction, and (7) availability and supplies of labour and materials. In their work, they highlighted 21 factors but focused on the perspective of consultants. According to them, it is believed that these factors may have effect on the accuracy design stage cost estimate and taking them into consideration will definitely improve the accuracy of consultant quantity surveyor's preliminary cost advice to his client.

In summary, making reference in agreement to a thorough review of the related literature, (Ogunlana & Thorpe, 1991) classified various factors affecting estimating accuracy into three broad categories as documented in (Jafarzadeh, 2012), being (1) project-based, (2) immediate environment-based, and (3) external environment-based categories. The first category reflected such factors as type, size, project duration, and the level of design information available. Factors included in the second category are number of bidders, ability of the estimator, local construction practices (i.e. geographical location of the project), resource availability, site access conditions, and price movements in the immediate environment. Finally, factors accommodated by the last category are industry structure, state of the market, and price movements in the external environment. A diagrammatical illustration of these categories and their contributing factors is represented in Figure 1.

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Figure 1: Factors affecting cost estimating accuracy
Source: (Ogunlana and Thorpe, 1991; Jafarzadeh, 2012)

Improving Accuracy in Design Stage Cost Estimating

Knowledge for Global Development

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Central to cost-based competition is the capability to accurately predict the cost of delivering a project. Overestimated cost could result in misjudgement for the feasibility of a project, or loss of a contract to competitors. On the other hand, the contractor could incur significant losses from underestimated cost (Liu & Zhu, 2007). Similarly, design stage cost estimates are susceptible to inaccuracies because they are often prepared within a limited time frame, and without finalized project scope (Aibinu & Pasco, 2008). They further stressed that pursuing an underestimated project can lead to project failure; on the other hand, overestimation of a project during the design stage can lead to a viable project being dropped or re-tendered for when there is no bid close enough to permit project award. While improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimates is important; from experience the first recognized characteristic of design stage cost estimating is the fact that it is yet another inexact process based on inadequate project information and the frequently existing risks and uncertainties during the design stage. (Serpell, 2005) in his study noted that the discussion and analysis of such an early stage cost estimating problems has consistently indicated specific needs or resources that permeate the early stage cost estimating in its entirety, and that addresses any effort leading to an improvement in the accuracy of design stage cost estimates.

Design stage cost estimating is a very important facet of the services that can provided by a quantity surveyor. The accuracy of design stage cost estimates is important in terms of overall project success, and it forms a substantial part of quantity surveying firms' workload. According to (Pasco & Aibinu, 2008) cost estimates produced at the design stage of project development determine whether a project is continued or dropped. They proceeded that accuracy of design stage cost estimate is an important piece of information needed for decision-making at the pre-tender stage. This study therefore explores the concepts of accuracy in design stage cost estimating to opine the accuracy in design stage cost planning by demonstrating the theoretical context of the relationship between both of them.

To ascertain the methods of improving accuracy, the estimating process is analysed as illustrated in Figure 2; this explains quantity surveying activities in transforming design into estimated costs which reflect four principal elements that affect design stage cost estimating accuracy namely (Ling & Boo, 2001): (1) design data, (2) time availability, (3) estimating technique, and (4) cost data. In addition, estimating skill and experience of the quantity surveyor is equally important to be considered as an element that affects design

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stage cost estimating accuracy, as this factor determines the proficiency with which an estimating technique is used. Also, the estimator's skill or experience determines the success or failure on any estimating technique adopted.

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Figure 2: Elements that affect the accuracy of design stage cost estimates
Source: Ling and Boo (2001)

An overview of previous studies suggested that a large number of methods have been identified as measures for improving accuracy of design cost estimates. In a study carried out in Singapore, (Ling & Boo, 2001) concluded that there has been no improvement in estimating accuracy over time. Meanwhile, 13 possible methods for improving estimating accuracy were identified and tested in the fieldwork. Based on their findings, the study outlined 9 methods as effective measures for improving estimating accuracy, out of which 3 methods were analysed as the most important measures for improving estimating accuracy.

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Those 9 methods are to: (1) ensure sufficient design information is available for estimating (H3), (2) check all assumptions with clients and consultants (H4), (3) ensure proper design documentation and information management (H1), (4) provide a realistic time frame for estimating activity (H6), (5) use more rigorous method of estimating (H7), (6) establish effective communication and co-ordination between members of project team (H2), (7) update cost database with new cost analyses and provide feedback for improving estimating accuracy (H13), (8) prepare estimates based on tender documents (H9), and (9) improve methods of selection, adjustments and application of cost data (H12). However, a possible shortfall exists in this research as an increase in cost planning and control activities during the design stage, as well as incorporating market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate by way of simulations, probability and utility functions convincingly appear important and relevant to improving estimating accuracy. To a great extent, (Ling & Boo, 2001) equally agreed in their study that it is common for changes to be made to designs, hence it is necessary to review the design cost estimates, and undertake cost planning and cost control activities. They concluded that if such activities are done progressively, such problems as issuing variations which may give rise to other problems like claims are possibly averted or reduced. Similarly, they further agreed that incorporating market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate can produce higher estimating accuracy, only that the use of simulations, probability and utility functions is highly theoretical and are more suitable for the academia than the industry as hypothesized in (Ling & Boo, 2001). Besides, other methods analysed by them are to: (10) establish formal feedback for design and estimating activities (H5), (11) increase cost planning and control activities during design stage (H11), (12) quantify and price effects of risk (H10), and (13) incorporate market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate by way of simulations, probability and utility functions.

In contrast to the foregoing study, (Pasco & Aibinu, 2008) opined that quantity surveyors in Australia only slightly agreed on the relative effectiveness of the 13 methods for improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimates as established in (Ling & Boo, 2001). The 3 most effective methods identified in this study are to: (1) ensure sufficient design information is available for estimating, (2) increase cost planning and control activities during the design stage, (3) check all assumptions with clients and consultants, out of 12 methods analysed. Other effective methods analysed in chronological order are to: (4) establish effective communication and co-ordination between members of the project team, (5) ensure proper design

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documentation, (6) update cost database with new cost analyses and provide feedback for improving estimate accuracy, (7) provide a realistic time frame for estimating activity, (8) incorporate other market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate, (9) improve methods of selection, adjustments and application of cost data, (10) establish formal feedback for design and estimating activities, (11) use a more rigorous method of estimating, and (12) incorporate market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate by way of simulations, probability and utility functions.

Similarly, (Ashworth, 2004) outlined three very important factors for improving design stage cost estimating accuracy which include: (1) an improvement in the quality of designer's information, since a vague design results only in an inaccurate estimate, (2) a reappraisal of the methods currently in use for estimating, and (3) to identify the qualities or attributes in the estimator or quantity surveyor which contribute towards accuracy in estimating, and to consider how these can be improved. In other words, qualities or attributes mentioned could be in terms of the skill and experience of the quantity surveyor involved in the estimating activity.

In another study in Australia, analysis of data from 56 building projects revealed in (Aibinu & Pasco, 2008) that the accuracy of design stage cost estimates has not improved over time. The Australian quantity surveyors perceived: (1) ensuring sufficient information is available at the time of estimating, as the most effective method of improving estimating (first); followed by (2) increased cost planning and control activities during the design stage (second), and (3) checking all assumptions with clients and consultants during the estimating period (third). Other effective methods, according to them include: (4) proper documentation of experience acquired in the estimation of projects, (5) reducing quantity surveying and cost engineering skill turnover, (6) incorporating market sentiments into estimates, (7) early involvement of the quantity surveyor at the brief stage of project development, and (8) probability estimation and simulation of past estimates. Based on their findings, these factors should help firms increase the accuracy of estimates for new projects undertaken by them. Thus, the result is similar to those established in (Ling & Boo, 2001) and (Pasco & Aibinu, 2008); the only difference perceived is the chronological order in which the methods or factors were arranged. In addition, these studies which have found universal acceptability and applicability suggested that there are a large number of effective methods that substantially influence

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improvement on the accuracy of design stage cost estimates. (Aibinu & Pasco, 2008) concluded that the similarities only indicate an international sentiment regarding methods of improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimates.

Research Methods

This study is a theoretical research based on literature review with a view to examining the critical methods for improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimating by demonstrating the theoretical context. In addition, the literature sources were accessed through databases which provided numerous academic journals and conference papers. Also, some textbooks found to be useful to the research process were referenced. A comprehensive literature survey was carried out towards securing design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool that guarantees cost for construction projects.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this paper is to provide a preliminary literature review, prior to a full research project aimed at developing a predictive model that will assist construction industry practitioners to have a better and reliable prediction of final tender sums of building projects from the design stage cost estimates. Extant literatures have indicated that certain circumstances observed as factors affecting design stage estimating accuracy have an impact on the deviations experienced during the design development stage between design stage cost estimates and final tender sums. The assessment of these identified factors and adequate consideration given to the critical methods for improving estimating accuracy could assist in determining the final tender sum from the design stage cost estimate. Thus, the review of relevant literature suggests that the essence of having a design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool that guarantees cost certainty for building projects is secured if those identified factors and critical methods for improving estimating accuracy are given adequate consideration in the estimation process.

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ENGINEERING PRACTICES FOR FUNCTIONALITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

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KEYWORDS: Functional; Sustainable; Engineering; Services; Society

ABSTRACT

Engineering as a profession is a call to service by the society. Perhaps next to soldiers, engineers are the most patriotic professionals. However unlike soldiers they remain servants of society at all times and in all circumstances. Despite her role to the society, engineering profession seems not to be enjoying the respect that is due to it probably because of the failures associated with some engineering projects. This paper discusses the potentials of engineering education and practices in the country to provide functional and sustainable services to the society. The major identified factors to achieve this quality have been as the teaching materials and equipment; staff capabilities and Industrial exposure. Though student recruitment was not a prominent factor for both students and employers, but was the main factor for staff. It is therefore important that it is not ignored. Engineering Services in the Country depends on a number of factors, some of which are not determined by Engineers themselves. However, there is no doubt that the future will be bright or dim depending on whether or not there exists a right relationship between the engineer and the Public or Institution which he serves.

INTRODUCTION

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Engineering practices and education in Nigeria has been going through some changes including the development of new engineering programmes, reorganization of course content, re-installation of equipment among others. However, the questions of concern have been – is the quality of engineering education meeting needs of stakeholders? Are employers satisfied with the training of engineering graduates? Are students equipped enough to stand tall in the world of competition?

A renowned Physicist, Sir John Cockroft said that “the capacity of science to advance the life of the so called new states depends, more than on any single factor these include the recognition by the Government of a state of the importance of science to its economy and a willingness to devote adequate resources to the advancement of science and technology (Williams, 1990). In Nigeria, these prerequisites are lacking. Day by day Governments continue to pay lip service to the recognition of technology as *a sine qua non* to our development. New Universities are springing up all over the place more as a political expediency than as a real desire to provide technological knowledge to the youths of this country. We establish these institutions and failed to either staff them adequately both with regard to number and quality of staff, nor are they properly equipped for the discipline they are established to impart. The available funds is spread thinly over a proliferation of Institutes of higher learning, rather than consolidate well established ones which naturally require more funds for their existence in the present circumstances of inflation in the country. The result is that the products have not the real foundation on which to build experience.

Universities and Polytechnics have become status symbols for our states in this country and therefore their establishments are highly politicized and the students are the pawns on the chessboard of politicized education. I hope we will not get to the stage where Governments will only recognize the degrees obtained in their own university in preference to all others, or that degrees will be awarded by the quota system in our universities

Engineering and Development

There has been a strong link between engineering and development, whenever any nation or world leader brags about his achievement; it is usually within the context of one engineering feat or the other. In modern

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days, the United Nations has established some indices of development. Olunloyo (2001) has linked these indices to engineering (Table 1)

Table 1.0 United Nations World Development Indicators

SN	Indicators	Linkage with Engineering		
		Direct	Indirect	Strong
1	Size of Economy			✓
2	Quality of Life	✓		
3	Population and Labour Force		✓	
4	Poverty		✓	
5	Distribution of Income or Consumption	✓		
6	Education			✓
7	Health			✓
8	Land Use and Agricultural Productivity	✓		
9	Water Use, deforestation and Protected Areas	✓		
10	Energy Use and Emissions	✓		
11	Growth of the Economy			✓
12	Structure of Output			✓
13	Structure of Demand		✓	
14	Central Government Finances			✓
15	Balance of Payment and International Reserves			✓
16	Private Sector Finance			✓
17	Role of Government in the Economy		✓	
18	Power and Transportation	✓		
19	Communication, Science and Information Technology	✓		
20	Global Trade	✓		

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21	Aid and Financial Flow			✓
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Sustainable Practices and Functionality

At the turn of 1990s, the United Nations through its various slogans adopted the slogan sustainable development. In other word, the world was called upon to embark on development that can be sustained. This slogan is more appropriate to a country like Nigeria where we love to embark on white elephant projects that can not be sustained.

Designing for Sustainability

If our Nigerian Engineers must meet their challenges in building the country, there must be a radical change to our engineering project planning activities. In planning the following factors must be taken into considerations

Designing in relation to Environment and services

The environmental requirements of modern buildings have a great influence on structural design. Some requirements are statutory, others arise from activities within the building or they may be directives of the client. Solar radiation is a major source of heat within a building especially in tropical climate. A good roof should be able to regulate the solar radiation into a building. The thermal coefficient of a roof (including the ceiling), should not be more than $0.35\text{w/m}^2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Barry, 1984). Thermal movement of heating and steam pipes can impose heavy loads on anchorage points and at other points of intentional or accidental restraints. Such movement and loads must be integrated in the structure. One of the greatest specialties of human being is the ability to modify the surrounding environment. This is best expressed in the method of clothing and building technology. Buildings are the most elaborate form of behavioral thermoregulation as they provide safe and controlled environment for humans and animals. The relative magnitude and the interactions of air and radiant temperature, humidity and air velocity have been found to determine the degree of thermal comfort of man (Hardy, 1973). While it is easy to construct structures against precipitation and high winds, it is not easy to build a system, which provides low thermal stress.

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It is therefore essential that building should be designed by integrating both the meteorological and physiological factors in order to produce pleasant and comfortable environments. The relative magnitude and the interactions of air and radiant temperature, humidity and air velocity have been found to determine the degree of thermal comfort of man (Olaleye, 2005). The apparent human environmental requirements are for light, good air, and warmth. If occupants of any building could not enjoy these requirements in a building, such building is termed sick. 'Sick' Buildings is a new expression for construction with physical properties affecting health.

Designing in relation to Structural design resources

The question of resources in labour and materials does not frequently arise in advance countries in sufficient degree to influence choice of structure. In developed countries, however, particularly in 'emergent' countries, inaccessible areas, or areas subject to extreme natural phenomena, the question of resources may be extremely relevant. Local building methods and materials are sometimes worthy of adoption, particularly when low cost buildings are to be erected. Experiments will indicate the most suitable materials and methods to be used, and these will vary from place to place- steel, concrete bricks and blocks.

Designing for Comfort

Our buildings must be designed for comfort in order to make them homely. Physiological comfort in man is determined by both meteorological and non-meteorological factors. Non-meteorological factors include age, sex, type of clothing, diet, metabolic rate, work type and emotional state amongst others. The meteorological controls of physiological comfort in man are temperature, humidity, wind speed and radiation. There are various bio-meteorological indices for measuring physiologic comfort but most of them are based on meteorological factors since non-meteorological factors are in general not quantifiable.

Effective Index Method

Using the effective temperature index, the diurnal and seasonal variations of physiologic comfort could be obtained to assist in designing a healthy building. The effective temperature index was actually derived based on laboratory experiments involving human beings and is approximated by the equation

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$$E_T = 0.4 (T_d + T_w) + 15 \dots \dots \dots \text{Eqn. 1}$$

Where E_T is the Effective Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{F}$; T_d and T_w are the dry bulb and wet bulb temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{F}$ respectively. Studies revealed that an ET value of 66 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ (18.9 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and below indicates uncomfortable condition arising from cold stress while ET value in excess of 78 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ (25.6 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) indicates uncomfortable condition due heat stress. Values of ET between 66 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ and 78 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ therefore represent optimum physiological comfort. Studies indicate that uncomfortable conditions arising from heat stress are common in most parts of the country during most of the day particularly during the dry season. The only exception is Jos Plateau area which because of its elevation does not suffer from heat stress. On the other hand, Jos and many of the far northern cities suffer from cold stress at nights and early in the mornings particularly between November and March when the harmattan weather prevails. Kaduna has been found out to have the best all year round climate in terms of physiological comfort while both Maiduguri and Lokoja emerge as having the worst. Altitude plays an important role in determining the physiological comfort in Nigeria because of its moderating effect on temperature. The Jos – Kaduna zone which has the best physiological climate in the country is in an area of relatively high elevation. In contrast, the lowland areas of the Niger Benue valley in the middle belt are oppressively hot. The Northern zones suffer from extremes of temperature usually associated with such continental locations while the Southern zones consisting mostly of low lying lands is relatively hot and humid for most parts of the year.

Physio-climatic stress is known to reduce the mental and physical efficiency of man and therefore deserves to be studied. Such studies can form the basis for wise scheduling of leave period and holidays as well as fixing appropriate official working hours amongst others (Ayoade, 1994).

HEATING AND COOLING DEGREE-DAYS Method

One method employed for this is finding the heating and cooling degree –days. A heating degree-day is defined as a 1 $^{\circ}$ departure of the daily mean temperature from a base of 18.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (65 $^{\circ}\text{F}$) towards a lower temperature (that is, when the average temperature of a day is below 18.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (65 $^{\circ}\text{F}$), its value is subtracted from the 18.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (65 $^{\circ}\text{F}$) base and the difference gives the number of heating degree-days), a cooling degree

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–days can also be based on the temperature-humidity index, in which case it is defined as a 1° departure from the daily average temperature-humidity index expressed in degrees Fahrenheit, above a base of 15.6°C (60°F). The temperature-humidity index is computed from the equation:

$$THI = 0.4 (T_d + T_w) + 15 \dots \dots \dots \text{Eqn. 2}$$

Where *THI* is the temperature-humidity index, *T_w* is the wet bulb temperature (°F) and *T_a* is the air temperature

Table 2 shows the heating and cooling degree-day for six stations in the zone, using the mean monthly temperature. The heating degree-days were calculated by finding the difference between the base temperature of 18.3°C (65°F) and the average monthly temperature whenever the latter was lower. From the table it can be seen that all the stations have zero heating degree-days. This is basically because West Africa is in the tropics and has high average temperatures throughout the year. The cooling degree-days show comparatively high values before the heavy rainy period, for example in Lagos between February and May, preceding the heavy rainfall.

TABLE 2 (a) HEATING DEGREE-DAYS

Location	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Lagos	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ibadan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ado Ekiti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Akure	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oshogbo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abeokuta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The Zeros emphasize the prevalence of constantly high temperature

(b): COOLING DEGREE-DAYS

Location	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
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Lagos	5	7	7	6	5	3	1	1	0	3	6	5
Ibadan	5	7	8	8	5	3	1	1	2	3	5	5
Ado Ekiti	6	7	7	8	8	6	3	3	4	5	6	6
Akure	4	7	12	15	14	9	5	4	5	7	6	3
Oshogbo	1	5	12	18	19	15	10	7	9	12	8	2
Abeokuta	7	11	13	12	8	5	4	3	3	5	8	5

(Temperatures in Fahrenheit)

Engineering Practice for Sustainability

If engineering services in the country is to be properly maintained, we need engineers, technicians, artisans, skilled and unskilled labour. Each of these categories of staff must be properly trained for the part he is expected to play in the establishment. The Engineer is the high level manpower, the technician is the middle level manpower and the artisans – skilled unskilled labour are the junior level manpower. The accepted norm in engineering practice all over the world is that in order to get full value from one professional engineer he will have to work with 4 to 6 engineering technicians. I have gone into these details to show that all our engineering services must have their full complement of staff consisting the high level, the middle level and the lower level or junior manpower to be truly effective. If this normal standard is not achieved, and everyone belongs to the high level manpower, then there will be the need to use high level manpower, then there will be the need to use high level manpower to do middle level manpower job leading to under-utilization of high level manpower, and therefore a wastage of manpower.

Administrators Intrusion

Another draw back to the advancement of Nigeria is the continued subjection of the professionals to the Administrators. The much desired development in this country will be retarded unless the Engineers are given their rightful place in the scheme of things in the country. Administrative Officer who has not the foggiest idea of what the engineers are expected to do. I made that statement because some years ago a high functionary of one of our Governments was reported to have said that if he could have his way he would sack all the engineers in the service and give all the jobs to Consultants. But then who are the consultants?

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Are they not engineers, some of whom might have resigned their appointments from the Service to become consultants?

Engineering Maintenance

Another important aspect of engineering practices is the maintenance of our infrastructures. One of the chief areas that our country is failing in is its inability to maintain what it has built or constructed. We plunge from one grandiose and expensive scheme to another whilst the previous ones are left to rack and ruin due to lack of maintenance, examples abound all over the country; buildings, fountains, express ways, Universities and so on. None of them has been properly maintained. When large sums have been spent on building, sufficient provision for their maintenance has not been made. Over a period of years, under tropical conditions where paint and fabric quickly deteriorate, it has been suggested that a sum of as much as 5 percent of the capital cost of erecting a building should be made available each year for its maintenance. If we accept this figure, then for buildings costing ₦2000, 000 a sum of ₦ 100,000 will be required each year. Another way of expressing this is to say that for every Naira spent on buildings, an equal sum should be put into an endowment fund to provide an income for their maintenance and upkeep. I think that it may be possible to keep the cost of repairs and or redecoration a little below this sum, but allowing for grass-cutting, gardens, and road repairs the economy will not be great.

Engineering Education

A survey was conducted among students, staff and employers of University of Ibadan to evaluate which factors they considered more important. Using a prioritization matrix, industrial exposure and linkages; Teaching Material and equipments have been found to be the most critical factors for quality engineering education. These factors have been weighed and the values compared for the different stakeholders. To ensure continuous improvement in the quality of education at the department a proposed strategic mapping for improvement has been suggested. According to Ibrahim (1999) “there is a difficulty in defining quality of engineering education”, however, there is the need to describe results of this quality in terms of ability to satisfy the current and future needs of industry, mobility, and life-long commitment to learning (Pile et al, 2013).

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Prioritization of Quality Factors

Having considered the various factors for Quality Management analysis and how they have affected the general performance of the department, the author have prioritized these factors using a matrix based on results from discussions and interview of different stakeholders. The results are shown below in Tables 3 and Table 4.

From the prioritization matrix Table 3, it was observed that the most important factor for quality engineering education according to student perspective Industrial Exposure and linkages (with priority rating of 24.7 percent) and Content of curriculum as the least important with 1.6 percent priority rating. The relative importance of the quality factors is reflected in the percentile weight ratings. The order of importance is as follows: Industrial Exposure (24.7 percent), Teaching Materials and Equipment (20.9 percent), Teaching Methodology (17.2 percent), Relevance of student research (17.2), Student Recruitment (10 percent), Staff Capabilities (8.7 percent), and Content of curriculum (1.6 percent).

The staff were of different opinion and felt the student recruited for engineering programs are very critical for producing quality and independent engineering graduate yielding a priority rating of 40.8 percent and the teaching methodology (with priority rating of 2.2 percent), the least important. The order of importance is as follows: Student Recruitment (40.8 percent), Teaching Materials and Equipment (27.5 percent), Staff Capabilities (23.3 percent), Relevance of student research (10.1), Industrial Exposure (2.5 percent), Content of curriculum (2.4 percent) and Teaching Methodology (2.2 percent).

According to employers, Teaching Materials and Equipment, Staff Capabilities and Content of curriculum are the most critical factors for an enhance quality engineering graduate with priority rating of 35, 17.6 and 17.0 percent respectively. The least important to them is Student recruitment with rating of 1.9 percent.

Analysis of Results

The result obtained above is an indication that different stakeholders value some factors more than others. The reason of the poor overall rating for content of curriculum could be explained by the fact that irrespective of the curriculum content, if the needed teaching materials and equipment are not available, no

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better output could be expected. The consistent appeal of students for industrial trips and places for attachment is not out of place since they see it as a critical factor for success in their engineering carrier. Student recruitment plays a major role in the delivering of quality education. It is important to note that in spite of the available modern teaching material and equipment at the Civil Engineering Department, the quality of graduate is still questionable. It is therefore not surprising it was the highest rated factor for the staff. However, some employers are of view that with right practical orientation using the right teaching materials and equipment any student could be turned into a useful engineering graduate.

Strategic Mapping for Continuous Improvement

Based on the result gathered and the corresponding discussions made, a strategic mapping for continuous improvement in the quality of engineering education has been developed. Competent and committed staff; Modern equipment; Advertisement programs to enhanced quality students; Relevant textbooks as well as an effective dialogue concerning quality education has been identified as the support for building this quality.

The main process of an enhance quality teaching could be achieved through a practically oriented curriculum, professional staff development to improve staff capabilities, partnership with industry, properly supervised student attachment and recruitment of good students.

These factors would in the long run ensure not only the result of qualified and independent engineering graduate but also a fulfilled staff and more importantly a satisfied and independent engineering graduate but also a fulfilled staff and more importantly a satisfied employed.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

To ensure an improvement in the quality of engineering education, all stakeholders must get on board. The major identified factors to achieve this quality have been as the teaching materials and equipment; staff capabilities and Industrial exposure. Though student recruitment was not a prominent factor for both students and employers, but was the main factor for staff. It is therefore important that it is not ignored. If the suggested strategic mapping is adopted then engineering will exalted in the country. Engineering

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Services in the Country depends on a number of factors, some of which are not determined by Engineers themselves. However, there is no doubt that the future will be bright or dim depending on whether or not there exists a right relationship between the engineer and the Public or Institution which he serves.

Table 3: Quality Factors Prioritization (Student Perspective)

Quality Factors	of Content curriculum	and Teaching Materials Equipment	Industrial Exposure	Teaching Methodology	of Relevance student research	Staff Capabilities	Student recruitment	Total	Percentage (%)
Content of curriculum		0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	1	0.1	1.7	1.6
Teaching Materials and Equipment	5		5	1	0.2	1	10	22.2	20.9
Industrial Exposure	10	0.2		5	1	5	5	26.2	24.7
Teaching Methodology	10	1	0.2		1	1	5	18.2	17.2

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Relevance of student research	5	5	1	1		1	5	18	17.0
Staff Capabilities	1	1	0.2	1	1		5	9.2	8.7
Student Recruitment	10	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1			10.6	10

Table 4: Success Factors Prioritization (Staff Perspective)

Quality Factors	of Content curriculum	and Teaching Materials Equipment	Industrial Exposure	Teaching Methodology	of Relevance student research	Staff Capabilities	Student recruitment	Total	Percentage (%)
Content of curriculum		0.2	1	1	0.2	0.2	0.1	2.7	2.4
Teaching Materials and Equipment	5		5	10	5	5	1	31.0	27.5
Industrial Exposure	1	0.2		0.2	0.2	1	0.2	2.8	2.5
Teaching Methodology	1	0.1	0.2		1	0.1	0.1	2.5	2.2
Relevance of student research	5	0.2	5	1		0.1	0.1	11.4	10.1

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Staff Capabilities	5	0.2	1	10	10		0.1	26.3	23.3
Student Recruitment	10	1	5	10	10	10		46	40.8

Table 5: Success Factors Prioritization (Employers Perspective)

Quality Factors	of Content curriculum	Teaching Materials and Equipment	Industrial Exposure	Teaching Methodology	of Relevance student research	Staff Capabilities	Student recruitment	Total	Percentage (%)
Content of curriculum		0.2	1	0.2	10	1	5	17.4	17.0
Teaching Materials and Equipment	5		5	5	10	1	10	36.0	35.2
Industrial Exposure	1	0.2		5	1	0.2	5	12.4	12.1
Teaching Methodology	5	1	0.2		1	0.2	1	8.4	8.2
Relevance of student research	0.1	0.1	1	1		1	5	8.2	8.0

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Staff Capabilities	1	1	5	5	1		5	18.0	17.6
Student Recruitment	0.2	0.1	0.2	1	0.2	0.2		1.9	1.9

1 Equally Important

5 Significantly More Important

10 Exceedingly More Important

1/5 Significantly Less Important

1/10 Exceedingly Less Important

Table 6: Quality factors comparison for different stakeholders

Quality Factors	Student Perspective	Student Perspective	Student Perspective	Overall (Total)
Content of curriculum	1.6	2.4	17.0	21
Teaching Materials and Equipment	20.9	27.5	35.2	83.6
Industrial Exposure and linkages	24.7	2.5	12.1	39.3
Teaching Methodology	17.2	2.2	8.2	27.6
Relevance of student research	17	10.1	8.0	35.1
Staff Capabilities	8.7	23.3	17.6	49.6
Student Recruitment	8.7	23.3	17.6	49.6

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LOSS ESTIMATION IN PORT HARCOURT POWER DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

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KEYWORDS: NTL's, TL's, PHCN, FERMIE, WATERWORKS, RIVOC AND RAINBOW

ABSTRACT

This work studied losses (technical, administrative and non technical) in one of the injection sub stations (trans-amadi) in Port Harcourt. It consists of 33kV incoming line and two (2) by 15MVA transformers sizes distributed to four (4) outgoing feeders three (3) feeders (Fermie, Waterworks, Rivoc and Rainbow). Data collected include current readings(energy supplied on hourly basis) and collation of consumers billed units for a period of six months(Jan-July 2013). Applying the required mathematical equations, a total energy loss (TL's and NTL's) were determined for each of the feeders and was translated into monetary terms. Necessary recommendations were made towards curbing these challenges

INTRODUCTION

Stable and quality power supply is synonymous to fast growing economic development and industrialization. Nigeria power network generates, transmits and distribute to final consumers at different voltage levels. Nigeria network currently consist of seventeen power generating stations that generates at 16kV and then transmits at 132/330kV consisting of sixty four transmission lines and fifty two buses, before it is finally distributed at 33/11/0.415kV. Each voltage levels are associated with losses either from generators, transmission or distribution lines that could either be in form of technical or non-technical. Technical losses (TL's) occur as a result of components failure, power dissipation in transmission lines, transformers (resistive losses in windings and core loss), metering and control calibration measuring instruments associated to electrical equipments etc and can easily be measured and controlled provided that the power system consist of known load quantities. It also include resistive losses in the primary feeder, resistive losses in secondary network, resistive losses in service drops and losses in kWh in meters(Fourie

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J.E, et al 2004). Other examples of technical losses include: unbalanced loadings, poor earthing, harmonic distortion, copper and dielectric losses due to finite resistance in conductors, etc. Non-technical losses (NTL's), on the other hand, is defined as any consumed energy or service which is not billed because of a measurement equipment failure or an ill-intention and fraudulent manipulation of the said equipment (Inigo M, et al, 2011). It may be caused from electricity theft through unmetered energy and metering inconsistencies or estimated through loads and conditions which technical losses failed to account for (Tejinder S, 2009). Electricity theft serves as the major component causing NTL's in power systems and can be defined as the deliberate attempt of an individual or group of individuals sometimes with or without power producing company's staff to alter actual billing charges or either not to pay consumed charges at all through illegal connections or using faulty meters. Recent research revealed that, electricity theft (major contributor to non-technical losses) accounts for 30% to 40% of the total annual revenue accrued in Nigeria (Anumaka M.C 2012). The aim of study is to study and determine NTL's and then provide possible solutions. This will be achieved by carrying out analytic estimation of NTL's in a local power distribution system in Port Harcourt using available records from Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Distribution losses are inherent along distribution network and comprise of TL's (load and no-load losses of transformers, line losses) and NTL's due to meter tampering, metering inaccuracies and illegal connections. No-load losses are independent of transformer loading while load losses are dependent on transformer loading. According to Millard R and Emmertson M in 2009, total loss in transmission and distribution power system comprises of three components namely the **technical losses**, inherent in the physical delivery of electric energy. It includes conductor loss, transformer core loss, and potential/current coils in metering equipment, **Administrative loss** that accounts for electric energy used by the distribution utility in the proper operation of the distribution network. and the **non technical losses**, caused primarily by human error, whether intentional or not. Non-technical losses include the electric energy lost due to pilferage, tampering of meters, and erroneous meter reading and/or billing. All estimates of non technical losses are based on the accuracy of the calculation of technical losses (World Bank Group, 2009). Though this study is focus on non technical losses but the technical losses have to be analyzed as the non technical losses are the result of the subtractions of the technical losses from the distribution network losses. Al-

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mahroqi Y et al (2012) stated that TL's are part of the electric losses in the system, resulting in: losses in drivers, corona effect, iron of the transformers, eddy currents, connectors, and ohmic losses. According to Navani J.P., et al in 2011, TL's consist mainly of power dissipation in electrical system component such as transmission lines, power transformer, and measurement system etc. According to Sayyed M.B et al in 2012, this part of losses depends on technical specification of equipment in power distribution system. In a system with appropriate operating condition, most losses in the system are caused by technical losses. Reduction of these losses is difficult and almost impractical. No load losses occur from the energy required to retain the continuously varying magnetic flux in the core and it invariant with load on the transformer and load losses mainly arises from resistance losses in the conducting material of the winding and it varies with loading (Al-mahroqi Y., 2012). Optimization of technical losses in electricity transmission and distribution grids is an engineering issue, involving classic tools of power system planning and modeling (World Bank group, 2009). Information technology and data acquisition techniques have made the calculation and verification easier. With the technical information of the electricity generators and the loads, expected technical losses in the power system can be determined using load-flow analysis software(s) such as ETAP, Power World Simulator(PWS), PSCAD, MATLAB etc. According to Inigo M. in 2011, NTL's is defined as any consumed energy or service which is not billed because of measurement equipment failure or ill-intentioned and fraudulent manipulation of equipment. NTL's are more difficult to measure because these losses are often unaccounted for by system operators and thus have no recorded information (Navani J.P et al, 2011). NTL's on the other hand, occur as a result of theft, metering inaccuracies and unmetered energy. Millard R and Emmertson M (2009) stated that NTL's technical loss is the residual loss after subtracting both administrative and technical losses from the total distribution network losses.

$$\text{i.e. } NTL = E_L - T_L - A_L \quad (1)$$

Where: NTL 's = non technical losses; E_L = distribution losses; T_L = Technical Los; A_L = administrative lossess. The estimation of NTL's requires accurate computation of TL's and administrative losses. There are wide ranges of situations creating NTL's. A classic case is electricity theft through illegal connections to the grid or tampering of consumption meter, unmetered consumption by

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utility customers not accurately metered etc. In all these cases, some level of poor management of the utility in execution of its operations is present (World Bank group, 2009). According to Navani J.P et al, 2011; Millard & Emmertson, 2009; World Bank Group, 2009; Fourie J & Calmeyer J, 2004; Al-mahroqi Y et al, 2012 and Sayyed M, 2012, the most probable causes of NTL's include: meter tampering to ensure that meter records lower consumption readings, errors in TL's computation, Tapping (illegal connection) on LT's lines, Arranging false readings by bribing meter readers (i.e. utility companies staff), Stealing by bypassing the meter, Ignoring unpaid bills by utility companies, Faulty energy meters or un-metered supply, Errors and delay in meter readings and billing, Non-payment by customers. According to world bank group in 2009, NTL's in the power sector are almost non-existent or negligibly small in developed countries, as most of the population can afford to pay tariff reflecting costs of supply. Many electricity utilities in developing countries succeeded in significantly reducing or eliminating non technical losses in electricity supply on a sustainable manner but others continue to show high losses. The level of NTL's varies generally according to the economic condition of the country. Countries where GDP per capital is very low it is common to find higher levels of NTL's. However, in countries such as Indonesia and Thailand, GDP per capital is low but the reported NTL's level is remarkably low (Millard R & Emmertson M, 2009). High rates of NTL's activities have been reported in developing countries like Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Lebanon etc where 20% to 30% of NTL's have been observed (world bank group, 2009) while Nigeria has been reported to have a large proportion of transmission and distribution losses of about 40% (Omorogiuwa E. and Ogunjor 2012; Anumaka M.C, 2012). According to world bank group in 2009, in all successful cases of reduction of NTL's in developing countries, a large share of NTL's was concentrated in users inability to pay for cost reflective tariff. Table 1.0 shows relationship of various countries estimated power losses based on total power generated

TABLE 2.1 RELATIONSHIP OF DISTRIBUTION LOSSES TO ECONOMIC PROSPERITY

COUNTRY	ESTIMATED LOSSES IN 2007	PPP PER CAPITAL 2010
Nigeria	40%	2100
India	NTL-20% to 40%	2700
Philippines	NTL-3,5%	3300
Indonesia	NTL-unknown	3400

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Jordon	NTL-3% to 5%	4700
Jamaica	NTL-13,2%	4800
China	NTL-10%	5300
Thailand	NTL-0,31%	8000
Brazil	0,5% to 25%	9370
Turkey	NTL-6% to 64%	9400

METHODOLOGY

This section shows the mathematical steps, formulation and numerical analysis carried out to determine and estimate distribution losses (NTL's) in the distribution network. It involves review of literatures relevant to the study, collection of energy supplied readings data on hourly basis from Trans-amadi injection substation situated in Port Harcourt (PH), collation of consumer/billed unit, determination of total energy losses and finally evaluating both TL's and NTL's in distribution network.

Data Acquisition

Data were taken from a 33/11kV substation, trans-amadi injection substation. The injection substation consists of 33kV incoming line and two step down transformer, T1 (15MVA) & T2 (15MVA) which step down 33kV incoming voltage to 11kV and distributed to four outgoing 11kV feeders namely: Fermie, Waterworks, Rivoc and Rainbow. The four outgoing 11kV feeders were considered for the analysis of NTL's. Load current readings from PHCN log book for each of the four feeders were taken on hourly basis for a period of 6 months. Also the total number of transformers, their respective ratings and expected losses were also obtained. Load currents on each feeder were given in 3-phase i.e. (Red[R], Yellow[Y], Blue [B]) and the average current obtained represents the current for that hour and the total load current I_T is the arithmetic sum of the hourly load current for the day. Figure 1.0 shows singleline diagram of the trans-amadi 33/11kV injection substation

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Fermie Waterworks Rivoc Rainbow

Figure1.0 Single line diagram of the trans-amandi 33/11kV injection substation

The voltage on each feeder is 11kV, in order to calculate the energy supplied, the power formula for a 3phase system is used:

$$P_S = \sqrt{3}I_T V \cos \phi \quad (2)$$

Where: P_S = Power supply, I_T ($\frac{\text{ampere}}{\text{hour}}$) = Total load current; V =

Voltage on the line(11kV); $\cos \phi$ = power factor(0.85). The total energy supplied for the month is calculated by taking average of the respective daily energy readings. Table 2.0 shows total energy supplied for the four feeders (Fermie, Waterworks, Rivoc and Rainbow) in kwh for the period of six months (Jan - June 2013) while the total energy consumed/billed E_B for the same period is shown table 3.0. The energy billed as obtained from PHCN for the period include combination of domestic, commercials and industrial consumers on the four 11kV going feeders.

Table 2.0 Total Energy supplied, E_S for the period of 6 month

MONTH	FERMIE total unit(kWh)	WATERWORKS total unit(kWh)	RIVOC total unit(kWh)	RAINBOW total unit(kWh)
JANUARY	1,104,946.51	351,554.00	1,210,519.57	1,632,131.75
FEBRUARY	1,360,352.69	456,398.33	1,485,731.88	1,726,643.86

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MARCH	1,477,189.28	468,107.09	1695756.79	1,594,398.15
APRIL	1,590,106.56	504,561.32	1,717,645.67	2,056,000.48
MAY	1,460,839.89	457,043.70	1,829,162.39	2,101,089.63
JUNE	1,313,073.76	479,580.18	1,892,837.66	1,816,987.51

Table 3.0 Total energy consumed/billed E_B for the period of 6 month

MONTH	FERMIE Unit billed(kWh)	WATERWORKS Unit billed (kWh)	RIVOC Unit billed(kWh)	RAINBOW Unit billed(kWh)
JANUARY	725,950.00	249,252.00	771,101.00	1,039,668.00
FEBRUARY	899,193.00	325,412.00	958,297.00	1,080,879.00
MARCH	988,240.00	338,910.00	1,064,935.00	1,007,750.00
APRIL	1,095,583.00	370,853.00	1,142,234.00	1,334,344.00
MAY	971,459.00	336,841.00	1,192,614.00	1,380,416.00
JUNE	861,376.00	346,257.00	1,194,381.00	1,153,787.00

DETERMINATION OF DISTRIBUTION LOSSES

The overall distribution losses in the system can be evaluated by comparing the results of the energy delivered by the injection substation and the total energy billed during the stipulated period of time. Mathematically; Let E_s be the overall energy delivered from the injection substation for the month, E_B be the energy billed for the month, E_L be Energy expended due to distribution losses;

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Then

$$E_L = E_S - E_B \quad (3.0)$$

Using the data obtained from PHCN and applying equation 3.0, tables 4.0(a-f) is obtained for each of the distribution feeders. This table contains energy supplied, billed/supplied energy and their associated line losses for the various months (Jan-June 2013).

Table 4.0a Distribution losses on the feeders for January

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,104,946.51	725,950.00	378,996.51	34.3
WATERWORKS	351,554.00	249,252.00	102,302.00	29.1
RIVOC	1,210,519.57	771,101.00	439,418.57	36.3
RAINBOW	1,632,131.75	1,039,668.00	592,463.75	36.3

Table 4.0b Distribution losses on the feeders for February

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,360,352.69	899,193.00	461,159.69	33.9
WATERWORKS	456,398.33	325,412.00	130,986.33	28.7
RIVOC	1,485,731.88	958,297.00	527,434.88	35.5
RAINBOW	1,726,643.86	1,080,879.00	645,764.86	37.4

Table 4.0c Distribution losses on the feeders for March

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,477,189.28	988,240.00	488,949.28	33.1

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WATERWORKS	468,107.09	338,910.00	129,197.09	27.6
RIVOC	1,695,756.79	1,064,935.00	630,821.79	37.2
RAINBOW	1,594,398.15	1,007,660.00	586,738.15	36.8

Table 4.0d Distribution losses on the feeders for April

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,590,106.56	1,095,583.00	494,523.56	31.1
WATERWORKS	504,561.32	370,853.00	133,708.32	26.5
RIVOC	1,717,645.67	1,142,234.00	575,411.67	33.5
RAINBOW	2,056,000.48	1,334,344.00	721,656.48	35.1

Table 4.0e Distribution losses on the feeders for May

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,460,839.89	971,459.00	489,380.89	33.5
WATERWORKS	457,043.70	336,841.00	120,202.70	26.3
RIVOC	1,829,162.39	1,192,614.00	636,548.39	34.8
RAINBOW	2,101,089.63	1,380,416.00	720,673.63	34.3

Table 4.0 f Distribution losses on the feeders for June

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
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FERMIE	1,313,073.76	861,377.00	451,696.76	34.4
WATERWORKS	479,580.18	346,257.00	133,323.18	27.8
RIVOC	1,892,837.66	1,194,381.00	698,456.66	36.9
RAINBOW	1,816,987.51	1,153,787.00	663,200.51	36.5

ESTIMATING TL'S

TL's in distribution systems consist of both transformers (load loss and no load loss) and line losses. The line losses was analyzed using the following parameters: span-length of each feeder lines from the injection substation and characteristic impedance per unit length of the feeders. Assuming negligible line losses in distribution lines, our primary focus was to obtain data containing the number of transformers and their ratings in the areas and the .The load and no load losses for each of the transformers are computed using equations 4.0 and 5.0 respectively and the various parameters are defined. Let T_{LL} = Total load losses; LL = Expected load loss for each transformer; T_L = Technical losses; tn = number of recorded hours for each month; Tn = number of transformers serving the area.

$$T_{LL} = LL \times tn \quad (4.0)$$

$$T_L = T_{LL} \times Tn \quad (5.0)$$

Table 5.0 Estimated T_L , for the period of 6 month

MONTH	FERMIE (kWh)	WATERWORKS (kWh)	RIVOC (kWh)	RAINBOW (kWh)
JANUARY	29,177.12	3,332.25	31,762.08	36,903.81
FEBRUARY	32,322.37	3,736.72	33,866.40	41,138.64
MARCH	33,727.68	3,862.32	32,682.72	39,189.27
APRIL	34,263.04	4,207.73	36,102.24	37,710.44
MAY	30,716.29	4,385.67	35,050.08	34,080.54
JUNE	25,095.01	4,427.54	35,576.16	33,407.76

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From the results obtained from the enlisted analyses, non-technical losses (NTL) are evaluated for each month by comparing the values obtained from the monthly distribution losses and the estimated technical losses. Let T_L be the estimated technical losses based on expected values from each transformer linked to a feeder.

Mathematically;

$$NTL(kWh) = E_L - T_L \quad (6.0)$$

Table 6.0a Estimated NTL on the feeders for January

FEEDER	E_L (kWh)	T_L (kWh)	$NTL = E_L - T_L$ (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	378,996.51	29,177.12	349,819.39	31.7
WATERWORKS	102,302.00	3,332.25	98,969.75	28.2
RIVOC	439,418.57	31,762.08	407,656.49	33.7
RAINBOW	592,463.75	36,903.81	555,559.94	34.0

Table 6.0b Estimated NTL on the feeders for February

FEEDER	E_L (kWh)	T_L (kWh)	$NTL = E_L - T_L$ (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	461,159.69	32,322.37	428,837.32	31.5
WATERWORKS	130,986.33	3,736.72	127,249.61	27.9
RIVOC	527,434.88	33,866.40	493,568.48	33.2
RAINBOW	645,764.86	41,138.64	604,626.22	35.0

Table 6.0c Estimated NTL on the feeders for the month March

FEEDER	E_L (kWh)	T_L (kWh)	$NTL = E_L - T_L$ (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	488,949.28	33,727.68	455,221.60	30.8

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WATERWORKS	129,197.09	3,862.32	125,334.77	26.8
RIVOC	630,821.79	32,682.72	598,139.07	35.3
RAINBOW	586,738.15	39,189.27	547,548.88	34.4

Table 6.0d Estimated NTL on the feeders for April

FEEDER	E_L (kWh)	T_L (kWh)	$NTL = E_L - T_L$ (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	494,523.56	34,263.04	460,260.52	28.9
WATERWORKS	133,708.32	4,207.73	129,500.59	25.7
RIVOC	575,411.67	36,102.24	539,309.43	31.4
RAINBOW	721,656.48	37,710.44	683,946.04	33.3

Table 6.0e Estimated NTL on the feeders for May

FEEDER	E_L (kWh)	T_L (kWh)	$NTL = E_L - T_L$ (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	489,380.89	30,716.29	458,664.60	31.4
WATERWORKS	120,202.70	4,385.67	115,817.03	25.3
RIVOC	636,548.39	35,050.08	601,498.31	32.9
RAINBOW	720,673.63	34,080.54	686,593.09	32.7

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Table 6.0f Estimated NTL on the feeders for June

FEEDER	E_L (kWh)	T_L (kWh)	$NTL = E_L - T_L$ (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	451,696.76	25,095.01	426,601.75	32.5
WATERWORKS	133,323.18	4427.54	128,895.64	26.9
RIVOC	698,456.66	35,576.16	662,880.50	35.0
RAINBOW	663,200.51	33,407.76	629,792.75	34.7

RESULTS & ANALYSIS

The collected data after analysis yielded the following results shown in table 7.0(a-f), these contains the total energy supplied E_s , monthly and the estimated distribution losses E_L , and NTL's, for a period of 6 month.

Table 7.0a Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for Jan

FEEDER	E_s (kWh)	E_L (kWh)	$E_L\%$	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,104,946.51	378,996.51	34.3	349,819.39	31.7
WATERWORKS	351,554.00	102,302.00	29.1	98,969.75	28.2
RIVOC	1,210,519.57	439,418.57	36.3	407,656.49	33.7
RAINBOW	1,632,131.75	592,463.75	36.3	555,559.94	34.0

Table 7.0b Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for Feb

FEEDER	E_s (kWh)	E_L (kWh)	$E_L\%$	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,360,352.69	461,159.69	33.9	428,837.32	31.5
WATERWORKS	456,398.33	130,986.33	28.7	127,249.61	27.9

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RIVOC	1,485,731.88	527,434.88	35.5	493,568.48	33.2
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Table 7.0c Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for March

FEEDER	E _S (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L %	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,477,189.28	488,949.28	33.1	455,221.60	30.8
WATERWORKS	468,107.09	129,197.09	27.6	125,334.77	26.8
RIVOC	1695756.79	630,821.79	37.2	598,139.07	35.3
RAINBOW	1,594,398.15	586,738.15	36.8	547,548.88	34.4

Table 7.0d Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for April

FEEDER	E _S (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L %	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,590,106.56	494,523.56	31.1	460,260.52	28.9
WATERWORKS	504,561.32	133,708.32	26.5	129,500.59	25.7
RIVOC	1,717,645.67	575,411.67	33.5	539,309.43	31.4
RAINBOW	2,056,000.48	721,656.48	35.1	683,946.04	33.3

Table 7.0e Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for May

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FEEDER	E _S (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L % (kWh)	~ NTL	NTL%
FERMIE	1,460,839.89	489,380.89	33.5	458,664.60	31.4
WATERWORKS	457,043.70	120,202.70	26.3	115,817.03	25.3
RIVOC	1,829,162.39	636,548.39	34.8	601,498.31	32.9
RAINBOW	2,101,089.63	720,673.63	34.3	686,593.09	32.7

Table 7.0f Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for June

FEEDER	E _S (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L % (kWh)	~ NTL	NTL%
FERMIE	1,313,073.76	451,696.76	34.4	426,601.75	32.5
WATERWORKS	479,580.18	133,323.18	27.8	128,895.64	26.9
RIVOC	1,892,837.66	698,456.66	36.9	662,880.50	35.0
RAINBOW	1,816,987.51	663,200.51	36.5	629,792.75	34.7

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

From these results, it shows, that feeders with more of domestic and industrial consumers such as Rivoc and Rainbow showed large proportion of distribution losses (34% - 35%) while feeders such as Waterworks < 27% and Fermie 32% - 34% with lesser domestic and more industrial consumers show a lower distribution losses. The research also showed that distribution losses (31.1%) are lower in the month with higher energy supply and higher (34.4%) in month with lower energy supplied for Fermie feeder and applicable also to other feeders. Moreso, the losses were computed in monetary terms done annually.

PHCN charge the sum of N12.82k for 1kWh and assuming that this for all loads (commercial, industrial and residential), multiplying this amount with the distribution loss estimated would yield the total revenue supposedly lost to distribution losses and NTL's for the period of 6 month estimated. Let the total revenue loosed be R_L

$$R_L = 12.82 \sum E_L (\text{naira})$$

(8.0)

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Upon application of equation 8.0 into the obtained data for the three feeders, total loss values (TL'S and NTL's) were computed and shown in tables 8.0 and 9.0 respectively.

Table 8.0 Revenue Lost in Distribution network for 6 month

MONTH	$\sum E_i(\text{kWh})$	$R_L = 12.82\sum E_i(\text{NAIRA})$
FERMIE	2,764,706.69	35,443,539.77
WATERWORKS	749,719.62	9,611,405.53
RIVOC	3,508,091.96	44,973,738.93
RAINBOW	3,930,497.38	50,388,976.42
Total	10,953,015.65	140,417,660.65

Table 9.0 revenue lost to NTL's for 6 month

MONTH	$\sum \text{NTL}(\text{kWh})$	$R_L = 12.82\sum E_i(\text{NAIRA})$
FERMIE	2,579,405.18	33,067,974.41
WATERWORKS	725,767.39	9,304,337.94
RIVOC	3,303,052.28	42,345,130.23
RAINBOW	3,708,066.92	47,537,417.91
Total	9,316,291.77	132,254,860.50

It can be seen from table 8.0 and 9.0 that a very large amount of N140, 417,660.60 is lost over the period of 6 month as TL's and NTL's amounted to N132,254,860.50

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research so far as shown that NTL's pose greater part of total losses in power system and majority of these are as a result of electricity pilferage. Reduction of NTL's requires regular monitoring, innovation and persistence. Six months analysis for Trans Amadi injection substation has shown that the cost of these

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losses (both distribution and NTL's) ranges between 26-37% of the total billed estimates of total energy delivered. NTL's have significant effect on the revenue collected each month by power utility company. If uncontrolled can bring huge financial losses. These losses are mostly accounted for by illegal connections, meter tampering, and errors due to record-keeping and metering inaccuracies such as equipment malfunction. This appalling state will continue to suffice if strict measures are not put in place. The effect of illegal connection can result in transformer overloading and life-span reduction. Rivers State Government should play a major role in combating this trend as it can bring a total collapse in the power sector due to revenue loss. The Government should not turn blind eye on these losses and must role out structures to reduce these losses to its barest minimum to lure huge private investors into the power industries and increase profit.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations to curb this power challenge include: fine and imprisonment, effective monitoring system, Implementation of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), Public Enlightenment etc.

Fines and Imprisonment: - There should be strict punitive laws to enforce those perpetrators caught in such illicit act to pay compulsory fines or face jail term.

Effective Monitoring System: - Routine monitoring teams should be setup to inspect each household and commercialized building for any form of illegal connections or meter tampering and to notify relevant personnel in PHCN of such acts.

Implementation of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI):- Advanced Metering Infrastructure is the means of providing effective data acquisition procedures, remote metering and monitoring of electricity consumption by using the best available technology. Since most NTL's losses are attributed to analog meters, full implementation of pre-paid energy meters will reduce drastically problems accounted for by these losses and as such give no room of any fictitious activities being committed by fraudulent customers.

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Public Enlightenment: - The public should be aware of the adverse effects of illegal connections or meter tampering and should be brought to their understanding the dangers NTL's pose to the economy and power sector.

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DETERMINATION OF RADIATION LEAKAGE OF A TYPICAL COBALT-60 TELETHERAPY UNIT

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KEYWORDS: Radiation, Dosimetry, Gantry, Dose rate and Radiotherapy

ABSTRACT

Radiation dose survey was carried out around the head of Cobalt-60 machine in ABUTH Zaria, purposely to assess the shielding integrity of the gantry. LiF TLD chips and portable digital dose rate meter (Atomtex)

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where used in this research. The results indicated a higher value of 1.8mSv/h and a lower 1.55mSv/h (with TLD placed on the gantry). Using Atomtex digital dose rate meter, a higher dose rate 52.00 μ Sv/h and a lower 00.62 μ Sv/h were recorded. Radiation doses ranging from 0.33 μ Sv/h to 0.65 μ Sv/h were obtained within the treatment room. The results show that the depleted lead covering the housing of the 229.061 TBq Co-60 gamma ray beam unit was able to shield the radiation source as required. The radiation dose measured was lower than the acceptable values as recommended by the ICRP.

INTRODUCTION

Radiation is a form of energy which is capable of producing biological effects on living cells (Greening, 1985). Radiation exposure occurs naturally example from cosmic rays the food we eat excreta and as a result of scientific or technological manipulations. When radiation is used at controlled level, a tremendous benefit can be derived. There is wide range of beneficial application radiation in life. Radiation and nuclear application in health science can be diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive (Groth, 2000). Radiation therapy is the last option for the treatment of cancerous cells (MLA, 2009). Amongst the types of Radiotherapy are Teletherapy, Brachotherapy and Chemotherapy.

Radiotherapy involves the treatment of cancer aimed to deliver a high radiation dose from some distance to the affected part of the patient (Alan et al 1986). The process is carried out without causing excessive injury to the surrounding healthy tissues.

Radiotherapy could be carried out with accelerated particles and x-rays or gamma rays. The gamma ray beam unit consists of Radium-226, Caesium-137 or Cobalt-60. Early units using Radium had the advantage of a long half-life and an effectively constant output dose rate. However the potential leakage of Radon gas, low specific activities and the very high photon energy made the protection of the source house of Radium very difficult. Nowadays Radium sources are replaced with Cobalt-60 sources. At “beam off” condition, the lead protects the radiographer to attend to the patients and other staff (cleaners for instance) to carry out their duties. Also at “beam off” condition, the lead reduces the level of radiation reaching part s of the patient other than the treatment area and reduces also the level of radiation reaching the walls of the treatment room. The gamma ray therefore needs to be housed in protective shield such that the gamma ray

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air, *KERMA* rates (kinetic energy absorbed per unit mass) at the surface and at 1.0m from the source are below accepted limits. The major part of the source housing will be heavy alloy, depleted Uranium or lead. This protective material will surround the sources in all direction except the direction of the useful beam. It is imperative to carryout routine leakage radiation test in any installation to ensure effective protection surrounding the head. Complete check is required to ensure leakage radiation is below the acceptable limits and to ensure there are no weaknesses such as cracks, or pinholes in the material used (Groth 2000). The concern for the paper is at the beam-off condition. In this situation any abnormal radiation can cause radiation hazard to the patients and or radiation workers. This paper presented the results of leakage radiation assessment through the limited attenuation afforded by the Cobalt-60 source housing.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

MATERIALS

The cobalt 60 was at ABUTH purposely to deliver successive doses of radiation energy to the affected part of the patient (Radiotherapy of cancer). The machine was brought to be used in Nigeria (Elegba1995) in collaboration with IAEA.

An X-ray and gamma ray digital dose rate meter (Atomtex) was the direct survey reading dosimeter used to carry out part of measurement. The other parts measurement was carried out with LiF TLD (Lithium Fluoride Thermo luminescence dosimeter) chips. The measurements were carried out at “*beam off*” condition. The Atomtex is self calibrated and manufactured with range 50nSv-10Sv/h. The Cobalt-60 machine was a 229.061 TBq (6190.84Ci). The CIRUS CO model was ensured leakage free at the time of manufacture. It was installed in the Oncology and Radiotherapy center at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital in Zaria Kaduna state of Nigeria (ABUTH) The Solaro TLD reader, TLD chips and the Atom text dose rate meter were obtained CERT ABU Zaria and the measurements were carried out at the centre under professional supervision.

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Figure 1.0 Head of Cobalt-60 machine (Gantry) Showing the marked survey points.

Both measurements were carried out on these points.

Following the Co-60 machine installation, the decay scheme of the radioactive isotopes is shown in figure 2.

Cobalt-60 is produced by bombarding cobalt-59 with fast moving neutrons and decay to Nickel-60 by emitting a beta -particle and two gamma -rays

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METHODS

Two TLD chips inside envelopes separated 1.0cm were placed on the marked points. These chips were kept for a duration of 65 hours which was the estimated time at ‘beam off’ condition over the weekend. The TLD chips were pre-annealed and with the same Cobalt-60 machine at SSD (source –skin- distance) 1.0cm, the chips were then calibrated. The calibrations and all readings were effected using Solaro TLD reader.

TLD calibration: Two annealed TLDS were assigned in an envelope 1.0cm apart and each set were exposed to gamma ray radiation of the Co-60 at the same source to TLD distance but with varying time of exposure. The corresponding Doses were obtained applying.

Dose = Dose rate x time 1

Dose rate = $\Gamma \frac{A}{r^2}$ 2

Where $\Gamma = 0.302 \frac{MGy/hr}{GBq/hr}$ is the specific gamma activity; A is the activity of the source and r is the distance from the source to the irradiated material.

But $A = A_0 e^{-\lambda t}$ 3

Where $\lambda = 0.693/T_{1/2}$ the radioactivity decay constant.

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Co-60 has $T_{1/2} = 5.3$ years. The activity of the source was determined at the time the research using the manufacture value and applying equation 3. From equation 2 the dose rate was calculated as 885.9117mGy/min. Time of exposures were varied obtaining various doses in mGy. The corresponding number of counts were obtained and plotted

A linear relationship was established by Dose against number of counts from the TLD reader. The result was used to determine the TLD dose rate as indicated in table 1.

Within the treatment room however, the TLD chips were not used because of the limited time at beam off. The direct survey meter was used at sample points which were marked randomly. At each point, three readings were recorded and the average recorded as one value corresponding to its code. These sections will comparatively indicate whether the walls are radioactive.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the result of radiation dose measured at the gantry of the Cobalt -60 machine in the treatment room.

Table 1.0 Radiation level at the Gantry

Table 1.0 Radiation Dose level at the Gantry

Code	Dose rate (Atomtex) $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ at 5-10 cm	Dose rate (TLD) mSv/h on the surface
C ₀₁	52.00	1.81
C ₀₂	42.00	1.63
C ₀₃	00.62	1.55
C ₀₄	12.30	1.59

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C0 ₅	29.00	1.60
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Radiation dose level in the treatment room with Atomtex is carefully displayed in table 2.

Table 2.0 Radiation Dose level around the C0-60 machine

Code	Dose rate (Atomtex) $\mu\text{Sv/h}$	Description of sample points
C0 ₆	0.51	At the first wall
C0 ₇	0.65	Far, top of machine
C0 ₈	0.64	At the bench
C0 ₉	0.33	At the second wall
C0 ₁₀	0.55	At the third wall
C0 ₁₁	0.33	At the forth wall
C0 ₁₂	0.49	Smoke detector

DISCUSSION

(Bonford et al 2000) published in his book the leakage air, *kerma* rate permitted from gamma ray beam units at beam off 0.1 mGy/hr maximum and average 0.02mGy/hr (at 1.0m from source). At 5.0cm from the source should not exceed 2.0mGy/hr. Table 3.0

Table3.0 Leakage air kerma rates permitted from gamma ray beam units

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	At 1m from Maximum	Source Average	At 5cm from surface
Beam off	0.1mGyh ⁻¹	0.02mGyh ⁻¹	2.0mGyh ⁻¹
Beam on	0.1%	–	–
Beam on (small units)	10mGyh ⁻¹	–	–

The percentage value at 'beam on' is of the useful beam kerma rate at 1m (**Bonford et al 2000**)

The dose rate obtained with the TLD is higher because it is closer to the radiation source. The TLDs were in contact with the gantry while the dose rate meter was at 5.0-10.0cm away from the gantry. Also the inconsistent of the TLD results with the dose rate meter may not be due to the fact that there is difference in the elemental material volume. since their relative distances from the gantry were not the same. Following fact that radiation dose decreases with increasing distance (inverse square law) the two results were are relatively comparable.

The TLD materials cannot be pre-annealed completely and transporting the TLD from the Teaching hospital may slightly affect the dose rate. However both measurements were carried out within fairly the same background.

Faria, (1995) published that TLDs have been extensible employed for environmental radiation measurements in some Brazilian radioactive facilities. They have low fading, high sensitivity and cumulatively. L/F is $Z_{\text{effective}}$ nearly tissue equivalent (Z_{eff} for tissue is 7.4) Christiansen et al, (1982) and Cember, (1986). Hence the TLDs used in the research are suitable.

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A typical cobalt-60 teletherapy unit could be the moving source or the fixed source type. The point Co₁ has relatively limited attenuation or is at the position where the source is stationed at beam off. This maybe the account for the higher radiation recorded. The sample point Co₃ with lower radiation level, could possess higher attenuation ability or away from the radiation source (Table 1.0)

In table 2.0 however points Co₉ and Co₁₁ are farther away from the machine this may be the account of lower radiation level. These doses also indicated the presence radioactive facility. Co₈ is closer the machine and Co₇ the bench maybe induced with radiation due to strays of radiation and ionization of the surrounding.

CONCLUSION

An average radiation dose of 0.50 μ Sv/h was determined in the treatment room also showing the presence radioactive facilities. This value is slightly above the out door radiation background limit

The position co₁ is likely adjacent to the point where radiation source is positioned at beam off. The other position co₃ is farther away from the radiation source at the beam off condition or subjected to thicker lead shielding. Co₉ and Co₁₁ were indoors radiation. Although the energy of the source reduces as it decays with time prolong staying in the treatment room may cause accumulation of radiation does. Touching the gantry for long time especially at co₁ could also result to unexpected exposure which could lead to biological effect. The concern for the paper is the beam off condition .However the limited attenuation afforded by the cobalt -60 machine housing is able to shield normally the radiation source.

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EFFECT OF FLOODING IN LOKOJA URBAN ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses attention on the hazard of flooding, which have become a menace in recent times. The effect of which are huge losses recorded in life and property. Urban areas which are expected to be safer are not spared of this menace. The occurrence of the flooding is as a result of bad planning and bad choice of settlement sites. Poverty owes its own expression in dictating to people where they should settle. Lokoja township which is the area of study, also show that there is poor attitude to management of the environment in terms of refuse disposal and the erection of structures in areas of high risk. The heavy rainfall in the months of July, August and September is another major factor. Flood waters often jump artificial drains which were inadequate in some cases, the drafts silt up. It is suggested that there should be a well articulated and comprehensive physical planning and land use planning control.

KEYWORDS: Rainfall, planning, urban areas, high risk, environment

INTRODUCTION

Flood occurs when more rainfalls than the soil and vegetation can absorb. The excess water runs off the land in greater quantities than rivers, streams, ponds and wet lands can contain. Such heavy rains, periodically cause rivers to overflow their banks, spilling onto the surrounding floodplains. In an urbanizing environment, the infiltration capacity is further reduced by the replacement of ground cover with impervious urban surfaces. Under such conditions, surface overland flow becomes the dominant method of disposal of excess rainwater. The term urban flood can be defined as any overland flow over urban streets sufficient to causes significant property damage, traffic obstructions, nuisance and health hazards. It includes river flood, flash floods and flood pondages (Rashedd, 2008).

Across the globe, studies show that more than two billion people representing one-third of the world's population have been subjected to natural disasters in the last decade, with floods and droughts accounting

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for 86 percent of all such catastrophes. The studies indicate that although earthquakes, volcanic eruptions and landslides may be more dramatic, and take a very high toll on human lives.

Floods have longer lasting and more far-reaching effects on the health of ordinary people (world socialist web site, WSWS, 5 October, 2002). It is common in flood plains, along longer rivers and coastal areas. If such area are not settled by man, the water attracts little or no attention, but when such areas are settled with large population such as the Ganges, Nile, Mississippi, Hwang Ho and Niger Benue flood plains, flooding becomes a menace causing great disaster to lives and properties (Giwa, 2006).

WSWS reported on April 2000 that south East Africa experienced the heaviest rain storms in 50 years as a result of three weeks of downpours. The floods that swept through the neighboring countries of South Africa, Botswana and Zimbabwe had particularly hit Mozambique some places experience a whole years rainfall in just three days. Mozambique was effectively cut to two by the flood water north of the capital Maputo. The river valleys of the Limpopo, the Elephant river and Save river broke their banks and flooded enormous tract of land.

On 8 August 2005, heavy rains that lasted for non hours caused flood with unusual heavy currents in Jalingo, the state capital of Taraba. A bridge collapsed when the Jalingo River burst its banks as a result of the heavy down pour. 60,000 people were displaced from the homes and over 200 people died as a result of the floods. The flooding was said to be unprecedented in the last 30 years. It cleaved away major bridges and road networks linking the city with other parts of the country (International Federation Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 14 March, 2007). Similarly, at least 24 persons were confirmed dead in Song Local Government Area of Adamawa State, as flash flood left at least three Local Government Areas devastated following two day of torrential rainfall. The flood which affected Yola North and South and Song Local Government, left hundreds of building and hectares of farmland submerged, while the song Galamayo bridge was washed away (This Day, 7 August, 2007).

Severe flooding has become an almost annual occurrence in Nigeria especially in the northern part of Nigeria. In 1989, flooding in Kano State resulted in the loss of 142 lives, destruction of 160,000 housed,

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washing away of 12,000 farms, displacement of 180,000 people and damage of residences and infrastructure worth about 520 million naira (NEST, 1991). In 1999, 38 people lost their lives and more than 200,000 people were displaced in the worst flood in 40 years in Niger State (BBC News, October 6, 1999). In 2000, twenty people died and 48,000 displaced after floods hit the state of Kano.

In Jigawa, 180 deaths were registered, 700 people injured and 35,000 displaced (WSWS, 5 October, 2001). In September 2003, property worth millions of naira were lost as a result of a heavy downpour which swelled the waters of river kaduna. The most affected areas are settlements that have located close to the banks of the river (Adejo, 2003).

Urban development process giver rise to increase runoff generation in response to removal of vegetation and concomitant increase in soil compaction and poor planning which invariably encouraged erosion and flooding phenomenon (Slay Maker, 2001). Lokoja town has experienced a number of flood disaster in the past years, (1932, 1965, 1980, 2012). In October, 2012 flood disasters were recorded in Lokoja and its environment as a result of the swelling of River Niger and Benue due to up stream discharge of rivers beyond the Nigeria boarder and heavy rainfall. The effects are the displacement of people and destruction of property worth millions of naira.

The intensity of flood problems over time and space in Nigeria Urban centres is closely related to the rapid rate of urban expansion, especially where the simultaneous provisions for an adequate urban runoff disposal system is lacking as it is in most Nigeria cities (Onoker horaye, 1995). The risk of flooding is derived as a function of both the probability of a flood happening and its impact. In urban areas, the impact can be very high because the areas affected are mostly built up area and contain vital infrastructure (post, 2007).

Many floods events in Lokoja have cause little damage and usually soon forgotten, except by those most directly affected, the floods of October, 2012 due to the swelling of River Niger and Benue, resulted in major disasters. The flood event of last year alone resulted in erosion damage, destruction of socio-economic activities, displacement of thousands of people, and damage of residences and infrastructure

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worth millions of naira (oral interviews, 2012). This calls for a study of the underlying causes of flood in Lokoja town.

THE STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in Lokoja town, the state capital of Kogi State and the headquarters of Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State (Fig 1)

MAP OF KOGI STATE SHOWING THE STUDY AREA

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The geology consists of under laid Precambrian rocks of the basement complex which are mainly granite, gneiss and quartzite. These rocks have had a complex history involving several phase of orogenesis and subsequent regional uplift and depression. These movements have determined the main pattern of drainage and the regional pattern of erosion and sedimentation since early cretaceous time (Ologe, 1995).

Climatically, the duration, intensity and the spatial spread of rainfall in Lokoja is generally controlled by the intertropical discontinuity (ITD). The rainy season begins when the ITD is north of the study area. The

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main monthly temperature rainfall is about 1680mm, while the main monthly temperature is 32c⁰. The relative humidity is about 58%.

The vegetation falls within the Guinea Savanna of the middle belt with tall grasses and trees of different kinds, while the soil is the tropical ferruginous mostly formed on granite and gneiss parell materials (Abaje, 2007).

The town (Lokoja) has witnessed a tremendous growth in population and area coverage during the last 22yrs. The built-up areas have expanded within the same period in an attempt by individuals, groups and government to meet the increasing demands for residential houses, roads, markets, parks and institutional facilities. The development of these urban facilities involves the replacement of the vegetation cover with impervious urban land use surfaces which increases surface run off.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Climatic data were collected from the Hydrology section of the Kogi State Water Board Investigation Department, Lokoja. These were used in calculating the mean annual and monthly rainfall, mean monthly temperature and relative humidity of the study area.

A steel tape was used to make direct measurement of the residential houses from the River Niger Bank. Measurement of the river to the build-up area were also taken. From the Muritala Bridge down stream, 70 houses along the river down to Ganaja Village were selected through systematic sampling. Flood affected persons and others residing close to the flood prone areas were randomly sampled to obtain information about their perceptual assessment of the intensity, causes and damage from the flood of October, 2012. During and after rainstorms, the researcher drove along the flood plain and major roads and streets in order to make proper observations and report appropriately what was witnessed from the field.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

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TABLE 1: YEARLY DISCHARGE RECORD OF NIGER RIVER AND RAINFALL.

Year	Rainfall (mm)	Minimum discharge	Maximum discharge	Range	Mean water level
2008	25	3628	17713	14085	8.8
2009	22	2811	19914	13103	9.4
2010	100	2700	15548	12848	8.2
2011	130	2664	23491	20827	10.5
2012	140	3756	24486	21836	10.63

Source: Extracted from NIWA gange record in Lokoja.

Table I above shows the mean rainfall in the town for the 2008-2012 periods. A close examination of the figure shows a peak range in the month of October, 2012. While the maximum discharge was in the month of October, 2012 resulted in high antecedent precipitation index (APT). The consequential effect due to the heavy rainfall was the flood hazard of that year. The result of direct field measurement of residential house from the Niger bank and of the river is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2: DISTANCE OF RESIDENTIAL HOUSES FROM RIVER BANK AND WIDTH.

Distance From River Bank	Width
7.80	5.65
0.27	5.40
1.40	5.40
1.54	5.40
9.40	4.60
2.24	4.60
1.65	4.30
1.73	5.30
1.74	5.30
10.44	3.40

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Total = 38.21	Total = 49.35
Mean Distance= 3.82	Mean Width= 4.94

Source: field work, 2013

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2002 2003 2004 2005 2006 2007 2008 2009 2010 2011 2012

Volumetry Discharge of Niger River at Lokoja.

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Field observations show that increasing frequency and severity of floods do not stem from, heavy rainfall alone. It is noted that increasing rate of urbanization in the absence of well articulated and comprehensive physical planning and land use planning control have caused the banks to be heavily settled. There are situations where buildings are at zero distance from the bank of the river. The further measured distance is 10.44 meters, where the surging waves of the flood did not spare, when it occurred recently. In some houses the flood water level reached between 0.30-0.72m downstream of the studied area.

There is visible evidence of the river expanding its channel width through lateral erosion around Pakta and Ganaja road; as a result, some residential houses have already been vacated before flooding. Where man has built hard concrete walk or floors, erosion under mines such efforts with a high vulnerability of a collapse in the near future. All these result from high and sudden urban storm runoff which forcefully releases its waters down the channel due to inadequate drainage facilities and dumping of refuse in drains and drainage paths. Impervious roads surface and built up surface also intercept rainfall which accumulates to form flood water.

Field observation shows that the river channel expansion is due to intensive farming enticed by the rich alluvial deposits and the constant tramping by human as path ways, domestic animals and especially pigs that often retire to the river in the hot afternoons. They often dig the mud and create caves which are easily, enlarged by wave action in the rainy season.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Flooding is a major environmental problem in Lokoja, Kogi State. It is not even more frequent but more severe and devastating in recent times especially the flood of October, 2012. The severity do not only result from heavy rainfall alone, but also increasing rate of urbanization without proper physical planning and land use planning control to cope with the development. Floods are therefore likely to increase in the study area if no changes are made to increase to the management of the River Niger that passes through the town (Lokoja). This can be a major source of water pollution.

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Rather than accepting the flooding as an inevitable product of nature, however, the residents, political leaders, engineering and environmental specialists have to look into the human actions that causes the severity of the flood and what steps might be taken in the future to avoid or mitigate another such catastrophe.

It is suggested that land use planning should avoid developing and building on flood plains, and policy for handling problems of floods should also include discouraging land users from engaging in activities in flood prone areas that have great potentials for runoff through enforceable land use laws. Based on the findings in this study, the provision of adequate drainage facilities should be an important segment of all development planning programs in the study areas. It is also recommended that River channel should constantly be cleared of trash materials as accumulation of such could easily block passage of the water and hence result in severe cases of flooding. Runoff can also be checked by retention ponds and other creative means to avoid much overland flow of water. In order to combat flooding effectively in the study area, it is recommended that the physical and human determinants of flooding should be understand. This calls for environmental management and perception studies.

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8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF AUTOMATED PRECISION COIL WINDER AIDED WITH
COMPUTER INTERPHASE

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ABSTRACT

This work is on design and construction of automated precision coil winder aided with computer inter phase. The essence is to overcome the challenges inherent in analogue winding machines such as over winding, misalignment, non-uniform windings, inaccuracy and slowness in windings among others. The design is an electromechanical system (consist of both electric and mechanical section) and were analyzed accordingly. Performance assessment was then carried out and found the machine to be satisfactory in overcoming these peculiar challenges of analogue machines

INTRODUCTION

Coils are used practically for all kinds of electrical applications such as transformers, relays, motors, generators, inductors, solenoids, fans, etc. Originally, coils were wound by hand, thus only few coils could be produced at a time and subsequently had lots of winding problems of different kinds. As demand increases the need to wound coils in large quantity, with improved quality, hence the need for automation (J.C. Darley, 1998) arises. Gradually, coil winding machines were invented beginning with manual (hand-crank operated) winding machine to the current coil winding machines with mechanical counters that are still currently been improved upon through modern innovations. Winding coils manually usually results in some problems such as; over-winding or overshoot and non-uniformity of wires across each pole (Penrose H.W, 1999), thus reducing the quality of the wound coil, because electromechanical properties of electric coil depends on turns ratio of coil, and the uniformity of the outlay of the wires for stable uniform magnetic flux. The technology involved in coil windings in terms of gauge accuracy and speed to meet the ever increasing demand for these electrical appliances is still a challenge. This paper aim to design and construct automatic digital coil winder prototype as an alternative to manual/hand winding and analogue winders. This will be achieved by applying embedded microprocessor control technology, precision stepping and computer software-based control to produce and a highly-accurate automatic machine. This design is limited to winding medium or small gauges of range between 20-40 ASWG (American Standard Wire Gauge). The work also tried to correct manual coil winding defects such as disarrangement, misalignment

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and non-uniformity of the windings per pole that often tend to lower reliability and reduced performance of electrical appliances/devices (J. Allen and others, 2003).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Their variety of applications and widespread use has made coil winding an important process to produce quality coils to meet consumer demands. As a result, coil winding techniques and machine prototypes have been designed over the years to eliminate problems associated with older models and to keep up with technological advances, incorporating new innovations to create better, faster, cheaper, safer, more versatile and superior models. Some previous designs and techniques include the work by J.R. Langham 1948, H.D Woodward 1960, C.Ronald *et al* 1999, T.Gary 2005 among others. J.R. Langham's work in 1948 presented classic hand-winding techniques used for coil winding. Despite using Lathe machine and mechanical counter, the researcher admitted that the final wound coils had faults and there were several overlaps in the turns. Langham then gave about 7 tips to wound a neat coil to improve the systems/appliance efficiency. H.D Woodward's own design in 1960 incorporated analog automation to solve the deficiencies resulting from the hand-winding or manual winding techniques previously used. His model was based on a single DC motor, to which a spindle was attached and held on bearings. The coil former (core) on which the coil is to be wound is placed on the spindle and secured in place by cone brackets. The transverse drive, which guides the wire being wound horizontally, to ensure they are neatly arranged on the coil, was fabricated using brass with two rollers to guide the wires, attached to it. While this design innovatively eliminates the problem of overlapping windings and produced more consistent layers, the problem of over wind and human errors still remains. R Casser *et al* in 1999 designed and constructed Coil winding machine. The prototype design of R Casser *et al* is an improved version of the work of H.D Woodward, though both systems are analog automation models. However, a few additional features make their design superior to that of Woodward. Fast or slow wound is possible though some problems of overshoot/over wound still persist and if the transverse is misaligned for any reason, it leads to series of overlapping windings for each turn and the coil will have to be driven back and forward again and again. T Gary in 2005 designed and constructed coil winder and the mechanical counter used for analog model by previous researchers was replaced with two 7 stage ripple counters. The limitation to this design is that it has foot pedal which means it is directly controlled by human operators hence affecting the quality of final wound coil (human error).

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L.Robert in 2009 designed and constructed computer controlled high stepping automatic coil winder with limitation of not been able to alter the already written program. F. Jorg and D Andreas in 2012 designed and constructed Robot-Based Winding-Process for Flexible Coil Production. These researchers introduced robotics technology to the field of coil winding and based their method on industrial delta-robot which places the wire on a programmable trajectory. The winding movement is generated solely by moving the wire guide on a bobbin-adapted trajectory. This approach offers several advantages particularly as the winding motion can easily be adapted to the requirements of different winding products and made it possible to wind virtually any winding pattern on arbitrary formed cores without special wire guides. For example, some electronic products require windings to be integrated into the circuit board or housing. Such “integrated windings” can easily be made using this method (J. Franke and A. Dodbroschke, 2012). The short coming of this approach is that programming the free-trajectory tripod robot is not easy for general users as it requires some skilled knowledge. Furthermore, this machine is adapted mainly for winding customized coils (J. Franke and A. Dodbroschke, 2012). The winding speed is slower here and hence it cannot do volume (bulk) work quickly.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The automatic coil winder is an electromechanical system hence both the electrical and mechanical design is considered. This design is implemented using Direct Current (DC) stepper motors for precision stepping, microcontroller for enhanced control preset inputs, liquid crystal display (LCD) to readout /display the status of the winding process at any instant, Universal Serial Bus (USB), software from which it can be controlled, power rectification unit, supply circuits and motor control circuits. DC stepper motor is used because of its ability to rotate precise angle in response to a particular input. The motor is controlled using Darlington transistor based motor drive integrated circuit. The microcontroller receives the inputs (required no of turns) from the preset input keypad or a PC through the USB port and then processes the input and control the motor via the motor control circuit. The output is displayed through the LCD. Feedback to the microprocessor is configured using turn counter made as “slotted switch” to give one input per revolution of the motor & coil spindle. Figure 1.0 shows control block diagram depicting the design methodology.

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Figure 1.0: Simple Control Block Diagram Depicting the Design Methodology
Power Supply: The power supply unit consists of step-down transformer, rectification unit, filtering and voltage stabilization circuit. It receives input of 220V AC rms and supply voltages of 12V and 5V DC for the stepper motor and the microcontroller respectively. Power supply circuit is shown in figure 2.0.

Knowledge for Global Development

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Figure 2.0: Power Supply Circuit

The transformer receives 220V supply at the primary, from the mains and produce 12V AC output at the secondary. The secondary terminals are then connected to a full wave bridge rectifier to produce 12V DC output. Thus the full wave bridge rectifier gives a rectified 12V DC output. This is then applied to the electrolytic filter capacitor connected in parallel to give 12V DC ripple voltage required by the stepper motor. For the microcontroller 5V DC stabilized voltage is required. This is obtained using 7805 voltage regulator IC, which converts the 12V DC ripple voltage to a stabilized 5V DC voltage for the micro controller. Thus the power supply block produces 5V DC regulated voltage applied to the microcontroller and a 12V DC voltage applied to the motor drive circuit.

Microcontroller: The microcontroller used is AT89S52 because of its low-power, high-performance CMOS 8-bit microcontroller with 8K bytes programmable Flash memory and it is designed with static logic for operation down to zero frequency and supports two software selectable power saving modes. The Idle Mode stops the CPU while allowing the RAM, timer/counters, serial port, and interrupt system to continue functioning. The Power-down mode saves the RAM contents but freezes the oscillator, disabling all other chip functions until the next interrupt or hardware reset. The idle mode is used for this work to allow the RAM to receive inputs while the machine is idle, so that the machine will drain its stored power and have to be reset every time it is left idle for a while. It consists of 32 single byte (8-bit) registers, accumulator (Acc), two temporary registers TMP2 & TMP1, flag register – PSW (Program Status Word), stack pointer, instruction register, program counter, memory address register, interrupt address register, timing and control unit and linked to both the RAM address register, and internal flash memory. The 32 input/output lines form 4 ports (8-bit each) – port 0, 1, 2, 3 & 4 through which it can receive inputs and

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instructions and produce outputs. The timing signal is generated externally by a suitable crystal oscillator within the range of 1 – 22MHz. The more the speed required, the more the current consumption. For this work, balance speed and current consumption is chosen at 11.0592MHz. This timing signal along with the various control signals will be applied to the timing and control register. The AT89S52 microcontroller is used as the main control element. It will receive inputs from the keypad and PC, drive the stepper motor and output to the LED display.

Motor drive circuit: The motor drive circuit is based on ULN2003A IC package. It is a high voltage/ high current Darlington array, each containing 7 open collector Darlington pair's with common emitters, integrated on a single chip (STMicroelectronics, 2002). Figure 3.0 is the Diagram Showing Each Driver (Grounding Omitted) [ST Microelectronics, 2002]

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Each channel is rated at 500mA and can withstand peak currents of 600mA. Suppression diodes are included for inductive load driving and the inputs are pinned opposite the outputs to simplify the board layouts. This ULN2003A version is a 5V package that can interface to the TTL, CMOS logic families and the micro controller unit. So it is compatible with the motor drive IC. The ULN2003A is powered by 12V DC, which it supplies to the motor. It has 16 pins. Each pin on the left side is the input pin with its corresponding output pin opposite to it, i.e. IN 1→OUT 16, IN2→OUT 15 etc. Pin 9 is point of application of the 12VDC power and pin 8 is the ground (GND). When a high pulse (+5V = logical 1) is supplied to pin 1, its output pin (16)–is connected to ground, causing the power supply of 12V DC to flow through it to the particular stepper motor terminal it is connected to, and the motor rotates through one step angle. Similarly, applying a high pulse to pin 2 causes 12V DC to flow through pin 15 to the next motor terminal producing further rotation through another precise step angle. Applying a high pulse to pin 3 causes 12V DC to flow through pin 14 and so on till pin 7. This way, the IC can drive the stepper motor through as many precise rotations as desired, depending on the number of applied pulses. These high/low pulses are achieved through the programmed microcontroller AT89S52.

Stepper Motors: Stepper motor is a form of synchronous motor, which rotates at precise angular distance (called step) for each pulse that is delivered to its drive circuit. (J. B. Gupta, 2011). Because the step pulses can be counted digitally and stopped when the desired number have been delivered, stepper motors lend themselves to digital control by a programmable controller or on-line computer. These motors can also provide precise open-loop speed control, since their rotational speed is determined solely by the step pulse

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frequency, independent of load (J. B. Gupta, 2011). DC unipolar stepper motors of the variable reluctance are used for this work. The motors both have step angles of 7.5° (i.e each energizing of its coil should rotate the shaft 7.5°). This means the number of pulses required to wind a given number of turns can be obtained directly. Say 20 turns is required to be wound; $1 \text{ turn} = 360^\circ$; $20 \text{ turns} = 360^\circ \times 20 = 7200^\circ \therefore$
 $\text{no. of pulses} = \frac{7200^\circ}{7.5^\circ} = 960 \text{ pulses}$. Therefore sending 960 pulses to the stepper motor through the motor drive IC will cause it to wind 20 turns with precision. This is the basic principle of operation of the automatic coil winder. The microcontroller would calculate the number of pulses using the formula;
 $\text{no. of pulses} = \frac{\text{no. of turns} \times 360^\circ}{\text{step angle}}$

Programmed into it, generate the required number of pulses and apply it to the stepper motor through the motor drive IC.

LCD Output Display: The LCD employed to display the output number of turns and other readings is the LCD – 016MOO2B by Vishay and it is a 16×2 character LCD. Pin 1 (Vss) for ground, & +5V power is supplied through pin 2 (Vdd). Pin 3 is for contrast adjustment through which the dark or light contrast may be adjusted i.e. the display intensity may be made darker or lighter. Pin 4 (RS) is used to send commands/data – Commands when activated high and data when activated low. Commands include: shift position, register select, etc. Pin 5 (R/W) is the read/write pin – read when activated high and write when activated low. Pin 6 (E) is the enable pin to toggle between a high and low state, i.e. $H \rightarrow L$ & $L \leftarrow H$. Pin 7 – 14 ($DB_0 - DB_7$) form the main data bus line and can also be active high or active low. Pin 15 & 16 (A/Vee and K) form the power supply for the back lighting provided using +4.2V LED to provide the extra lighting required to view the contents of the LCD display.

Keypad: The keypad used for the automatic coil winder is a generic 4×4 input keypad formed from an array of push button switches. When awaiting an input, the microcontroller continuously scans all the 4 rows (row A, B, C & D) in turn with a +5V DC input and checks each of the 4 columns (column 1, 2, 3 & 4) simultaneously for an output. If say key 8 is depressed, a +5V output will occur at column 4 from row D, which corresponds to 08D (8 – decimal) to the microcontroller. If say key 9 is depressed, a +5V output will

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occur at column 1 from row C, which corresponds to 09D (9 – decimal) to the microcontroller. This way any number of inputs can be sent to the microcontroller. Keys A –F may also be configured for special functions and commands.

RS232 Logic Level Converter: The microcontroller functions using two logic levels; +5V for high and 0V for low. Most computers however are designed to function using logic levels of the range of +3 to +12 (high) and -3 to -12 (low). For example, a typical HP laptop/system uses +7 & -7 for it's high and low voltage levels. For this reason, there cannot be direct communication between a PC and the microcontroller. In order to facilitate communication between a PC and the device microcontroller, a logic level converter is used. The RS232 logic level converter acts as an interface between the PC and the microcontroller. It converts the logic state of the PC to the logic level of the microcontroller and vice versa, while maintaining the information being transmitted.

MECHANICAL DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The first motor is attached to a spindle, on which the core is to be wound is mounted on. Shackles are present on the spindle to fasten and secure the core. The second motor is attached to a threaded spindle. On this spindle is placed wire guide using threaded rollers. The microcontroller generates the appropriate pulses to drive the winding motor. As the winding motor rotates, the wire is wound around the core. figure 4.0 shows the mechanical design diagram used for the study.

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Figure 4.0 Depiction of Mechanical Design Methodology

TESTS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, tests were carried out on various components used in constructing the automatic coil winder. These tests include both static and dynamic tests to determine their respective reliabilities, before hardware implementation. The completed coil winding machine is put through tests and performance evaluations to prove its functionality and reliability.

Components Tests

The major components used for this design are: microcontroller, two motor drive ICs, LCD, RS232/MAX232 logic level converter, input keypad, power supply module and two stepper motors. Others include; resistors, electrolytic capacitors, diodes, a transformer, crystal oscillator, bridge rectifier (full-wave), voltage regulator.

Hardware Implementation

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For the frame, wood is used because of it allows for easy modification. It is used for both the sides and bottom of the winder have a 1/2 inch nominal thickness. The sides are cut to 8" X 8", and the bottom is 8" X 18" whose supports are 3/4" X 2 1/2" X 8", and the channels cut into the supports are 3/8" deep. Both sides are set up in the channels cut into the supports. Screws are used at first to allow for later modification. A drawing depicting the measurements and placements is given in figure 6.0

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Figure 6.0 Technical Description of Frame

This base is cut to attach a nut which will guide it on the threaded spindle. A short tube is also attached to it for the other rod to balance the transverse as shown in figure 7.0

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Figure 7.0: Base for Transverse

The motors are mounted on the frame and the spindles are inserted into their respective holes as shown in figure 8.0. Motors and Spindle Mounted on Frame are shown in figure 9.0

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Figure 8.0: Motors and Spindle Mounted on Frame

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The electrical circuits are built using a Vero board. The board and its components are shown in figure 9.0 before it is mounted on the frame.

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Figure 9.0: Assembled Electrical Circuit

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CONCLUSION

This work has presented the design and construction of an automatic coil winder. Stepper motors was used for precision positioning to avoid over wound problems. The stepper motor was controlled digitally using programmable microprocessor. Most of the commercially available coil winders, being analog based requires some form of human supervisory control. This design is digital based and incorporates programmable microprocessor thus enabling it to operate automatically. An electronic LCD display was used in place of mechanical counter to display the current number of turns and eliminated eliminate deadlock problems often associated with mechanical counters due to friction at high speeds. Additional control through computer's USB (upgrade from parallel ports) interface was also included to increase its versatility and enable the winder to be programmed and controlled using computer software (in this work visual basic program was written) to automatically estimate the wire length and stop the winding process when the required number of windings are reached.

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**THE POOR STATE OF BROADBAND DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA IS AN IMPEDIMENT TO
NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND GLOBALISATION**

Ariyo Ayodeji Olusola and Olaojoyetan Modupe Christianah

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ABSTRACT

Harnessing ICT for development requires a strategic framework that takes advantage of various ICT roles which helps integrate the options made possible by technological revolution into the design and implementation of sector development strategies. As such, ICT is not just a sector of the knowledge economy, but a lens through which new possibilities and modalities of comprehensive development can be realised. There has been a competition among many nations nowadays toward the adoption of ICT as a veritable tool for national development and globalization. In spite of the rush towards the adoption of ICT by many African countries, the reports of WEF on NRI released for year 2013 reveals that many African countries are still ranked low. The review made in this paper is to investigate the causes of low rankings characterizing the African countries, Nigeria as a case study. This paper also investigated the present level of broadband ICT infrastructures available in the country and made suggestions on how the rate of broadband penetration could be increased. As a result, People from all walks of life such as youths, professionals, career personnel and host of others would benefit from the wealth embedded in ICT world. In conclusion, the recommendation was made on what to be done for Nigeria to move up some steps in NRI ladder. There are tendencies that when the country fully harness the benefits of ICT available within her that would develop the country economically and tackle the challenges of unemployment which seems to be one of the prevailing problems in Africa and even in some developed countries. Sarcastically in Nigeria, in spite of the satellite own by the country and several cables at the shore of the country, broadband penetration is presently less than 6%

KEYWORDS: WEF (World Economic Forum), NRI (Networked Readiness Index) GDP (Gross Domestic Product), Broadband , ICT Infrastructure, Optical Cables

INTRODUCTION

Access to advanced information and communication technology (ICT) is a key factor in the economic and social development of Sub-Saharan Africa. Analysis of economic data at the national level shows that

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investment in ICT results in a higher rate of long-term economic growth [1]. At the level of small businesses, research shows that access to basic ICT services can result in a sustained increase in the incomes of the poor in developing countries [2]. Although limited data make the impact of broadband harder to quantify, emerging evidence suggests that access to more advanced ICT services, such as those that require broadband connectivity for delivery, can also have a positive economic and social impact [3].

However, In spite of Nigeria's growing appetite for data to provide for high speed Internet, e-commerce, e-learning, e-health, e-business register, e-law, e-policing, e-prescription, e-governance, data ICT, and cloud computing, video and voice services, the level of ICT uptake and broadband penetration in the country is still very low. Validation of this assessment is borne out by our low position on the World Economic Forum (WEF) Networked Readiness Forum for 2013 [4].

In other to reverse the trend, urgent steps must be taken to investigate the reasons for the low rate of ICT uptake and mete out appropriate strategies and tactics to address the situation. The country needs to move up in the ladder of (Networked Readiness Index) NRI especially nowadays that ICT has become the pivot that holds growth and development

A. The Global Information Technology Report 2013

The Global Information Technology Report 2013 features the results of the NRI and offer an overview of the state of ICT readiness in the world for the year 2013. The report coverage includes a record number of 144 economies, accounting for over 98 percent of global GDP. [5]

Table 2.1: Leading 20 Countries In GITR And NRI Ranking

RANK	COUNTRY/ECONOMY	SCORE
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1	Finland	5.98
2	Singapore	5.96
3	Sweden	5.91
4	Netherlands	5.81
5	Norway	5.66
6	Switzerland	5.66
7	United Kingdom	5.64
8	Denmark	5.58
9	United States	5.57
10	Taiwan/China	5.47
11	Korea Republic	5.46
12	Canada	5.44
13	Germany	5.43
14	Hong Kong SAR	5.40
15	Israel	5.39
16	Luxembourg	5.37
17	Iceland	5.31
18	Australia	5.26
19	Austria	5.26
20	New Zealand	5.25

Table 2.2: *Leading African Countries on GTR: WEF NRI Ranking*

RANK	COUNTRY/ECONOMY	SCORE
70	South Africa	3.87
80	Egypt	3.78
81	Cape Verde	3.78
88	Rwanda	3.68

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89	Morocco	3.64
92	Kenya	3.54
95	Ghana	3.51
96	Botswana	3.50
97	Liberia	3.48
98	Gambia	3.47
110	Uganda	3.30
111	Namibia	3.29
113	Nigeria	3.27

B. Interpreting the Global Information Technology Report 2013

The Global Information Technology Report 2013 is a project within the framework of the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness and Benchmarking Network and the Industry Partnership Programme for Information and Communication Technologies. However, Networked Readiness Index (NRI) 2013 Benchmark ICT Uptake and Support for Growth and Jobs in a Hyperconnected World for the year 2013.

The NRI includes features related to access and usage that cover not only affordable ICT infrastructure but also digital resources, including software and skills. In addition, the NRI includes proxies to assessing some of the economic and social impacts accruing from ICTs. Thus, the Index facilitates the identification of areas where policy intervention—through investment, smart regulation, and/or incentives—could boost the impact of ICTs on development and growth.

The country ranked 113 out of 144 countries surveyed in the Networked Readiness Index (NRI), declining by one rank on the ladder from its position of 112 (out of 142) in the previous year's Report. However, the country inched up by 0.1 points in actual NRI scores to 3.3 points this year from 3.2 points in 2012, when measured on a scale of one (lowest) to seven (highest).

According to the latest World Economic Forum (WEF) report on Global Information Technology Report (GITR) 2013 and published with the theme Growth and jobs in a hyper connected world, it measured the

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extent to which 144 countries took advantage of ICT and other new technologies to increase their growth and well-being.

Highlight of the report about Nigeria's ICT competitiveness showed that the country has remained in the lowest quartile of countries sampled in the report. This shows the extent to which the country still grapples with the necessary conditions to close the ICT competitiveness gap with most advanced economies.

Notwithstanding this gap, the report noted that the country has improved in seeking the delivery of societal benefits from ICT by initiating a broad-based National Broadband and ICT Plan, which focuses on greater broadband adoption through intensifying the motivators of technology use.

“This is attributed to ICT Skill Development Plan incorporated in Nigeria's National Information Communication Technology (ICT) Policy Draft 2012. This development has led to Nigeria's significant improvement in one of the 10 NRI pillars - Social Impacts - ranking 88 in 2013 from 102 in 2012,” the WEF report noted.

The report also acknowledged that Nigeria's market and regulatory framework has been able to support high levels of ICT uptake, adding, however, that the cost of accessing ICT, either via mobile telephony or fixed broadband internet, has remained a constraint towards widespread technology adoption in the country. The GITR 2013 underscored Nigeria's clear divide in ICT usage between individuals and businesses.

While corporate organisations in the country have intensified their efforts to integrate ICT into business processes - improving in that regard to a rank of 68 from 77; the penetration of ICT among individuals has deteriorated to a rank of 111 from 105 in the last one year.

C. WHY NIGERIA IS RANKED LOW IN YEAR 2013 GLOBAL INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY REPORT (GITR) WEF AND NRI REPORT

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The apparent success recorded in the country's ICT sector is as a result of the great success made by the telecommunication industry. The situation in the data communication is highly incomparable. The rates of Internet usage and broadband penetration are both still very low. Though investigation shows that Nigeria is in number 10 position when considering the countries alongside their respective number of internet users but the number is a low percentage of the population of the country.

Table showing the Top 10 countries with Internet users

Rank	Country	Population of Active Internet users
1.	China	511,963,000
2.	USA	242,614,880
3.	India	119,749,712
4.	Japan	101,376,528
5.	Brazil	88,917,974
6.	Russia	69,837,538
7.	Germany	67,621,622
8.	France	51,962,632

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9.	United Kingdom	51,412,657
10.	Nigeria	47,143,356

“With tele-density in the country growing from below 2 per cent in 2001 to about 65 per cent within 10 years, the broadband segment is yet to catch-up. Recent statistics show that there are over 47.1 million internet users in Nigeria, which on the surface appears to be a large number but that figure represents only 29 per cent of the population. In reality, we estimate that actual broadband penetration in Nigeria is in the 10 per cent range, (which) places us in several published studies behind South Africa, Kenya and Ghana in sub Saharan Africa”.

Evidently, the issue of low ranking in the uptake of ICT lies majorly with poor broadband (data) communication in spite of the potential that lies in the broadband infrastructures at the shore of the country which could make us ranked among the best in the sub-Sahara region.

I. WHAT ARE THE ICT INFRASTRUCTURE NEEDED FOR BROADBAND COMMUNICATIONS

A. Various Elements of Broadband Connectivity

Broadband is the common term for a very fast connection to the Internet. It allows users to download online entertainment such as video clips and music, listen to digital radio and television, send e-mail faster and speeds up everything they do online.

A broadband service can transmit information at up to 40 times the speed of a dial-up modem connection. As the connection is always on, like water or electricity, users don't need to dial up every time they want to log on. [9]

The provision of broadband connectivity to end users involves several elements. A problem in any of these elements will constrain the delivery of affordable broadband services. In Nigeria, the inadequacy of one element, *domestic backbone networks*, is one of the factors underlying the limited growth of broadband in Nigeria.

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Table1: Broadband Communication Supply Chain

Supplying communications services involves a combination of network elements, processing, and business services. These can be thought of as the “supply chain.” At the top of the chain is the international connectivity that provides the link to the rest of the world. The second level is the domestic and regional backbone networks that carry traffic from the landing point of the international communications infrastructure to other points within the country (in some African countries, regional connectivity is missing). The third level is the “intelligence” contained in the networks. Below this is the access network that links the core network to the customer. Finally, there is a suite of retail services such as customer

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acquisition, billing, and customer care that allow the business to function. This supply chain is illustrated in Table 1

In practice, there are many variations on the structure of this supply chain. For example, voice services do not rely as heavily on international connectivity as Internet services, and landlocked countries require regional connectivity if they are to access high bandwidth submarine fiber-optic cable networks.

Domestic backbone networks lie at the heart of any communications services supply chain and are an integral component in the provision of broadband connectivity.

One of the first decisions to be made is what kind of connection you want. There are several options for setting up high-speed services, which all come under the broadband umbrella. However, the type of broadband service you need and have access to will be determined by the speed requirements, budget, and the location (city or regional) of your home or office.

B. Comparative advantage of fiber optic networks over satellite in building broadband backbones

The two commonly used media of connectivity of a country to the rest of the world and domestic backbone include satellite and fiber optic networks. However, in spite of the popularity of satellite in building national backbone, there are still some shortcomings associated with satellite when the issue involves building a national or international communication backbones.

One of the most likely reactions one gets when discussing fiber-optic networks in Nigeria is “why not satellite technology?” Satellite communications has been around for a while and has provided telecommunications links between Nigeria and the rest of the world. However, a comparison between fiber optic and satellite technologies reveals that although satellite systems are the most efficient solutions for TV broadcast, for access to remote locations, and essentially, for wireless access to the local loop and the

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network backbone, fiber optic networks are more suited for high bandwidth transmission between countries and continents through core networks (or backbones) and submarine links respectively. Fiber optic networks offer very high bandwidth necessary for a country (Nigeria) or African nations to catch up with the new global information technology. For example, fiber cables today can have capacity up to 2 Tbps - an equivalent of millions of simultaneous voice channels per cable. This is far from the reach of any anticipated satellite system, which is less than 1Gbps - lower than our own SAT-3/WASC/SAFE undersea cable system.

Real time transmission and very low bit error rate offered by fiber optic networks are among the advantages of fiber over satellite. Satellite communications add a delay to communications making interactive data transmission difficult and subject the quality of transmission to external factors. A geostationary satellite link has a transmission delay of up to 600 milliseconds compared to 100ms for a combination of fiber and coaxial cable networks.

The open space nature of satellite (and any other wireless) communications makes satellite communication vulnerable to interception and corruption. Although several schemes are available for data encryption for IP over satellite, the high bit error rate may cause failures in the encryption systems. Fiber optic transmission offers undoubtedly the best confidentiality and security of transmission than any other means by its mere nature.

In order to address increasing traffic demand, it is relatively easy to increase the capacity of fiber optic networks during their lifetime by means of wavelength division multiplexing technology. For example, the SAT-3/WASC/SAFE system can be upgraded 12 fold from 10Gbps to 120Gbps. It is impossible to do a similar upgrade on satellite systems.

Perhaps the main disadvantage of satellite communication is their high cost relative to fiber optics communication. In the US, for example, the monthly rate for broadband connectivity through cable is about \$35 for 3Mbps data rate compared to \$200 for 200Kbps by Satellite. While the initial cost of a continental

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fiber optic network for Africa may appear too high, the long term cost savings over satellite transmission are overwhelming.

Thus due to their high bandwidth, high reliability, high signal quality, long lifetime, better security and low service cost, fiber optic networks are suited for inter and intra continental backbone network infrastructure. On the other hand, satellite systems are more dedicated to video broadcasting and personal communication services such as mobile telephony satellite or to access remote areas.

II. PRESENT STATE OF BROADBAND INFRASTRUCTURE IN NIGERIA

According to experts, any country seeking growth, job and wealth creation must address how it can increase its access to broadband and if governments can improve broadband penetration in the continent most Africans would have increased access to the internet.

Today, people are realising their life goals due to broadband services with greater access to researches and findings about education, culture and entertainment.

The major Broadband backbone infrastructure in Nigeria includes NigcomSat-1R, WACS, Main-one and Glo 1 fiber optic Cables. SAT-3/WASC (South Africa Trans-Atlantic - West Africa Submarine Cable) which continues from South Africa to Portugal and Spain in Europe with landings at a number of west and southern African countries; Nitel's cable, international submarine fibre-optic cable (Glo-1),

A. BROADBAND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BUILDING COMMUNICATION BACKBONES THAT CONNECT NIGERIA TO THE REST OF THE WORLD

NIGCOMSAT-1R

NigComSat-1R is a hybrid geostationary satellite located at an orbital position of 42.50 E with a life span of at least 15 years, a total of 40 transponders which will provide optimal and cost effective voice, data, video, internet and application services solutions.

NigComSat-1R is a replacement satellite for NigComSat-1 Satellite. It is a critical ICT backbone infrastructure to drive the National ICT revolution in providing revenue diversification for the

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Nation and offering cost effective solution and affordable access to meet Nigeria's telecommunications, broadcast, aviation, maritime, defense and security needs.

SAT-3/WASC (South Africa Trans-Atlantic - West Africa Submarine Cable)

SAT-3/WASC (South Africa Trans-Atlantic - West Africa Submarine Cable) which continues from South Africa to Portugal and Spain in Europe with landings at a number of west and southern African countries. The funding agreement for the project was signed in 1999 and President Wade, one of the founding members of NEPAD, officially launched the networks in Dakar in May 2002. The original capacity was 20 Gbps and is upgradeable to 120Gbps. The submarine cables span a total of 28,000 km and connect the countries of Portugal, Spain (Canary Islands), Senegal, Ghana, Benin, Cote D'Ivoire, Nigeria, Cameroon, Gabon, Angola, South Africa, France (Reunion), Mauritius, India and Malaysia.

Mainone and GLO-1 and WACS (own by MTN) Submarine cables

These submarine cables landed in Nigeria to produce additional capability to the earlier existing ones. With the advent of these cables there is a huge broadband capacity for Nigerians to benefit from.

B. BROADBAND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BUILDING DOMESTIC BACKBONES

In Nigeria, the inadequacy of one element, *domestic backbone networks*, is one of the factors underlying the limited growth of broadband in Nigeria.

Fibre-Optic backbone infrastructure in the Nigeria states and the federal capital territory are not interconnected and are concentrated in the state capitals and a few urban areas. It is recorded that Broadband penetration is low and of about 6% (Omobola Johnson- the Minister of Communication,) while that of Internet penetration is equally low and of about 28%and 33%.

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Few states such as Ondo State are having special schemes inaugurated mainly to supervise the connectivity of broadband infrastructure to the interior towns apart from the state capital having interconnection of broadband infrastructure with other parts of the state. The situation is different in most states of the country. There is no long distance national backbone to carry and distribute the capacities provided by submarine cables to the users in offices, schools, and homes in the hinterland.

III. SUCCESSES AND CHALLENGES FACING BROADBAND COMMUNICATION IN NIGERIA

A. Successes of made in the area of Broadband communication Development in Nigeria

In spite of low penetration in the broadband communications in the country, Nigeria still records some success in the area of the development of broadband communication. Some of the successes are as discussed below:

Several operators have successfully landed submarine cables in Lagos that provide over 9 terabits per second of combined capacity which has enhanced the infrastructure for broadband communication and will help to accommodate the increase in broadband penetration.

The network roll out of number of licenses has also resulted in the installation of a fibre-optic backbone infrastructure in all Nigeria states and the federal capital territory.

Some states such as ondo state are special schemes inaugurated mainly to supervise the connectivity of broadband infrastructure to the interior towns apart form the state capital. having interconnection of broadband infrastructure with other parts of the state.

B. CHALLENGES FACING BROADBAND COMMUNICATION IN NIGERIA

Fibre-Optic backbone infrastructure in the Nigeria states and the federal capital territory are not interconnected and are concentrated in the state capitals and a few urban areas. It is recorded that

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Broadband penetration is low and of about 6% (Omobola Johnson) while that of Internet penetration is equally low and of about 28% and 33%.

National Broadband Plan identifies some of the major challenges faced by operators, such as:

1. High cost of procuring rights of way which ultimately results in high costs for leasing of transmission infrastructures);
2. The incumbent operator, Nigerian Telecommunication Limited (NITEL) has been out of operation for a number of years and all attempts made to privatise NITEL and its subsidiary MTEL, have been unsuccessful.
3. Dearth of investment in fixed household broadband primarily because of the multi-faceted challenges facing operators which prompt the operators to concentrate their household broadband activities on the major cities.
4. Long delay in procuring approval for such rights of the way;
5. Multiple forms of taxation and
6. Regulation;
7. Vandalism; and
8. Distruption caused by roadworks.
9. Generally power supply is a major problem to (operators) doing business in Nigeria
Other reasons for low penetration of broadband include:
10. Incumbent operator NITEL has been out of operation for a number of years.
11. Dearth of investment in fixed household broadband, primarily because of the multi-faceted challenges facing operators. So far some operators have concentrated their household broadband activities on the major cities, such as Abuja, Lagos, and PortHarcourt.

C. HOW TO DEVELOP BROADBAND INFRASTRUCTURE IN NIGERIA

Ajayi,[7] therefore, says the goal of tremendously increasing Internet/broadband penetration in Nigeria must be given utmost priority in 2013. He advises that the major way to fast-track broadband penetration is to stimulate demand for broadband access by promoting the deployment of applications that are relevant to Nigerian users and will add values to their lives.

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Incentivize the quick and effective rollout of new infrastructure and services by all players in the industry; provide universal access to broadband services to the same extent as basic telephony services; provide industry players with requisite spectrum and other resources; and ensure requisite protection for existing infrastructure.

Stanley Jegede, Chief Executive Officer, Phase 3 Telecoms has called on the Federal Government to invest in a national backbone infrastructure that will carry and distribute data capacity from the shores of the country to the hinterland. Jegede made the statement in Lagos recently, insisting that a fully established national backbone infrastructure would boost capacity distribution of broadband and deepen internet penetration in the country.

He noted that Nigeria has a lot of broadband capacities from MainOne, Glo 1, and MTN's West African Cable System (WACS) at the shores of the country, but without a long distance national backbone to carry and distribute the capacities to users in offices, schools, and homes in the hinterland, our dream of accelerated broadband penetration would be grossly hindered.

There is a serious need for government to subsidize the creation of a national broadband backbone network, this subsidy which is very similar to subsidy in America, Australia, and in the UK, will work towards effectively building critical infrastructure required to create a platform where costs associated in delivering the services to the consumers at the right price is determinable." Jegede said.

D. BENEFITS DERIVABLE FROM BROADBAND COMMUNICATION

Mrs. Opeke (CEO of Main One Cable Company) maintained that "when broadband is readily available, behaviour patterns will change because we will rely on such to obtain services and get tasks required in our daily existence as students or workers or business people done. [12]

The 2009, World Bank Information and Communications for Development report showed that access to broadband boosts economic growth in all countries, but most especially in developing

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ones. The study showed that in developing countries, for every ten-percentage points of broadband penetration, their economies grew by 1.38 per cent. The report, conducted in 120 countries between 1980 and 2006, showed that developed countries' economies grew by 1.21 per cent. The figures confirm that broadband access is key for economic growth and even more vital in developing countries. Many Africans are seizing the opportunity that it offers to move their economies forward.

In the same way that the construction of electricity grids and transport links spurred innovation far beyond the dreams of their builders, high-speed broadband networks stimulate greater efficiency and the advancement of businesses.

The 2010 U.S. National Broadband policy document captures it even better when it states: "Broadband is the great infrastructure challenge of the early 21st century. Like electricity a century ago, broadband is a foundation for economic growth, job creation, global competitiveness and a better way of life. It is enabling entire new industries and unlocking vast new possibilities for existing ones. It is changing how we educate children, deliver health care, manage energy, ensure public safety, engage government, and access, organize and disseminate knowledge."

It is a known fact that one of the key requirements for any successful business is the ability to communicate effectively and efficiently especially in this digital age. Anything that can speed up the rate at which communication takes place improves radically the output from any business endeavour and enhances the efficiency with which business processes are carried out. This is the whole new vista of opportunity that broadband technology offers us.

Broadband gives you a high-speed, 'always-on' connection to the Internet, which is typically at least 10 times faster than regular Internet connections. Besides being fast, it is highly cost-effective and provides consistency and reliability. It can save you time when using email and the web, thereby helping your staff to become more productive. In addition, it allows you to build online links with customers and suppliers, as well as with off-site and remote workers.

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The term ‘broadband’ is used to describe any high-speed connection to the Internet with speeds starting from at least 1mbps.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the review work, the reasons for the low ranking in WEF NRI for 2013 was discussed with the major reason being the poor development of broadband communication industry in Nigeria. Based on this discovery, the level of broadband infrastructure in the country was also investigated.

However, it was also discovered that Nigeria has enough fibre optic cable at her shore to provide us with the capacity needed for the Nigerians but due to lack of domestic connectivity, many Nigerians are not benefitting from this wealth of Broadband communication capability.

Not that alone the ways of developing broadband communication was also discussed. Finally, what the country stand to benefit by improving on the broadband communication was also discussed.

By implementing the suggestions given in this paper, I am very optimistic that Nigeria will soon been singing a new song of great innovation.

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EFFECT OF HIGH LOST ON IGNITION (LOI) CONTENT CEMENT KILN DUST ON THE INDEX PROPERTIES OF BLACK COTTON SOIL

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ABSTRACT

The preliminary investigation carried out on a black cotton soil shows that it falls under A-7-6 (16) using AASHTO classification and CL according to Unified Soil Classification System (USCS). The tests carried out on the cement kiln dust treated soil showed that the liquid limit of the natural soil increased from 48.2% to a peak value of 51.8% at 2% CKD treatment and thereafter decreased with higher CKD content. The plastic limit also increased from 27.2% for the natural soil to a peak value of 36.8% at 4% CKD treatment. The plasticity index value, decreases from 21.0% for the natural soil to a minimum value of 12.8% at 6% CKD content. The maximum dry density (MDD) for British Standard Light (BSL) and British Standard Heavy (BSH) compactive efforts increased to peak values of 1.66 and 1.91 Mg/m³ at 6% and 4%CKD

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contents respectively. The MDD for West African Standard (WAS) compactive effort increased with higher CKD content. The Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) for BSL and BSH compactive efforts increased up to 6%CKD content then decreased with higher CKD content. For the WAS compactive effort, the OMC generally decreased with higher CKD content.

KEYWORDS: Cement Kiln Dust, Black Cotton Soil, Atterberg limits, Compaction.

INTRODUCTION

The need to reduce the cost of waste disposal and the growing cost of soil stabilizers has led to intense global research towards economic utilization of wastes for engineering purposes. The safe disposal of industrial and agricultural wastes demands urgent and cost effective solutions because of the debilitating effect of these materials on the environment and the health hazards they constitute.

Expansive soils are also referred to as “black cotton soil” in some parts of the world. They are so named because of their colour and suitability for growing cotton. Black cotton soils have colours ranging from light grey to dark grey and black [1]. Black cotton soils are confined to the semi-arid regions of tropical and temperate climatic zones and are abundant where the annual evaporation exceeds the precipitation [2, 3]. Black cotton soils occur in continuous stretches as superficial deposits and are typical of flat terrains with poor drainage. The absence of quartz in the clay mineralogy enhances the formation of fine-grained soil material, which is impermeable and waterlogged [4].

The mineralogy of this soil is dominated by the presence of montmorillonite which is characterized by large volume change from wet to dry seasons and vice versa. Deposits of black cotton soil, which occupy an estimated area of $104 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ in Northeastern Nigeria, show a general pattern of cracks during the dry season of the year. Cracks measuring 70mm wide and over 1m deep have been observed and may extend up to 3m or more in case of high deposit [5].

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Cement kiln dust (CKD) or cement by-pass dust (CBPD) is the fine grained, solid highly alkaline waste removed from cement kiln exhaust gas by air pollution control devices. A typical Portland cement is manufactured by feeding materials containing appropriate proportions of lime, silica, alumina and iron into the upper end of a kiln. The mix passes through the kiln at a rate controlled by the slope of the kiln and the speed at which the kiln rotates. Burning fuel is forced into the lower end of the kiln where it produces temperatures of 1400-1650°C, changing the raw mix to a cement clinker. During this operation a small percentage of the material in the form of dust (i.e. CKD) is collected. The physical and chemical properties of CKD can vary from plant-to-plant, depending on the raw materials used and type of collection process in the plant. However, the dust collected from the same kiln and producing the same cement type will typically have a relatively consistent composition.

The major parameters that determine CKD characteristics are the raw feed material, type of kiln operation, dust collection systems, and fuel type. Since the properties of CKD can be significantly affected by the design, operation and materials used in a cement kiln, the chemical and physical characteristics of CKD must be evaluated on an individual plant basis [6].

CKD containing high CaO content and low loss on ignition (LOI) performs best for most applications. High LOI dusts contain a higher percentage of bound water within its chemical structure and less CaO is available to react. The high LOI can also interfere with the hydration process. Several processing factors influence the chemical and physical properties of CKD. Because plant operations differ considerably with respect to raw feed, type of operation, dust collection facility, and type of fuel used, CKD from each plant can vary markedly in chemical, mineralogical and physical composition. Therefore it is important to thoroughly test CKD for any proposed application prior to use [7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The disturbed black cotton soil samples used for this study were collected in March, 2012 at Deba (Latitude 10°13'N and longitude 11°23'E), Deba Local Government Area along Dadinkowa which is 30 km from Gombe town, the state capital of Gombe State, Nigeria.

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The Cement Kiln Dust (CKD) used for this study was obtained from Sokoto Cement Factory, Sokoto, the capital of Sokoto State of Nigeria. The chemical composition of the CKD was conducted by method of Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence. The result of the chemical composition test is shown in Table 1. Laboratory tests were performed on the natural soil samples in accordance with BS 1377 (1990) [8] and on the cement kiln dust treated black cotton soil in accordance with BS 1924 (1990) [9]. These tests include, particle size distribution, Atterberg limits and compactions. The compaction tests were carried out for the natural soil and the stabilized soils (in 0, 2, 4, 6 8 and 10% CKD); using the British Standard light (BSL), West African Standard (WAS) and the British Standard heavy (BSH) energies, in accordance with the Nigerian General Specifications (1997) [10].

3kg of the soil/soil-admixture samples were mixed thoroughly with 4% of water (and the water is added at 4% for each of the compactions). The sample was then compacted into the 1000cm³ mould in three layers of approximately equal mass with each layer receiving 27 blows of 2.5kg rammer falling through a height of 300mm, for the British Standard light compaction; 10 blows of 4.5kg rammer falling through a height of 450mm, in five layers for West African Standard compaction and 27 blows of 4.5kg rammer in five layers falling through a height of 450mm, for the British Standard Heavy. The blows were uniformly distributed over the surface of each layer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil Identification

The results of the identification test conducted on the natural soil are summarized in Table 2.

Particle Size Distribution

The particle size analysis from hydrometer sedimentation test for black cotton soil – cement kiln dust mixtures are shown in Figure 1. On a general note, a nominal increase in the percentage fines was observed with increasing cement kiln dust content. This was as a result of the soil particles been replaced by the finer CKD particles, hence the increased finer particles.

Effect of CKD on Atterberg Limits

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The variation of liquid limit of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust content is shown in Fig. 2. The introduction of cement kiln dust into the soil first caused an increase in the Atterberg limits to a peak value at 2%CKD treatment in the case of the liquid limit and 4%CKD treatment for plastic limit and linear Shrinkage and thereafter decreased. The increase can be attributed to addition of CKD which introduced more pozzolanic substance into the specimen that required more water for hydration to be completed. The subsequent decrease can be associated with the agglomeration and flocculation of the clay particles which is as a result of exchange ions at the surface of the clay particles. The trend observed in liquid and plastic limits is in agreement with Ramzi et al. (2001) [11]. There was a general decrease in the plasticity index value from a value of 21.0% for the natural soil to a least value of 12.8% at 6% CKD treatment. [12] and [13] reported that the reduction in plasticity index with chemical treatment could be attributed to the depressed double layer thickness due to cation exchange by potassium, calcium and ferric ions. A nominal increment was observed at 8 and 10%CKD contents.

Effect of CKD on Compaction Characteristics

Maximum Dry Density

The variation of maximum dry density (MDD) of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust contents for the three compactive efforts are shown in Fig. 3.

For British Standard light (BSL) and British Standard Heavy (BSH) compactions, the MDD increased from 1.63 and 1.82Mg/m³ for the natural soil to 1.66 and 1.91Mg/m³ at 4 and 6% CKD contents respectively. This increase in dry density with addition of CKD may be due to cation exchange reactions. It could also be due to CKD occupying the void within the soil matrix and in addition, the flocculation and agglomeration of the clay particle due to exchange of ions [1, 14, 15,]. The subsequent reduction in MDD may be probably due to the fact that for any soil/admixture, there is always a water content to produce maximum strength [16]. This trend is in agreement with Ola (1991) [17], Lees et al (1982) [18] and Iorliam et al. (2012) [19]. The result of the West African Standard (WAS) compaction is in conformity with the trend of decreasing OMC with increasing MDD.

Optimum Moisture Content

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The variation of optimum moisture content of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust contents for the three compactive efforts is shown in Fig.4. For BSL and BSH compactions, the OMC increased from values of 18.0% and 14.6% for the natural soil to peak values of 19.7% and 15.8% both at 6%CKD contents.

This trend is in conformity with results reported by Ola (1978) [20], Gidigas (1976) [21] and Osinubi (1999) [16]. An explanation that was offered for this trend is that there was increasing desire for water which commensurates with the higher amount of the additives because more water was required for the dissociation of admixtures with Ca^{2+} and OH^- ions to supply more Ca^{2+} for the cation exchange reaction. The subsequent decrease in OMC with increase in CKD content might be due to cation exchange reaction that caused the flocculation of clay particles.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the study conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- ❖ The black cotton soil is classified as A-7-6 (16) using the AASHTO classification system and CL using the USCS. This makes it geotechnically a problem soil.
- ❖ A high lost on ignition (LOI) content cement kiln dust (CKD) has no significant effect on the particle sizes of black cotton soil.
- ❖ The effect of high LOI content CKD on the Atterberg limits is most significant (for soil modification) at 10% or more.
- ❖ Generally, the chemical, mineralogical and physical composition of CKD should be thoroughly evaluated on an individual plant basis because several processing factors influence them.

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TABLES

Table 1. Chemical composition of cement kiln dust

Oxide	CKD (%)
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CaO	44.28
SiO ₂	7.23
Al ₂ O ₃	1.90
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.47
MgO	0.82
MnO	0.11
In ₂ O ₃	0.66
BaO	0.10
SO ₃	0.13
Lu ₂ O ₃	0.05
LOI(1000 ⁰ C)	39.28
TiO ₂	0.23
V ₂ O ₅	0.03
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.02
Y ₂ O ₃	0.54
ZnO	0.01
Rh ₂ O ₃	0.10
CdO	1.30
Re ₂ O ₇	0.21

Table 2: Properties of the natural black cotton soil

Property	Quantity
Percentage passing BS No 200 sieve	73.6
Natural Moisture Content, %	21.0
Liquid Limit, %	48.2
Plastic Limit, %	27.2
Plasticity Index, %	21.0
Linear Shrinkage, %	16.9
Free Swell, %	80.0

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Specific Gravity	2.33
AASHTO Classification	A-7-6 (16)
USCS	CL
NBRI Classification	High swell potential
Maximum Dry Density, Mg/m ³	
British Standard light	1.63
West African Standard	1.72
British Standard heavy	1.82
Optimum Moisture Content, %	
British Standard light	18.0
West African Standard	17.9
British Standard heavy	14.6
Colour	Greyish black
Dominant clay mineral	Montmorillonite

FIGURES

Fig. 1: Particle size distribution curves of combined dry and hydrometer sedimentation tests of black cotton soil-cement kiln dust mixtures

Fig. 2: Variation of Atterberg limits of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust content

Fig. 3: Variation of maximum dry density of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust content

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Fig. 4: Variation of optimum moisture content of balck cotton soil with cement kiln dust

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